

ISSN	TITULO	ESTRATO
2237-5953	(RE) PENSANDO DIREITO	B4
2469-4312	[IN] TRANSITION	B2
1981-030X	19&20 (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B1
2053-1583	2D MATERIALS	A2
2237-8758	2º SIMPÓSIO INTERNACIONAL DE ENSINO DE LÍNGUA PORTUGUESA	B1
2190-5738	3 BIOTECH	A4
2329-7662	3D PRINTING AND ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING	A2
2329-7670	3D PRINTING AND ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING (ONLINE)	A2
1619-4500	4OR (BERLIN)	A2
1808-1142	5% ARQUITETURA + ARTE	A4
2525-6556	A (IN)AFASTABILIDADE DOS DIREITOS FUNDAMENTAIS NO ÂMBITO	B4
2236-6695	A BARRIGUDA: REVISTA CIENTÍFICA	B3
2237-0455	A COMUNICAÇÃO DIALÓGICA ENTRE UNIVERSIDADE E COMUNIDAD	B4
1548-7083	A CONTRACORRIENTE (RALEIGH, N.C.)	B3
2594-9675	A COR DAS LETRAS	A3
1415-8973	A COR DAS LETRAS (UEFS)	A3
0011-7641	A DEFESA NACIONAL	B4
1413-6090	A ECONOMIA EM REVISTA	B3
2236-2029	A ECONOMIA EM REVISTA - AERE	B3
1983-6422	A FÍSICA NA ESCOLA (IMPRESSO)	B1
1557-8100	A JOURNAL OF INTEGRATIVE BIOLOGY	A4
2175-2516	A MARGEM: REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS, LETRAS	B3
1676-0336	A TERCEIRA IDADE	B4
1516-3210	A&C. REVISTA DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO & CONSTITUCIONAL (II	A2
2448-5764	A&H	B2
2362-6089	A&P CONTINUIDAD	A4
0094-6354	A.A.N.A. JOURNAL	A3
1559-7776	AACN ADVANCED CRITICAL CARE	B1
1232-1966	AAEM. ANNALS OF AGRICULTURAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICIN	B3
0149-1423	AAPG BULLETIN (PRINT)	A1
1522-1059	AAPS PHARMSCI	A3
1530-9932	AAPS PHARMSCITECH	A3
0747-0088	ABA JOURNAL	B1
0213-6252	ABACO (GIJÓN)	A4
0001-3072	ABACUS (SYDNEY. PRINT)	B1
2316-9451	ABAKÓS	B2
0102-6720	ABCD. ARQUIVOS BRASILEIROS DE CIRURGIA DIGESTIVA	B1
2318-4965	ABCS HEALTH SCIENCES	A3
2357-8114	ABCS HEALTH SCIENCES	A3
1980-4814	ABCUSTOS (SÃO LEOPOLDO, RS)	B3
0942-8925	ABDOMINAL IMAGING	A3
2366-0058	ABDOMINAL RADIOLOGY (ONLINE)	B1
2596-0873	ABEÁFRICA	B3
2238-3026	ABEHACHE	B3
2471-0938	AB-ORIGINAL. JOURNAL OF INDIGENOUS STUDIES AND FIRST NATIO	B3
1984-2090	ABRIL (NITERÓI)	B3
2014-8534	ABRIU: TEXTUALITY STUDIES ON BRAZIL, GALICIA AND PORTUGAL	B1
1807-9792	ABSTRACTA : LINGUAGEM, MENTE E AÇÃO (NITERÓI)	B3
1012-8255	ACADEMIA (CARACAS)	A3

2241-1402	ACADEMIA (ONLINE)	B4
2315-7739	ACADEMIA JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH	B4
1069-6563	ACADEMIC EMERGENCY MEDICINE	A1
2281-3993	ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDIES	B4
2079-3456	ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF SURINAME	B4
1040-2446	ACADEMIC MEDICINE	A1
1876-2859	ACADEMIC PEDIATRICS (PRINT)	A2
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1076-6332	ACADEMIC RADIOLOGY	A3
2318-1494	ACADÊMICO MUNDO	B3
1631-0691	ACADEMIE DES SCIENCES. COMPTES RENDUS. BIOLOGIES	A2
1806-9495	ACADEMUS: REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA SAÚDE	B4
1528-2686	ACADEMY OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP JOURNAL	A4
2151-6561	ACADEMY OF MANAGEMENT ANNUAL MEETING PROCEEDINGS	B4
1095-6298	ACADEMY OF MARKETING STUDIES JOURNAL	A4
1939-6104	ACADEMY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	B1
2358-6559	ACANTO EM REVISTA	B4
2238-0701	AÇÃO MIDIÁTICA - ESTUDOS EM COMUNICAÇÃO, SOCIEDADE E CUL	B2
0132-8077	ACARINA: RUSSIAN JOURNAL OF ACAROLOGY	B1
0044-586X	ACAROLOGIA (LA VARENNE-SUR-SEINE)	B1
0001-4575	ACCIDENT ANALYSIS AND PREVENTION	A1
0810-5391	ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE (PARKVILLE. PRINT)	A2
0963-9284	ACCOUNTING EDUCATION: AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL	A2
0155-9982	ACCOUNTING FORUM (ADELAIDE. PRINT)	A2
0951-3574	ACCOUNTING, AUDITING & ACCOUNTABILITY JOURNAL	A1
0001-4842	ACCOUNTS OF CHEMICAL RESEARCH	A1
0949-1775	ACCREDITATION AND QUALITY ASSURANCE	B2
2358-5587	ACENO - REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGIA DO CENTRO-OESTE	A3
2237-8723	ACERVO: REVISTA DO ARQUIVO NACIONAL	A3
2319-0698	ACESSO LIVRE	B1
2326-3253	ACG CASE REPORTS JOURNAL	B1
0329-9147	ACHERONTA (EN LÍNEA)	B4
2318-5724	ACHIOTE.COM ¿ REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE MODA	B3
0889-325X	ACI MATERIALS JOURNAL	A2
0889-3241	ACI STRUCTURAL JOURNAL	A3
0360-0300	ACM COMPUTING SURVEYS	A1
2153-2184	ACM INROADS	B2
1550-4832	ACM JOURNAL ON EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES IN COMPUTING SYST	A3
1936-7228	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON ACCESSIBLE COMPUTING (TACCESS)	A3
1544-3566	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON ARCHITECTURE AND CODE OPTIMIZATION	A3
1556-4665	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON AUTONOMOUS AND ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS	A2
0734-2071	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON COMPUTER SYSTEMS	A1
1946-6226	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON COMPUTING EDUCATION	A1
1084-4309	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON DESIGN AUTOMATION OF ELECTRONIC SY!	A4
1539-9087	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON EMBEDDED COMPUTING SYSTEMS	A4
0730-0301	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON GRAPHICS	A1
1046-8188	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON INFORMATION SYSTEMS	A1
1533-5399	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON INTERNET TECHNOLOGY	A2
1556-4681	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY FROM DATA	A1
2376-3639	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON MODELING AND PERFORMANCE EVALUAT	B3

1551-6857	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON MULTIMEDIA COMPUTING COMMUNICAT	A2
2471-2566	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON PRIVACY AND SECURITY	B4
1049-331X	ACM TRANSACTIONS ON SOFTWARE ENGINEERING AND METHODO	A2
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2574-0962	ACS APPLIED ENERGY MATERIALS	B4
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4283-4293	ACS APPLIED NANO MATERIALS	B4
2373-9878	ACS BIOMATERIALS SCIENCE & ENGINNERING	A2
2155-5435	ACS CATALYSIS	A1
2374-7951	ACS CENTRAL SCIENCE (ONLINE)	A1
1554-8929	ACS CHEMICAL BIOLOGY	A1
1554-8937	ACS CHEMICAL BIOLOGY	A1
1948-7193	ACS CHEMICAL NEUROSCIENCE	A1
2156-8952	ACS COMBINATORIAL SCIENCE	A2
2472-3452	ACS EARTH AND SPACE CHEMISTRY	B4
2373-8227	ACS INFECTIOUS DISEASES	A1
2161-1653	ACS MACRO LETTERS	A1
1948-5875	ACS MED CHEM LETT	A2
1936-0851	ACS NANO	A1
2470-1343	ACS OMEGA	A3
2330-4022	ACS PHOTONICS	A2
2379-3694	ACS SENSORS	A1
2168-0485	ACS SUSTAINABLE CHEMISTRY & ENGINEERING	A1
2161-5063	ACS SYNTHETIC BIOLOGY	A1
0906-4710	ACTA AGRICULTURAE SCANDINAVICA. SECTION B, SOIL AND PLANT	A4
0120-2812	ACTA AGRONOMICA	B4
1809-4392	ACTA AMAZONICA	B1
1677-7298	ACTA AMBIENTAL CATARINENSE	B1
0001-5172	ACTA ANAESTHESIOLOGICA SCANDINAVICA	A3
0353-5150	ACTA ANALYTICA	A4
1234-950X	ACTA ANGIOLOGICA	B4
2358-2375	ACTA APICOLA BRASILICA	B3
0167-8019	ACTA APPLICANDAE MATHEMATICAE	B1
0001-5202	ACTA ARACHNOLOGICA	B4
0065-101X	ACTA ARCHAEOLOGICA (PAPIRFORM)	B1
0094-5765	ACTA ASTRONAUTICA	A1
0001-5237	ACTA ASTRONOMICA	A1
1672-9145	ACTA BIOCHIMICA ET BIOPHYSICA SINICA	A4
1726-569X	ACTA BIOETHICA (EN LÍNEA)	B4
0120-548X	ACTA BIOLOGICA COLOMBIANA	B1
1742-7061	ACTA BIOMATERIALIA	A1
2236-0867	ACTA BIOMEDICA BRASILIENSIA	B1
0325-2957	ACTA BIOQUÍMICA CLÍNICA LATINOAMERICANA	B4
0001-5342	ACTA BIOTHEORETICA	A2
1677-941X	ACTA BOTANICA BRASILICA	B1
2526-4338	ACTA BRASILIENSIS	B1
2526-432X	ACTA BRASILIENSIS	B1
0001-5385	ACTA CARDIOLOGICA (IMPRIMÉ)	B2
0583-6050	ACTA CARSOLOGICA	B1

1318-0207	ACTA CHIMICA SLOVENICA (PRINT ED.)	B1
1508-1109	ACTA CHIROPTEROLOGICA	A3
1733-5329	ACTA CHIROPTEROLOGICA (ONLINE)	A3
1233-2356	ACTA CHROMATOGRAPHICA	B2
0253-7338	ACTA CIENCIA INDICA. CHEMISTRY	B2
1984-0918	ACTA CIENTÍFICA (PATOS DE MINAS)	B4
1519-9800	ACTA CIENTÍFICA. CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS	B4
1678-2674	ACTA CIRÚRGICA BRASILEIRA (ONLINE)	B1
1909-9711	ACTA COLOMBIANA DE PSICOLOGIA	A3
0188-8145	ACTA COMPORTAMENTALIA	A3
2053-2733	ACTA CRYSTALLOGRAPHICA A - FOUNDATION AND ADVANCES	A2
2052-5206	ACTA CRYSTALLOGRAPHICA SECTION B	A1
2053-2296	ACTA CRYSTALLOGRAPHICA SECTION C: STRUCTURAL CHEMISTRY	A3
2056-9890	ACTA CRYSTALLOGRAPHICA SECTION E, CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC COMM	B4
0108-7673	ACTA CRYSTALLOGRAPHICA. SECTION A, FOUNDATIONS OF CRYSTAL	A2
2053-230X	ACTA CRYSTALLOGRAPHICA. SECTION F: STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY COM	B2
0001-5547	ACTA CYTOLOGICA	B1
1938-2650	ACTA CYTOLOGICA	B1
0001-5555	ACTA DERMATO-VENEREOLOGICA	A2
1330-027X	ACTA DERMATOVENEROLOGICA CROATICA	B2
0940-5429	ACTA DIABETOLOGICA (PRINT)	A2
2065-1430	ACTA DIDACTICA NAPOCENSIA	A3
0374-1036	ACTA ENTOMOLOGICA MUSEI NATIONALIS PRAGAE	B1
1437-9546	ACTA ETHOLOGICA (INTERNET)	A3
0104-7795	ACTA FISIATRICA	A3
2317-0190	ACTA FISIÁTRICA	A3
0300-9033	ACTA GASTROENTEROLÓGICA LATINOAMERICANA	B3
1980-5772	ACTA GEOGRÁFICA (UFRR)	A2
0001-5709	ACTA GEOLOGICA POLONICA	B1
1895-6572	ACTA GEOPHYSICA (DRUK)	B1
1861-1125	ACTA GEOTECHNICA (BERLIN. PRINT)	A2
0001-5792	ACTA HAEMATOLOGICA	B2
1827-9635	ACTA HERPETOLOGICA	A4
0065-1281	ACTA HISTOCHEMICA (PRINT)	A4
2406-6168	ACTA HORTICULTURAE	B4
0567-7572	ACTA HORTICULTURAE	B4
0137-1592	ACTA ICHTHYOLOGICA ET PISCATORIA	B2
2316-4093	ACTA IGUAZU	B4
2221-870X	ACTA IMEKO	B2
2448-6469	ACTA LATINOAMERICANA DE MATEMATICA EDUCATIVA	B3
2179-975X	ACTA LIMNOLOGICA BRASILIENSIA (ONLINE)	B1
0716-0909	ACTA LITERARIA (IMPRESA)	B1
1359-6454	ACTA MATERIALIA (OXFORD)	A1
0001-5962	ACTA MATHEMATICA	A1
0236-5294	ACTA MATHEMATICA HUNGARICA (PRINT)	B2
0252-9602	ACTA MATHEMATICA SCIENTIA	B2
0001-5970	ACTA MECHANICA	A2
0044-6025	ACTA MEDICA IRANICA	A2
0870-399X	ACTA MÉDICA PORTUGUESA	A4
1646-0758	ACTA MÉDICA PORTUGUESA	A4

1006-7191	ACTA METALLURGICA SINICA	A2
2594-7680	ACTA NEGÓCIOS	B4
0065-1400	ACTA NEUROBIOLOGIAE EXPERIMENTALIS (DRUK)	B1
0001-6268	ACTA NEUROCHIRURGICA	A3
0300-9009	ACTA NEUROLOGICA BELGICA	B2
0001-6314	ACTA NEUROLOGICA SCANDINAVICA	A2
0001-6322	ACTA NEUROPATHOLOGICA	A1
2051-5960	ACTA NEUROPATHOLOGICA COMMUNICATIONS	A1
1601-5215	ACTA NEUROPSYCHIATRICA	A3
0001-6349	ACTA OBSTETRICIA ET GYNECOLOGICA SCANDINAVICA	A3
1852-4834	ACTA ODONTOLOGICA LATINOAMERICANA	A4
1502-3850	ACTA ODONTOLOGICA SCANDINAVICA	A2
0001-6365	ACTA ODONTOLÓGICA VENEZOLANA	B4
1146-609X	ACTA OECOLOGICA (MONTROUGE)	A3
1509-409X	ACTA OF BIOENGINEERING AND BIOMECHANICS	B1
0284-186X	ACTA ONCOLOGICA (STOCKHOLM)	A3
2027-7822	ACTA ONDONTOLÓGICA COLOMBIANA	B4
1755-375X	ACTA OPHTHALMOLOGICA	A2
0001-6454	ACTA ORNITHOLOGICA	A4
1745-3674	ACTA ORTHOPAEDICA (PRINT)	A1
1413-7852	ACTA ORTOPÉDICA BRASILEIRA (IMPRESSO)	B3
0001-6489	ACTA OTO-LARYNGOLOGICA	A4
0392-100X	ACTA OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGICA ITALICA	A4
2173-5735	ACTA OTORRINOLARINGOLOGICA (ENGLISH EDITION)	B4
0001-6519	ACTA OTORRINOLARINGOLÓGICA ESPAÑOLA	B2
0803-5253	ACTA PAEDIATRICA (OSLO)	A2
0567-7920	ACTA PALAEONTOLOGICA POLONICA	A2
1230-2821	ACTA PARASITOLOGICA	B3
0103-2100	ACTA PAULISTA DE ENFERMAGEM (UNIFESP. IMPRESSO)	A3
0001-6640	ACTA PEDIÁTRICA ESPAÑOLA	B1
1330-0075	ACTA PHARMACEUTICA	A4
2211-3835	ACTA PHARMACEUTICA SINICA B	A1
1671-4083	ACTA PHARMACOLOGICA SINICA	A2
0587-4246	ACTA PHYSICA POLONICA. A	B1
0587-4254	ACTA PHYSICA POLONICA. B	B1
0137-5881	ACTA PHYSIOLOGIAE PLANTARUM	A3
1861-1664	ACTA PHYSIOLOGIAE PLANTARUM	A3
1748-1716	ACTA PHYSIOLOGICA (ONLINE)	A1
0231-424X	ACTA PHYSIOLOGICA HUNGARICA (PRINT)	B4
0185-3082	ACTA POÉTICA	A4
2448-735X	ACTA POÉTICA (ONLINE)	A4
0001-6837	ACTA POLONIAE PHARMACEUTICA: DRUG RESEARCH	B1
1210-2709	ACTA POLYTECHNICA	B1
1785-8860	ACTA POLYTECHNICA HUNGARICA	B1
0065-1583	ACTA PROTOZOOLOGICA (DRUK)	A3
0001-6896	ACTA PSIQUIÁTRICA Y PSICOLÓGICA DE AMÉRICA LATINA	A2
0001-690X	ACTA PSYCHIATRICA SCANDINAVICA	A2
0001-6918	ACTA PSYCHOLOGICA	A3
2469-6676	ACTA PSYCHOPATHOLOGICA	B4
0284-1851	ACTA RADIOLOGICA (1987)	A4

0303-464X	ACTA REUMATOLÓGICA PORTUGUESA	B3
2317-8957	ACTA SCIENTIAE ET TECHNICAE	B3
1679-9216	ACTA SCIENTIAE VETERINARIAE (ONLINE)	B1
1678-0345	ACTA SCIENTIAE VETERINARIAE (UFRGS. IMPRESSO)	B1
1644-0730	ACTA SCIENTIARUM POLONORUM TECHNOLOGIA ALIMENTARIA	A4
1679-9275	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. AGRONOMY (IMPRESSO)	A4
1806-2636	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. ANIMAL SCIENCES	B2
1807-863X	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES (ONLINE)	B1
2178-5201	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. EDUCATION (ONLINE)	A2
1679-9291	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. HEALTH SCIENCES (IMPRESSO)	B2
1679-7361	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. HUMAN AND SOCIAL SCIENCES (IMPRESSO)	B4
1983-4675	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. LANGUAGE AND CULTURE (IMPRESSO)	B1
1806-2563	ACTA SCIENTIARUM. TECHNOLOGY (IMPRESSO)	B2
0102-4264	ACTA SEMIÓTICA ET LINGUÍSTICA	B3
0186-6028	ACTA SOCIOLOGICA	A1
0001-6993	ACTA SOCIOLOGICA (TRYKT UTG.)	A2
0001-7019	ACTA STOMATOLOGICA CROATICA	B3
1982-422X	ACTA TECNOLÓGICA	B3
0327-9286	ACTA TOXICOLÓGICA ARGENTINA	A4
1851-3743	ACTA TOXICOLÓGICA ARGENTINA (ONLINE)	A4
0001-706X	ACTA TROPICA	A1
0001-7132	ACTA UNIVERSITATIS CAROLINAE. GEOLOGICA	B2
0567-8315	ACTA VETERINARIA (BEOGRAD)	A4
1981-5484	ACTA VETERINARIA BRASILICA	B2
0001-7213	ACTA VETERINARIA BRNO (PRINT)	B1
1751-0147	ACTA VETERINARIA SCANDINAVICA (ONLINE)	A2
0001-723X	ACTA VIROLOGICA (ENGLISH ED.)	B3
0001-7272	ACTA ZOOLOGICA (STOCKHOLM)	A4
0065-1737	ACTA ZOOLOGICA MEXICANA	B4
1463-6395	ACTA ZOOLOGICA ONLINE	A4
1850-2032	ACTAS DE DISEÑO	B3
0001-7310	ACTAS DERMO-SIFILIOGRÁFICAS (ED. IMPRESA)	B2
1139-9287	ACTAS ESPAÑOLAS DE PSIQUIATRÍA	A2
1578-2735	ACTAS ESPAÑOLAS DE PSIQUIATRÍA	A2
0210-4806	ACTAS UROLÓGICAS ESPAÑOLAS	B2
0335-5322	ACTES DE LA RECHERCHE EN SCIENCES SOCIALES	A1
2270-4957	ACTES SÉMIOTIQUES (EN LIGNE)	A1
2525-8923	ACTIO: DOCÊNCIA EM CIÊNCIAS	A3
1545-4517	ACTION, CRITICISM, & THEORY FOR MUSIC EDUCATION	A2
2519-7355	ACTUALIDAD BRICS- BOLETIN DE RELACIONES INTERNACIONALES	B4
0304-3584	ACTUALIDADES BIOLÓGICAS	B4
2215-3535	ACTUALIDADES EN PSICOLOGÍA	A4
1409-4703	ACTUALIDADES INVESTIGATIVAS EN EDUCACIÓN	A2
0120-1700	ACTUALIDADES PEDAGÓGICAS	A4
1778-4034	ACTUALITÉS DE LA CONSERVATION	B3
1669-8975	ACTUALIZACIONES EN OSTEOLOGÍA (IMPRESA)	B4
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0718-0179	ACTUEL MARX INTERVENCIONES	B2
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0964-5284	ACUPUNCTURE IN MEDICINE	A2

1983-442X	ACÚSTICA E VIBRAÇÕES	B4
1610-1928	ACUSTICA UNITED WITH ACTA ACUSTICA	A3
1570-8705	AD HOC NETWORKS	A2
2325-0496	ADA	B2
0736-5829	ADAPTED PHYSICAL ACTIVITY QUARTERLY	A2
1543-2777	ADAPTED PHYSICAL ACTIVITY QUARTERLY	A2
0965-2140	ADDICTION (ABINGDON. PRINT)	A1
1355-6215	ADDICTION BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1606-6359	ADDICTION RESEARCH & THEORY	A2
1940-0640	ADDICTION SCIENCE & CLINICAL PRACTICE	A1
0306-4603	ADDICTIVE BEHAVIORS	A1
2352-8532	ADDICTIVE BEHAVIORS REPORTS	B1
1866-6116	ADHD - ATTENTION DEFICIT AND HYPERACTIVITY DISORDERS	A4
1551-9899	ADHOC & SENSOR WIRELESS NETWORKS	B1
1518-9929	ADM. MADE (UNIVERSIDADE ESTÁCIO DE SÁ)	A4
1692-0279	AD-MINISTER	B1
2316-7548	ADMINISTRAÇÃO DE EMPRESAS EM REVISTA	B4
2175-5787	ADMINISTRAÇÃO PÚBLICA E GESTÃO SOCIAL	A4
2177-6083	ADMINISTRAÇÃO: ENSINO E PESQUISA	A3
2500-5227	ADMINISTRACIÓN Y DESARROLLO (VERSÃO DIGITAL)	B4
1015-4833	ADMINISTRATIO PUBLICA	A3
0894-587X	ADMINISTRATION AND POLICY IN MENTAL HEALTH	A1
1005-0078	ADMINISTRATIVE LAW REVIEW	B1
0001-8392	ADMINISTRATIVE SCIENCE QUARTERLY	A1
2076-3387	ADMINISTRATIVE SCIENCES	B1
0751-7696	ADOLESCENCE (PARIS)	B1
2177-5281	ADOLESCÊNCIA & SAÚDE	B4
1679-9941	ADOLESCÊNCIA & SAÚDE (UERJ)	B4
0929-5607	ADSORPTION (BOSTON)	A2
0263-6174	ADSORPTION SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	B1
0342-7633	ADULT EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT	B4
2119-0275	ADVANCED ELECTROMAGNETICS	B1
2199-160X	ADVANCED ELECTRONIC MATERIALS	A2
1474-0346	ADVANCED ENGINEERING INFORMATICS	A1
1438-1656	ADVANCED ENGINEERING MATERIALS (PRINT)	A1
1616-301X	ADVANCED FUNCTIONAL MATERIALS (PRINT)	A1
2192-2659	ADVANCED HEALTHCARE MATERIALS	A1
1521-4095	ADVANCED MATERIALS (ONLINE)	A1
0935-9648	ADVANCED MATERIALS (WEINHEIM PRINT)	A1
2196-7350	ADVANCED MATERIALS INTERFACES	A2
1841-4311	ADVANCED MODELLING AND OPTIMIZATION	A4
1536-1365	ADVANCED NONLINEAR STUDIES	A2
2195-1071	ADVANCED OPTICAL MATERIALS	A1
2251-7308	ADVANCED PHARMACEUTICAL BULLETIN	A3
0921-8831	ADVANCED POWDER TECHNOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
0169-1864	ADVANCED ROBOTICS (PRINT)	A4
2164-6627	ADVANCED SCIENCE, ENGINEERING AND MEDICINE	B2
1615-4150	ADVANCED SYNTHESIS & CATALYSIS (PRINT)	A1
0974-6803	ADVANCES AND APPLICATIONS IN MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES	B4
0065-2113	ADVANCES IN AGRONOMY	A1

2307-8316	ADVANCES IN ANIMAL AND VETERINARY SCIENCES	B3
2040-4700	ADVANCES IN ANIMAL BIOSCIENCES	B4
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1864-8266	ADVANCES IN CALCULUS OF VARIATIONS	A1
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1062-8606	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL QUALITY (PRINT)	A4
1557-9883	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MEN'S HEALTH	A3
0250-8095	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF NEPHROLOGY	A2

0195-6108	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF NEURORADIOLOGY	A1
1097-6868	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
0002-9378	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
2160-8849	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OPERATIONS RESEARCH	B2
0002-9394	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OPHTHALMOLOGY	A1
2451-9936	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OPHTHALMOLOGY CASE REPORTS	B3
0889-5406	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ORTHODONTICS AND DENTOFACIAL ORTHO	A3
0196-0709	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF OTOLARYNGOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
0735-1631	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PERINATOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
0002-9459	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION	A3
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0894-9115	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL MEDICINE & REHABILITATION	A3
1537-7385	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL MEDICINE AND REHABILITATION	A3
0002-9505	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSICS	B1
0363-6143	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY. CELL PHYSIOLOGY	A2
0363-6135	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY. HEART AND CIRCULATORY PI	A1
1040-0605	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY. LUNG CELLULAR AND MOLEC	A1
1522-1490	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY. REGULATORY, INTEGRATIVE	A2
1931-857X	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY. RENAL PHYSIOLOGY	A1
0363-6127	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY. RENAL, FLUID AND ELECTROI	A1
0193-1849	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHYSIOLOGY: ENDOCRINOLOGY AND META	A1
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0092-5853	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF POLITICAL SCIENCE	A1
1099-209X	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF POTATO RESEARCH	A3
0749-3797	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE	A1
0275-2565	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PRIMATOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1548-7776	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PSYCHIATRIC REHABILITATION	B1
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1046-7408	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF REPRODUCTIVE IMMUNOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
1073-449X	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF RESPIRATORY AND CRITICAL CARE MEDICIN	A1
1044-1549	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF RESPIRATORY CELL AND MOLECULAR BIOL	A1
1945-8924	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF RHINOLOGY & ALLERGY (PRINT)	A3
1546-3141	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ROENTGENOLOGY	A2
0361-803X	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ROENTGENOLOGY (1976. PRINT)	A2
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1058-0360	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SPEECH-LANGUAGE PATHOLOGY	A1
0363-5465	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SPORTS MEDICINE	A1
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1600-6135	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF TRANSPLANTATION (PRINT)	A1
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0002-9645	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF VETERINARY RESEARCH	A3
0740-2783	AMERICAN MALACOLOGICAL BULLETIN	B3
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0003-0082	AMERICAN MUSEUM NOVITATES	A1
2313-4410	AMERICAN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR ENGINEERING, TEC	A3
2313-4402	AMERICAN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR ENGINEERING, TEC	A3
1841-964X	AMERICAN, BRITISH AND CANADIAN STUDIES (ONLINE)	B3
2174-0178	AMERICANÍA: REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS LATINOAMERICANOS	B1

2107-0806	AMERIKA	B2
1506-8900	AMERYKA LACINSKA	B1
1438-2199	AMINO ACIDS (WIEN. INTERNET)	A2
0719-997X	AMOXTLI	B3
1083-446X	AMPHIBIAN & REPTILE CONSERVATION	A4
2640-4141	AMPHIBIAN ARK NEWSLETTER	B4
1350-6129	AMYLOID (CARNFORTH)	A2
2167-8421	AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS AND FRONTOTEMPORAL DEGEI	A2
0212-9728	AN PSICOL-SPAIN	A2
1075-9964	ANAEROBE (LONDON. PRINT)	A3
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1642-5758	ANAESTHESIOLOGY INTENSIVE THERAPY	A4
1692-2522	ANAGRAMAS RUMBOS Y SENTIDOS DE LA COMUNICACION	A3
1518-6539	ANAIS ... SIMPÓSIO DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA PRODUÇÃO, LOGÍSTICA	B4
0365-0596	ANAIS BRASILEIROS DE DERMATOLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	B2
0001-3765	ANAIS DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS (IMPRESSO)	A2
1980-0258	ANAIS DA ACADEMIA PERNAMBUCANA DE CIÊNCIA AGRONÔMICA	B4
1982-5323	ANAIS DE FILOSOFIA CLÁSSICA (ONLINE)	B1
0874-9671	ANAIS DE HISTÓRIA DE ALÉM-MAR	A4
2317-0239	ANAIS DO ENCONTRO VIRTUAL DE DOCUMENTAÇÃO EM SOFTWARE	B1
0303-7762	ANAIS DO INSTITUTO DE HIGIENE E MEDICINA TROPICAL	B4
2236-0220	ANAIS DO IV CONGRESSO INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCAÇÃO	B3
0101-4714	ANAIS DO MUSEU PAULISTA: HISTÓRIA, CULTURA E MATERIAL (IMP	A2
0373-9260	ANAIS HIDROGRÁFICOS	B4
1948-206X	ANAL PDE	A1
2448-0096	ANALECTA	B1
2027-7458	ANALECTA POLÍTICA	A3
0185-1225	ANALES DE ANTROPOLOGÍA	A1
1138-3399	ANALES DE BIOLOGIA	A4
1697-7904	ANALES DE DOCUMENTACIÓN (INTERNET)	A4
0214-6452	ANALES DE HISTORIA DEL ARTE	B1
2301-1505	ANALES DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN ARQUITECTURA	A4
1025-5583	ANALES DE LA FACULTAD DE MEDICINA	B4
0210-4547	ANALES DE LITERATURA HISPANOAMERICANA	B2
1695-4033	ANALES DE PEDIATRÍA (2003. ED. IMPRESA)	B2
0328-9796	ANALES DEL INSTITUTO DE ARTE AMERICANO E INVESTIGACIONES E	B4
0211-2337	ANALES DEL SEMINARIO DE HISTORIA DE LA FILOSOFÍA	B3
0102-9924	ANÁLISE ECONÔMICA (UFRGS)	A3
2525-457X	ANÁLISE ESTRATÉGICA	B3
2183-9565	ANÁLISE EUROPÉIA	B3
0870-8231	ANÁLISE PSICOLÓGICA	A2
0003-2573	ANÁLISE SOCIAL	A1
2386-8066	ANÁLISIS (ZARAGOZA. 2014)	A4
1696-3466	ANÁLISIS DEL REAL INSTITUTO ELCANO	B3
0121-4705	ANÁLISIS POLÍTICO (BOGOTÁ)	A1
0925-1030	ANALOG INTEGRATED CIRCUITS AND SIGNAL PROCESSING	B1
1678-3468	ANALÓGOS (PUCRJ)	B4
0003-2638	ANALYSIS (OXFORD. PRINT)	A4
0133-3852	ANALYSIS MATHEMATICA (PRINT)	B1
0003-2654	ANALYST (LONDON. 1877. PRINT)	A1

1873-4324	ANALYTICA CHIMICA ACTA (ONLINE)	A1
0003-2670	ANALYTICA CHIMICA ACTA (PRINT)	A1
1414-3004	ANALYTICA. REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA	A2
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1618-2642	ANALYTICAL AND BIOANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A2
0884-6812	ANALYTICAL AND QUANTITATIVE CYTOLOGY AND HISTOLOGY	B2
0003-2697	ANALYTICAL BIOCHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A3
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2214-1812	ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY RESEARCH	B1
0003-2719	ANALYTICAL LETTERS	B1
1759-9660	ANALYTICAL METHODS	A2
0910-6340	ANALYTICAL SCIENCES	B1
2357-8602	ANAMORFOSE - REVISTA DE ESTUDOS MODERNOS	B1
2446-8088	ANAMORPHOSIS - REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE DIREITO E LITERATL	A3
1129-8219	ANANKE	B4
2156-6909	ANATOLIA AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TOURISM AND HOSPIT.	A3
2547-9652	ANATOLIAN JOURNAL OF EDUCATION	B4
0340-2096	ANATOMIA, HISTOLOGIA, EMBRYOLOGIA	A4
1935-9772	ANATOMICAL SCIENCES EDUCATION	A1
0740-2007	ANCIENT PHILOSOPHY	A2
2359-375X	ÂNCORA - REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE JORNALISMO	B1
1870-0063	ANDAMIOS -REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN SOCIAL	B2
0718-7092	ANDEAN GEOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
1439-0272	ANDROLOGIA	A3
0303-4569	ANDROLOGIA (BERLIN)	A3
2047-2919	ANDROLOGY-US	A1
2090-1267	ANEMIA	A4
0003-2999	ANESTHESIA AND ANALGESIA	A2
0003-3006	ANESTHESIA PROGRESS	B1
0003-3022	ANESTHESIOLOGY (PHILADELPHIA)	A1
1521-3773	ANGEWANDTE CHEMIE (INTERNATIONAL ED. INTERNET)	A1
0044-8249	ANGEWANDTE CHEMIE (PRINT)	A1
0969-6970	ANGIOGENESIS (LONDON)	A1
0003-3197	ANGIOLOGY (ROSLYN, N.Y.)	A3
1984-7947	ÂNGULO	B4
0101-191X	ÂNGULO (FATEA. IMPRESSO)	B4
2530-9986	ANIAV - REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN ARTES VISUALES	B3
2183-1750	ANIKI: REVISTA PORTUGUESA DA IMAGEM EM MOVIMENTO	A3
2526-1940	ANIMA TERRA (ONLINE)	B4
2175-7119	ANIMA: REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DA OPET	B4
1751-7311	ANIMAL (CAMBRIDGE. PRINT)	A1
0003-3472	ANIMAL BEHAVIOUR	A1
1578-665X	ANIMAL BIODIVERSITY AND CONSERVATION	A4
1570-7555	ANIMAL BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
1049-5398	ANIMAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	B1
1532-2378	ANIMAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	B1
1435-9448	ANIMAL COGNITION (PRINT)	A1
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1367-9430	ANIMAL CONSERVATION (PRINT)	A2

1873-2216	ANIMAL FEED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	A1
0268-9146	ANIMAL GENETICS (PRINT)	A1
2405-6545	ANIMAL NUTRITION	A3
1836-5787	ANIMAL PRODUCTION SCIENCE	A2
1806-9614	ANIMAL REPRODUCTION	A4
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0378-4320	ANIMAL REPRODUCTION SCIENCE (PRINT)	A2
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2377-7478	ANIMAL SENTIENCE	A2
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2076-2615	ANIMALS	A3
1677-907X	ANIMUS (SANTA MARIA)	A3
2444-5703	ANKULEGI	B1
0003-3804	ANNALEN DER PHYSIK (LEIPZIG)	A2
1239-629X	ANNALES ACADEMIAE SCIENTIARUM FENNICAE. MATHEMATICA (P/	A2
0003-3847	ANNALES BOTANICI FENNICI (PRINT)	B1
0151-9638	ANNALES DE DERMATOLOGIE ET DE VÉNÉRÉOLOGIE	B3
1777-5884	ANNALES DE GÉOGRAPHIE (PARIS)	B3
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0037-9271	ANNALES DE LA SOCIÉTÉ ENTOMOLOGIQUE DE FRANCE	B2
1370-4788	ANNALES DE L'ÉCONOMIE PUBLIQUE, SOCIALE ET COOPÉRATIVE (EI	B1
0246-0203	ANNALES DE L'I.H.P. PROBABILITÉS ET STATISTIQUES	A2
0003-4088	ANNALES DE LIMNOLOGIE	B1
0373-0956	ANNALES DE L'INSTITUT FOURIER	A2
2308-5835	ANNALES DE L'INSTITUT HENRI POINCARÉ (D) COMBINATORICS, PH'	A2
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0003-4347	ANNALES DES TELECOMMUNICATIONS	A4
2526-0782	ANNALES FAJE (ONLINE)	B4
1879-7261	ANNALES FRANCAISES D'OTO-RHINO-LARYNGOLOGIE ET DE PATHOI	B4
1432-0576	ANNALES GEOPHYSICAE	A3
1424-0637	ANNALES HENRI POINCARÉ (PRINT)	A2
1259-1734	ANNALES MATHÉMATIQUES BLAISE PASCAL	B1
2195-4755	ANNALES MATHÉMATIQUES DU QUÉBEC	A4
0012-9593	ANNALES SCIENTIFIQUES DE L'ECOLE NORMALE SUPÉRIEURE	A1
0003-4541	ANNALES ZOOLOGICI	A4
0003-455X	ANNALES ZOOLOGICI FENNICI (PRINT)	A4
0391-173X	ANNALI DELLA SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE DI PISA. CLASSE DI SC	A1
2384-8553	ANNALI DELL'ISTITUTO SUPERIORE DI SANITÀ	B3
0430-3202	ANNALI DELL'UNIVERSITÀ DI FERRARA. SEZIONE 7: SCIENZE MATEM	B2
0373-3114	ANNALI DI MATEMATICA PURA ED APPLICATA	A2
1221-4639	ANNALS OF "DUNAREA DE JOS" UNIVERSITY OF GALATI, FASCICLE XI	B3
1512-1887	ANNALS OF AGRARIAN SCIENCE	B3
1898-2263	ANNALS OF AGRICULTURAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICINE	B3
1081-1206	ANNALS OF ALLERGY, ASTHMA & IMMUNOLOGY	A3
0940-9602	ANNALS OF ANATOMY	A4
2300-8733	ANNALS OF ANIMAL SCIENCE	A3
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0090-6964	ANNALS OF BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING	A1
0305-7364	ANNALS OF BOTANY (PRINT)	A1
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2304-1021	ANNALS OF CARDIOTHORACIC SURGERY	A3
2328-9503	ANNALS OF CLINICAL AND TRANSLATIONAL NEUROLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
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1476-0711	ANNALS OF CLINICAL MICROBIOLOGY AND ANTIMICROBIALS	A2
1040-1237	ANNALS OF CLINICAL PSYCHIATRY	B2
2287-9714	ANNALS OF COLOPROCTOLOGY.	B2
0218-0006	ANNALS OF COMBINATORICS (PRINT)	B1
2198-5812	ANNALS OF DATA SCIENCE	A3
1013-9087	ANNALS OF DERMATOLOGY	A4
1092-9134	ANNALS OF DIAGNOSTIC PATHOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
0196-0644	ANNALS OF EMERGENCY MEDICINE	A3
1047-2797	ANNALS OF EPIDEMIOLOGY	A2
1544-1709	ANNALS OF FAMILY MEDICINE	A1
1614-2446	ANNALS OF FINANCE (PRINT)	A3
2010-4960	ANNALS OF FINANCIAL ECONOMICS	A4
1844-8135	ANNALS OF FOREST RESEARCH	A3
1286-4560	ANNALS OF FOREST SCIENCE (PRINT)	A2
2008-8752	ANNALS OF FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS	B2
1744-859X	ANNALS OF GENERAL PSYCHIATRY	A4
1593-5213	ANNALS OF GEOPHYSICS	B2
0260-3055	ANNALS OF GLACIOLOGY	A2
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2214-9996	ANNALS OF GLOBAL HEALTH	A1
0939-5555	ANNALS OF HEMATOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
1665-2681	ANNALS OF HEPATOLOGY	B2
0301-4460	ANNALS OF HUMAN BIOLOGY	A3
0003-4800	ANNALS OF HUMAN GENETICS (PRINT)	B2
2110-5820	ANNALS OF INTENSIVE CARE	A1
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2234-3806	ANNALS OF LABORATORY MEDICINE	B1
2159-6816	ANNALS OF LEISURE RESEARCH (ONLINE)	A1
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2231-0746	ANNALS OF MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY	B1
0785-3890	ANNALS OF MEDICINE (HELSINKI)	A1
2049-0801	ANNALS OF MEDICINE AND SURGERY	A4
1590-4261	ANNALS OF MICROBIOLOGY	A4
0364-5134	ANNALS OF NEUROLOGY	A1
0972-7531	ANNALS OF NEUROSCIENCES	B2
1082-720X	ANNALS OF NONINVASIVE ELECTROCARDIOLOGY	B1
0306-4549	ANNALS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY	A2
0914-7187	ANNALS OF NUCLEAR MEDICINE	A4
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2052-4374	ANNALS OF OCCUPATIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICINE	B1
1569-8041	ANNALS OF ONCOLOGY	A1
0254-5330	ANNALS OF OPERATION RESEARCH	A3
2224-5820	ANNALS OF PALLIATIVE MEDICINE	A1
2299-0631	ANNALS OF PARASITOLOGY	A2
0974-2069	ANNALS OF PEDIATRIC CARDIOLOGY	B3
2373-9312	ANNALS OF PEDIATRICS & CHILD HEALTH	A1

1440-1754	ANNALS OF PEDIATRICS AND CHILD HEALTH	B1
1877-0657	ANNALS OF PHYSICAL AND REHABILITATION MEDICINE	A1
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2288-6575	ANNALS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT AND RESEARCH (IMPRESSO)	B1
1958-9395	ANNALS OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS	A4
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0077-8923	ANNALS OF THE NEW YORK ACADEMY OF SCIENCES	A1
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1146-7363	ANNUAIRE D'HISTOIRE DU VAL ET DE LA VILLE DE MUNSTER	B4
2347-565X	ANNUAL RESEARCH & REVIEW IN BIOLOGY	B2
2165-8110	ANNUAL REVIEW OF ANIMAL BIOSCIENCES	A1
0066-4146	ANNUAL REVIEW OF ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS (PRINT)	A1
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0066-4170	ANNUAL REVIEW OF ENTOMOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
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1543-5008	ANNUAL REVIEW OF PLANT BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1883-9452	ANNUAL REVIEW OF THE TOKAI SOCIOLOGICAL SOCIETY	B4
0003-5157	ANNUARIUM HISTORIAE CONCILIORUM	B3
0104-236X	ANOS 90 (UFRGS. IMPRESSO)	A2
0954-1020	ANTARCTIC SCIENCE (PRINT)	A4
1984-4921	ANTARES: LETRAS E HUMANIDADES	A4
2317-0824	ANTHESIS	B3
2076-2704	ANTHROPÍA	B3
0254-9212	ANTHROPOLOGICA	A2
2526-3781	ANTHROPOLÓGICAS VISUAL	B4
0702-8997	ANTHROPOLOGIE ET SOCIÉTÉS	A3
1364-8470	ANTHROPOLOGY & MEDICINE	A3
1609-9168	ANTHROPOLOGY OF FOOD	B1
0268-540X	ANTHROPOLOGY TODAY	A4
0892-7936	ANTHROZOOS (HANOVER)	A1
2079-6382	ANTIBIOTICS-BASEL	A1
2073-4468	ANTIBODIES	A3
1871-5206	ANTI-CANCER AGENTS IN MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY	A4
0959-4973	ANTI-CANCER DRUGS	A4

0250-7005	ANTICANCER RESEARCH	B1
2211-3533	ANTI-EFFECTIVE AGENTS	B3
2314-3908	ANTIGUOS JESUITAS EN IBEROAMÉRICA	A4
1098-6596	ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS AND CHEMOTHERAPY (ONLINE)	A1
2047-2994	ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE AND INFECTION CONTROL	A1
1523-0864	ANTIOXIDANTS & REDOX SIGNALLING	A1
1900-5407	ANTIPODA REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGIA Y ARQUEOLOGIA	B1
1467-8330	ANTIPODE (ONLINE)	A1
0066-4812	ANTIPODE (OXFORD. PRINT)	A1
0003-598X	ANTIQUITY (CAMBRIDGE)	A1
1984-3356	ANTÍTESES (LONDRINA)	A1
0003-603X	ANTITRUST BULLETIN	A2
0166-3542	ANTIVIRAL RESEARCH	A1
1359-6535	ANTIVIRAL THERAPY (LONDON)	A4
0003-6072	ANTONIE VAN LEEUWENHOEK (GEDRUKT)	B1
2183-1386	ANTROPE	B3
1414-7378	ANTROPOLÍTICA (UFF)	A2
2281-4043	ANTROPOLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	A3
1390-4256	ANTROPOLOGÍA CUADERNOS DE INVESTIGACIÓN	B2
0870-0990	ANTROPOLOGIA PORTUGUESA	B1
0873-819X	ANTROPOLÓGICAS (PORTO)	A4
1695-9752	ANTROPÓLOGOS IBEROAMERICANOS EN RED (ED. IMPRESA)	A1
2239-625X	ANUAC RIVISTA DELL'ASSOCIAZIONE NAZIONALI UNIVERSITARIA AN	A4
2014-1416	ANUARI DE FILOLOGIA. LITERATURES CONTEMPORÀNIES	A1
0102-4302	ANUÁRIO ANTROPOLÓGICO	A2
2357-738X	ANUÁRIO ANTROPOLÓGICO	A2
1980-9484	ANUÁRIO BRASILEIRO DE DIREITO INTERNACIONAL	B4
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1510-4974	ANUARIO DE DERECHO CONSTITUCIONAL LATINOAMERICANO	B2
0210-5810	ANUARIO DE ESTUDIOS AMERICANOS (ED. IMPRESA)	A1
0377-7316	ANUARIO DE ESTUDIOS CENTROAMERICANOS	B1
0518-0872	ANUARIO DE FILOSOFÍA DEL DERECHO	B4
0122-2066	ANUARIO DE HISTORIA REGIONAL Y DE LAS FRONTERAS	B4
1317-0953	ANUÁRIO DE LA INTEGRACIÓN REGIONAL DE AMÉRICA LATINA E EL	B2
2448-8224	ANUARIO DE LETRAS. LINGÜÍSTICA Y FILOLOGÍA	B1
2175-7917	ANUÁRIO DE LITERATURA	A4
0066-5126	ANUARIO DE PSICOLOGÍA	B3
1666-6836	ANUARIO DEL CENTRO DE ESTUDIOS HISTÓRICOS PROFESOR CARLC	A4
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2526-592X	AORISTO - INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHENOMENOLOGY, HERM	B3
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0268-7038	APHASIOLOGY (LONDON)	A1
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2166-532X	APL MATERIALS	A1
0903-4641	APMIS. ACTA PATHOLOGICA, MICROBIOLOGICA ET IMMUNOLOGIC/	A3
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0195-6663	APPETITE (LONDON. PRINT)	A1
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2168-0450	APPLICATIONS IN PLANT SCIENCES	A4
0862-7940	APPLICATIONS OF MATHEMATICS (PRAHA)	B2
0003-682X	APPLIED ACOUSTICS	A2
2196-4351	APPLIED ADHESION SCIENCE	B1
1098-5336	APPLIED AND ENVIRONMENTAL MICROBIOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
1687-7667	APPLIED AND ENVIRONMENTAL SOIL SCIENCE	A3
0168-1591	APPLIED ANIMAL BEHAVIOUR SCIENCE (PRINT)	A2
0883-9514	APPLIED ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	B2
0273-2289	APPLIED BIOCHEMISTRY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	A3
2468-0842	APPLIED BIOLOGICAL CHEMISTRY	B1
0926-860X	APPLIED CATALYSIS. A, GENERAL (PRINT)	A1
0926-3373	APPLIED CATALYSIS. B, ENVIRONMENTAL (PRINT)	A1
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1054-4887	APPLIED COMPUTATIONAL ELECTROMAGNETICS SOCIETY JOURNAL	B1
2210-8327	APPLIED COMPUTING AND INFORMATICS	B1
2572-6846	APPLIED EARTH SCIENCE (ONLINE)	B3
1589-1623	APPLIED ECOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH (PRINT)	B1
1466-4291	APPLIED ECONOMIC LETTERS	A2
1466-4283	APPLIED ECONOMICS (ONLINE)	A1
2332-7294	APPLIED ECONOMICS AND FINANCE	B3
1350-4851	APPLIED ECONOMICS LETTERS (PRINT)	A2
0306-2619	APPLIED ENERGY	A1
0883-8542	APPLIED ENGINEERING IN AGRICULTURE	A4
0003-6862	APPLIED ENTOMOLOGY AND ZOOLOGY	A4
0003-6870	APPLIED ERGONOMICS	A1
2374-2429	APPLIED FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING	B4
0883-2927	APPLIED GEOCHEMISTRY	A2
0143-6228	APPLIED GEOGRAPHY (SEVENOAKS)	A1
1866-9298	APPLIED GEOMATICS	A1

1175-5652	APPLIED HEALTH ECONOMICS AND HEALTH POLICY	A2
1179-1896	APPLIED HEALTH ECONOMICS AND HEALTH POLICY	A2
1541-2016	APPLIED IMMUNOHISTOCHEMISTRY & MOLECULAR MORPHOLOGY	A3
0924-669X	APPLIED INTELLIGENCE (BOSTON)	A3
1868-6311	APPLIED LINGUISTICS REVIEW	A3
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1350-486X	APPLIED MATHEMATICAL FINANCE (PRINT)	B1
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0893-9659	APPLIED MATHEMATICS LETTERS	A2
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2364-8228	APPLIED NETWORK SCIENCE	B4
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1559-128X	APPLIED OPTICS	A2
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1077-3118	APPLIED PHYSICS LETTERS	A1
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1359-4311	APPLIED THERMAL ENGINEERING	A1
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2359-246X	APRENDER é CADERNO DE FILOSOFIA E PSICOLOGIA DA EDUCAÇÃO	B3
2256-5779	APUNTES DEL CENES	A4
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2193-567X	ARABIAN JOURNAL FOR SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING (IMPRESSO)	B1
1878-5352	ARABIAN JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY	A2
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0003-7982	ARCADIA - INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR LITERARY STUDIES	A4
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1359-2998	ARCHIVES OF DISEASE IN CHILDHOOD. FETAL AND NEONATAL EDITI	A1
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0932-0067	ARCHIVES OF GYNECOLOGY AND OBSTETRICS (PRINT)	A3
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1677-809X	ARGUMENTUM	A3
1583-2767	ARGUMENTUM - JOURNAL OF THE SEMINAR OF DISCURSIVE LOGIC,	B4
2069-573X	ARGUMENTUM - JOURNAL OF THE SEMINAR OF DISCURSIVE LOGIC,	B4
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2174-856X	ARKEOGAZTE	B1
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1551-7004	ARKIVOC	B2
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1989-4104	ARQUEOLOGÍA IBEROAMERICANA.	A4
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2250-4206	ARQUISUR REVISTA	A4
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0381-7032	ARS COMBINATORIA	B4
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1516-8603	ARTCULTURA (UFU)	A3
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2448-3338	ARTE & ENSAIOS	B1
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2151-4658	ARTHRITIS CARE & RESEARCH (ONLINE)	A2
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2525-8303	ARTICULANDO E CONSTRUINDO SABERES	B1
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1177-2719	BIOMARKER INSIGHTS	B2
1354-750X	BIOMARKERS (LONDON. PRINT)	B1
1752-0363	BIOMARKERS IN MEDICINE (PRINT)	A4
0961-9534	BIOMASS & BIOENERGY	A1
2190-6815	BIOMASS CONVERSION AND BIOREFINERY	B1
0142-9612	BIOMATERIALS (GUILDFORD)	A1
2047-4830	BIOMATERIALS SCIENCE	A1
2314-6141	BIOMED RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	A3
2314-6133	BIOMED RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	A3
0120-4157	BIOMÉDICA (BOGOTÁ)	B2
0895-3988	BIOMEDICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	A3
0974-6242	BIOMEDICAL AND PHARMACOLOGY JOURNAL	B3
0006-3398	BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING	B2
1475-925X	BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING ONLINE (ONLINE)	A2
2299-3932	BIOMEDICAL GLASSES	B3
2080-2234	BIOMEDICAL HUMAN KINETICS	B3
2319-4170	BIOMEDICAL JOURNAL (PRINT)	A3
1748-6041	BIOMEDICAL MATERIALS (BRISTOL. PRINT)	A3
0959-2989	BIO-MEDICAL MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING	B3
1878-3619	BIO-MEDICAL MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING	B3
1387-2176	BIOMEDICAL MICRODEVICES (PRINT)	A3
2156-7085	BIOMEDICAL OPTICS EXPRESS	A1
2057-1976	BIOMEDICAL PHYSICS & ENGINEERING EXPRESS	A4
2049-9434	BIOMEDICAL REPORTS	A4
0388-6107	BIOMEDICAL RESEARCH (TOKYO)	B1
1746-8094	BIOMEDICAL SIGNAL PROCESSING AND CONTROL (PRINT)	A1
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0013-5585	BIOMEDIZINISCHE TECHNIK (BERLIN. ZEITSCHRIFT)	B3
0966-0844	BIOMETALS (OXFORD)	A3
0323-3847	BIOMETRICAL JOURNAL (1977)	A3
0006-341X	BIOMETRICS (WASHINGTON)	A1
1932-1058	BIOMICROFLUIDICS	A3
1874-2718	BIOMOLECULAR NMR ASSIGNMENTS (PRINT)	B4
2218-273X	BIOMOLECULES	A1
1679-8074	BIOMOTRIZ (UNICRUZ)	B4
2191-1630	BIONANOSCIENCE (IMPRESSO)	B2
1179-7649	BIONOMINA (PRINT)	B4
0968-0896	BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A2
0960-894X	BIOORGANIC & MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY LETTERS (PRINT)	A2
0045-2068	BIOORGANIC CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A2
0301-4622	BIOPHYSICAL CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A4
0006-3495	BIOPHYSICAL JOURNAL (PRINT)	A2
1867-2450	BIOPHYSICAL REVIEWS	A3
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1947-5543	BIOPRESERVATION AND BIOBANKING	A4
1615-7591	BIOPROCESS AND BIOSYSTEMS ENGINEERING (PRINT)	A2
2164-7860	BIORESEARCH OPEN ACCESS	A2
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1517-9664	BIOSAÚDE (LONDRINA)	B3
0006-3568	BIOSCIENCE (WASHINGTON. PRINT)	A1
1981-3163	BIOSCIENCE JOURNAL (ONLINE)	B1
0144-8463	BIOSCIENCE REPORTS	A3
1573-4935	BIOSCIENCE REPORTS	A3
0916-8451	BIOSCIENCE, BIOTECHNOLOGY, AND BIOCHEMISTRY	B1
2079-6374	BIOSENSORS	A3
0956-5663	BIOSENSORS & BIOELECTRONICS	A1
1745-8552	BIOSOCIETIES (PRINT)	A2
1465-4644	BIOSTATISTICS (OXFORD. PRINT)	A2
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2179-5746	BIOTA AMAZÔNIA	B4
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1678-6424	BIOTA NEOTROPICA (EDIÇÃO EM PORTUGUÊS. IMPRESSO)	B1
1052-0295	BIOTECHNIC & HISTOCHEMISTRY	A4
0736-6205	BIOTECHNIQUES	A4
1310-2818	BIOTECHNOLOGY & BIOTECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT (SOFIA)	B1
0734-9750	BIOTECHNOLOGY ADVANCES	A1
0885-4513	BIOTECHNOLOGY AND APPLIED BIOCHEMISTRY	A4
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1226-8372	BIOTECHNOLOGY AND BIOPROCESS ENGINEERING (SEOUL. PRINT)	B1
1754-6834	BIOTECHNOLOGY FOR BIOFUELS	A1
1860-7314	BIOTECHNOLOGY JOURNAL (INTERNET)	A2
1860-6768	BIOTECHNOLOGY JOURNAL (PRINT)	A2
0141-5492	BIOTECHNOLOGY LETTERS	A4
1573-6776	BIOTECHNOLOGY LETTERS (DORDRECHT. ONLINE)	A4
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8756-7938	BIOTECHNOLOGY PROGRESS (PRINT)	A3
2215-017X	BIOTECHNOLOGY REPORTS	A2
2452-0721	BIOTECHNOLOGY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION	A4
1780-4507	BIOTECHNOLOGY, AGRONOMY AND SOCIETY AND ENVIRONMENT	B1
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2175-7925	BIOTEMAS	B4
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2352-5738	BIOTRIBOLOGY	A4
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1542-0752	BIRTH DEFECTS RESEARCH. CLINICAL AND MOLECULAR TERATOLOG	A2
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1079-9796	BLOOD CELLS, MOLECULES & DISEASES (PRINT)	B1
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1651-1999	BLOOD PRESSURE (ONLINE)	A3
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2447-8504	BOLETIM CEARENSE DE EDUCAÇÃO E HISTÓRIA DA MATEMÁTICA	B2
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0214-7807	BOLETÍN DAS CIENCIAS	B2
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0524-9767	BOLETÍN DEL INSTITUTO DE HISTORIA ARGENTINA Y AMERICANA DC	A2
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2156-5163	BOLIVIAN STUDIES JOURNAL	B4
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0268-3369	BONE MARROW TRANSPLANTATION (BASINGSTOKE)	A2
1476-5365	BONE MARROW TRANSPLANTATION (ONLINE)	A2
2352-1872	BONE REPORTS	B2
2190-7307	BONN ZOOLOGICAL BULLETIN	A3
0210-5934	BORDON: REVISTA DE PEDAGOGIA	A2
0304-8799	BOSQUE (VALDIVIA. IMPRESA)	B1
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1821-2638	BOTANICA SERBICA	B2
0024-4074	BOTANICAL JOURNAL OF THE LINNEAN SOCIETY (PRINT)	A2
2007-4476	BOTANICAL SCIENCES	B2
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1687-2762	BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEMS (PRINT)	B2
1573-1472	BOUNDARY-LAYER METEOROLOGY (DORDRECHT. ONLINE)	A3
2357-7681	BPC PAPERS	B4
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1538-4721	BRACHYTHERAPY (NEW YORK, N.Y.)	A3
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0524-2053	BRASÍLIA MÉDICA	B2

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2359-0599	CAMINHO ABERTO: REVISTA DE EXTENSÃO DO IFSC	A4
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1809-6271	CAMPO - TERRITÓRIO	A2
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1480-3291	CANADIAN JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY	B1
0008-4042	CANADIAN JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	B1
0315-1468	CANADIAN JOURNAL OF CIVIL ENGINEERING (PRINT)	A4
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0706-652X	CANADIAN JOURNAL OF FISHERIES AND AQUATIC SCIENCES (PRINT)	A2
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0008-4174	CANADIAN JOURNAL OF OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY (1939)	A2
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0733-8651	CARDIOLOGY CLINICS	A4
1061-5377	CARDIOLOGY IN REVIEW (PRINT)	A4
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1923-2829	CARDIOLOGY RESEARCH	B4
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1868-4300	CARDIOVASCULAR INTERVENTION AND THERAPEUTICS	B1
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2090-6501	CASE REPORTS IN ENDOCRINOLOGY (IMPRESSO)	B2
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2090-6765	CASE REPORTS IN OTOLARYNGOLOGY	B4
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1869-5590	CEAS AERONAUTICAL JOURNAL	A3
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1432-0878	CELL & TISSUE RESEARCH (INTERNET)	A2
0092-8674	CELL (CAMBRIDGE)	A1
1933-6918	CELL ADHESION & MIGRATION	A2
2045-3701	CELL AND BIOSCIENCE	A2
1389-9333	CELL AND TISSUE BANKING	A4
0302-766X	CELL AND TISSUE RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2
1085-9195	CELL BIOCHEMISTRY AND BIOPHYSICS	B1

0263-6484	CELL BIOCHEMISTRY AND FUNCTION	B1
0742-2091	CELL BIOLOGY AND TOXICOLOGY	A1
1095-8355	CELL BIOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	A4
1065-6995	CELL BIOLOGY INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	A4
0143-4160	CELL CALCIUM (EDINBURGH)	A2
2451-9456	CELL CHEMICAL BIOLOGY	A1
1478-811X	CELL COMMUNICATION AND SIGNALING	A2
1538-4101	CELL CYCLE (GEORGETOWN, TEX.)	B1
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1350-9047	CELL DEATH AND DIFFERENTIATION	A1
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1462-5814	CELLULAR MICROBIOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
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1570-5870	CELLULAR ONCOLOGY	A1
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2152-4971	CELLULAR REPROGRAMMING	A4
2152-4998	CELLULAR REPROGRAMMING	A4
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0008-8846	CEMENT AND CONCRETE RESEARCH	A1
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2177-1960	CENÁRIOS: REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DA LINGUAGEM	B1
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0254-2129	CHASQUI. REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DA COMUNICACIÓN	A2
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1521-4125	CHEMICAL ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY (INTERNET)	A2
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0263-8762	CHEMICAL ENGINEERING RESEARCH & DESIGN	A1
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2153-2168	CHILDHOOD OBESITY	A1
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1815-2406	COMMUNICATIONS IN COMPUTATIONAL PHYSICS (PRINT)	A2
1865-0929	COMMUNICATIONS IN COMPUTER AND INFORMATION SCIENCE (PF	B2
0219-1997	COMMUNICATIONS IN CONTEMPORARY MATHEMATICS	A1
0010-3616	COMMUNICATIONS IN MATHEMATICAL PHYSICS	A1
1539-6746	COMMUNICATIONS IN MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES	A3
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1007-5704	COMMUNICATIONS IN NONLINEAR SCIENCE & NUMERICAL SIMULA	A3
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2237-4027	COMMUNICATIONS IN PLANT SCIENCES	B4
0010-3624	COMMUNICATIONS IN SOIL SCIENCE AND PLANT ANALYSIS	B1
1532-2416	COMMUNICATIONS IN SOIL SCIENCE AND PLANT ANALYSIS	B1
1532-415X	COMMUNICATIONS IN STATISTICS, THEORY AND METHODS (ONLINI	B2
0361-0918	COMMUNICATIONS IN STATISTICS. SIMULATION AND COMPUTATIC	B2
2373-7484	COMMUNICATIONS IN STATISTICS: CASE STUDIES, DATA ANALYSIS /	B4
1532-4141	COMMUNICATIONS IN STATISTICS: SIMULATION AND COMPUTATIC	B2
0253-6102	COMMUNICATIONS IN THEORETICAL PHYSICS	B1
0001-0782	COMMUNICATIONS OF THE ACM	A1
1534-0392	COMMUNICATIONS ON PURE AND APPLIED ANALYSIS	A2
0010-3640	COMMUNICATIONS ON PURE AND APPLIED MATHEMATICS (PRINT)	A1
1942-0889	COMMUNICATIVE & INTEGRATIVE BIOLOGY	A3
0265-539X	COMMUNITY DENTAL HEALTH	A4
0301-5661	COMMUNITY DENTISTRY AND ORAL EPIDEMIOLOGY	A1
1600-0528	COMMUNITY DENTISTRY AND ORAL EPIDEMIOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
1557-5330	COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT (COLUMBUS, OHIO)	A3
1468-2656	COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT JOURNAL (ONLINE)	B3
1585-8553	COMMUNITY ECOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
0010-3853	COMMUNITY MENTAL HEALTH JOURNAL	A4
2531-7547	COMPARATISMI: RIVISTA DELLA CONSULTA DI CRITICA LETTERARIA	B3
1532-0456	COMPARATIVE BIOCHEMISTRY AND PHYSIOLOGY. C. TOXICOLOGY &	A2
1095-6433	COMPARATIVE BIOCHEMISTRY AND PHYSIOLOGY. PART A, MOLECU	A2
1531-4332	COMPARATIVE BIOCHEMISTRY AND PHYSIOLOGY. PART A, MOLECU	A2
1096-4959	COMPARATIVE BIOCHEMISTRY AND PHYSIOLOGY. PART B: BIOCHEN	A3
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1755-2559	COMPARATIVE EXERCISE PHYSIOLOGY	B3

0147-9571	COMPARATIVE IMMUNOLOGY, MICROBIOLOGY AND INFECTIOUS D	A1
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0332-1649	COMPEL (BRADFORD)	B1
1548-8578	COMPENDIUM OF CONTINUING EDUCATION IN DENTISTRY (JAMESI	A4
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1744-3881	COMPLEMENTARY THERAPIES IN CLINICAL PRACTICE	A2
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0891-2513	COMPLEX SYSTEMS	B3
1747-6941	COMPLEX VARIABLES AND ELLIPTIC EQUATIONS (ONLINE)	B1
1747-6933	COMPLEX VARIABLES AND ELLIPTIC EQUATIONS (PRINT)	B1
1099-0526	COMPLEXITY	A2
1076-2787	COMPLEXITY (NEW YORK, N.Y.)	A2
0927-6440	COMPOSITE INTERFACES (PRINT)	A4
0263-8223	COMPOSITE STRUCTURES	A1
0266-3538	COMPOSITES SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	A1
1359-835X	COMPOSITES. PART A, APPLIED SCIENCE AND MANUFACTURING	A1
1359-8368	COMPOSITES. PART B, ENGINEERING	A1
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2040-4603	COMPREHENSIVE PHYSIOLOGY	A1
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1631-0721	COMPTES RENDUS. MÉCANIQUE	A4
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0101-8205	COMPUTATIONAL & APPLIED MATHEMATICS	B1
1748-670X	COMPUTATIONAL AND MATHEMATICAL METHODS IN MEDICINE (P	A3
1381-298X	COMPUTATIONAL AND MATHEMATICAL ORGANIZATION THEORY	B1
2210-271X	COMPUTATIONAL AND THEORETICAL CHEMISTRY	A4
1476-9271	COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY AND CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A3
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1572-9974	COMPUTATIONAL ECONOMICS (ONLINE)	B1
1420-0597	COMPUTATIONAL GEOSCIENCES (AMSTERDAM)	A2
1467-8640	COMPUTATIONAL INTELLIGENCE (ONLINE)	A2
1687-5265	COMPUTATIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND NEUROSCIENCE	A2
0891-2017	COMPUTATIONAL LINGUISTICS	A1
0927-0256	COMPUTATIONAL MATERIALS SCIENCE	A3
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1505-0602	COMPUTATIONAL METHODS IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	B3

0926-6003	COMPUTATIONAL OPTIMIZATION AND APPLICATIONS	A4
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0167-8396	COMPUTER AIDED GEOMETRIC DESIGN	B1
1061-3773	COMPUTER APPLICATIONS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION	A3
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0140-3664	COMPUTER COMMUNICATIONS	A2
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1477-8424	COMPUTER LANGUAGES, SYSTEMS & STRUCTURES	A3
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1025-5842	COMPUTER METHODS IN BIOMECHANICS AND BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING	A4
1476-8259	COMPUTER METHODS IN BIOMECHANICS AND BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING	A4
2168-1171	COMPUTER METHODS IN BIOMECHANICS AND BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING	B1
1526-1492	COMPUTER MODELING IN ENGINEERING & SCIENCES	B2
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0898-1221	COMPUTERS & MATHEMATICS WITH APPLICATIONS (1987)	A4
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2237-8049	CONHECIMENTO & DIVERSIDADE	B1
1809-3442	CONHECIMENTO INTERATIVO	B4
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0010-5945	CONJUNTURA ECONOMICA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B1
2317-6563	CONJUNTURA GLOBAL	A4
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1676-6016	CONTEXTO (UFRGS)	B4
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2354-0036	CREATIVITY (ONLINE)	A2
1040-0419	CREATIVITY RESEARCH JOURNAL	A2
1532-6934	CREATIVITY RESEARCH JOURNAL	A2
2340-8960	CRENEIDA. ANUARIO DE LITERATURAS HISPANICAS	A4
0195-6671	CRETACEOUS RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2
2317-2452	CRIAR EDUCAÇÃO REVISTA DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM	B2
0925-4994	CRIME, LAW AND SOCIAL CHANGE (PRINT)	A2
1748-8958	CRIMINOLOGY & CRIMINAL JUSTICE (PRINT)	A1
2311-8172	CRISIS AND CRITIQUE (IMPRESSO)	A4
1980-6493	CRÍTICA CULTURAL	B1
2447-4223	CRÍTICA EDUCATIVA	B2
0104-9321	CRITICA MARXISTA (SÃO PAULO)	B2
2014-3753	CRÍTICA PENAL Y PODER	A3
2525-0841	CRITICA Y RESISTENCIAS	B1
2049-8675	CRITICAL AND RADICAL SOCIAL WORK (ONLINE)	A3
0256-0046	CRITICAL ARTS	A3
1364-8535	CRITICAL CARE (LONDON. PRINT)	A1
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0090-3493	CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE	A2
2090-1305	CRITICAL CARE RESEARCH & PRACTICE	A3
1740-5904	CRITICAL DISCOURSE STUDIES (PRINT)	A2
1742-2043	CRITICAL PERSPECTIVES ON INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS	A3
1946-0171	CRITICAL POLICY STUDIES	A2
0958-1596	CRITICAL PUBLIC HEALTH (PRINT)	A2
1040-8347	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY	A2
0738-8551	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN BIOTECHNOLOGY	A1
1064-3389	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	A1
1045-4403	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN EUKARYOTIC GENE EXPRESSION	B1
1549-7852	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN FOOD SCIENCE & NUTRITION	A1
1040-8398	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN FOOD SCIENCE AND NUTRITION	A1
1040-8401	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN IMMUNOLOGY	B2
1040-841X	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN MICROBIOLOGY	A1
1040-8428	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN ONCOLOGY/HEMATOLOGY	A1
0896-2960	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN PHYSICAL AND REHABILITATION MEDICINE	B3
0735-2689	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN PLANT SCIENCES	A1
1040-8444	CRITICAL REVIEWS IN TOXICOLOGY	A1
0896-9205	CRITICAL SOCIOLOGY	A3
0301-7605	CRITIQUE (GLASGOW)	A2
1518-0689	CRONOS (NATAL. IMPRESSO)	B4
1836-0947	CROP & PASTURE SCIENCE (PRINT)	A3
1984-7033	CROP BREEDING AND APPLIED BIOTECHNOLOGY (ONLINE)	A4
0261-2194	CROP PROTECTION	A2
0011-183X	CROP SCIENCE	A2
2374-3832	CROP, FORAGE AND TURFGRASS MANAGEMENT	B2
0011-1953	CROSS CURRENTS	B2
1069-3971	CROSS-CULTURAL RESEARCH	A2
0011-216X	CRUSTACEANA (LEIDEN. PRINT)	B2
0011-2240	CRYOBIOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
0011-2275	CRYOGENICS (GUILDFORD)	A4
0143-2044	CRYO-LETTERS	A2

0181-1568	CRYPTOGAMIE. ALGOLOGIE	A4
1290-0796	CRYPTOGAMIE. BRYOLOGIE	B1
0181-1584	CRYPTOGAMIE. MYCOLOGIE	A2
1528-7483	CRYSTAL GROWTH & DESIGN	A1
2073-4352	CRYSTALS	B1
1466-8033	CRYSTENGCOMM (CAMBRIDGE. ONLINE)	A2
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0719-3483	CUADERNOS CHILENOS DE HISTORIA DE LA EDUCACIÓN	B2
2256-5078	CUADERNOS DE ADMINISTRACIÓN (ONLINE)	B1
0120-3592	CUADERNOS DE ADMINISTRACIÓN. SERIE DE ORGANIZACIONES	A4
1850-275X	CUADERNOS DE ANTROPOLOGÍA SOCIAL (EN LÍNEA)	A2
0327-3776	CUADERNOS DE ANTROPOLOGÍA SOCIAL (IMPRESA)	A2
0210-962X	CUADERNOS DE ARTE DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	B3
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0122-1450	CUADERNOS DE DESARROLLO RURAL	A2
0210-0266	CUADERNOS DE ECONOMÍA	A3
0121-4772	CUADERNOS DE ECONOMÍA (SANTAFÉ DE BOGOTÁ)	B2
1989-4155	CUADERNOS DE EDUCACIÓN Y DESARROLLO	B3
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0121-215X	CUADERNOS DE GEOGRAFÍA	B3
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1575-2410	CUADERNOS DE LA SOCIEDAD ESPAÑOLA DE CIENCIAS FORESTALES	B2
1852-9879	CUADERNOS DE MARTE	B1
1135-7606	CUADERNOS DE MEDICINA FORENSE	B4
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1794-6670	CUADERNOS DE MUSICA, ARTES VISUALES Y ARTES ESCENICAS	A2
2215-9959	CUADERNOS DE MUSICA, ARTES VISUALES Y ARTES ESCENICAS	A2
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2443-468X	CUADERNOS DEL CENDES (EN LÍNEA)	A2
1668-0227	CUADERNOS DEL CENTRO DE ESTUDIOS DE DISEÑO Y COMUNICACI	A3
1515-6125	CUADERNOS DEL CILHA	A3
1666-5112	CUADERNOS DEL CIMBAGE	B1
0797-6062	CUADERNOS DEL CLAEH	B2
2393-5979	CUADERNOS DEL CLAEH	B2
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0718-8749	CUADERNOS JUDAICOS	A2

2262-8339	CUADERNOS LIRICO	A3
2254-4455	CUADERNOS MANUEL GIMÉNEZ ABAD	B1
2451-6821	CUADERNOS MEDIEVALES	B3
1130-7498	CUADERNOS SOBRE VICO	A4
0719-367X	CUADERNOS.INFO	A1
0719-3661	CUADERNOS.INFO	A1
0864-0408	CUBAN JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE	B4
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1405-9193	CUESTIONES CONSTITUCIONALES: REVISTA MEXICANA DE DERECHC	A2
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2346-8904	CUESTIONES DE SOCIOLOGÍA	B1
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1982-5838	CULTUR: REVISTA DE CULTURA E TURISMO	B1
1138-1728	CULTURA DE LOS CUIDADOS	B1
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0122-8455	CULTURA Y DROGA (IMPRESSO)	B1
0718-4727	CULTURA Y RELIGIÓN (EN LÍNEA)	A3
2007-8110	CULTURA Y REPRESENTACIONES SOCIALES	A4
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1871-1510	CULTURAL STUDIES OF SCIENCE EDUCATION (ON LINE)	A1
1816-5435	CULTURAL-HISTORICAL PSYCHOLOGY	A1
1983-5930	CULTURAS MEDIÁTICAS	B4
1354-067X	CULTURE & PSYCHOLOGY	A2
1475-5629	CULTURE AND RELIGION	A3
1369-1058	CULTURE, HEALTH & SEXUALITY (PRINT)	A2
2566-7742	CULTURE, PRACTICE AND EUROPEANIZATION	B3
2261-0758	CULTURES-KAIRÓS	A4
2151-6952	CURATOR	A1
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1567-2050	CURRENT ALZHEIMER RESEARCH	A2
1573-4110	CURRENT ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY	B2
0011-3204	CURRENT ANTHROPOLOGY	A1
1567-1739	CURRENT APPLIED PHYSICS	A4
1523-3804	CURRENT ATHEROSCLEROSIS REPORTS	A4
1573-4072	CURRENT BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS	B1
1574-8936	CURRENT BIOINFORMATICS (PRINT)	B3
0960-9822	CURRENT BIOLOGY	A1
2468-4236	CURRENT BIOMARKERS (ONLINE)	B4
1568-0096	CURRENT CANCER DRUG TARGETS (PRINT)	A4
1523-3782	CURRENT CARDIOLOGY REPORTS (PRINT)	A4
1573-403X	CURRENT CARDIOLOGY REVIEWS	B1
1941-9066	CURRENT CARDIOVASCULAR IMAGING REPORTS	B2
1872-3136	CURRENT CHEMICAL BIOLOGY	B3

2198-6061	CURRENT CLIMATE CHANGE REPORTS	B4
2212-3938	CURRENT CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY	B1
1556-3790	CURRENT COLORECTAL CANCER REPORTS	B2
1573-4099	CURRENT COMPUTER-AIDED DRUG DESIGN	B3
1573-3998	CURRENT DIABETES REVIEWS	A4
1567-2018	CURRENT DRUG DELIVERY	A4
1570-1638	CURRENT DRUG DISCOVERY TECHNOLOGIES	B1
1389-2002	CURRENT DRUG METABOLISM	A3
1873-5592	CURRENT DRUG TARGETS	A2
1389-4501	CURRENT DRUG TARGETS (PRINT)	A2
1574-8855	CURRENT DRUG THERAPY (HILVERSUM)	B2
1573-4080	CURRENT ENZYME INHIBITION	B3
2196-2995	CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGY REPORTS	B2
0271-3683	CURRENT EYE RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2
2198-6436	CURRENT FORESTRY REPORTS	A1
1936-3761	CURRENT FUNGAL INFECTION REPORTS	B2
1936-377X	CURRENT FUNGAL INFECTIONS REPORT	B2
1522-8037	CURRENT GASTROENTEROLOGY REPORTS (PRINT)	A3
1566-5232	CURRENT GENE THERAPY	A4
2167-4876	CURRENT GENETIC MEDICINE REPORTS	B2
0172-8083	CURRENT GENETICS	A3
1389-2029	CURRENT GENOMICS	B1
1687-7063	CURRENT GERONTOLOGY AND GERIATRICS RESEARCH	A4
1570-162X	CURRENT HIV RESEARCH (PRINT)	B1
1522-6417	CURRENT HYPERTENSION REPORTS (PRINT)	A3
1573-3955	CURRENT IMMUNOLOGY REVIEWS	B4
1523-3847	CURRENT INFECTIOUS DISEASE REPORTS (PRINT)	A4
1466-4208	CURRENT ISSUES IN LANGUAGE PLANNING	A2
1467-3037	CURRENT ISSUES IN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
1368-3500	CURRENT ISSUES IN TOURISM (IMPRESSO)	A1
0300-7995	CURRENT MEDICAL RESEARCH AND OPINION	A1
0929-8673	CURRENT MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY	A2
1875-533X	CURRENT MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY	A2
1432-0991	CURRENT MICROBIOLOGY	B1
0343-8651	CURRENT MICROBIOLOGY (PRINT)	B1
1566-5240	CURRENT MOLECULAR MEDICINE	A4
1874-4672	CURRENT MOLECULAR PHARMACOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
1573-4137	CURRENT NANOSCIENCE	A4
1570-159X	CURRENT NEUROPHARMACOLOGY	A1
1567-2026	CURRENT NEUROVASCULAR RESEARCH	B1
2161-3311	CURRENT NUTRITION REPORTS (ONLINE)	A4
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2161-3303	CURRENT OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY REPORTS	B1
1528-4050	CURRENT OPINION IN ALLERGY AND CLINICAL IMMUNOLOGY	A3
0958-1669	CURRENT OPINION IN BIOTECHNOLOGY	A1
2211-3398	CURRENT OPINION IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	A2
1363-1950	CURRENT OPINION IN CLINICAL NUTRITION AND METABOLIC CARE	A1
1359-0294	CURRENT OPINION IN COLLOID & INTERFACE SCIENCE	A1
1070-5295	CURRENT OPINION IN CRITICAL CARE	A2
1752-296X	CURRENT OPINION IN ENDOCRINOLOGY, DIABETES AND OBESITY (P	A2

1877-3435	CURRENT OPINION IN ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY (PRINT)	A1
2214-7993	CURRENT OPINION IN FOOD SCIENCE	A1
0267-1379	CURRENT OPINION IN GASTROENTEROLOGY	A2
2452-2236	CURRENT OPINION IN GREEN AND SUSTAINABLE CHEMISTRY	B2
1065-6251	CURRENT OPINION IN HEMATOLOGY	A2
0951-7375	CURRENT OPINION IN INFECTIOUS DISEASES	A2
2214-5745	CURRENT OPINION IN INSECT SCIENCE	A1
0957-9672	CURRENT OPINION IN LIPIDOLOGY	A2
1369-5274	CURRENT OPINION IN MICROBIOLOGY	A1
1062-4821	CURRENT OPINION IN NEPHROLOGY AND HYPERTENSION	A2
0959-4388	CURRENT OPINION IN NEUROBIOLOGY	A1
1350-7540	CURRENT OPINION IN NEUROLOGY	A1
1040-872X	CURRENT OPINION IN OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY	A1
1040-8746	CURRENT OPINION IN ONCOLOGY	A3
1040-8738	CURRENT OPINION IN OPHTHALMOLOGY	A2
1068-9508	CURRENT OPINION IN OTOLARYNGOLOGY & HEAD AND NECK SURG	A4
1040-8703	CURRENT OPINION IN PEDIATRICS	A1
1369-5266	CURRENT OPINION IN PLANT BIOLOGY	A1
0951-7367	CURRENT OPINION IN PSYCHIATRY	A1
1070-5287	CURRENT OPINION IN PULMONARY MEDICINE	A2
1040-8711	CURRENT OPINION IN RHEUMATOLOGY	A1
0959-440X	CURRENT OPINION IN STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY	A1
1751-4258	CURRENT OPINION IN SUPPORTIVE AND PALLIATIVE CARE	A3
1879-6257	CURRENT OPINION IN VIROLOGY	A1
2196-3002	CURRENT ORAL HEALTH REPORTS	B1
1385-2728	CURRENT ORGANIC CHEMISTRY	A4
1570-1794	CURRENT ORGANIC SYNTHESIS	B1
1544-1873	CURRENT OSTEOPOROSIS REPORTS	A2
1534-3081	CURRENT PAIN AND HEADACHE REPORTS (ONLINE)	A3
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1573-4129	CURRENT PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS	B1
1389-2010	CURRENT PHARMACEUTICAL BIOTECHNOLOGY (PRINT)	B1
1381-6128	CURRENT PHARMACEUTICAL DESIGN (PRINT)	A3
1875-6921	CURRENT PHARMACOGENOMICS AND PERSONALIZED MEDICINE: TI	B4
2214-6628	CURRENT PLANT BIOLOGY	A2
0146-2806	CURRENT PROBLEMS IN CARDIOLOGY	A3
1389-2037	CURRENT PROTEIN AND PEPTIDE SCIENCE	A4
1570-1646	CURRENT PROTEOMICS	B4
2160-4762	CURRENT PROTOCOLS IN CHEMICAL	A3
1934-3663	CURRENT PROTOCOLS IN PROTEIN SCIENCE	B2
1523-3812	CURRENT PSYCHIATRY REPORTS	A1
1046-1310	CURRENT PSYCHOLOGY (NEW BRUNSWICK, N.J.)	B1
1874-4710	CURRENT RADIOPHARMACEUTICALS	B1
2229-2225	CURRENT RESEARCH IN ENVIRONMENTAL & APPLIED MYCOLOGY	B3
1573-398X	CURRENT RESPIRATORY MEDICINE REVIEWS	B2
1935-9748	CURRENT REVIEWS IN MUSCULOSKELETAL MEDICINE	A3
1523-3774	CURRENT RHEUMATOLOGY REPORTS	A3
0011-3891	CURRENT SCIENCE (BANGALORE)	A3
1548-3592	CURRENT SEXUAL HEALTH REPORTS	B4

0011-3921	CURRENT SOCIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1574-888X	CURRENT STEM CELL RESEARCH AND THERAPY	A4
1568-0266	CURRENT TOPICS IN MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A2
0070-217X	CURRENT TOPICS IN MICROBIOLOGY AND IMMUNOLOGY	A1
0972-4559	CURRENT TOPICS IN PHARMACOLOGY	B3
0972-8228	CURRENT TOPICS IN TOXICOLOGY	B4
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0973-8916	CURRENT TRENDS IN BIOTECHNOLOGY AND PHARMACY	B3
0972-4567	CURRENT TRENDS IN IMMUNOLOGY	B4
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2328-4919	CURRENT URBAN STUDIES (ONLINE)	B4
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1570-1611	CURRENT VASCULAR PHARMACOLOGY	A3
1573-4048	CURRENT WOMEN'S HEALTH REVIEWS (PRINT)	B2
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1877-1297	CURRENTS IN PHARMACY TEACHING AND LEARNING	B1
1645-1384	CURRÍCULO SEM FRONTEIRAS	A1
1808-2882	CUSTOS E @GRONEGOCIOSONLINE	A3
2591-555X	CUYONOMICS. INVESTIGACIONES EN ECONOMÍA REGIONAL	B4
1278-3366	CYBERGEO (PARIS)	A4
2226-4116	CYBERNETICS AND PHYSICS	A4
2152-2715	CYBERPSYCH BEH SOC N	A1
1802-7962	CYBERPSYCHOLOGY	A3
2101-0315	CYBIUM	B2
0399-0974	CYBIUM (PARIS)	B2
1305-905X	CYPRIOT JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES	A1
1424-859X	CYTOGENETIC AND GENOME RESEARCH (ONLINE)	A4
1424-8581	CYTOGENETIC AND GENOME RESEARCH (PRINTED ED.)	A4
1043-4666	CYTOKINE	A2
1359-6101	CYTOKINE & GROWTH FACTOR REVIEWS	A1
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1552-4922	CYTOMETRY. PART A	A2
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0956-5507	CYTOPATHOLOGY (OXFORD. PRINT)	B1
0920-9069	CYTOTECHNOLOGY (DORDRECHT)	B1
1477-2566	CYTOTHERAPY	A2
1465-3249	CYTOTHERAPY (OXFORD)	A2
1212-1819	CZECH JOURNAL OF ANIMAL SCIENCE	A4
1212-1800	CZECH JOURNAL OF FOOD SCIENCES	B2
0011-4642	CZECHOSLOVAK MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL (PRAGUE, PRINT)	B3
2182-1372	DA INVESTIGAÇÃO ÀS PRÁTICAS	B3
1678-4588	DADOS - REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	A1
0011-5266	DAEDALUS (CAMBRIDGE)	A1
2192-5283	DAGSTUHL REPORTS	B2
1477-9226	DALTON TRANSACTIONS (2003. PRINT)	A1
1808-3129	DAPESQUISA	A4
1983-8379	DARANDINA REVISTELETRÔNICA	B3
2008-2231	DARU JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES	A4
0011-6793	DARWINIANA	B2

2447-7087	DAS QUESTÕES	B4
0169-023X	DATA & KNOWLEDGE ENGINEERING	A3
1384-5810	DATA MINING AND KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY	A1
1683-1470	DATA SCIENCE JOURNAL	A4
1758-0463	DATABASE: THE JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL DATABASES AND CURATI	A1
2526-1789	DATJOURNAL DESIGN ART AND TECHNOLOGY	B1
2465-2415	DE GENERE	A3
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1464-3154	DEAFNESS & EDUCATION INTERNATIONAL	B1
2011-3188	DE-ARQ - REVISTA DE ARQUITETURA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE LOS AI	B1
0748-1187	DEATH STUDIES	A3
0188-9478	DEBATE FEMINISTA	A3
1813-1867	DEBATE TERMINOLÓGICO	B3
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1519-843X	DEBATES DO NER (UFRGS. IMPRESSO)	A2
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0167-9236	DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS	A1
2182-018X	DEDICA. REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO E HUMANIDADES (DREH)	B1
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1662-9507	DEFECT AND DIFFUSION FORUM	B3
1985-6571	DEFENCE S&T TECHNICAL BULLETIN	B2
0011-748X	DEFENCE SCIENCE JOURNAL	B1
0770-8378	DEGRÉS	B4
1988-5245	DELOS: DESARROLLO LOCAL SOSTENIBLE	A4
1678-460X	DELTA. DOCUMENTAÇÃO DE ESTUDOS EM LINGUÍSTICA TEÓRICA E	A1
0719-4730	DEMARCACIONES	B4
1980-5764	DEMENTIA & NEUROPSYCHOLOGIA	B3
1471-3012	DEMENTIA (LONDON)	A2
1420-8008	DEMENTIA AND GERIATRIC COGNITIVE DISORDERS	A2
1421-9824	DEMENTIA AND GERIATRIC COGNITIVE DISORDERS (ONLINE)	A2
2238-913X	DEMETRA: ALIMENTAÇÃO, NUTRIÇÃO & SAÚDE	B4
2175-9391	DEMOCRACIA DIGITAL E GOVERNO ELETRÔNICO	B1
1741-9166	DEMOCRACY AND SECURITY	B1
1435-9871	DEMOGRAPHIC RESEARCH	A2
0070-3370	DEMOGRAPHY (CHICAGO)	A1
0420-1213	DEMONSTRATIO MATHEMATICA	B3
1641-1307	DENDROBIOLOGY	A3
1125-7865	DENDROCHRONOLOGIA (VERONA)	A2
0011-8524	DENTAL CADMOS	B4
2155-8213	DENTAL HYPHOTESSES	B3
0109-5641	DENTAL MATERIALS	A1
0287-4547	DENTAL MATERIALS JOURNAL	A3
2178-3713	DENTAL PRESS ENDODONTICS	B4
2176-9451	DENTAL PRESS JOURNAL OF ORTHODONTICS	A4
1735-3327	DENTAL RESEARCH JOURNAL	A4
1600-4469	DENTAL TRAUMATOLOGY (PRINT)	A3

8750-2186	DENTISTRY TODAY	B4
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1091-4269	DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY (PRINT)	A1
0038-9145	DER STAHLBAU	B3
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0251-3420	DERECHO PUCP	B1
2224-4131	DERECHO Y CAMBIO SOCIAL	B1
1133-0937	DERECHOS Y LIBERTADES	A4
2526-2637	DERIVAS ANALÍTICAS	B4
1938-1980	DERMATO-ENDOCRINOLOGY	A1
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1018-8665	DERMATOLOGY (BASEL)	A2
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2526-2793	ENTROPIA	B3
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0122-6339	ENUNCIACIÓN	A3
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0265-8135	ENVIRONMENT & PLANNING. B, PLANNING & DESIGN (PRINT)	A1
1355-770X	ENVIRONMENT AND DEVELOPMENT ECONOMICS (PRINT)	A2
1927-0496	ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES RESEARCH	B2
1472-3409	ENVIRONMENT AND PLANNING A	A2
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1936-6582	FLEXIBLE SERVICES AND MANUFACTURING JOURNAL	A1
0367-2530	FLORA (JENA)	A3
0015-3826	FLORESTA (UFPR. IMPRESSO)	B2
1415-0980	FLORESTA E AMBIENTE	B2
0098-4590	FLORIDA SCIENTIST	B4
0955-5986	FLOW MEASUREMENT AND INSTRUMENTATION	A3
1386-6184	FLOW, TURBULENCE AND COMBUSTION	A2
1793-6780	FLUCTUATION AND NOISE LETTERS (ONLINE)	B3
0169-5983	FLUID DYNAMICS RESEARCH	A4
0378-3812	FLUID PHASE EQUILIBRIA	A2
2045-8118	FLUIDS AND BARRIERS OF THE CNS	A3
0015-4725	FLUORIDE	A3
1661-5719	FLUSSER STUDIES	B3
1933-6934	FLY	A3
1451-2092	FME TRANSACTIONS	A4
1981-223X	FOCO (FACULDADE NOVO MILÊNIO)	B2
2318-0463	FOCO: CADERNO DE DE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS	B2
2395-258X	FOCUS JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS	B4
1018-5674	FOLIA AMAZONICA	B4
0015-5497	FOLIA BIOLOGICA (KRAKÓW)	B2
1211-9520	FOLIA GEOBOTANICA (PRUHONICE)	A3
2083-5965	FOLIA HORTICULTURAE	B3
1506-7629	FOLIA MALACOLOGICA	B3
0015-5632	FOLIA MICROBIOLOGICA (PRAGUE)	B2
0015-5659	FOLIA MORPHOLOGICA	B2
0015-5683	FOLIA PARASITOLOGICA (PRAHA)	B1
1021-7762	FOLIA PHONIATRICA ET LOGOPAEDICA	A2
0015-5713	FOLIA PRIMATOLOGICA	A4
2176-4182	FÓLIO - REVISTA DE LETRAS	A3
1981-3422	FÓLIO (CENTRO UNIVERSITÁRIO METODISTA)	B2
0123-1022	FOLIOS	B4
2042-6496	FOOD & FUNCTION	A1

1944-0049	FOOD ADDITIVES & CONTAMINANTS. PART A. CHEMISTRY, ANALYSI	A2
1939-3210	FOOD ADDITIVES & CONTAMINANTS. PART B. SURVEILLANCE COM	A2
1936-9751	FOOD ANALYTICAL METHODS (PRINT)	A2
0954-0105	FOOD AND AGRICULTURAL IMMUNOLOGY	A2
1935-5149	FOOD AND BIOPROCESS TECHNOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
0960-3085	FOOD AND BIOPRODUCTS PROCESSING	A2
0278-6915	FOOD AND CHEMICAL TOXICOLOGY	A1
2048-3694	FOOD AND ENERGY SECURITY	A1
1867-0334	FOOD AND ENVIRONMENTAL VIROLOGY	A2
0379-5721	FOOD AND NUTRITION BULLETIN (TOKYO. PRINT)	A2
1557-1858	FOOD BIOPHYSICS	A3
2212-4292	FOOD BIOSCIENCE	A2
0308-8146	FOOD CHEMISTRY	A1
0956-7135	FOOD CONTROL	A1
1866-7910	FOOD ENGINEERING REVIEWS	A1
0268-005X	FOOD HYDROCOLLOIDS	A1
0740-0020	FOOD MICROBIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
2214-2894	FOOD PACKAGING AND SHELF LIFE	A1
0306-9192	FOOD POLICY	A1
0950-3293	FOOD QUALITY AND PREFERENCE	A1
0963-9969	FOOD RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	A1
1525-6103	FOOD REVIEWS INTERNATIONAL	A2
8755-9129	FOOD REVIEWS INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	A2
2048-7177	FOOD SCIENCE & NUTRITION	A4
1096-1127	FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
1226-7708	FOOD SCIENCE AND BIOTECHNOLOGY (SEOUL)	B2
1082-0132	FOOD SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	A2
1876-4517	FOOD SECURITY	A1
2213-3291	FOOD STRUCTURE	A2
1330-9862	FOOD TECHNOLOGY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	B1
2352-2496	FOOD WEBS	A3
1535-3141	FOODBORNE PATHOGENS AND DISEASE	A1
1268-7731	FOOT AND ANKLE SURGERY (PRINT)	A4
0228-0671	FOR THE LEARNING OF MATHEMATICS	A1
1981-6898	FORÇAS ARMADAS EM REVISTA	B4
1460-9819	FORCED MIGRATION REVIEW	B3
0015-7120	FOREIGN AFFAIRS (NEW YORK, N.Y.)	A1
1945-2276	FOREIGN POLICY	B2
1743-8586	FOREIGN POLICY ANALYSIS (PRINT)	A2
2468-1709	FORENSIC CHEMISTRY	A2
0379-0738	FORENSIC SCIENCE INTERNATIONAL	A2
1872-4973	FORENSIC SCIENCE INTERNATIONAL. GENETICS (PRINT)	A1
1875-1768	FORENSIC SCIENCE INTERNATIONAL. GENETICS SUPPLEMENT SERIE	B2
1860-8965	FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY (TOKYO. PRINT)	A1
2500-2597	FORESIGHT AND STI GOVERNANCE	B4
0378-1127	FOREST ECOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT	A1
1437-4781	FOREST PATHOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
1389-9341	FOREST POLICY AND ECONOMICS	A1
0015-749X	FOREST SCIENCE	A2
2171-5068	FOREST SYSTEMS	A3

0015-752X	FORESTRY (LONDON)	A1
1999-4907	FORESTS	A2
2318-986X	FORM@RE -REVISTA DO PLANO NACIONAL DE FORMAÇÃO DE PROF	B4
2183-4709	FORMA BREVE	B1
2178-7298	FORMAÇÃO (ONLINE)	A4
2176-4360	FORMAÇÃO DOCENTE	B1
0718-5006	FORMACIÓN UNIVERSITARIA	A4
1698-7799	FORO DE EDUCACIÓN	A3
1698-7802	FORO DE EDUCACIÓN	A3
0185-013X	FORO INTERNACIONAL	A2
2318-6356	FORSIENCE	B2
0720-4299	FORTSCHRITTE DER NEUROLOGIE, PSYCHIATRIE	B3
0015-8208	FORTSCHRITTE DER PHYSIK (BERLIN. WILEY-VCH)	A3
1984-4107	FÓRUM ADMINISTRATIVO - DIREITO PÚBLICO	B4
1980-0827	FÓRUM AMBIENTAL DA ALTA PAULISTA	B1
1984-7556	FÓRUM DE LITERATURA BRASILEIRA CONTEMPORÂNEA	B1
0803-9410	FORUM FOR DEVELOPMENT STUDIES	A2
1860-5605	FORUM HISTORIAE IURIS - ERSTE EUROPÄISCHE INTERNETZEITSCHR	A2
1984-8412	FÓRUM LINGUISTICO (ONLINE)	A2
0933-7741	FORUM MATHEMATICUM	A3
1438-5627	FORUM QUALITATIVE SOZIALFORSCHUNG	A2
0872-8380	FORUM SOCIOLOGICO	B4
2182-7427	FORUM SOCIOLOGICO	B4
2216-1767	FORUM. REVISTA DEPARTAMENTO CIENCIA POLÍTICA	B4
2172-0150	FOTOCINEMA	B1
2595-3559	FOTOCRONOGRAFIAS	B4
1802-5439	FOTTEA	A3
1832-5203	FOUCAULT STUDIES	A3
1615-3383	FOUNDATIONS OF COMPUTATIONAL MATHEMATICS (INTERNET)	A1
0015-9018	FOUNDATIONS OF PHYSICS	A4
1233-1821	FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENCE (PRINT)	A1
1984-0292	FRACTAL: REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA	A2
0218-348X	FRACTALS (SINGAPORE)	A3
1311-0454	FRACTIONAL CALCULUS AND APPLIED ANALYSIS	A1
1983-7828	FRAGMENTOS DE CULTURA	B1
2179-2194	FRAGMENTUM (ON LINE)	A1
0120-1468	FRANCISCANUM - REVISTA DE LA CIENCIA DEL ESPÍRITU	B1
1971-8993	FRATTURA E INTEGRITA STRUTTURALE	B1
0891-5849	FREE RADICAL BIOLOGY & MEDICINE	A1
1071-5762	FREE RADICAL RESEARCH	A3
1029-2470	FREE RADICAL RESEARCH	A3
2264-4733	FRENCH JOURNAL FOR MEDIA RESEARCH	B1
1018-4619	FRESENIUS ENVIRONMENTAL BULLETIN	B2
0046-5070	FRESHWATER BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
2161-9565	FRESHWATER SCIENCE	A1
2161-9549	FRESHWATER SCIENCE	A1
1131-5776	FREUDIANA : REVISTA PSICOANALÍTICA PUBLICADA EN BARCELONA	B4
2223-7690	FRICTION	A3
1679-5377	FRONTEIRA (PUCMG)	B4
2595-3788	FRONTEIRAS	B4

1517-9265	FRONTEIRAS (CAMPO GRANDE)	A3
1415-8701	FRONTEIRAS (FLORIANÓPOLIS)	B2
2446-8215	FRONTEIRAS E DEBATES	B1
2238-8869	FRONTEIRAS: JOURNAL OF SOCIAL, TECHNOLOGICAL AND ENVIRON	B1
1983-4373	FRONTEIRAZ (SÃO PAULO)	A4
0187-7372	FRONTERA NORTE	A3
2027-4688	FRONTERAS DE LA HISTÓRIA	A1
1916-0976	FRONTIÈRES	B3
0160-9009	FRONTIERS (BOULDER)	B2
1663-4365	FRONTIERS IN AGING NEUROSCIENCE	A1
1662-5153	FRONTIERS IN BEHAVIORAL NEUROSCIENCE	A1
2296-4185	FRONTIERS IN BIOENGINEERING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	A1
1945-0516	FRONTIERS IN BIOSCIENCE - SCHOLAR	A1
1093-9946	FRONTIERS IN BIOSCIENCE (PRINT)	A3
1945-0508	FRONTIERS IN BIOSCIENCE-ELITE	A4
2297-055X	FRONTIERS IN CARDIOVASCULAR MEDICINE	B4
2296-634X	FRONTIERS IN CELL AND DEVELOPMENTAL BIOLOGY	A3
2235-2988	FRONTIERS IN CELLULAR AND INFECTION MICROBIOLOGY	A1
1662-5102	FRONTIERS IN CELLULAR NEUROSCIENCE	A1
2296-2646	FRONTIERS IN CHEMISTRY	A2
1662-5188	FRONTIERS IN COMPUTATIONAL NEUROSCIENCE	A3
2296-6463	FRONTIERS IN EARTH SCIENCE	A2
2296-701X	FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION	A2
1540-9295	FRONTIERS IN ECOLOGY AND THE ENVIRONMENT (PRINT)	A1
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2296-598X	FRONTIERS IN ENERGY RESEARCH	A1
2296-665X	FRONTIERS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE	A1
1664-8021	FRONTIERS IN GENETICS	A2
1662-5161	FRONTIERS IN HUMAN NEUROSCIENCE	A2
1664-3224	FRONTIERS IN IMMUNOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
1662-5145	FRONTIERS IN INTEGRATIVE NEUROSCIENCE	A2
2296-7745	FRONTIERS IN MARINE SCIENCE	A2
1664-302X	FRONTIERS IN MICROBIOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
2296-889X	FRONTIERS IN MOLECULAR BIOSCIENCES	A3
1662-5099	FRONTIERS IN MOLECULAR NEUROSCIENCE	A1
1662-5110	FRONTIERS IN NEURAL CIRCUITS	A1
1662-5129	FRONTIERS IN NEUROANATOMY	A1
1664-2295	FRONTIERS IN NEUROLOGY	A2
1662-5218	FRONTIERS IN NEUROROBOTICS	A2
1662-453X	FRONTIERS IN NEUROSCIENCE	A2
1662-4548	FRONTIERS IN NEUROSCIENCE (PRINT)	A2
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2296-2360	FRONTIERS IN PEDIATRICS	A3
1663-9812	FRONTIERS IN PHARMACOLOGY	A1
1664-042X	FRONTIERS IN PHYSIOLOGY	A2
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1664-1078	FRONTIERS IN PSYCHOLOGY	A1
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2096-0255	FRONTIERS OF ENGINEERING MANAGEMENT	B4
0301-3073	FRONTIERS OF HORMONE RESEARCH	B1
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2095-9184	FRONTIERS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY & ELECTRONIC ENGINE	A4
2095-0233	FRONTIERS OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING	A4
1660-4431	FRONTIERS OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSCIENCE	B2
2095-2767	FRONTIERS OF OPTOELECTRONICS	B1
2095-0470	FRONTIERS OF PHYSICS (ONLINE)	A3
0248-1294	FRUITS (PARIS. IMPRIMÉ)	A4
2525-8729	FTT JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND BUSINESS	B4
1674-0750	FUDAN JOURNAL OF THE HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES	A4
0016-2361	FUEL (GUILDFORD)	A1
1615-6846	FUEL CELLS (WEINHEIM. PRINT)	A3
0378-3820	FUEL PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY	A1
2526-4494	FULIA UFMG	A4
2175-7437	FULL DENTISTRY IN SCIENCE	B4
1536-383X	FULLERENES, NANOTUBES, AND CARBON NANOSTRUCTURES	A4
0104-351X	FUMDHAMENTOS	B3
1438-793X	FUNCTIONAL & INTEGRATIVE GENOMICS (PRINT)	A2
1821-410X	FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS, APPROXIMATION AND COMPUTATION	B4
0269-8463	FUNCTIONAL ECOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
0393-5264	FUNCTIONAL NEUROLOGY (ROMA. TESTO STAMPATO)	B1
1445-4408	FUNCTIONAL PLANT BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
0169-2968	FUNDAMENTA INFORMATICAЕ	A2
0016-2736	FUNDAMENTA MATHEMATICAE	A4
0767-3981	FUNDAMENTAL & CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY	A4
1472-8206	FUNDAMENTAL & CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY	A4
2313-7525	FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED RESEARCHES IN PRACTICE OF LEADIN	B1
1878-6146	FUNGAL BIOLOGY	A3
1749-4613	FUNGAL BIOLOGY REVIEWS	A2
1560-2745	FUNGAL DIVERSITY	A1
1754-5048	FUNGAL ECOLOGY	A1
1087-1845	FUNGAL GENETICS AND BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
2165-8056	FUNGAL GENOMICS AND BIOLOGY	B2
0532-8721	FUNKCIALAJ EKVACIOJ	B1
0920-3796	FUSION ENGINEERING AND DESIGN	A2
2314-7210	FUTURE BUSINESS JOURNAL	B3
0167-739X	FUTURE GENERATION COMPUTER SYSTEMS	A1
1999-5903	FUTURE INTERNET	B1
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1746-0921	FUTURE MICROBIOLOGY	A3
1746-0913	FUTURE MICROBIOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
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2175-5825	FUTURE STUDIES RESEARCH JOURNAL	A4
1746-0794	FUTURE VIROLOGY (PRINT)	B3
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1573-2908	FUZZY OPTIMIZATION AND DECISION MAKING	A2
0165-0114	FUZZY SETS AND SYSTEMS	A1
2160-1836	G3: GENES, GENOMES, GENETICS (BETHESDA)	A3
0213-9111	GACETA SANITARIA (BARCELONA. ED. IMPRESA)	A4
1981-1268	GAIA SCIENTIA (UFPB)	A4
0966-6362	GAIT & POSTURE	A1
1519-311X	GALÁXIA (PUCSP)	A2
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2161-783X	GAMES FOR HEALTH JOURNAL	A2
2161-7856	GAMES FOR HEALTH: RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT, AND CLINICAL AP	A2
0016-5085	GASTROENTEROLOGY (NEW YORK, N.Y. 1943)	A1
0889-8553	GASTROENTEROLOGY CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA	A2
1918-2805	GASTROENTEROLOGY RESEARCH	B2
1687-6121	GASTROENTEROLOGY RESEARCH AND PRACTICE	B1
1097-6779	GASTROINTESTINAL ENDOSCOPY (ONLINE)	A1
0016-5107	GASTROINTESTINAL ENDOSCOPY (PRINT)	A1
0717-652X	GAYANA (CONCEPCIÓN. IMPRESA)	B2
0016-5301	GAYANA. BOTÁNICA (IMPRESA)	B2
0393-3660	GAZZETTA MEDICA ITALIANA. ARCHIVIO PER LE SCIENZE MEDICHE (B2
0016-5751	GEBURTSCHILFE UND FRAUENHEILKUNDE	A4
0101-7772	GED. GASTROENTEROLOGIA E ENDOSCOPIA DIGESTIVA	B4
2310-2861	GELS	A2
1747-6321	GENDER AND LANGUAGE (PRINT)	A4
1213-0028	GENDER, ROVNÉ PRÍLEŽITOSTI, VYZKUM	B1
0378-1119	GENE (AMSTERDAM)	A4
1567-133X	GENE EXPRESSION PATTERNS (TOKYO)	B2
2452-0144	GENE REPORTS	B4
0969-7128	GENE THERAPY (BASINGSTOKE)	A3
1095-6840	GENERAL AND COMPARATIVE ENDOCRINOLOGY (ONLINE)	A2
0016-6480	GENERAL AND COMPARATIVE ENDOCRINOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
0363-6771	GENERAL DENTISTRY	B2
0163-8343	GENERAL HOSPITAL PSYCHIATRY	A2
2515-4737	GENERAL MEDICINE OPEN	B3
0001-7701	GENERAL RELATIVITY AND GRAVITATION	A4
1517-9699	GÊNERO	A4
2238-8184	GÊNERO NA AMAZÔNIA	B2
2014-3613	GÉNEROS - MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF GENDER STUDIES	A4
2073-4425	GENES	A2
1555-8932	GENES & NUTRITION: A JOURNAL DEVOTED TO STUDY OF RELATION	B1
1466-4879	GENES AND IMMUNITY	A4
1045-2257	GENES CHROMOSOMES & CANCER (PRINT)	A2
1526-954X	GENESIS (NEW YORK, N.Y. 2000. PRINT)	A3
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1945-0257	GENETIC TESTING AND MOLECULAR BIOMARKERS (ONLINE)	B3
0016-6707	GENETICA ('S-GRAVENHAGE)	A3
1980-3540	GENÉTICA NA ESCOLA	B3
1943-2631	GENETICS	A2
1415-4757	GENETICS AND MOLECULAR BIOLOGY (IMPRESSO)	A4
1676-5680	GENETICS AND MOLECULAR RESEARCH	B3
1098-3600	GENETICS IN MEDICINE	A1
1297-9686	GENETICS SELECTION EVOLUTION	A1
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1756-994X	GENOME MEDICINE	A1
1088-9051	GENOME RESEARCH	A1
0888-7543	GENOMICS (SAN DIEGO, CALIF.)	A3
2213-5960	GENOMICS DATA	B1
2104-3736	GENRE, SEXUALITÉ & SOCIÉTÉ	A2
2035-5556	GENUS (ONLINE): JOURNAL OF POPULATION STUDIES	B3
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1679-9860	GEOAMBIENTE ON-LINE	B2
0883-6353	GEOARCHAEOLOGY (NEW YORK. PRINT)	A1
1472-4677	GEOBIOLOGY	A1
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1010-6049	GEOCARTO INTERNATIONAL	B2
1525-2027	GEOCHEMISTRY, GEOPHYSICS, GEOSYSTEMS	A2
0102-9800	GEOCHIMICA BRASILIENSIS	B4
0016-7037	GEOCHIMICA ET COSMOCHIMICA ACTA	A1
1733-8387	GEOCHRONOMETRIA	A4
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2359-6007	GEOCONEXÕES	B3
0016-7061	GEODERMA (AMSTERDAM)	A1
2352-0094	GEODERMA REGIONAL	A3
2448-413X	GEDIÁLOGOS	B2
0016-7169	GEOFÍSICA INTERNACIONAL	B1
0352-3659	GEOFIZIKA (ZAGREB)	B4
1468-8115	GEOFLUIDS (OXFORD. PRINT)	A3
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2447-9195	GEOFRONTER	B1
1518-2002	GEOGRAFARES: REVISTA DO MESTRADO E DO DEPARTAMENTO DE	A4
0102-3888	GEOGRAFIA (LONDRINA)	A4
1983-8700	GEOGRAFIA (RIO CLARO. ONLINE)	B3
1806-8553	GEOGRAFIA E PESQUISA (UNESP. OURINHOS)	B3
1984-1647	GEOGRAFIA EM ATOS (ONLINE)	B2
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2178-3306	GEOGRAFIA, MEIO AMBIENTE E ENSINO (GEOMAE)	B3
0103-1538	GEOGRAFIA. ENSINO & PESQUISA (UFSM)	A3
2237-549X	GEOGRAFIAS	B4

1808-8058	GEOGRAFIAS (UFMG)	B4
0435-3676	GEOGRAFISKA ANNALER. SERIES A, PHYSICAL GEOGRAPHY (PRINT)	A2
1517-7793	GEOGRAPHIA (UFF)	B1
0016-7312	GEOGRAPHICA HELVETICA	B3
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0016-7398	GEOGRAPHICAL JOURNAL	A1
0016-7479	GEOGRAPHISCHE ZEITSCHRIFT	B4
2071-9388	GEOGRAPHY, ENVIRONMENT, SUSTAINABILITY	A3
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1384-6175	GEOINFORMATICA (DORDRECHT)	A1
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0343-2521	GEOJOURNAL	A2
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1519-874X	GEOLOGIA USP. SÉRIE CIENTÍFICA	B2
2316-9095	GEOLOGIA USP. SÉRIE CIENTÍFICA (ONLINE)	B2
0072-1050	GEOLOGICAL JOURNAL (CHICHESTER)	A2
0016-7606	GEOLOGICAL SOCIETY OF AMERICA BULLETIN	A1
0435-4052	GEOLOGICAL SOCIETY OF LONDON. MEMOIRS	B1
0305-8719	GEOLOGICAL SOCIETY SPECIAL PUBLICATION	A2
0091-7613	GEOLOGY (BOULDER, COLO.)	A1
0276-0460	GEO-MARINE LETTERS	A2
2161-7538	GEOMATERIALS	B4
1947-5713	GEOMATICS, NATURAL HAZARDS AND RISK	A3
1748-6025	GEOMECHANICS AND GEOENGINEERING (PRINT)	A4
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1016-443X	GEOMETRIC AND FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS (PRINTED ED.)	A1
1465-3060	GEOMETRY & TOPOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
0149-0451	GEOMICROBIOLOGY JOURNAL	B1
0169-555X	GEOMORPHOLOGY (AMSTERDAM)	A1
0104-4486	GEONOMOS	B4
1518-6059	GEONORDESTE (UFS)	A4
2237-1419	GEONORTE	B1
2594-5033	GEOPAUTA	A4
1365-246X	GEOPHYSICAL JOURNAL INTERNATIONAL	A2
0956-540X	GEOPHYSICAL JOURNAL INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	A2
0016-8025	GEOPHYSICAL PROSPECTING (PRINT)	A3
0094-8276	GEOPHYSICAL RESEARCH LETTERS	A1
0016-8033	GEOPHYSICS	A2
2172-3958	GEOPOLITICA(S): REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SOBRE ESPACIO Y PODER	A3
1465-0045	GEOPOLITICS (LONDON)	A4
1983-3644	GEOPUC (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B3
2560-6115	GEO-RESOURCES ENVIRONMENT AND ENGINEERING (GREE)	B4
1550-5200	GEORGETOWN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW	A2
1072-947X	GEORGIAN MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL	B3
1749-9518	GEORISK: ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF RISK FOR ENGINEEF	A3
2178-0463	GEOSABERES REVISTA DE ESTUDOS GEOEDUCACIONAIS	A1
1674-9871	GEOSCIENCE FRONTIERS	A1
2076-3263	GEOSCIENCES	A2
1991-9603	GEOSCIENTIFIC MODEL DEVELOPMENT	A1
1827-1987	GEOSPATIAL HEALTH (TESTO STAMPATO)	A3

1009-5020	GEO-SPATIAL INFORMATION SCIENCE	A3
1639-4488	GEOSTANDARDS AND GEOANALYTICAL RESEARCH	A1
2177-5230	GEOSUL	A2
1751-7613	GEOSYNTHETICS INTERNATIONAL (ONLINE)	A3
0960-3182	GEOTECHNICAL AND GEOLOGICAL ENGINEERING	A2
0046-5828	GEOTECHNICAL ENGINEERING JOURNAL OF THE SEAGS & AGSSEA	B2
0149-6115	GEOTECHNICAL TESTING JOURNAL	A3
0016-8505	GEOTECHNIQUE	A1
2045-2543	GÉOTECHNIQUE LETTERS	A2
0266-1144	GEOTEXTILES AND GEOMEMBRANES	A1
1984-5537	GEOTEXTOS (ONLINE)	A4
1809-189X	GEOTEXTOS (SALVADOR)	A4
2179-0892	GEOUSP: ESPAÇO E TEMPO	A2
1983-8220	GERAIS: REVISTA INTERINSTITUCIONAL DE PSICOLOGIA	A4
0197-4572	GERIATRIC NURSING (NEW YORK)	A4
0016-867X	GERIATRICS	B4
1444-1586	GERIATRICS AND GERONTOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	A2
2447-2115	GERIATRICS, GERONTOLOGY AND AGING	B2
2397-0030	GERMAN JOURNAL OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT	B3
2071-8322	GERMAN LAW JOURNAL	A1
1983-4020	GERMINAL : GRUPO DE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS MARXISMO, HISTÓR	B2
2175-5604	GERMINAL: MARXISMO E EDUCAÇÃO EM DEBATE	A4
2248-2997	GERMS	B2
0734-0664	GERODONTOLOGY	A3
1741-2358	GERODONTOLOGY	A3
1134-928X	GEROKOMOS (MADRID. ED. IMPRESA)	B2
1569-1101	GERONTECHNOLOGY (VALKENSWAARD. GEDRUKT)	B3
0270-1960	GERONTOLOGY & GERIATRICS EDUCATION (PRINT)	B2
0304-324X	GERONTOLOGY (BASEL)	A1
1423-0003	GERONTOLOGY (BASEL. ONLINE)	A1
2333-7214	GERONTOLOGY AND GERIATRIC MEDICINE	B3
2509-2715	GEROSCIENCE	A2
2526-3102	GESTÃO & APRENDIZAGEM	B2
1516-9103	GESTÃO & PLANEJAMENTO (SALVADOR)	A3
1806-9649	GESTÃO & PRODUÇÃO	B2
0104-530X	GESTÃO & PRODUÇÃO (UFSCAR. IMPRESSO)	B2
1981-1543	GESTÃO & TECNOLOGIA DE PROJETOS	A3
2238-4170	GESTÃO CONTEMPORÂNEA	B3
1809-0214	GESTÃO CONTEMPORÂNEA (FAPA)	B3
2317-5087	GESTÃO E CONEXÕES	A4
0872-556X	GESTÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B3
1807-5436	GESTÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO (PRINT)	B1
2446-8738	GESTÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM REVISTA	B4
1808-5792	GESTÃO E REGIONALIDADE	A3
1980-5756	GESTÃO E SOCIEDADE	B1
2175-733X	GESTÃO EM FOCO - UNISEPE	B3
2595-5861	GESTÃO, INOVAÇÃO E EMPREENDEDORISMO	B3
1679-1827	GESTÃO.ORG	B1
0123-5834	GESTIÓN & DESARROLLO	A4
2406-4734	GESTION 2000	B1

1988-9011	GESTIÓN JOVEN	B2
0717-1811	GESTIÓN TURÍSTICA (VALDIVIA. IMPRESA)	A3
2595-3109	GESTO-DEBATE	A4
1040-483X	GESTOS (IRVINE, CALIF.)	B3
1862-3573	GIGA-FOCUS. LATEINAMERIKA	A4
2174-9515	GIGAPP ESTUDIOS WORKING PAPERS	A4
2047-217X	GIGASCIENCE (ONLINE)	A1
0017-0011	GINEKOLOGIA POLSKA	B2
2240-7995	GIORNALE CRITICO DI STORIA DELLE IDEE - RIVISTA INTERNAZIONA	B3
2037-7975	GIORNALE DI STORIA CONTEMPORANEA	B4
0392-0488	GIORNALE ITALIANO DI DERMATOLOGIA E VENEREOLOGIA: A JOURI	B2
1121-4171	GIORNALE ITALIANO DI ENDODONZIA (TESTO STAMPATO)	B2
2358-4467	GIRAMUNDO - REVISTA DE GEOGRAFIA DO COLÉGIO PEDRO II	B1
2525-3123	GIS - GESTO, IMAGEM E SOM - REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGIA	B3
1548-1603	GISCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING	A1
2227-8575	GLAND SURGERY	A3
0017-0895	GLASGOW MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL (PRINT)	B1
2318-7131	GLÁUKS ONLINE	B1
0894-1491	GLIA (NEW YORK, N.Y. : PRINT)	A1
0921-8181	GLOBAL AND PLANETARY CHANGE (PRINT)	A1
0886-6236	GLOBAL BIOGEOCHEMICAL CYCLES	A1
1097-4954	GLOBAL BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS REVIEW	A4
1947-5667	GLOBAL BUSINESS AND MANAGEMENT RESEARCH	B1
0972-1509	GLOBAL BUSINESS REVIEW (PRINT)	A3
1354-1013	GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1757-1693	GLOBAL CHANGE BIOLOGY. BIOENERGY	A1
1986-2601	GLOBAL DIALOGUE	A4
1466-822X	GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY (PRINT)	A1
0960-7447	GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND BIOGEOGRAPHY LETTERS	A1
2351-9894	GLOBAL ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION	A2
1973-3739	GLOBAL ENVIRONMENT	A4
1044-0283	GLOBAL FINANCE JOURNAL	A3
2211-9124	GLOBAL FOOD SECURITY	A1
1075-2846	GLOBAL GOVERNANCE	A2
1654-9880	GLOBAL HEALTH ACTION	A2
1757-9759	GLOBAL HEALTH PROMOTION (PRINT)	B2
2169-575X	GLOBAL HEALTH, SCIENCE AND PRACTICE	A3
2211-8160	GLOBAL HEART (PRINT)	A1
2383-3866	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND MANAGEMEI	B3
0974-0198	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF FLEXIBLE SYSTEMS MANAGEMENT (ONLINE)	A2
1916-9736	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SCIENCE	A4
0975-587X	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF HUMAN SOCIAL SCIENCES	B1
2249-460X	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF HUMAN-SOCIAL SCIENCE	A2
2575-8586	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF INTELLECTUAL & DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILIT	B4
0975-5861	GLOBAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCHES IN ENGINEERING	B4
1676-2819	GLOBAL MANAGER (FSG)	B3
2059-4372	GLOBAL MEDIA AND CHINA	A3
1742-7665	GLOBAL MEDIA AND COMMUNICATION (PRINT)	A3
1550-7521	GLOBAL MEDIA JOURNAL	A3
1790-7632	GLOBAL NEST JOURNAL	B1

1470-2266	GLOBAL NETWORKS (OXFORD. PRINT)	A1
1758-5899	GLOBAL POLICY JOURNAL	A2
1744-1706	GLOBAL PUBLIC HEALTH (ONLINE)	A3
1875-9858	GLOBAL RESPONSIBILITY TO PROTECT	A4
1360-0826	GLOBAL SOCIETY	A4
2192-5682	GLOBAL SPINE JOURNAL	A3
2042-5805	GLOBAL STRATEGY JOURNAL	A2
2058-7449	GLOBAL SUMMITRY	A3
1476-7724	GLOBALISATION, SOCIETIES AND EDUCATION (PRINT)	A1
1744-8603	GLOBALIZATION AND HEALTH	A1
1474-7731	GLOBALIZATIONS (PRINT)	A1
2182-1380	GLOSAS	B1
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0959-6658	GLYCOBIOLOGY (OXFORD)	A2
0282-0080	GLYCOCONJUGATE JOURNAL	A4
2164-5701	GM CROPS & FOOD: BIOTECHNOLOGY IN AGRICULTURE AND THE F	A2
2366-5017	GMS JOURNAL FOR MEDICAL EDUCATION	A3
2317-2002	GNARUS REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA	B3
2474-2678	GOBERNAR: THE JOURNAL OF LATIN AMERICAN PUBLIC POLICY ANI	B4
2364-821X	GOLD BULLETIN	A4
2231-5063	GOLDEN RESEARCH THOUGHTS	B3
2346-4712	GÓNDOLA, ENSEÑANZA Y APRENDIZAJE DE LAS CIENCIAS	A4
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1809-6689	GOVERNET. BOLETIM RECURSOS HUMANOS	B4
0740-624X	GOVERNMENT INFORMATION QUARTERLY	A1
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2172-8690	GRAN TOUR: REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIONES TURÍSTICAS	A4
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1980-1858	GUAVIRA LETRAS	A3
1794-192X	GUILLERMO DE OCKHAM	A2
0213-8581	GUIX: ELEMENTS D'ACCIÓ EDUCATIVA	B1
0017-5749	GUT (LONDON)	A1
1949-0976	GUT MICROBES	A1
1757-4749	GUT PATHOGENS	A2
1610-2894	GYNAKOLOGISCHE ENDOKRINOLOGIE (PRINT)	B3
0378-7346	GYNECOLOGIC AND OBSTETRIC INVESTIGATION	B2
1423-002X	GYNECOLOGIC AND OBSTETRIC INVESTIGATION	B2
0090-8258	GYNECOLOGIC ONCOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
2352-5789	GYNECOLOGIC ONCOLOGY REPORTS	B3
0951-3590	GYNECOLOGICAL ENDOCRINOLOGY	A4
0197-3975	HABITAT INTERNATIONAL	A1
2173-125X	HÁBITAT Y SOCIEDAD	A4
1678-6475	HABITUS (UCG. IMPRESSO)	A3
1303-5010	HACETTEPE JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS AND STATISTICS	B2
2462-8425	HACIA LA PROMOCIÓN DE LA SALUD	B3
0390-6078	HAEMATOLOGICA (ROMA)	A1
1351-8216	HAEMOPHILIA (OXFORD. PRINT)	A4
1558-9447	HAND (NEW YORK, N.Y.)	B2
2468-1229	HAND SURGERY AND REHABILITATION	B1
1758-9983	HAND THERAPY	B3
0171-2004	HANDBOOK OF EXPERIMENTAL PHARMACOLOGY	A2
0100-3283	HANSENOLOGIA INTERNATIONALIS (IMPRESSO)	B4
1568-9883	HARMFUL ALGAE	A1
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1067-3229	HARVARD REVIEW OF PSYCHIATRY	A2
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1746-160X	HEAD & FACE MEDICINE	A2
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1936-0568	HEAD AND NECK PATHOLOGY (ONLINE)	A2
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1079-0969	HEALTH AND HUMAN RIGHTS	A2

2150-4113	HEALTH AND HUMAN RIGHTS JOURNAL	A2
1353-8292	HEALTH AND PLACE	A1
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2190-7188	HEALTH AND TECHNOLOGY	B2
2326-4403	HEALTH BEHAVIOR AND POLICY REVIEW	B4
0739-9332	HEALTH CARE FOR WOMEN INTERNATIONAL	B1
1386-9620	HEALTH CARE MANAGEMENT SCIENCE	A4
1057-9230	HEALTH ECONOMICS (PRINT)	A1
2191-1991	HEALTH ECONOMICS REVIEW (ONLINE)	A3
1090-1981	HEALTH EDUCATION & BEHAVIOR	A2
0965-4283	HEALTH EDUCATION (LONDON)	A4
1460-4582	HEALTH INFORMATICS JOURNAL	A4
0017-9078	HEALTH PHYSICS (1958)	B1
0168-8510	HEALTH POLICY (AMSTERDAM. PRINT)	A1
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0268-1080	HEALTH POLICY AND PLANNING (PRINT)	A1
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1366-5278	HEALTH TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT (WINCHESTER)	A1
0378-5955	HEARING RESEARCH	A2
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1468-201X	HEART	A2
0147-9563	HEART & LUNG	A2
1355-6037	HEART (LONDON. 1996)	A2
0910-8327	HEART AND VESSELS	A3
1382-4147	HEART FAILURE REVIEWS	A1
1547-5271	HEART RHYTHM	A2
1443-9506	HEART, LUNG AND CIRCULATION (PRINT)	A4
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1064-2285	HEAT TRANSFER RESEARCH	A4
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1809-1261	HEGEMONIA (BRASÍLIA)	B2
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1438-387X	HELGOLAND MARINE RESEARCH (PRINT)	A4
1018-1806	HELIA (NOVI SAD)	B2
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1083-4389	HELICOBACTER (CAMBRIDGE, MASS.)	A1
2357-9366	HELIKON - REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA	B4
0160-0923	HELIOS (LUBBOCK)	B4
2405-8440	HELIYON	A4
1109-9666	HELLENIC JOURNAL OF CARDIOLOGY	B1
1336-9083	HELMINTHOLOGIA	B2
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1099-1069	HEMATOLOGICAL ONCOLOGY	A3
0278-0232	HEMATOLOGICAL ONCOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
1520-4391	HEMATOLOGY (PRINT)	A3

2038-8330	HEMATOLOGY REPORTS (ONLINE)	B2
1658-3876	HEMATOLOGY/ONCOLOGY AND STEM CELL THERAPY	B1
1492-7535	HEMODIALYSIS INTERNATIONAL	B1
0363-0269	HEMOGLOBIN	B2
1735-143X	HEPATITIS MONTHLY	B1
1499-3872	HEPATOBIILIARY AND PANCREATIC DISEASES INTERNATIONAL	B2
2304-3881	HEPATOBIILIARY SURGERY AND NUTRITION	A1
0171-6123	HEPATOLOGY	A1
0270-9139	HEPATOLOGY (BALTIMORE, MD.)	A1
1936-0533	HEPATOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	A3
1386-6346	HEPATOLOGY RESEARCH	A3
0018-067X	HEREDITY (EDINBURGH. PRINT)	A2
1983-6996	HERINGERIANA	B4
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2284-0753	H-ERMES. JOURNAL OF COMMUNICATION	B2
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1265-4906	HERNIA (PARIS. PRINT)	A2
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0018-0831	HERPETOLOGICA (AUSTIN, TX)	A4
1473-0928	HERPETOLOGICAL BULLETIN	B4
1931-7603	HERPETOLOGICAL CONSERVATION AND BIOLOGY	A4
0268-0130	HERPETOLOGICAL JOURNAL	A3
0733-1347	HERPETOLOGICAL MONOGRAPH	A1
0018-084X	HERPETOLOGICAL REVIEW	B4
2071-5773	HERPETOLOGY NOTES	B3
1013-4425	HERPETOZOA (WIEN)	A4
0793-0283	HETEROCYCLIC COMMUNICATIONS	B3
1989-2616	HIB: REVISTA DE HISTORIA IBEROAMERICANA	A2
0188-8897	HIDROBIOLOGICA	B3
1359-8139	HIGH ABILITY STUDIES	A3
1120-9879	HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE & CARDIOVASCULAR PREVENTION	A4
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0895-7959	HIGH PRESSURE RESEARCH	A4
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0952-8733	HIGHER EDUCATION POLICY	A3
0951-5224	HIGHER EDUCATION QUARTERLY (PRINT)	A2
1120-7000	HIP INTERNATIONAL (TESTO STAMPATO)	A4
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1050-9631	HIPPOCAMPUS (NEW YORK, N.Y. PRINT)	A2
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0018-2133	HISPANIA (UNIVERSITY, MISS)	A3
1676-904X	HISPANISTA (EDIÇÃO EM PORTUGUÊS)	B1
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0948-6143	HISTOCHEMISTRY AND CELL BIOLOGY	A2
1954-3670	HISTOIRE @ POLITIQUE	A3

1638-1580	HISTOIRE EPISTEMOLOGIE LANGAGE	A1
1661-4577	HISTOIRE ET CIVILISATION DU LIVRE - REVUE INTERNACIONAL	B4
0213-3911	HISTOLOGY AND HISTOPATHOLOGY	A3
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2176-4352	HISTÓRIA & PERSPECTIVAS	B1
0073-2435	HISTORIA (SANTIAGO. IMPRESA)	A1
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1696-2060	HISTORIA ACTUAL ON-LINE	A2
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2322-6889	HISTORIA CARIBE	A3
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1414-3518	HISTÓRIA DA EDUCAÇÃO (UFPEL)	A1
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1983-9928	HISTÓRIA DA HISTORIOGRAFIA	A1
0212-0267	HISTORIA DE LA EDUCACIÓN	B4
2238-6270	HISTÓRIA E CULTURA	A3
2318-8294	HISTÓRIA E CULTURAS	B2
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2238-3018	HISTÓRIA E ENSINO	A3
1519-3314	HISTÓRIA ECONÔMICA & HISTÓRIA DE EMPRESAS	A4
1516-2095	HISTÓRIA EM REVISTA (UFPEL)	B3
2036-4040	HISTORIA MAGISTRA	B2
1516-7658	HISTÓRIA ORAL (RIO DE JANEIRO)	A2
1414-6312	HISTÓRIA REVISTA	A2
2359-2370	HISTÓRIA UNICAP	A4
1519-3861	HISTÓRIA UNISINOS	A2
2236-1782	HISTÓRIA UNISINOS	A2
1988-3056	HISTORIA Y COMUNICACIÓN SOCIAL	A4
0120-4661	HISTORIA Y ESPACIO	A2
1405-0927	HISTORÍA Y GRAFÍA	A3
2027-5137	HISTORIA Y MEMORIA	A1
2444-0043	HISTORIA Y MEMORIA DE LA EDUCACIÓN	A3
0121-8417	HISTORIA Y SOCIEDAD (MEDELLIN. 1994)	A1
1678-4758	HISTÓRIA, CIÊNCIAS, SAÚDE (ONLINE)	B1
2318-1729	HISTÓRIA, HISTÓRIAS	B1
2317-8361	HISTÓRIA, NATUREZA E ESPAÇO	B2
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2319-0256	JURIS PLENUM DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO	B1
2317-210X	JURIS PLENUM PREVIDENCIÁRIA	B1
2448-0517	JURIS POIESIS	B1
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1413-7038	JUSTIÇA DO DIREITO (UPF)	A1
2177-4811	JUSTIÇA E SISTEMA CRIMINAL	B4
1808-107X	KALAGATOS (UECE)	B1
1808-6977	KALÍOPE (PUCSP)	B3
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2378-5977	KANSAS AGRICULTURAL EXPERIMENT STATION RESEARCH REPORTS	B2
1677-163X	KANT E-PRINTS (ONLINE)	B1
0022-8877	KANT-STUDIEN	A1
0022-9040	KARDIOLOGIÁ / CARDIOLOGY (MOSKVA)	B3
1937-8572	KARPA: JOURNAL OF THEATRICALITIES AND VISUAL CULTURE	B1
2410-1923	KAYPUNKU (REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS INTERDISCIPLINARIOS DE ARTE Y	B4
1794-7111	KEPES	A4
0075-5974	KEW BULLETIN	B2
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2358-9159	KHÓRA ¿ REVISTA TRANSDICLINAR	B4
2447-2158	KHRONOS: REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA CIÊNCIA	B4
1423-0143	KIDNEY AND BLOOD PRESSURE RESEARCH (ONLINE)	A2
0085-2538	KIDNEY INTERNATIONAL	A1
2468-0249	KIDNEY INTERNATIONAL REPORTS	B2
1916-985X	KINEPHANOS	A4
1984-3844	KINESIA	B4
1331-1441	KINESIOLOGY (ZAGREB)	A4

1984-8900	KÍNESIS (MARÍLIA)	B2
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0386-5991	KODAI MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL	B2
0288-4534	KONA (HIRAKATA, OSAKA)	A2
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1225-5610	KOREAN JOURNAL OF ORTHODONTICS	A2
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2273-0095	L¿ORDINAIRE DES AMÉRIQUES	B3
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1168-4704	LA FAUTE À ROUSSEAU	B4
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2357-8289	LEITURAS DO JORNALISMO	B1
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0180-930X	LES ANNALES DE LA RECHERCHE URBAINE (PARIS)	B4
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2237-1184	LITERATURA E SOCIEDADE	B2
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1387-5841	METHODOLOGY AND COMPUTING IN APPLIED PROBABILITY (PRINT)	B2
1769-7379	METHODOS	B1
1626-0600	METHODOS	B1
1046-2023	METHODS (SAN DIEGO, CALIF., PRINT)	A2
2050-6120	METHODS AND APPLICATIONS IN FLUORESCENCE	A2
1073-2772	METHODS AND APPLICATIONS OF ANALYSIS	A4
2413-6166	METHODS AND OBJECTS OF CHEMICAL ANALYSIS	B4
2041-210X	METHODS IN ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION	A1
1940-6029	METHODS IN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	B3
0026-1270	METHODS OF INFORMATION IN MEDICINE	A2

2215-0161	METHODSX	A2
1677-0706	MÉTIS (UCS)	A4
2525-3867	MÉTODOS E PESQUISA EM ADMINISTRAÇÃO	B4
0026-1335	METRIKA (HEIDELBERG)	B1
1435-926X	METRIKA (ONLINE)	B1
0026-1386	METROECONOMICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	A2
0026-1394	METROLOGIA (PARIS. PRINT)	A2
1047-8485	METROPOLITAN UNIVERSITIES JOURNAL	B2
1659-097X	MHSALUD	B4
1342-6311	MICROBES AND ENVIRONMENTS	A2
1286-4579	MICROBES AND INFECTION	A2
1751-7907	MICROBIAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	A2
1751-7915	MICROBIAL BIOTECHNOLOGY (ONLINE)	A2
1475-2859	MICROBIAL CELL FACTORIES	A2
1076-6294	MICROBIAL DRUG RESISTANCE (LARCHMONT, N.Y.)	A4
0095-3628	MICROBIAL ECOLOGY	A1
2057-5858	MICROBIAL GENOMICS	B2
0882-4010	MICROBIAL PATHOGENESIS	A3
2352-3522	MICROBIAL RISK ANALYSIS	B1
1982-1301	MICROBIOLOGIA IN FOCO	B4
1618-0623	MICROBIOLOGICAL RESEARCH (INTERNET)	A3
0944-5013	MICROBIOLOGICAL RESEARCH (PRINT)	A3
1465-2080	MICROBIOLOGY (READING. ONLINE)	B1
0385-5600	MICROBIOLOGY AND IMMUNOLOGY	B2
2165-0497	MICROBIOLOGY SPECTRUM	A2
2045-8827	MICROBIOLOGYOPEN	A4
2049-2618	MICROBIOME	A1
0026-265X	MICROCHEMICAL JOURNAL (PRINT)	A3
1073-9688	MICROCIRCULATION (NEW YORK, N.Y. 1994)	A2
0167-9317	MICROELECTRONIC ENGINEERING	A3
0026-2714	MICROELECTRONICS AND RELIABILITY	A3
0026-2692	MICROELECTRONICS JOURNAL	A4
2072-666X	MICROMACHINES	A2
0968-4328	MICRON	A3
0968-4328	MICRON (OXFORD. 1993)	A3
2076-2607	MICROORGANISMS	B1
0026-2803	MICROPALEONTOLOGY	B1
1387-1811	MICROPOROUS AND MESOPOROUS MATERIALS (PRINT)	A1
0141-9331	MICROPROCESSORS AND MICROSYSTEMS	B1
2211-5374	MICRORNA (ONLINE)	A1
1431-9276	MICROSCOPY AND MICROANALYSIS (PRINT)	A2
1059-910X	MICROSCOPY RESEARCH AND TECHNIQUE (PRINT)	A3
0738-1085	MICROSURGERY	A3
0946-7076	MICROSYSTEM TECHNOLOGIES	A4
0026-2862	MICROVASCULAR RESEARCH (PRINT)	A4
0895-2477	MICROWAVE AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY LETTERS (PRINT)	A4
2182-9543	MIDAS. MUSEUS E ESTUDOS INTERDISCIPLINARES	A4
0974-9233	MIDDLE EAST AFRICAN JOURNAL OF OPHTHALMOLOGY	B3
1793-8171	MIDDLE EAST DEVELOPMENT JOURNAL	A4
2423-4451	MIDDLE EAST JOURNAL OF REHABILITATION AND HEALTH	A4

1073-9467	MIDDLE EAST QUARTERLY	B3
2178-602X	MÍDIA E COTIDIANO	A4
0266-6138	MIDWIFERY	A2
1989-8681	MIGUEL HERNÁNDEZ COMMUNICATION JOURNAL	A4
2317-0433	MIGUILIM - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO NETLLI	A3
0026-3672	MIKROCHIMICA ACTA (1966. PRINT)	A1
1424-9286	MILAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS (PRINTED ED.)	A3
0026-4075	MILITARY MEDICINE (PRINT)	B2
0026-4148	MILITARY REVIEW	A4
1647-662X	MILLENIUM - JOURNAL OF EDUCATION, TECHNOLOGIES, AND HEAL	B3
0873-3015	MILLENIUM (VISEU)	B3
0305-8298	MILLENNIUM	A2
0102-065X	MINAS GERAIS. SUPLEMENTO LITERÁRIO	B1
0268-1064	MIND & LANGUAGE (PRINT)	A2
1074-9039	MIND, CULTURE AND ACTIVITY	A2
1532-7884	MIND, CULTURE, AND ACTIVITY	A2
1868-8527	MINDFULNESS	A1
2445-4079	MINDFULNESS & COMPASSION	B2
1025-9112	MINE WATER AND THE ENVIRONMENT (PRINT)	A3
0882-7508	MINERAL PROCESSING AND EXTRACTIVE METALLURGY REVIEW	A2
0026-4598	MINERALIUM DEPOSITA	A1
0026-461X	MINERALOGICAL MAGAZINE (PRINT)	A4
0930-0708	MINERALOGY AND PETROLOGY	A3
2075-163X	MINERALS	A3
0747-9182	MINERALS & METALLURGICAL PROCESSING	A2
0892-6875	MINERALS ENGINEERING	A1
0026-4725	MINERVA CARDIOANGIOLOGICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	B2
0026-4733	MINERVA CHIRURGICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	B2
0391-1977	MINERVA ENDOCRINOLOGICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	B2
0026-4784	MINERVA GINECOLOGICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	B3
0026-4806	MINERVA MEDICA: A JOURNAL ON INTERNAL MEDICINE	A1
1827-1715	MINERVA PEDIATRICA	A1
0026-4946	MINERVA PEDIATRICA: A JOURNAL ON PEDIATRICS, NEONATOLOGY	A1
0026-4970	MINERVA STOMATOLOGICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	B1
2199-1413	MINIMAX THEORY AND ITS APPLICATIONS	B2
0026-5187	MINING ENGINEERING	B3
2353-5423	MINING SCIENCE	B1
1389-5575	MINI-REVIEWS IN MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY	A3
1570-193X	MINI-REVIEWS IN ORGANIC CHEMISTRY	B3
0938-8249	MIR. MANAGEMENT INTERNATIONAL REVIEW (1990)	A1
1676-5818	MIRABILIA JOURNAL	B1
1984-2899	MISCELÂNEA (ASSIS. ONLINE)	A4
2084-2937	MISCELLANEA ANTHROPOLOGICA ET SOCIOLOGICA	B2
2594-9187	MISES	B3
2318-0811	MISES: REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE FILOSOFIA, DIREITO E ECONC	B3
1794-600X	MISIÓN JURÍDICA - REVISTA DE DERECHO Y CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B3
1518-0263	MISSIONEIRA (SANTO ÂNGELO)	B2
2447-0244	MISSÕES: REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS E SOCIAIS	B2
1364-5706	MITAT. MINIMALLY INVASIVE THERAPY & ALLIED TECHNOLOGIES	B1
1381-2386	MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION STRATEGIES FOR GLOBAL CHANGE	A1

1940-1736	MITOCHONDRIAL DNA	B4
2470-1394	MITOCHONDRIAL DNA PART A (PRINT)	B4
2380-2359	MITOCHONDRIAL DNA PART B: RESOURCES	B4
1567-7249	MITOCHONDRION (AMSTERDAM. PRINT)	A3
2447-0899	MIX SUSTENTÁVEL (PRINT)	A4
1080-6598	MLN	B1
2240-4554	MLTJ MUSCLES, LIGAMENTS AND TENDONS JOURNAL	A4
0267-257X	MM. JOURNAL OF MARKETING MANAGEMENT	A2
1980-6590	MNEMOCINE	B2
1809-8894	MNEMOSINE (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B1
2237-3217	MNEMOSINE REVISTA	B1
2358-0658	MOARA	A2
1759-8753	MOBILE DNA	A1
2159-256X	MOBILE GENETIC ELEMENTS	B1
1875-905X	MOBILE INFORMATION SYSTEMS	B3
1086-671X	MOBILIZATION	A2
1982-615X	MODAPALAVRA E-PERÍODICO	A3
1574-1699	MODEL ASSISTED STATISTICS AND APPLICATIONS	B3
2363-6211	MODELING EARTH SYSTEMS AND ENVIRONMENT	B3
2363-6203	MODELING EARTH SYSTEMS AND ENVIRONMENT (PRINT)	B3
0764-583X	MODÉLISATION MATHÉMATIQUE ET ANALYSE NUMÉRIQUE (IMPRIMÉ)	A1
1687-5591	MODELLING AND SIMULATION IN ENGINEERING	A4
0965-0393	MODELLING AND SIMULATION IN MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING	A3
1259-5985	MODELLING, MEASUREMENT & CONTROL. A, GENERAL PHYSICS, ELECTRONICS	A3
2152-7245	MODERN ECONOMY	A3
0893-3952	MODERN PATHOLOGY	A1
0217-7323	MODERN PHYSICS LETTERS A	B1
0217-9849	MODERN PHYSICS LETTERS B	B2
1439-7595	MODERN RHEUMATOLOGY (PRINT)	B1
0026-8577	MODERNA SPRAAK	B3
2000-3560	MODERNA SPRÁK	A3
2595-1211	MODERNOS & CONTEMPORÂNEOS	B1
1809-1385	MÓIN-MÓIN (UDESC)	A2
2374-6939	MOJ ORTHOPEDICS & RHEUMATOLOGY	B4
2574-9773	MOJ POLYMER SCIENCE	B4
1422-8599	MOLBANK	B4
1535-9476	MOLECULAR & CELLULAR PROTEOMICS	A1
1872-9428	MOLECULAR AND BIOCHEMICAL PARASITOLOGY (ONLINE)	A4
0300-8177	MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR BIOCHEMISTRY	A3
1573-4919	MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR BIOCHEMISTRY	A3
0303-7207	MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR ENDOCRINOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
1044-7431	MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR NEUROSCIENCES (PRINT)	A2
0890-8508	MOLECULAR AND CELLULAR PROBES	B2
2049-9450	MOLECULAR AND CLINICAL ONCOLOGY	B2
0098-2997	MOLECULAR ASPECTS OF MEDICINE	A1
2405-6758	MOLECULAR ASTROPHYSICS	A4
0737-4038	MOLECULAR BIOLOGY AND EVOLUTION	A1
1059-1524	MOLECULAR BIOLOGY OF THE CELL	A2
1939-4586	MOLECULAR BIOLOGY OF THE CELL (ONLINE)	A2
0301-4851	MOLECULAR BIOLOGY REPORTS	B1

1573-4978	MOLECULAR BIOLOGY REPORTS	B1
1742-206X	MOLECULAR BIOSYSTEMS (PRINT)	A3
1073-6085	MOLECULAR BIOTECHNOLOGY	A4
1380-3743	MOLECULAR BREEDING	A1
1476-4598	MOLECULAR CANCER	A1
1541-7786	MOLECULAR CANCER RESEARCH	A2
1535-7163	MOLECULAR CANCER THERAPEUTICS	A1
0899-1987	MOLECULAR CARCINOGENESIS (PRINT)	A3
2468-8231	MOLECULAR CATALYSIS	A2
1097-2765	MOLECULAR CELL	A1
1542-1406	MOLECULAR CRYSTALS AND LIQUID CRYSTALS (PHILADELPHIA, PA. :	B2
1058-725X	MOLECULAR CRYSTALS AND LIQUID CRYSTALS SCIENCE AND TECHN	B2
1755-8166	MOLECULAR CYTOGENETICS	B1
1177-1062	MOLECULAR DIAGNOSIS & THERAPY	A4
1381-1991	MOLECULAR DIVERSITY	A3
0962-1083	MOLECULAR ECOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1755-0998	MOLECULAR ECOLOGY RESOURCES (ONLINE)	A1
2324-9269	MOLECULAR GENETICS & GENOMIC MEDICINE	A4
1617-4623	MOLECULAR GENETICS AND GENOMICS	A4
1096-7192	MOLECULAR GENETICS AND METABOLISM (PRINT)	A2
2214-4269	MOLECULAR GENETICS AND METABOLISM REPORTS	B3
1360-9947	MOLECULAR HUMAN REPRODUCTION (PRINT)	A1
1536-1632	MOLECULAR IMAGING AND BIOLOGY	A1
0161-5890	MOLECULAR IMMUNOLOGY	A4
1868-1743	MOLECULAR INFORMATICS	A3
1791-2997	MOLECULAR MEDICINE REPORTS	B1
2212-8778	MOLECULAR METABOLISM	A1
0950-382X	MOLECULAR MICROBIOLOGY (PRINT)	A2
0893-7648	MOLECULAR NEUROBIOLOGY	A1
1750-1326	MOLECULAR NEURODEGENERATION	A1
1613-4133	MOLECULAR NUTRITION & FOOD RESEARCH	A1
1613-4125	MOLECULAR NUTRITION & FOOD RESEARCH (PRINT)	A1
2041-1006	MOLECULAR ORAL MICROBIOLOGY	A1
1543-8384	MOLECULAR PHARMACEUTICS (PRINT)	A1
1055-7903	MOLECULAR PHYLOGENETICS AND EVOLUTION (PRINT)	A1
0026-8976	MOLECULAR PHYSICS (PRINT)	A4
1674-2052	MOLECULAR PLANT (PRINT)	A1
1464-6722	MOLECULAR PLANT PATHOLOGY	A1
1364-3703	MOLECULAR PLANT PATHOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
0894-0282	MOLECULAR PLANT-MICROBE INTERACTIONS	A1
1359-4184	MOLECULAR PSYCHIATRY	A1
1040-452X	MOLECULAR REPRODUCTION AND DEVELOPMENT	A1
1098-2795	MOLECULAR REPRODUCTION AND DEVELOPMENT (ONLINE)	A1
0892-7022	MOLECULAR SIMULATION (PRINT)	A4
1661-8769	MOLECULAR SYNDROMOLOGY	B2
1525-0016	MOLECULAR THERAPY (PRINT)	A1
2329-0501	MOLECULAR THERAPY ¿ METHODS & CLINICAL DEVELOPMENT	A3
2162-2531	MOLECULAR THERAPY ¿ NUCLEIC ACIDS	A1
1090-0535	MOLECULAR VISION	A3
1420-3049	MOLECULES (BASEL. ONLINE)	A2

1323-5818	MOLLUSCAN RESEARCH	B2
2316-3100	MOMENTO - DIÁLOGOS EM EDUCAÇÃO	B2
2500-8013	MOMENTO e REVISTA DE FÍSICA	A1
1678-0795	MOMENTUM (ATIBAIA)	B3
1434-4475	MONATSCHEFTE FÜR CHEMIE (INTERNET)	A4
0026-9255	MONATSCHEFTE FÜR MATHEMATIK (PRINT)	A3
2358-6524	MONÇÕES REVISTA DO CURSO DE HISTÓRIA DA UFMS/CPCX	B4
2316-8323	MONÇÕES: REVISTA DE RELAÇÕES INTERNACIONAIS DA UFGD	A4
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2594-0929	MONTAJES REVISTA DE ANÁLISIS CINEMATográfico	A4
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0035-8711	MONTHLY NOTICES OF THE ROYAL ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (PRINT)	A2
1745-3925	MONTHLY NOTICES OF THE ROYAL ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY: LETTE	A2
0027-0520	MONTHLY REVIEW (NEW YORK. 1949)	A4
0027-0644	MONTHLY WEATHER REVIEW	A2
0149-2195	MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY WEEKLY REPORT (PRINT)	A1
2177-8841	MORINGA - ARTES DO ESPETÁCULO (UFPB)	A3
1676-2924	MORPHEUS (UNIRIO. ONLINE)	B1
1286-0115	MORPHOLOGIE (ASSOCIATION DES ANATOMISTES)	B2
2447-0996	MORUS - UTOPIA E RENASCIMENTO	B3
1808-561X	MORUS (UNICAMP)	B3
2175-9537	MOSAICO	A4
1983-7801	MOSAICO (GOIÂNIA)	A3
2176-8943	MOSAICO (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B1
1678-6254	MOSAICO (SÃO JOSÉ DO RIO PRETO)	B1
2178-7719	MOSAICO REVISTA MULTIDISCIPLINAR DE HUMANIDADES	B2
1609-3321	MOSCOW MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL	A2
1609-4514	MOSCOW MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL (ONLINE)	A2
1087-1640	MOTOR CONTROL	B1
1646-107X	MOTRICIDADE (SANTA MARIA DA FEIRA)	B2
2175-8042	MOTRIVIVÊNCIA (FLORIANÓPOLIS)	B3
1415-9805	MOTRIZ (RIO CLARO) (CESSOU EM 2006)	B1
1980-6574	MOTRIZ : REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA (ONLINE)	B1
2175-4837	MOURO	B3
2175-4519	MOURO: REVISTA MARXISTA (IMPRESSO)	B3
1496-9343	MOUSEION (CALGARY)	B1
1981-7207	MOUSEION (UNILASALLE)	B2
1291-6412	MOUVEMENTS (IMPRESSO)	A4
2118-5743	MOVEMENT & SPORT SCIENCES (ONLINE)	B2
0885-3185	MOVEMENT DISORDERS	A1
2330-1619	MOVEMENT DISORDERS CLINICAL PRACTICE	A3
1517-199X	MOVENDO IDÉIAS (UNAMA)	A4
1984-4298	MOVIMENTA	B2
2359-3296	MOVIMENTO - REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO	B2
1982-8918	MOVIMENTO (UFRGS. ONLINE)	B2
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2159-6859	MRS COMMUNICATIONS	A2
0960-1295	MSCS. MATHEMATICAL STRUCTURES IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (PRIN	B1
2379-5042	MSPHERE	A3

2379-5077	MSYSTEMS	A1
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2176-1019	MUDANÇAS-PSICOLOGIA DA SAÚDE	B1
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2176-381X	MULEMBA	A3
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2317-0379	MULTICES-REVISTA ACADEMICA MULTIDISCIPLINAR	B4
2594-4568	MULTIDEBATES (ONLINE)	B4
0923-6082	MULTIDIMENSIONAL SYSTEMS AND SIGNAL PROCESSING	A2
2014-2862	MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH	A4
1828-695X	MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESPIRATORY MEDICINE	A4
2595-9670	MULTIFACES	B4
2221-4216	MULTILINGUAL MARGINS	B1
0942-4962	MULTIMEDIA SYSTEMS	A2
1380-7501	MULTIMEDIA TOOLS AND APPLICATIONS	A2
0276-1459	MULTIPHASE SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	B3
1352-4585	MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS	A1
2211-0348	MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS AND RELATED DISORDERS	A3
2526-4036	MÚLTIPLOS ACESSOS - REVISTA CIENTÍFICA INTERDISCIPLINAR	B3
2237-6658	MÚLTIPLOS OLHARES EM CIÊNCIA DA INFORMAÇÃO	B2
1540-3467	MULTISCALE MODELING & SIMULATION (ONLINE)	A2
1540-3459	MULTISCALE MODELING & SIMULATION (PRINT)	A2
2595-6590	MULTI-SCIENCE RESEARCH	B4
1414-512X	MULTITEMAS (UCDB)	B1
1777-5841	MULTITUDES	A4
0292-0107	MULTITUDES (PARIS)	A4
1515-5994	MUNDO AGRARIO (LA PLATA)	B3
2145-5082	MUNDO AMAZONICO	A4
2145-5074	MUNDO AMAZONICO	A4
2527-1105	MUNDO DO TRABALHO CONTEMPORÂNEO	B4
2596-108X	MUNDO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B4
2525-5819	MUNDO LIVRE: REVISTA MULTIDISCIPLINAR DISCENTE	B4
2175-2052	MUNDORAMA	B2
1390-9193	MUNDOS PLURALES: REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE POLÍTICAS Y A	B1
1097-4598	MUSCLE & NERVE (ONLINE)	A4
1557-0681	MUSCULOSKELETAL CARE	A4
2468-7812	MUSCULOSKELETAL SCIENCE AND PRACTICE	A2
0975-1815	MUSE INDIA	B3
2369-3045	MUSEMEDUSA	B3
1984-3917	MUSEOLOGIA E PATRIMÔNIO	B4
1479-8360	MUSEUM & SOCIETY	A2
1461-3808	MUSIC EDUCATION RESEARCH (PRINT)	A1
0730-7829	MUSIC PERCEPTION	A1
1981-7126	MÚSICA EM PERSPECTIVA	B4
1676-3939	MÚSICA HODIE	A1
2525-5541	MUSICA THEORICA	A2
1029-8649	MUSICAE SCIENTIAE	A1
2526-3757	MUSMAT ¿ REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MÚSICA E MATEMÁTICA	A4

0267-8357	MUTAGENESIS	A3
1464-3804	MUTAGENESIS	A3
0027-5107	MUTATION RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2
1383-5718	MUTATION RESEARCH. GENETIC TOXICOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENT/	A4
1383-5742	MUTATION RESEARCH. REVIEWS IN MUTATION RESEARCH (PRINT)	A1
2011-799X	MUTATIS MUTANDIS (MEDELLIN. 2008)	B4
0122-0268	MVZ CORDOBA	B2
1229-8093	MYCOBIOLOGY	A4
1314-4049	MYCOKEYS	A1
0027-5514	MYCOLOGIA	A2
1617-416X	MYCOLOGICAL PROGRESS	A3
2150-1203	MYCOLOGY (PRINT)	B1
0301-486X	MYCOPATHOLOGIA (1975. PRINT)	A4
0940-6360	MYCORRHIZA (BERLIN)	A2
1340-3540	MYCOSCIENCE (TOKYO)	A4
0933-7407	MYCOSES (BERLIN)	A1
2077-7019	MYCOSPHERE ONLINE	A3
0093-4666	MYCOTAXON	B1
1867-1632	MYCOTOXIN RESEARCH	A2
2470-8593	MYOPAIN. A JOURNAL OF MYOFASCIAL PAIN AND FIBROMYALGIA	B4
1994-4136	MYRMECOLOGICAL NEWS	A2
2527-0621	MYTHOS	B4
0027-7630	NAGOYA MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL	A3
1878-7789	NANO COMMUNICATION NETWORKS	A2
2211-2855	NANO ENERGY	A1
1530-6984	NANO LETTERS	A1
1530-6992	NANO LETTERS (ONLINE)	A1
1998-0124	NANO RESEARCH (PRINT)	A1
2452-0748	NANOIMPACT	A1
2079-4991	NANOMATERIALS	A2
1743-5889	NANOMEDICINE	A1
1549-9634	NANOMEDICINE: NANOTECHNOLOGY, BIOLOGY AND MEDICINE	A1
2150-5551	NANO-MICRO LETTERS	A1
2040-3364	NANOSCALE (PRINT)	A2
2040-3372	NANOSCALE (PRINT)	A2
2055-6764	NANOSCALE HORIZONS (ONLINE)	A1
1556-276X	NANOSCALE RESEARCH LETTERS (ONLINE)	A3
2210-6812	NANOSCIENCE & NANOTECHNOLOGY - ASIA	B3
2163-2588	NANOSCIENCE AND NANOTECHNOLOGY	B4
2352-507X	NANO-STRUCTURES & NANO-OBJECTS	A4
1361-6528	NANOTECHNOLOGY (BRISTOL. ONLINE)	A3
0957-4484	NANOTECHNOLOGY (BRISTOL. PRINT)	A3
2191-9097	NANOTECHNOLOGY REVIEWS	A3
1177-8903	NANOTECHNOLOGY, SCIENCE AND APPLICATIONS	A1
1743-5390	NANOTOXICOLOGY.	A1
1166-3243	NARRATIVA	B3
1886-2519	NARRATIVAS	B1
1996-4196	NAS GOROD PLUS	B2
1319-2442	NASRAT AMRA? WA ZIRA'AT AL-KULAT / SAUDI JOURNAL OF KIDNE'	B1
2318-7670	NATIVA	B4

1567-7818	NATURAL COMPUTING	B1
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0169-6238	OASE	A4
1930-7381	OBESITY (SILVER SPRING, MD.)	A2
1662-4025	OBESITY FACTS	A1
2451-8476	OBESITY MEDICINE	B1
1871-403X	OBESITY RESEARCH & CLINICAL PRACTICE (PRINT)	A3
1467-7881	OBESITY REVIEWS (PRINT)	A1
0960-8923	OBESITY SURGERY	A1
1708-0428	OBESITY SURGERY (ONLINE)	A1
2014-5039	OBRA DIGITAL: JOURNAL OF COMMUNICATION AND TECHNOLOGY	A4
1991-7740	OBRAZOVANIE I SAMORAZVITIE	A1
1646-5954	OBSERVATORIO (OBS*)	B2
1982-4564	OBSERVATÓRIO DA JURISDIÇÃO CONSTITUCIONAL	B4
2359-2826	OBSERVATÓRIO DE ELITES POLÍTICAS E SOCIAIS DO BRASIL	B4
1696-8352	OBSERVATORIO DE LA ECONOMÍA LATINOAMERICANA	B2
1984-4891	OBSERVATORIUM	B2
1753-495X	OBSTETRIC MEDICINE	B1
0029-7828	OBSTETRICAL & GYNECOLOGICAL SURVEY	B1
0029-7844	OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY (NEW YORK. 1953)	A1
1687-9589	OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	B3
1470-7926	OCCUPATIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICINE	A1
1351-0711	OCCUPATIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL MEDICINE (LONDON)	A1
0885-114X	OCCUPATIONAL MEDICINE (PHILADELPHIA): STATE OF THE ART REV	B1
0966-7903	OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY INTERNATIONAL	A3
2526-3676	OCCURSUS ¿ REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA	B3
0964-5691	OCEAN & COASTAL MANAGEMENT	A2
1616-7341	OCEAN DYNAMICS (PRINT)	A3
0029-8018	OCEAN ENGINEERING	A1
1463-5003	OCEAN MODELLING (OXFORD. PRINT)	A1
1812-0792	OCEAN SCIENCE	A1
1812-0822	OCEAN SCIENCE DISCUSSIONS	B3
0078-3234	OCEANOLOGIA (SOPOT)	A2
0162-2870	OCTOBER (CAMBRIDGE, MASS.)	B1

0927-3948	OCULAR IMMUNOLOGY AND INFLAMMATION	A1
2296-4681	OCULAR ONCOLOGY AND PATHOLOGY (PRINT)	B4
2526-3404	ÓCULO	B4
2318-0919	OCULUM ENSAIOS	A2
2408-445X	ODISEA. REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS MIGRATORIOS	B2
1870-1477	ODISEO	B4
0375-0183	ODONATOLOGICA (UTRECHT)	B2
1677-3888	ODONTOLOGIA CLÍNICO-CIENTÍFICA (IMPRESSO)	B4
1618-1247	ODONTOLOGY	A3
2215-3411	ODOVTOS - INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DENTAL SCIENCES	B4
0029-8549	OECOLOGIA	A2
2177-6199	OECOLOGIA AUSTRALIS	B3
2178-3748	OFICINA DO HISTORIADOR	A3
1988-2483	OÍDLES (MÁLAGA)	B2
0030-1299	OIKOS (KOBENHAVN)	A1
1808-0235	OIKOS (RIO DE JANEIRO)	A3
2236-8493	OIKOS: FAMÍLIA E SOCIEDADE EM DEBATE	B2
1294-4475	OIL & GAS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	A3
1953-8189	OIL & GAS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	A3
1982-7784	OLAM: CIÊNCIA & TECNOLOGIA (RIO CLARO. ONLINE)	B4
2317-7853	OLH@RES - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO DEPARTAMENTO DE EDUCAÇÃO	B2
1984-0187	OLHAR DE PROFESSOR	B1
1518-2851	OLHARES & TRILHAS (UFU. IMPRESSO)	B1
2318-1095	OLHARES AMAZÔNICOS	B3
1852-4478	OLIVAR	A3
1972-4527	OLTREOCEANO (TESTO STAMPATO)	B2
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2079-5971	ONATI SOCIO - LEGAL SERIES	A2
0950-9232	ONCOGENE (BASINGSTOKE)	A1
2157-9024	ONCOGENESIS	A2
2162-4011	ONCOIMMUNOLOGY	A2
1423-0232	ONCOLOGY	A4
0030-2414	ONCOLOGY (BASEL)	A4
1792-1074	ONCOLOGY LETTERS	B1
1021-335X	ONCOLOGY REPORTS	A3
0965-0407	ONCOLOGY RESEARCH	A3
1949-2553	ONCOTARGET	A2
1178-6930	ONCOTARGETS AND THERAPY	A3
2367-8194	ONE ECOSYSTEM	B4
2352-7714	ONE HEALTH	A4
1676-4285	ONLINE BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF NURSING	B1
1468-4527	ONLINE INFORMATION REVIEW (PRINT)	A1
1608-4217	ONLINE JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	A3
1539-3399	ONLINE JOURNAL OF RURAL NURSING AND HEALTH CARE	B4
2472-5730	ONLINE LEARNING JOURNAL	B1
2061-0661	ONOMASTICA URALICA	B3
1852-3854	ONTEAIKEN. BOLETÍN SOBRE PRÁCTICAS Y ESTUDIOS DE ACCIÓN CC	B4
2317-9465	OPARÁ	B2
1519-3128	OPÇÃO LACANIANA	B4
2177-2673	OPÇÃO LACANIANA ONLINE NOVA SÉRIE	B4

1012-1587	OPCIÓN (MARACAIBO)	B2
1179-1543	OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL OF SPORTS MEDICINE	B3
2333-9721	OPEN ACCESS LIBRARY JOURNAL	B4
1179-156X	OPEN ACCESS RHEUMATOLOGY	B2
1874-6136	OPEN AIDS JOURNAL	B1
2046-2441	OPEN BIOLOGY	A2
2391-5420	OPEN CHEMISTRY (ONLINE)	B1
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2328-8957	OPEN FORUM INFECTIOUS DISEASES	A3
2363-7501	OPEN GEOSPATIAL DATA, SOFTWARE AND STANDARDS	B3
2053-3624	OPEN HEART (BMJ)	A2
2164-5531	OPEN JOURNAL OF ANESTHESIOLOGY	B4
2161-7597	OPEN JOURNAL OF ANIMAL SCIENCES	B4
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2165-9389	OPEN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL PSYCHOLOGY	B4
2162-5344	OPEN JOURNAL OF NURSING	B4
2165-6681	OPEN JOURNAL OF POLYMER CHEMISTRY	B4
2327-5952	OPEN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES	B3
2160-8709	OPEN JOURNAL OF STOMATOLOGY	B2
2165-3356	OPEN JOURNAL OF VETERINARY MEDICINE	B4
2165-3364	OPEN JOURNAL OF VETERINARY MEDICINE	B4
2056-6700	OPEN LIBRARY OF HUMANITIES	A2
2391-5412	OPEN LIFE SCIENCES	B1
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2543-8875	OPEN PHILOSOPHY	B2
2304-070X	OPEN PRAXIS	A2
1874-3129	OPEN RHEUMATOLOGY JOURNAL	B1
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2218-6050	OPEN VETERINARY JOURNAL	B3
2226-4485	OPEN VETERINARY JOURNAL	B3
0163-5980	OPERATING SYSTEMS REVIEW	A3
1109-2858	OPERATIONAL RESEARCH	A2
0030-364X	OPERATIONS RESEARCH	A2
2211-6923	OPERATIONS RESEARCH FOR HEALTH CARE	A3
0167-6377	OPERATIONS RESEARCH LETTERS	B1
0361-7734	OPERATIVE DENTISTRY	A1
2332-4252	OPERATIVE NEUROSURGERY	B1
1048-6666	OPERATIVE TECHNIQUES IN ORTHOPAEDICS	B2
0928-6586	OPHTHALMIC EPIDEMIOLOGY	A4
1381-6810	OPHTHALMIC GENETICS	A4
0740-9303	OPHTHALMIC PLASTIC AND RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGERY	B1
0030-3747	OPHTHALMIC RESEARCH	A3
2325-8160	OPHTHALMIC SURGERY, LASERS AND IMAGING RETINA	A3
0030-3755	OPHTHALMOLOGICA (BASEL)	A3
0161-6420	OPHTHALMOLOGY (ROCHESTER, MINN.)	A1
2193-8245	OPHTHALMOLOGY AND THERAPY	A1
2468-6530	OPHTHALMOLOGY RETINA	B4
2525-8133	OPINIÕES - REVISTA DOS ALUNOS DE LITERATURA BRASILEIRA	B1
1807-0191	OPINIÃO PÚBLICA	A1
1692-2530	OPINION JURIDICA	A4

2177-5648	OP SIS	A2
2334-2536	OPTICA	A1
0306-8919	OPTICAL AND QUANTUM ELECTRONICS	B1
0091-3286	OPTICAL ENGINEERING (BELLINGHAM. PRINT)	A3
1068-5200	OPTICAL FIBER TECHNOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
0925-3467	OPTICAL MATERIALS (AMSTERDAM. PRINT)	A3
2159-3930	OPTICAL MATERIALS EXPRESS	A4
1340-6000	OPTICAL REVIEW	B2
1573-4277	OPTICAL SWITCHING AND NETWORKING (PRINT)	A3
0030-3992	OPTICS AND LASER TECHNOLOGY	A2
0143-8166	OPTICS AND LASERS IN ENGINEERING	A1
0030-400X	OPTICS AND SPECTROSCOPY (PRINT)	B2
0030-4018	OPTICS COMMUNICATIONS (PRINT)	A3
1094-4087	OPTICS EXPRESS	A1
0146-9592	OPTICS LETTERS	A2
0030-4026	OPTIK (STUTT GART)	A4
0143-2087	OPTIMAL CONTROL APPLICATIONS & METHODS	A2
1029-4945	OPTIMIZATION (ONLINE)	A3
0233-1934	OPTIMIZATION (PRINT)	A3
1389-4420	OPTIMIZATION AND ENGINEERING (PRINT)	A2
1862-4472	OPTIMIZATION LETTERS (PRINT)	A4
1029-4937	OPTIMIZATION METHODS AND SOFTWARE	B1
0103-7412	OPUS (PORTO ALEGRE)	A1
2063-1588	OPUSCULA ZOOLOGICA INSTITUTI ZOOSYSTEMATICI ET OECOLOGIC	B4
0237-5419	OPUSCULA ZOOLOGICA INSTITUTI ZOOSYSTEMATICI ET OECOLOGIC	B4
1865-1550	ORAL AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY (PRINT)	B1
2214-5419	ORAL AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY CASES	B4
1354-523X	ORAL DISEASES	A2
1602-1622	ORAL HEALTH & PREVENTIVE DENTISTRY	A4
1368-8375	ORAL ONCOLOGY (1997)	A1
0911-6028	ORAL RADIOLOGY	B3
1752-248X	ORAL SURGERY	B3
1752-2471	ORAL SURGERY (PRINT)	B3
2212-4403	ORAL SURGERY, ORAL MEDICINE, ORAL PATHOLOGY AND ORAL RAI	A3
1528-395X	ORAL SURGERY, ORAL MEDICINE, ORAL PATHOLOGY, ORAL RADIOL	A4
1851-7811	ORBIS TERTIUS (EN LÍNEA)	A3
0167-6830	ORBIT (AMSTERDAM)	B1
1984-6428	ORBITAL: THE ELECTRONIC JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY	B4
2525-4898	ORÇAMENTO EM DISCUSSÃO	B3
0169-1368	ORE GEOLOGY REVIEWS	A1
2525-5304	ORFEU	A1
1519-0110	ORG & DEMO (UNESP. MARÍLIA)	A4
1477-0520	ORGANIC & BIOMOLECULAR CHEMISTRY	A2
1879-4238	ORGANIC AGRICULTURE	A4
2052-4129	ORGANIC CHEMISTRY FRONTIERS	A1
1307-6175	ORGANIC COMMUNICATIONS	B2
1566-1199	ORGANIC ELECTRONICS (PRINT)	A2
0146-6380	ORGANIC GEOCHEMISTRY	A2
1523-7060	ORGANIC LETTERS (PRINT)	A1
1083-6160	ORGANIC PROCESS RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT	A2

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1439-6092	ORGANISMS DIVERSITY & EVOLUTION (PRINT)	A2
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2318-9223	ORGANIZAÇÕES E SUSTENTABILIDADE	B2
1809-1040	ORGANIZAÇÕES EM CONTEXTO (IMPRESSO)	A3
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1086-0266	ORGANIZATION & ENVIRONMENT	A1
1350-5084	ORGANIZATION (LONDON)	A1
0170-8406	ORGANIZATION STUDIES	A1
0749-5978	ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR AND HUMAN DECISION PROCESSES (P	A1
1547-6278	ORGANOGENESIS	A3
0276-7333	ORGANOMETALLICS	A2
2238-8915	ORGANON	A1
0970-020X	ORIENTAL JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY	B4
0474-6805	ORIGINI	B1
0169-6149	ORIGINS OF LIFE AND EVOLUTION OF THE BIOSPHERE	A4
0301-1569	ORL (BASEL)	B2
1423-0275	ORL (ONLINE)	B2
2447-536X	ORNAMENTAL HORTICULTURE	B4
1075-4377	ORNITOLOGÍA NEOTROPICAL	B3
1750-1172	ORPHANET JOURNAL OF RARE DISEASES	A2
1982-8799	ORTHO SCIENCE: ORTHODONTIC SCIENCE AND PRACTICE	B4
1344-0241	ORTHODONTIC WAVES	B3
1601-6335	ORTHODONTICS & CRANIOFACIAL RESEARCH (PRINT)	A1
2325-9671	ORTHOPAEDIC JOURNAL OF SPORTS MEDICINE	B2
1877-0568	ORTHOPAEDICS & TRAUMATOLOGY: SURGERY & RESEARCH.	A4
0147-7447	ORTHOPEDICS (THOROFARE, N.J.)	A4
1509-3492	ORTOPEDIA, TRAUMATOLOGIA, REHABILITACJA	B2
0030-6053	ORYX (OXFORD. PRINT)	A3
0030-6126	OSAKA JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS	B1
1063-4584	OSTEOARTHRITIS AND CARTILAGE	A1
0937-941X	OSTEOPOROSIS INTERNATIONAL	A2
0889-5899	OSTOMY/WOUND MANAGEMENT	B1
1539-4492	OTJR (THOROFARE, N.J.)	A3
0030-6665	OTOLARYNGOLOGIC CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA	A4
0194-5998	OTOLARYNGOLOGY AND HEAD AND NECK SURGERY	A1
1531-7129	OTOLOGY & NEUROTOLOGY	A2
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1743-1034	OUTLOOKS ON PEST MANAGEMENT	B3
1743-1026	OUTLOOKS ON PEST MANAGEMENT (PRINT)	B3
1807-5002	OUTRA TRAVESSIA (UFSC)	B1
2176-8552	OUTRA TRAVESSIA (UFSC)	B1
2358-7377	OUTRAMARGEM: REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA	B4
2318-5503	OUTRAS FRONTEIRAS: REVISTA DISCENTE DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS-C	B3
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1516-6333	OUTUBRO (SÃO PAULO)	B3
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0030-7653	OXFORD ECONOMIC PAPERS	A1

0305-4985	OXFORD REVIEW OF EDUCATION	A2
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1679-0944	P@RANOÁ (UNB)	B1
2358-7814	P2P & INOVAÇÃO	B2
2007-3607	PAAKAT: REVISTA DE TECNOLOGIA Y SOCIEDAD	A4
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0030-8730	PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS	A3
1348-9151	PACIFIC JOURNAL OF OPTIMIZATION (PRINT)	B3
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0894-3214	PACKAGING TECHNOLOGY & SCIENCE (PRINT)	A3
1099-1522	PACKAGING TECHNOLOGY AND SCIENCE (ONLINE)	A3
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2070-0466	P-ADIC NUMBERS, ULTRAMETRIC ANALYSIS AND APPLICATIONS (PR	B3
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1155-5645	PAEDIATRIC ANAESTHESIA (PARIS. PRINT)	A2
0269-5022	PAEDIATRIC AND PERINATAL EPIDEMIOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
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1982-6109	PAIDÉI@ (SANTOS)	B3
2595-265X	PAIDEIA	B4
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0103-863X	PAIDÉIA (USP. RIBEIRAO PRETO. IMPRESSO)	A1
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1918-1523	PAIN RESEARCH & MANAGEMENT	B3
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1414-1434	PAISAGENS (USP)	B4
0253-8318	PAK VET J	A3
0552-9034	PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES	B1
1028-8880	PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	B1
0556-3321	PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY	B1
2070-3368	PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF BOTANY (ONLINE)	B1
1816-2711	PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF STATISTICS AND OPERATION RESEARCH	B4
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0122-8285	PALABRA CLAVE	A4
1853-9912	PALABRA CLAVE (LA PLATA)	A2
1867-1594	PALAEODIVERSITY AND PALAEOENVIRONMENTS: INTERNATION.	A4
0031-0174	PALAEOBOTANIST (LUCKNOW)	B4
0031-0182	PALAEOGEOGRAPHY, PALAEOCLIMATOLOGY, PALAEOECOLOGY	A1
1094-8074	PALAEONTOLOGIA ELECTRONICA	A4
0031-0239	PALAEONTOLOGY (LONDON)	A1

1871-174X	PALAEOWORLD (AMSTERDAM)	A4
2372-1391	PALAEOSTRA	B3
0883-1351	PALAIOS (TULSA)	A3
0031-0220	PALAONTOLOGISCHE ZEITSCHRIFT	A4
2055-5563	PALEOAMERICA: A JOURNAL OF EARLY HUMAN MIGRATION AND D	A2
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2055-1045	PALGRAVE COMMUNICATIONS	A4
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1880-5302	PALLIATIVE CARE RESEARCH (ONLINE)	B3
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2357-9641	PAN AMERICAN JOURNAL OF AGING RESEARCH	B2
2358-4696	PAN AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL THERMOLOGY	B4
1809-9009	PAN-AMERICAN JOURNAL OF AQUATIC SCIENCES	B4
0885-3177	PANCREAS (NEW YORK)	A3
1424-3903	PANCREATOLOGY	A4
1982-8837	PANDAEMONIUM GERMANICUM (ONLINE)	A1
0031-0808	PANMINERVA MEDICA (TESTO STAMPATO)	A3
1452-595X	PANOECONOMICUS	A2
2237-1087	PANORAMA	B2
1414-8161	PANORAMA ACADÊMICO (UNEB)	B4
2317-7977	PANORAMA EUA	B4
2447-2867	PANORAMA INTERNACIONAL FEE	B4
1517-9257	PAPÉIS (UFMS)	A1
1807-0205	PAPÉIS AVULSOS DE ZOOLOGIA (ONLINE)	B1
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1516-9111	PAPERS DO NAEA (UFPA)	B3
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0033-3352	PAR. PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION REVIEW	A1
1982-0003	PARA ONDE!?! (UFRGS)	B1
1011-2251	PARADIGMA (MARACAY)	A2
0103-5908	PARADIGMA (RIBEIRÃO PRETO)	A4
2317-4919	PARÁGRAFO: REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DE COMUNICAÇÃO SOCIAL DA FI/	A2
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2178-8162	PARALELLUS. REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DE RELIGIÃO - UNICAP	B1
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0129-6264	PARALLEL PROCESSING LETTERS	B3
2237-0390	PARANÁ COOPERATIVO TÉCNICO CIENTÍFICO	B4
1414-7866	PARANÁ ELEITORAL	B2
1776-1042	PARASITE	A1
1252-607X	PARASITE (PARIS)	A1

2405-6731	PARASITE EPIDEMIOLOGY AND CONTROL	B2
0141-9838	PARASITE IMMUNOL.	A3
1365-3024	PARASITE IMMUNOLOGY	A3
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1469-8161	PARASITOLOGY (CAMBRIDGE. ONLINE)	A2
1383-5769	PARASITOLOGY INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	A4
1432-1955	PARASITOLOGY RESEARCH (1987. INTERNET)	A1
1980-6809	PARC : PESQUISA EM ARQUITETURA E CONSTRUÇÃO	A3
1413-9375	PARCERIAS ESTRATÉGICAS (IMPRESSO)	B2
1353-8020	PARKINSONISM & RELATED DISORDERS	A1
2090-8083	PARKINSON'S DISEASE	A4
2035-6609	PARTECIPAZIONE E CONFLITTO (ONLINE)	A3
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1749-8716	PARTICIPATIONS: JOURNAL OF AUDIENCE & RECEPTION STUDIES	A3
0934-0866	PARTICLE & PARTICLE SYSTEMS CHARACTERIZATION	A1
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1984-2503	PASSAGENS: REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE HISTÓRIA POLÍTICA E CUL	A2
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0264-3944	PASTORAL CARE IN EDUCATION (PRINT)	A2
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1015-2008	PATHOBIOLOGY (BASEL)	B1
2076-0817	PATHOGENS	A2
2049-632X	PATHOGENS AND DISEASE	A3
2047-7724	PATHOGENS AND GLOBAL HEALTH	A4
1320-5463	PATHOLOGY INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	B1
1219-4956	PATHOLOGY ONCOLOGY RESEARCH	A3
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1079-7440	PDA JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	B2
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1545-5009	PEDIATRIC BLOOD & CANCER	A3
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1399-543X	PEDIATRIC DIABETES (PRINT)	A1
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1170-7690	PHARMACOECONOMICS (AUCKLAND)	A1
1744-6872	PHARMACOGENETICS AND GENOMICS (PRINT)	A4
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1178-7066	PHARMACOGENOMICS AND PERSONALIZED MEDICINE	A1
1473-1150	PHARMACOGENOMICS JOURNAL (ONLINE)	A2
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1063-7788	PHYSICS OF ATOMIC NUCLEI (PRINT)	B2
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1548-9213	PHYSIOLOGY	A1
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2177-1642	PLANETA AMAZÔNIA: REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE DIREITO AMBIEI	B2
2358-2251	PLANETARIA	B4
0032-0633	PLANETARY AND SPACE SCIENCE	A4
2468-0648	PLANEXT	B4
1880-8247	PLANKTON & BENTHOS RESEARCH	B2
0266-5433	PLANNING PERSPECTIVES (PRINT)	A3
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1573-5036	PLANT AND SOIL (DORDRECHT. ONLINE)	A1
1438-8677	PLANT BIOLOGY	A2
1435-8603	PLANT BIOLOGY (STUTTGART)	A2
1126-3504	PLANT BIOSYSTEMS (FIRENZE. TESTO STAMPATO)	A4
1467-7644	PLANT BIOTECHNOLOGY JOURNAL (PRINT)	A1
0179-9541	PLANT BREEDING	A3
0721-7714	PLANT CELL REPORTS (PRINT)	A1
0167-6857	PLANT CELL, TISSUE AND ORGAN CULTURE (PRINT)	A1
0191-2917	PLANT DISEASE	A2
1755-0874	PLANT ECOLOGY & DIVERSITY (PRINT)	A3
1385-0237	PLANT ECOLOGY (DORDRECHT)	A2
2032-3913	PLANT ECOLOGY AND EVOLUTION	A4
0921-9668	PLANT FOODS FOR HUMAN NUTRITION (DORDRECHT)	A2
2352-4073	PLANT GENE	A2

1479-2621	PLANT GENETIC RESOURCES (PRINT)	B1
1573-5087	PLANT GROWTH REGULATION	A2
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0960-7412	PLANT JOURNAL (PRINT)	A1
1746-4811	PLANT METHODS	A1
0167-4412	PLANT MOLECULAR BIOLOGY	A1
0735-9640	PLANT MOLECULAR BIOLOGY REPORTER	A2
1365-3059	PLANT PATHOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
0032-0889	PLANT PHYSIOLOGY (BETHESDA)	A1
0981-9428	PLANT PHYSIOLOGY AND BIOCHEMISTRY (PARIS)	A1
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0168-9452	PLANT SCIENCE (LIMERICK)	A1
2348-1900	PLANT SCIENCE TODAY	B4
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0913-557X	PLANT SPECIES BIOLOGY	A4
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1365-3040	PLANT, CELL AND ENVIRONMENT	A1
0140-7791	PLANT, CELL AND ENVIRONMENT (PRINT)	A1
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0032-0935	PLANTA (HEIDELBERG)	A1
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1723-0993	PLANUM THE JOURNAL OF URBANISM	B4
0272-4324	PLASMA CHEMISTRY AND PLASMA PROCESSING	A2
1947-5764	PLASMA MEDICINE	B2
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2178-4442	POÍESIS PEDAGOGICA	B3
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0300-9440	PROGRESS IN ORGANIC COATINGS (PRINT)	A2
2196-1042	PROGRESS IN ORTHODONTICS	A2
0146-6410	PROGRESS IN PARTICLE AND NUCLEAR PHYSICS	A1
1058-9813	PROGRESS IN PEDIATRIC CARDIOLOGY	B2
0079-6727	PROGRESS IN QUANTUM ELECTRONICS	A1
1350-9462	PROGRESS IN RETINAL AND EYE RESEARCH	A1
1477-7606	PROGRESS IN RUBBER, PLASTICS AND RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY	B2
1526-9248	PROGRESS IN TRANSPLANTATION	B2
2050-3911	PROGRESS OF THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PHYSICS	A3
1514-0032	PROHISTORIA (ROSARIO)	A3
8756-9728	PROJECT MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	A1
1518-5125	PROJECTARE (PELOTAS)	B2
2525-4146	PROJECTUS	B4
2236-2207	PROJETICA	A4
0102-4442	PROJETO HISTÓRIA (PUCSP)	A3
1983-9979	PROLÍNGUA (JOÃO PESSOA)	A2
2175-0920	PROMETEU (NATAL)	B3
2176-5960	PROMETEUS FILOSOFIA EM REVISTA	B1
1311-9109	PROPAGATION OF ORNAMENTAL PLANTS	B2
0721-3115	PROPELLANTS, EXPLOSIVES, PYROTECHNICS	A4
1980-6248	PRÓ-POSIÇÕES (UNICAMP. ONLINE)	A1
1677-8065	PROSPECTIVA (PORTO ALEGRE)	A3

0033-1538	PROSPECTS (PARIS)	B3
1098-8823	PROSTAGLANDINS & OTHER LIPID MEDIATORS	A3
0952-3278	PROSTAGLANDINS, LEUKOTRIENES AND ESSENTIAL FATTY ACIDS	A3
2287-8882	PROSTATE INTERNATIONAL	A3
0309-3646	PROSTHETICS AND ORTHOTICS INTERNATIONAL	A4
2070-2051	PROTECTION OF METALS AND PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF SURFACES	B1
1875-5305	PROTEIN & PEPTIDE LETTERS	B2
0929-8665	PROTEIN AND PEPTIDE LETTERS	B2
1046-5928	PROTEIN EXPRESSION AND PURIFICATION (PRINT)	B2
0961-8368	PROTEIN SCIENCE (PRINT)	A4
1097-0134	PROTEINS (ONLINE)	B1
0887-3585	PROTEINS (PRINT)	B1
2227-7382	PROTEOMES	B3
1615-9861	PROTEOMICS	A2
1862-8354	PROTEOMICS - CLINICAL APPLICATIONS	A2
1862-8346	PROTEOMICS - CLINICAL APPLICATIONS (PRINT)	A2
1615-9853	PROTEOMICS (WEINHEIM. PRINT)	A2
1678-6408	PROTESTANTISMO EM REVISTA	A4
1434-4610	PROTIST (JENA. PRINT)	A3
0033-183X	PROTOPLASMA	A2
1852-0006	PROYECCIÓN (MENDOZA. EN LÍNEA)	B3
0716-0917	PROYECCIONES (ANTOFAGASTA. IMPRESA)	B4
1853-6352	PROYECCIONES UTN-BA	B4
0326-2774	PRUDENTIA IURIS	B2
2446-7340	PRUMO	B2
2082-1212	PRZEGLĄD PRAWA KONSTITUCYJNEGO	B2
0033-2097	PRZEGLAD ELEKTROTECHNICZNY	B3
2527-1288	PSI UNISC	B4
1679-9887	PSICANÁLISE & BARROCO EM REVISTA	B3
1518-8256	PSICANÁLISE EM REVISTA	B4
0103-5371	PSICO (PUCRS. IMPRESSO)	A1
0124-0137	PSICOGENTE	A4
2316-1124	PSICOLOGIA & SABERES	B4
1807-0310	PSICOLOGIA & SOCIEDADE (ONLINE)	A1
0874-2049	PSICOLOGIA (LISBOA)	A4
0103-7013	PSICOLOGIA ARGUMENTO (PUCPR. IMPRESSO)	B1
1980-5438	PSICOLOGIA CLINICA (ONLINE)	A2
1824-078X	PSICOLOGIA CLINICA DELLO SVILUPPO	B1
1414-6975	PSICOLOGIA DA EDUCAÇÃO (IMPRESSO)	B1
0123-417X	PSICOLOGIA DESDE EL CARIBE	A3
2011-7485	PSICOLOGIA DESDE EL CARIBE	A3
2238-779X	PSICOLOGIA E SABER SOCIAL	B1
2446-922X	PSICOLOGIA E SAÚDE EM DEBATE	B3
0102-7182	PSICOLOGIA E SOCIEDADE (IMPRESSO)	A1
1413-7372	PSICOLOGIA EM ESTUDO (IMPRESSO)	A1
2175-0734	PSICOLOGIA EM FOCO (ARACAJU)	B4
1982-1247	PSICOLOGIA EM PESQUISA (UFJF)	A4
1677-1168	PSICOLOGIA EM REVISTA (IMPRESSA)	A3
2179-5800	PSICOLOGIA ENSINO & FORMAÇÃO	B3
1870-350X	PSICOLOGÍA PARA AMÉRICA LATINA	B3

1138-0853	PSICOLOGÍA POLÍTICA	B2
1413-4063	PSICOLOGIA REVISTA	B1
2594-3871	PSICOLOGIA REVISTA (ONLINE)	B1
1678-5177	PSICOLOGIA USP	A2
1688-7026	PSICOLOGÍA, CONOCIMIENTO Y SOCIEDAD	B1
0874-2391	PSICOLOGIA, EDUCAÇÃO E CULTURA	B1
1645-0086	PSICOLOGIA, SAÚDE & DOENÇAS	A3
1982-3703	PSICOLOGIA: CIÊNCIA E PROFISSÃO (ONLINE)	A2
1678-7153	PSICOLOGIA: REFLEXÃO E CRÍTICA	A1
1806-3446	PSICOLOGIA: TEORIA E PESQUISA (BRASÍLIA. ONLINE)	A1
1415-8809	PSICÓLOGO INFORMAÇÃO	B4
1696-7240	PSICOONCOLOGÍA	A3
0103-8486	PSICOPEDAGOGIA (SÃO PAULO)	B1
1808-6225	PSICOPEDAGOGIA ON LINE	B2
0717-7798	PSICOPERSPECTIVAS. INDIVIDUO Y SOCIEDAD	A3
0214-9915	PSICOTHEMA (OVIEDO)	A2
1413-8271	PSICO-USF (IMPRESSO)	A2
2250-5504	PSIENCIA. REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE CIENCIA PSICOLÓGICA	B2
1809-0796	PSIQUE (SÃO PAULO)	B4
2037-3635	PSL QUARTERLY REVIEW	A3
0033-2623	PSYCHE (STUTT GART) / PSYCHOANALYSE (STUTT GART)	B2
0033-2615	PSYCHE: A JOURNAL OF ENTOMOLOGY (CAMBRIDGE)	B3
1849-0867	PSYCHIATRIA DANUBINA	B3
0048-5713	PSYCHIATRIC ANNALS	A2
0955-8829	PSYCHIATRIC GENETICS	B1
0033-2720	PSYCHIATRIC QUARTERLY	A4
1323-1316	PSYCHIATRY AND CLINICAL NEUROSCIENCES (CARLTON, VIC. PRINT)	A3
1738-3684	PSYCHIATRY INVESTIGATION	B1
0165-1781	PSYCHIATRY RESEARCH (PRINT)	A4
0925-4927	PSYCHIATRY RESEARCH. NEUROIMAGING (PRINT)	A3
1755-201X	PSYCHOANALYSIS AND HISTORY	A4
0736-9735	PSYCHOANALYTIC PSYCHOLOGY	A2
0266-8734	PSYCHOANALYTIC PSYCHOTHERAPY	A3
1479-8301	PSYCHOGERIATRICS (ONLINE)	B1
1346-3500	PSYCHOGERIATRICS (TOKYO)	B1
1647-8606	PSYCHOLOGICA	B1
1939-134X	PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT	A2
0033-2917	PSYCHOLOGICAL MEDICINE (PRINT)	A1
0033-2941	PSYCHOLOGICAL REPORTS	A2
1145-1882	PSYCHOLOGIE CLINIQUE (REVUE)	B4
2118-4496	PSYCHOLOGIE CLINIQUE ET PROJECTIVE (ONLINE)	B2
1420-2530	PSYCHOLOGIE DU TRAVAIL ET DES ORGANISATIONS	B1
0887-0446	PSYCHOLOGY & HEALTH	A1
1983-3288	PSYCHOLOGY & NEUROSCIENCE (ONLINE)	A1
2152-7180	PSYCHOLOGY (IRVINE)	B3
1476-0835	PSYCHOLOGY AND PSYCHOTHERAPY	A3
0893-164X	PSYCHOLOGY OF ADDICTIVE BEHAVIORS	A2
2326-5523	PSYCHOLOGY OF CONSCIOUSNESS: THEORY, RESEARCH, AND PRACTICE	A2
2083-8506	PSYCHOLOGY OF LANGUAGE AND COMMUNICATION	A4
0305-7356	PSYCHOLOGY OF MUSIC	A2

1469-0292	PSYCHOLOGY OF SPORT AND EXERCISE	A1
2159-5550	PSYCHOLOGY RESEARCH	A4
2159-5542	PSYCHOLOGY RESEARCH	A4
1179-1578	PSYCHOLOGY RESEARCH AND BEHAVIOR MANAGEMENT	A2
2182-438X	PSYCHOLOGY, COMMUNITY & HEALTH	B1
1354-8506	PSYCHOLOGY, HEALTH & MEDICINE	A4
1465-3966	PSYCHOLOGY, HEALTH & MEDICINE	A4
2171-2085	PSYCHOLOGY, SOCIETY & EDUCATION	A4
0306-4530	PSYCHONEUROENDOCRINOLOGY	A1
1057-9249	PSYCHO-ONCOLOGY (CHICHESTER, ENGLAND)	A1
0254-4962	PSYCHOPATHOLOGY	A2
0033-3158	PSYCHOPHARMACOLOGY	A2
1432-2072	PSYCHOPHARMACOLOGY (BERLIN. INTERNET)	A2
1469-8986	PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGY (CAMBRIDGE. ONLINE)	A3
0048-5772	PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGY (NEW YORK. PRINT)	A3
0033-3174	PSYCHOSOMATIC MEDICINE	A1
0033-3182	PSYCHOSOMATICS (WASHINGTON, D.C. PRINT)	A2
1476-9263	PSYCHOTHERAPY AND POLITICS INTERNATIONAL	B1
0033-3190	PSYCHOTHERAPY AND PSYCHOSOMATICS	A1
1055-0143	PSYCOLOQUY (WASHINGTON, D.C.)	A3
2171-1976	PSYCOLOGY: REVISTA BILINGUE DE PSICOLOGIA AMBIENTAL	B1
0951-418X	PTR. PHYTOTHERAPY RESEARCH	A2
1927-5188	PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION RESEARCH	B2
0048-5829	PUBLIC CHOICE	A1
1091-1421	PUBLIC FINANCE REVIEW	A4
0033-3506	PUBLIC HEALTH (LONDON)	A4
1662-8063	PUBLIC HEALTH GENOMICS (ONLINE)	A3
1662-4246	PUBLIC HEALTH GENOMICS (PRINT)	A3
1525-1446	PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING	A4
0737-1209	PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING (BOSTON, MASS.)	A4
1475-2727	PUBLIC HEALTH NUTRITION	A2
0033-3549	PUBLIC HEALTH REPORTS (1974)	A4
1471-9037	PUBLIC MANAGEMENT REVIEW (PRINT)	A1
1566-7170	PUBLIC ORGANIZATION REVIEW	B1
0363-8111	PUBLIC RELATIONS REVIEW (RIVERDALE, N.Y.)	A2
0963-6625	PUBLIC UNDERSTANDING OF SCIENCE (PRINT)	A1
1900-6608	PUBLICACIONES Y INVESTIGACION	B2
0214-1493	PUBLICACIONES MATEMÀTIQUES	A2
1676-8493	PUBLICATIO UEPG. CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS, CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS APLICAD	B4
0033-3883	PUBLICACIONES MATHEMATICAE (DEBRECEN)	B1
1448-6083	PUBLICATIONS OF THE ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY OF AUSTRALIA	A4
0004-6264	PUBLICATIONS OF THE ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY OF JAPAN	A4
0004-6280	PUBLICATIONS OF THE ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY OF THE PACIFIC	A4
1747-7107	PUBLIUS (ONLINE)	A2
0048-5950	PUBLIUS (PHILADELPHIA)	A2
1982-1263	PUBVET (LONDRINA)	B4
1563-0013	PUENTES	B3
1669-8452	PUENTES (LA PLATA)	B4
2398-3108	PULMONARY AND CRITICAL CARE MEDICINE	B4
2045-8932	PULMONARY CIRCULATION	A3

2090-1836	PULMONARY MEDICINE	B2
1094-5539	PULMONARY PHARMACOLOGY & THERAPEUTICS	A3
2594-5041	PUÑADO	B3
1365-3075	PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY (ONLINE)	A2
0033-4545	PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A2
1420-9136	PURE AND APPLIED GEOPHYSICS	A3
1573-9538	PURINERGIC SIGNALLING (PRINT)	A2
1460-2393	QJM (OXFORD. 1994. ONLINE)	A2
1460-2725	QJM (OXFORD. 1994. PRINT)	A2
1592-4424	QUADERNI DI RICERCA IN DIDATTICA	B4
0392-1867	QUADERNI FIORENTINI PER LA STORIA DEL PENSIERO GIURIDICO M	A2
1138-9761	QUADERNS DEL CAC	B1
1885-4516	QUADERNS D'HISTÒRIA DE L'ENGINYERIA	B4
1696-8298	QUADERNS-E (INSTITUT CATALÀ D'ANTROPOLOGIA)	A3
0872-3915	QUADRANTE (LISBOA)	B1
2282-4219	QUADRANTI - RIVISTA INTERNAZIONALE DI FILOSOFIA CONTEMPOR	B1
2448-6485	QUADRIPARTITA RATIO	B1
1518-2886	QUAESTIO (UNISO)	A4
1807-8389	QUAESTIO IURIS (IMPRESSO)	B2
1607-3606	QUAESTIONES MATHEMATICAE (GRAHAMSTOWN. PRINT)	B2
2447-9616	QUÆSTIONIS DOCUMENTA	B4
1677-4280	QUALIT@S (UEPB)	B2
1049-7323	QUALITATIVE HEALTH RESEARCH	A1
1352-2752	QUALITATIVE MARKET RESEARCH	A2
1052-0147	QUALITATIVE REPORT	A3
1176-6093	QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN ACCOUNTING & MANAGEMENT	A2
1746-5648	QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN ORGANIZATIONS AND MANAGEMENT (F	A4
1478-0887	QUALITATIVE RESEARCH IN PSYCHOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
1443-9883	QUALITATIVE RESEARCH JOURNAL	A3
1575-5460	QUALITATIVE THEORY OF DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS	B2
0033-5177	QUALITY AND QUANTITY	A2
0748-8017	QUALITY AND RELIABILITY ENGINEERING INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	A3
1757-8361	QUALITY ASSURANCE AND SAFETY OF CROPS & FOODS	B2
0968-4883	QUALITY ASSURANCE IN EDUCATION	A2
0898-2112	QUALITY ENGINEERING	A3
0962-9343	QUALITY OF LIFE RESEARCH	A2
1759-7331	QUANTITATIVE ECONOMICS	A1
1469-7688	QUANTITATIVE FINANCE (PRINT)	A4
2223-4292	QUANTITATIVE IMAGING IN MEDICINE AND SURGERY	A4
1533-7146	QUANTUM INFORMATION & COMPUTATION	A3
1570-0755	QUANTUM INFORMATION PROCESSING (PRINT)	A3
0272-4987	QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF EXPERIMENTAL PSYCHOLOGY	A2
0033-5606	QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS	A3
0035-9009	QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF THE ROYAL METEOROLOGICAL SOCIETY	A2
0033-569X	QUARTERLY OF APPLIED MATHEMATICS	B1
1965-0795	QUATERNAIRE	A1
2176-6142	QUATERNARY AND ENVIRONMENTAL GEOSCIENCES	B3
1871-1014	QUATERNARY GEOCHRONOLOGY (PRINT)	A1
1040-6182	QUATERNARY INTERNATIONAL	A3
0033-5894	QUATERNARY RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2

0277-3791	QUATERNARY SCIENCE REVIEWS	A1
0872-1769	QUEIROSIANA	B3
0918-4732	QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS IN GENERAL TOPOLOGY	B4
0774-5524	QUESTIONS LITURGIQUES (IMPRESSO)	A4
2318-6372	QUESTÕES TRANSVERSAIS - REVISTA DE EPISTEMOLOGIAS DA COMI	A3
2250-4060	QUID 16	B4
0211-3325	QUIMERA (BARCELONA)	B1
0481-4118	QUÍMICA & DERIVADOS	B4
0100-4042	QUÍMICA NOVA (IMPRESSO)	A4
2175-2699	QUIMICA NOVA NA ESCOLA	B2
0102-8235	QUÍMICA TÊXTIL	B3
0033-6572	QUINTESENCE INTERNATIONAL	A4
1690-7582	QUÓRUM ACADÉMICO	B2
0033-6807	R & D MANAGEMENT (PRINT)	A1
1678-068X	R.E.V.I. REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DO VALE IGUAÇU	B3
2175-4705	R@U: REVISTA DE @NTROPOLOGIA DA UFSCAR	B3
1678-6483	RACE : REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO, CONTABILIDADE E ECONOMIA	A4
1867-1756	RACE AND SOCIAL PROBLEMS	A2
1361-3324	RACE, ETHNICITY AND EDUCATION	A1
2178-7638	RACEF ¿ REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO, CONTABILIDADE E ECONOMIA	A4
1808-8406	RACRE (CREUPI)	B4
0301-634X	RADIATION AND ENVIRONMENTAL BIOPHYSICS	A3
1350-4487	RADIATION MEASUREMENTS	A2
1748-717X	RADIATION ONCOLOGY (ONLINE)	A2
0969-806X	RADIATION PHYSICS AND CHEMISTRY (1993)	A2
0144-8420	RADIATION PROTECTION DOSIMETRY	B2
0033-7587	RADIATION RESEARCH	A2
0048-6604	RADIO SCIENCE	A3
0033-8222	RADIOCARBON	A1
1066-3622	RADIOCHEMISTRY (NEW YORK, N.Y.)	B3
1210-2512	RADIOENGINEERING	A4
0271-5333	RADIOGRAPHICS	A2
1078-8174	RADIOGRAPHY (LONDON. 1995)	B2
0033-8419	RADIOLOGY	A1
2515-0200	RADIOLOGY AND DIAGNOSTIC IMAGING	B3
1581-3207	RADIOLOGY AND ONCOLOGY	A4
0033-8451	RADIOPROTECTION (PARIS. 1966)	B3
2446-8967	RADIOTERAPIA MINEIRA	B4
0167-8140	RADIOTHERAPY AND ONCOLOGY	A1
2177-2738	RA'E GA: O ESPAÇO GEOGRÁFICO EM ANÁLISE	A3
0034-7590	RAE. REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DE EMPRESAS	A2
1852-8171	RAES REVISTA ARGENTINA DE EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR	B4
1983-5205	RAHIS. REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO HOSPITALAR E INOVAÇÃO EM	B1
1809-2039	RAI : REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO	A2
1984-4018	RAÍDO (ONLINE)	A2
0399-0559	RAIRO. RECHERCHE OPÉRATIONNELLE	B2
1981-3872	RAÍZES JURÍDICAS (UNIVERSIDADE POSITIVO. ONLINE)	B4
0102-552X	RAIZES. REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS E ECONÔMICAS	A4
1518-6776	RAM. REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO MACKENZIE	A2
1981-9951	RAMA : REVISTA EM AGRONEGÓCIO E MEIO AMBIENTE	A4

1042-9832	RANDOM STRUCTURES & ALGORITHMS (PRINT)	A2
1355-2546	RAPID PROTOTYPING JOURNAL	A1
1519-6453	RAPSÓDIA (USP)	B2
2358-3703	RASCUNHOS - CAMINHOS DA PESQUISA EM ARTES CÊNICAS	A4
2347-0151	RATIO IURIS	A4
2595-3257	RATIO JURIS	A2
0952-1917	RATIO JURIS (PRINT)	B2
1794-6638	RATIO JURIS ¿ UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA LATINOAMERICANA	A2
1806-1907	RAU. REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA UNIME	B4
1806-5961	RAU. REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO UNISAL	B4
2531-0488	RAUSP MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	A2
0080-2107	RAUSP-E - REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO - ELETRÔNICA	A2
1605-4806	RAZÓN Y PALABRA	A2
1808-6020	RBB. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE BIOÉTICA	B4
1980-6949	RBB. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE BIBLIOTECONOMIA E DOCUMENTAÇ	A4
1808-0936	RBC. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CARTOGRAFIA (ONLINE)	B2
2317-6695	RBCEH. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS DO ENVELHECIMENTO HL	A4
1676-8000	RBEE. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ECONOMIA DE EMPRESAS	B2
0034-7264	RBM. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B3
1806-8405	RBPG. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO	B1
1676-8965	RBSE. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SOCIOLOGIA DA EMOÇÃO (ONLINE)	B1
1984-6266	RC&C. REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE E CONTROLADORIA	B2
1981-8858	RCA. REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS AMBIENTAIS (UNILASALLE)	B1
0951-4198	RCM. RAPID COMMUNICATIONS IN MASS SPECTROMETRY	A4
2318-0897	RCM. REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS	B4
2447-7028	RCT: REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA	B4
1983-4659	REA REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA UFSM	A4
1679-9127	REA. REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO (FRANCA. ONLINE)	B1
2058-9883	REACTION CHEMISTRY & ENGINEERING	A1
1878-5190	REACTION KINETICS, MECHANISMS AND CATALYSIS	A3
1381-5148	REACTIVE & FUNCTIONAL POLYMERS (PRINT)	A2
1413-2311	READ. REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO	A2
2237-8812	REAGRO - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE AGRONEGÓCIO	B4
2179-7501	REALIS REVISTA DE ESTUDOS ANTIUTILITARISTAS E POSCOLONIAIS	B2
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2316-5812	REAT - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E TURISMO	B2
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0101-8434	REB. REVISTA ECLESIASTICA BRASILEIRA	A4
1983-8166	REBAP - REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO POLÍTICA	B4
2316-9230	REBECA - REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DE CINEMA E AUDIOVIS	B1
2595-3206	REBEH	B3
1981-4542	REBEJ (BRASÍLIA)	B1
2178-1206	REBENTO: REVISTA DAS ARTES DO ESPETÁCULO	B3
1983-8484	REBRAE. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTRATÉGIA (IMPRESSO)	B1
1677-7387	RECADM : REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIA ADMINISTRATIVA	A4
0958-3440	RECALL (HULL)	A1
2448-0126	RECAT - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA CIÊNCIAS DA ADMINISTRAÇÃO E TUR	B3
1677-3098	RECE : REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIAS DA EDUCAÇÃO	B4
1574-891X	RECENT PATENTS ON ANTI-INFECTIVE DRUG DISCOVERY (PRINT)	B1
1872-2083	RECENT PATENTS ON BIOTECHNOLOGY	B2

1872-2113	RECENT PATENTS ON DRUG DELIVERY & FORMULATION	A4
1872-2148	RECENT PATENTS ON ENDOCRINE, METABOLIC & IMMUNE DRUG D	A2
1874-4648	RECENT PATENTS ON MATERIALS SCIENCE (PRINT)	B2
1872-2105	RECENT PATENTS ON NANOTECHNOLOGY	A3
1130-6149	RECERCA REVISTA DE PENSAMENT I ANÀLISI	A1
1760-7760	RECHERCHES & ÉDUCTIONS	B4
0318-4137	RECHERCHES AMÉRINDIENNES AU QUÉBEC	A3
1954-3077	RECHERCHES EN ÉDUCATION	B4
1767-5448	RECHERCHES EN PSYCHANALYSE	B1
2175-2168	RECHTD. REVISTA DE ESTUDOS CONSTITUCIONAIS, HERMENÊUTICA	A1
1619-4993	RECHTSGESCHICHTE (FRANKFURT)	A4
0034-1398	RECHTSTHEORIE	A1
1853-4112	RECIAL	A4
1981-6286	RECIIS	A3
1981-6278	RECIIS-REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE COM. INFORMAÇÃO & INOVAÇÃO I	B3
2238-2127	RECONCAVO: REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA UNIABEU	B2
1982-8985	RECORDE: REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DO ESPORTE	B2
0956-5698	RECORDS MANAGEMENT JOURNAL (LONDON)	A2
1307-6167	RECORDS OF NATURAL PRODUCTS	A4
0067-1975	RECORDS OF THE AUSTRALIAN MUSEUM	A2
1807-8591	RECORTE (UNINCOR)	A3
2313-4321	RECYCLING	B3
2595-5667	REDAP - REVISTA DE DIREITO DA ADMINISTRAÇÃO PÚBLICA	B3
1984-1736	REDD - REVISTA ESPAÇO DE DIÁLOGO E DESCONEXÃO	B4
1982-5528	REDE - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO PRODEMA	B1
1982-6451	REDE DE CUIDADOS EM SAÚDE	B4
2318-8081	REDES - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DIREITO E SOCIEDADE	B1
1414-7106	REDES (SANTA CRUZ DO SUL. IMPRESSO)	A3
1679-4265	REDES (VITÓRIA)	B4
1982-6745	REDES REVISTA DO DESENVOLVIMENTO REGIONAL	A3
1579-0185	REDES, REVISTA HISPANA PARA EL ANÁLISIS DE REDES SOCIALES	B1
0328-3186	REDES. REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SOBRE LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA	A4
2255-5919	REDES.COM	A1
1696-2079	REDES.COM (SEVILLA)	A1
2035-8008	REDICONTI ONLINE DELLA SOCIETÀ GEOLOGICA ITALIANA	B4
2014-3621	REDIMAT- REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN DIDÁCTICA DE LAS MATE	B4
2594-4576	REDIN REVISTA EDUCACIONAL INTERDISCIPLINAR	B3
2316-1213	REDISCO - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ESTUDOS DO DISCURSO E DO C	B3
2213-2317	REDOX BIOLOGY	A1
1351-0002	REDOX REPORT (EDINBURGH)	A4
1743-2928	REDOX REPORT (ONLINE)	A4
1579-1513	REEC. REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE ENSEÑANZA DE LAS CIENCIAS	B3
2317-1367	REFACER - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FACULDADE DE CERES	B2
2359-182X	REFAS - REVISTA FATEC ZONA SUL	B2
0102-0269	REFLEXÃO	B1
2447-6803	REFLEXÃO (ONLINE)	B1
1982-9949	REFLEXÃO E AÇÃO (ONLINE)	A4
2447-9705	REFLEXÕES ECONÔMICAS	B4
1982-0828	REFLEXUS	A4
2358-4874	REFLEXUS: REVISTA SEMESTRAL DE TEOLOGIA E CIÊNCIAS DAS RELI	A4

1020-4067	REFUGEE SURVEY QUARTERLY	A3
2359-1919	REGA - REVISTA DE GESTÃO DE ÁGUA DA AMÉRICA LATINA	B2
2176-2171	REGAE: REVISTA DE GESTÃO E AVALIAÇÃO EDUCACIONAL	A4
1956-7413	REGARDS CROISÉS SUR L'ÉCONOMIE	A3
1809-2276	REGE. REVISTA DE GESTÃO USP	A3
1746-0751	REGENERATIVE MEDICINE (PRINT)	A3
2316-2058	REGEPE - REVISTA DE EMPREENDEDORISMO E GESTÃO DE PEQUEN.	A3
2409-5370	REGION	B2
1870-3925	REGION Y SOCIEDAD	A3
1436-378X	REGIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGE (ONLINE)	A2
1436-3798	REGIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGE (PRINT)	A2
1757-7802	REGIONAL SCIENCE POLICY AND PRACTICE	A4
0034-3404	REGIONAL STUDIES	A1
1360-0591	REGIONAL STUDIES (ONLINE)	A1
2352-4855	REGIONAL STUDIES IN MARINE SCIENCE	A3
2168-1376	REGIONAL STUDIES, REGIONAL SCIENCE	A2
2152-906X	REGIONS AND COHESIONS	B2
2250-8112	REGISTROS - REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN HISTÓRICA	A2
1668-1576	REGISTROS (MAR DEL PLATA)	B1
2526-1045	REGRASP	B4
1560-3547	REGULAR AND CHAOTIC DYNAMICS	B1
0273-2300	REGULATORY TOXICOLOGY AND PHARMACOLOGY	A2
0278-4807	REHABILITATION NURSING	A2
2090-2867	REHABILITATION RESEARCH AND PRACTICE	A3
1809-6220	REI. REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO DO IDEAU	A4
1549-1684	REJUVENATION RESEARCH	A3
1983-4624	REL. REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE LETRAS	B4
0185-0814	RELACIONES INTERNACIONALES	B2
1515-3371	RELACIONES INTERNACIONALES (LA PLATA)	B1
1699-3950	RELACIONES INTERNACIONALES (MADRID)	A2
1645-9199	RELAÇÕES INTERNACIONAIS (LISBOA)	A2
2316-2880	RELAÇÕES INTERNACIONAIS DO MUNDO ATUAL	B2
2525-7870	RELACULT - REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE ESTUDOS EM CULTUR.	B3
2255-0666	RELADEI - REVISTA LATINO AMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN INFANTIL	B4
2317-3688	RELEGENS THRÉSKEIA: ESTUDOS E PESQUISA EM RELIGIÃO	B1
0951-8320	RELIABILITY ENGINEERING & SYSTEMS SAFETY	A1
2477-9083	RELIGACIÓN: REVISTA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES Y HUMANIDADES	B2
1982-6605	RELIGARE: REVISTA DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM CIÊNC	A4
1984-0438	RELIGIÃO & SOCIEDADE	A1
1878-5417	RELIGION & GENDER	B2
1096-1151	RELIGION (LONDON. 1971)	A1
2150-9301	RELIGION AND SOCIETY	A3
2150-9298	RELIGION AND SOCIETY: ADVANCES IN RESEARCH	A3
0394-9397	RELIGIONI E SOCIETÀ (NAPOLI. TESTO STAMPATO)	B2
2077-1444	RELIGIONS	A1
2448-167X	REM - INTERNATIONAL ENGINEERING JOURNAL	B1
1807-0353	REM: REVISTA ESCOLA DE MINAS	B1
2177-5184	REMARK. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MARKETING	A2
2447-2689	REMAT: REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA MATEMÁTICA	B1
0103-183X	REMATE DE MALES	A3

2316-5758	REMATE DE MALES (ONLINE)	A3
1980-3141	REMATEC. REVISTA DE MATEMÁTICA, ENSINO E CULTURA (UFRN)	B4
1415-2762	REME. REVISTA MINEIRA DE ENFERMAGEM	B1
1980-8585	REMHU (BRASÍLIA)	A2
2072-4292	REMOTE SENSING	A1
2352-9385	REMOTE SENSING APPLICATIONS: SOCIETY AND ENVIRONMENT	A1
2056-3485	REMOTE SENSING IN ECOLOGY AND CONSERVATION	A2
2150-704X	REMOTE SENSING LETTERS	A3
0034-4257	REMOTE SENSING OF ENVIRONMENT	A1
0034-4338	RENAISSANCE QUARTERLY	A4
0886-022X	RENAL FAILURE	B1
2179-426X	RENCIMA	A3
0009-725X	RENDICONTI DEL CIRCOLO MATEMATICO DI PALERMO (TESTO STAN	B2
0041-8994	RENDICONTI DEL SEMINARIO MATEMATICO DELL'UNIVERSITÀ DI PA	B3
2037-4631	RENDICONTI LINCEI. SCIENZE FISICHE E NATURALI	B1
1364-0321	RENEWABLE & SUSTAINABLE ENERGY REVIEWS	A1
1742-1705	RENEWABLE AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SYSTEMS (PRINT)	A2
0960-1481	RENEWABLE ENERGY	A2
2172-038X	RENEWABLE ENERGY & POWER QUALITY JOURNAL (RE&PQJ)	B4
1755-0084	RENEWABLE ENERGY FOCUS	B4
1679-1916	RENTE. REVISTA NOVAS TECNOLOGIAS NA EDUCAÇÃO	A4
2281-3020	REPÈRES-DORIF	B1
2175-8131	REPERTÓRIO: TEATRO & DANÇA (ONLINE)	A4
1507-1367	REPORTS OF PRACTICAL ONCOLOGY AND RADIOTHERAPY	B1
0034-4877	REPORTS ON MATHEMATICAL PHYSICS	B2
2526-9542	REPPE REVISTA DE PRODUTOS EDUCACIONAIS E PESQUISAS EM ENS	A4
0034-4893	REPRESENTATION	A4
1413-2087	REPRODUÇÃO & CLIMATÉRIO	B3
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0936-6768	REPRODUCTION IN DOMESTIC ANIMALS (1990)	A2
1448-5990	REPRODUCTION, FERTILITY AND DEVELOPMENT (ONLINE)	A2
1642-431X	REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY	A2
1477-7827	REPRODUCTIVE BIOLOGY AND ENDOCRINOLOGY	A1
1472-6491	REPRODUCTIVE BIOMEDICINE ONLINE (ONLINE)	A2
1472-6483	REPRODUCTIVE BIOMEDICINE ONLINE (PRINT)	A2
1742-4755	REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH	A2
0968-8080	REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH MATTERS (PRINT)	A4
1933-7205	REPRODUCTIVE SCIENCES	A2
1933-7191	REPRODUCTIVE SCIENCES (THOUSAND OAKS, CALIF.)	A2
2161-038X	REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM AND SEXUAL DISORDERS	B1
0890-6238	REPRODUCTIVE TOXICOLOGY (ELMSFORD, N.Y.)	A4
0277-1322	RES	A4
2238-1589	RESBCAL - REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA EM ANIM	B4
2278-2249	RESEARCH & REVIEWS: JOURNAL OF FOOD SCIENCE & TECHNOLOG'	B3
1442-2018	RESEARCH & REVIEWS: JOURNAL OF NURSING AND HEALTH SCIENC	A1
0958-2029	RESEARCH EVALUATION (PRINT)	A1
1674-4527	RESEARCH IN ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS	B1
0891-4222	RESEARCH IN DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILITIES	A2
1356-9783	RESEARCH IN DRAMA EDUCATION (PRINT)	A1
0275-5319	RESEARCH IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS AND FINANCE	A2

1479-4802	RESEARCH IN MATHEMATICS EDUCATION	B1
0923-2508	RESEARCH IN MICROBIOLOGY (PARIS)	A4
0160-6891	RESEARCH IN NURSING & HEALTH (PRINT)	A1
0161-7230	RESEARCH IN POLITICAL ECONOMY	B3
1551-7411	RESEARCH IN SOCIAL & ADMINISTRATIVE PHARMACY	A3
0276-5624	RESEARCH IN SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND MOBILITY	A2
1543-8627	RESEARCH IN SPORTS MEDICINE (PRINT)	A2
0275-4959	RESEARCH IN THE SOCIOLOGY OF HEALTH CARE	B1
0733-558X	RESEARCH IN THE SOCIOLOGY OF ORGANIZATIONS	A3
2210-5395	RESEARCH IN TRANSPORTATION BUSINESS & MANAGEMENT	A1
0739-8859	RESEARCH IN TRANSPORTATION ECONOMICS	A3
0034-5288	RESEARCH IN VETERINARY SCIENCE	A1
2278-4721	RESEARCH INVENTY: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING A	B2
1819-3412	RESEARCH JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES	A3
0975-8585	RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL, BIOLOGICAL AND CHEM	A4
1819-3552	RESEARCH JOURNAL OF SEED SCIENCE	A4
1560-6074	RESEARCH JOURNAL OF TEXTILE AND APPAREL	B1
2446-4740	RESEARCH ON BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING	A4
0922-6168	RESEARCH ON CHEMICAL INTERMEDIATES (PRINT)	A4
2224-5766	RESEARCH ON HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES	A3
1049-7315	RESEARCH ON SOCIAL WORK PRACTICE	A3
0267-1522	RESEARCH PAPERS IN EDUCATION	A2
0270-1367	RESEARCH QUARTERLY FOR EXERCISE AND SPORT	A3
2525-3409	RESEARCH, SOCIETY AND DEVELOPMENT	A3
0751-7971	RÉSEAUX	B3
2525-3069	RESENHA BM&F	B4
0104-6152	RESENHA ELEITORAL - TRIBUNAL REGIONAL ELEITORAL DE SANTA C.	B4
2178-3284	RESGATE: REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE CULTURA	A3
0717-3474	RESONANCIAS (SANTIAGO)	A4
1076-3333	RESOURCE (SAINT JOSEPH, MICH.)	B4
2079-9276	RESOURCES	A2
0301-4207	RESOURCES POLICY	A1
0921-3449	RESOURCES, CONSERVATION AND RECYCLING	A1
0025-7931	RESPIRATION (BASEL)	A3
0020-1324	RESPIRATORY CARE	A3
0954-6111	RESPIRATORY MEDICINE	A2
2213-0071	RESPIRATORY MEDICINE CASE REPORTS	B2
1569-9048	RESPIRATORY PHYSIOLOGY & NEUROBIOLOGY	A4
1465-9921	RESPIRATORY RESEARCH	A1
1323-7799	RESPIROLOGY (CARLTON SOUTH. PRINT)	A2
1061-2971	RESTORATION ECOLOGY	A2
2234-7666	RESTORATIVE DENTISTRY & ENDODONTICS	A3
0922-6028	RESTORATIVE NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSCIENCE	B1
1422-6383	RESULTS IN MATHEMATICS / RESULTATE DER MATHEMATIK	A4
2211-3797	RESULTS IN PHYSICS	A3
0300-9572	RESUSCITATION (LONDON, PRINT)	A1
1806-0323	RETEC. REVISTA DE TECNOLOGIAS (OURINHOS)	B4
0893-5696	RETHINKING MARXISM	A3
0275-004X	RETINA (PHILADELPHIA, PA.)	A1
1935-1089	RETINAL CASES & BRIEF REPORTS	B1

1853-6034	RÉTOR - REVISTA DE LA ASOCIACIÓN ARGENTINA DE RETÓRICA (AAI	A4
1988-2041	RETOS	A4
2524-1125	RETOS XXI	B4
2524-1133	RETOS XXI	B4
2238-4391	RETRATOS DA ESCOLA	A3
1516-8182	RETRATOS DE ASSENTAMENTOS	A4
1742-4690	RETROVIROLOGY (LONDON)	A2
1518-3025	REUNA - REVISTA DE ECONOMIA, ADMINISTRAÇÃO E TURISMO	A4
2237-3667	REUNIR: REVISTA DE ADMINISTRACAO, CIENCIAS CONTABEIS E SUS1	A4
1517-3852	REV RENE (IMPRESSO)	B4
2175-1609	REV. TRIANGULO	B3
2177-8183	REVASF - REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO DA UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO V.	B2
2179-4456	REVELL ? REVISTA DE ESTUDOS LITERÁRIOS DA UEMS	A3
1984-6576	REVELLI: REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO, LINGUAGEM E LITERATURA DA UE	B1
1981-1322	REVMAT : REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	B1
1677-1222	REVER: REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DA RELIGIÃO	A2
0102-7395	REVERSO (BELO HORIZONTE. IMPRESSO)	B3
2595-4490	REVES - REVISTA RELAÇÕES SOCIAIS	B4
2409-1189	REVICSO - REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B4
0305-6244	REVIEW OF AFRICAN POLITICAL ECONOMY	A2
1940-5979	REVIEW OF BEHAVIORAL FINANCE	A3
1467-9361	REVIEW OF DEVELOPMENT ECONOMICS	A2
1363-6669	REVIEW OF DEVELOPMENT ECONOMICS (PRINT)	A2
1879-9337	REVIEW OF DEVELOPMENT FINANCE	A2
1094-2025	REVIEW OF ECONOMIC DYNAMICS (PRINT)	A2
0034-6527	REVIEW OF ECONOMIC STUDIES	A1
1923-8401	REVIEW OF ECONOMICS & FINANCE	B1
1923-7529	REVIEW OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE	B1
1530-9142	REVIEW OF ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS (ONLINE: CATCHWORD LT	A1
0034-6543	REVIEW OF EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH	A1
2333-5718	REVIEW OF HISTORY AND POLITICAL SCIENCE	A4
0889-938X	REVIEW OF INDUSTRIAL ORGANIZATION	A2
2059-6014	REVIEW OF INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS AND STRATEGY	A3
0969-2290	REVIEW OF INTERNATIONAL POLITICAL ECONOMY (PRINT)	A1
2049-5323	REVIEW OF KEYNESIAN ECONOMICS	A3
1555-5879	REVIEW OF LAW & ECONOMICS	A2
0034-6667	REVIEW OF PALAEOBOTANY AND PALYNOLOGY	A2
1878-5166	REVIEW OF PHILOSOPHY AND PSYCHOLOGY	A2
0953-8259	REVIEW OF POLITICAL ECONOMY	A3
2249-894X	REVIEW OF RESEARCH	B3
0034-6748	REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC INSTRUMENTS	A2
2547-9385	REVIEW OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES	B4
1753-5131	REVIEWS IN AQUACULTURE	A1
0167-8299	REVIEWS IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	A1
1569-1705	REVIEWS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND BIO-TECHNOLOGY	A1
0960-3166	REVIEWS IN FISH BIOLOGY AND FISHERIES	A1
2330-8257	REVIEWS IN FISHERIES SCIENCE & AQUACULTURE	A1
0954-139X	REVIEWS IN MEDICAL MICRO-BIOLOGY	B3
1052-9276	REVIEWS IN MEDICAL VIROLOGY (PRINT)	A1
0334-1763	REVIEWS IN THE NEUROSCIENCES	A2

2191-0200	REVIEWS IN THE NEUROSCIENCES	A2
8755-1209	REVIEWS OF GEOPHYSICS (1985)	A1
0034-6861	REVIEWS OF MODERN PHYSICS	A1
0303-4240	REVIEWS OF PHYSIOLOGY, BIOCHEMISTRY AND PHARMACOLOGY	A2
1605-8127	REVIEWS ON ADVANCED MATERIALS SCIENCE (ONLINE)	A4
1606-5131	REVIEWS ON ADVANCED MATERIALS SCIENCE (PRINT)	A4
2359-4861	REVISE - REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE EDUCAÇÃO	B4
2525-5843	REVISTA - CIÊNCIA É MINHA PRAIA	B4
1541-1443	REVISTA - HARVARD REVIEW OF LATIN AMERICA	A4
2236-0824	REVISTA - O OLHO DA HISTÓRIA	B3
2177-3726	REVISTA "VIANNA SAPIENS"	B3
2317-3475	REVISTA (CON)TEXTOS LINGUÍSTICOS	A2
1982-8632	REVISTA @MBIENTEEDUCAÇÃO	B4
2357-7428	REVISTA ABRACICON SABER	B4
2525-4022	REVISTA ABUSÕES	A4
2448-2307	REVISTA ACADÊMICA	B4
1981-4178	REVISTA ACADÊMICA : CIÊNCIAS AGRÁRIAS E AMBIENTAIS (PUCPR. I	B4
2358-9140	REVISTA ACADÊMICA DA FACULDADE FERNÃO DIAS	B2
2594-4878	REVISTA ACADÊMICA INTEGRA/AÇÃO	B4
2444-7439	REVISTA ACADÊMICA LILETRAD	B3
1980-6965	REVISTA ACADÊMICA OBSERVATÓRIO DE INOVAÇÃO DO TURISMO	B1
2237-2733	REVISTA ACADÊMICA SÃO MARCOS	B4
0103-989X	REVISTA ACADÊMICA. CIÊNCIAS AGRÁRIAS E AMBIENTAIS	B4
1414-0594	REVISTA ACB: BIBLIOTECONOMIA EM SANTA CATARINA	A4
2237-5643	REVISTA ACREDITAÇÃO	B4
2178-7727	REVISTA ACTA SCIENTIAE	A1
2236-1774	REVISTA ACTA TECNOLÓGICA	B3
2178-0080	REVISTA ADMINISTRAÇÃO EM DIÁLOGO - RAD	A4
2524-9568	REVISTA ADMINISTRACIÓN PÚBLICA Y SOCIEDAD	B4
1989-6972	REVISTA ADMIRA DA FACULDADE DE COMUNICAÇÃO DA UNIVERSII	B3
1983-2354	REVISTA ÁFRICA E AFRICANIDADES	B1
2318-1990	REVISTA ÁFRICA(S)	B1
1984-185X	REVISTA ÁGORA	B4
1807-698X	REVISTA ÁGORA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B3
1980-0096	REVISTA ÁGORA (VITÓRIA)	A4
2318-0188	REVISTA AGROECOSSISTEMAS	A4
1984-428X	REVISTA AGROGEOAMBIENTAL	B4
2316-1817	REVISTA AGROGEOAMBIENTAL	B4
2595-1084	REVISTA AGULHAS NEGRAS	B3
0718-378X	REVISTA AIDIS DE INGENIERÍA Y CIENCIAS AMBIENTALES	B1
1981-0253	REVISTA ALAMEDAS (UNIOESTE. TOLEDO)	B4
1984-0055	REVISTA ALERE	B1
2176-1507	REVISTA ALTERJOR USP	B1
1983-6929	REVISTA AMAZONENSE DE GERIATRIA E GERONTOLOGIA	B4
2594-7494	REVISTA AMAZÔNIA MODERNA	B3
2238-8893	REVISTA AMAZÔNIA, ORGANIZAÇÕES E SUSTENTABILIDADE	B1
1983-3415	REVISTA AMAZÔNICA	B3
2527-0141	REVISTA AMAZÔNIDA	B2
1980-993X	REVISTA AMBIENTE & ÁGUA	A3
2176-9036	REVISTA AMBIENTE CONTÁBIL	B2

2317-0727	REVISTA AMPLA DE GESTÃO EMPRESARIAL	B2
0102-2105	REVISTA AMRIGS	A4
1982-1689	REVISTA ANAGRAMA (USP)	A3
2317-9708	REVISTA ANALISANDO EM CIÊNCIA DA INFORMAÇÃO	B4
2177-1294	REVISTA ANÁPOLIS DIGITAL	B3
2174-6796	REVISTA ANDALUZA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA	A2
1888-7546	REVISTA ANDALUZA DE MEDICINA DEL DEPORTE	B2
2221-4135	REVISTA ANDINA DE ESTUDIOS POLÍTICOS	A3
2179-5487	REVISTA ANGELUS NOVUS	B3
1516-7372	REVISTA ANTHROPOLÓGICAS	A4
2525-5223	REVISTA ANTHROPOLÓGICAS	A4
2447-1267	REVISTA APOTHEKE	B2
2357-7843	REVISTA APRENDIZAGEM EM EAD	B4
2447-3618	REVISTA APROXIMANDO	B4
2525-8354	REVISTA ARA	B2
1695-2588	REVISTA ARANZADI DE DERECHO AMBIENTAL	B2
2179-6793	REVISTA ARATICUM	B3
1853-6387	REVISTA ARGENTINA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA BIOLÓGICA	A3
0329-5257	REVISTA ARGENTINA DE BIOINGENIERÍA	B4
2591-376X	REVISTA ARGENTINA DE BIOINGENIERÍA	B4
1852-4206	REVISTA ARGENTINA DE CIENCIAS DEL COMPORTAMIENTO	A1
0325-7541	REVISTA ARGENTINA DE MICROBIOLOGÍA	B2
2443-4442	REVISTA ARJÉ	B1
2525-3832	REVISTA ARQUITETAS INVISÍVEIS	B4
2595-4407	REVISTA ARQUIVOS CIENTÍFICOS	B4
2358-6060	REVISTA ARTE DA CENA	B1
2316-5251	REVISTA ÁRTEMIS	A2
2525-4944	REVISTA ARTICULANDO E CONSTRUINDO SABERES	B1
1806-9088	REVISTA ÁRVORE (ONLINE)	B2
2238-3999	REVISTA ASPAS	B1
2177-4242	REVISTA ATELIÊ	B4
2358-4440	REVISTA ATELIÊ DE HISTÓRIA	B4
2237-9304	REVISTA ATHENA	B3
1981-1896	REVISTA AUGUSTUS (UNISUAM. ONLINE)	B2
0102-5430	REVISTA BAIANA DE ENFERMAGEM	B2
1222-412X	REVISTA BAIANA DE SAÚDE PÚBLICA	B3
2318-2660	REVISTA BAIANA DE SAÚDE PÚBLICA (ONLINE)	B3
2469-1135	REVISTA BARDA	B3
2591-5802	REVISTA BBM - REVISTA DA BIBLIOTECA GUITA E JOSÉ MINDLIN	B4
2316-1205	REVISTA BINACIONAL BRASIL ARGENTINA	B4
2007-3380	REVISTA BIO CIENCIAS	B4
1983-8034	REVISTA BIOÉTICA (ONLINE)	A2
2179-4308	REVISTA BORGES	B3
1853-5704	REVISTA BORROMEO.	B4
0103-7072	REVISTA BRASILEIRA	B4
2447-1801	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DA EDUCAÇÃO PROFISSIONAL E TECNOLÓGICA	B3
2179-684X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA	B2
2525-5495	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO POLÍTICA	B4
1516-7429	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO PÚBLICA E DE EMPRESAS	B1
1982-7679	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE AGRICULTURA IRRIGADA	B4

2178-5317	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE AGRICULTURA SUSTENTÁVEL	B4
0104-8996	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE AGROCIENCIA (UFPEL)	B3
0104-1347	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE AGROMETEOROLOGIA	B4
2236-9724	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE AGROPECUÁRIA SUSTENTÁVEL	B4
2317-3114	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE AGROTECNOLOGIA	B4
2446-8584	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ALFABETIZAÇÃO	B2
1807-8338	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ANÁLISE DO COMPORTAMENTO	B4
0034-7094	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ANESTESIOLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	B1
1806-907X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ANESTESIOLOGIA (ONLINE)	B1
0101-7659	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE APLICAÇÕES DE VÁCUO (IMPRESSO)	B4
1983-4047	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE APLICAÇÕES DE VÁCUO (ONLINE)	B4
1806-1362	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE APRENDIZAGEM ABERTA E A DISTÂNCIA	A3
1806-809X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ARBITRAGEM	B1
2448-0460	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ASSUNTOS REGIONAIS E URBANOS (BARU)	B1
1413-3482	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ATIVIDADE FÍSICA E SAÚDE	B3
0100-0691	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE BIBLIOTECONOMIA E DOCUMENTAÇÃO (IM	A4
1679-2343	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE BIOCÊNCIAS (IMPRESSO)	B4
2176-9745	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CANCEROLOGIA	B2
0560-4613	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CARTOGRAFIA (IMPRESSO)	B2
2179-135X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CASOS DE ENSINO EM ADMINSTRAÇÃO (GV	B3
1516-635X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA AVÍCOLA / BRAZILIAN JOURNAL OF	B1
1806-9657	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA DO SOLO (ONLINE)	A3
0103-1716	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA E MOVIMENTO	B3
2178-4884	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA POLÍTICA	A1
1984-7130	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA VETERINÁRIA	B4
1413-0130	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA VETERINÁRIA (IMPRESSO)	B4
2359-4748	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIA, TECNOLOGIA E INOVAÇÃO	B4
1981-1160	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS AGRÁRIAS	B1
1808-4524	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS AMBIENTAIS	A3
2176-9478	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS AMBIENTAIS (IMPRESSA)	A3
1415-5400	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS CRIMINAIS	A1
2178-0137	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS DA SAÚDE	B3
1415-2177	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS DA SAÚDE (JOÃO PESSOA)	B2
0101-3289	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS DO ESPORTE	B2
0102-9010	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS MORFOLÓGICAS	B3
2178-0013	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIENCIAS POLICIAIS	B1
0102-6909	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS (IMPRESSO)	A1
1415-8426	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CINEANTROPOMETRIA & DESEMPENHO HU	B2
0102-7638	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CIRURGIA CARDIOVASCULAR (IMPRESSO)	B2
1980-055X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CLIMATOLOGIA	A3
2237-8642	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CLIMATOLOGIA	A3
2176-6649	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE COMPUTAÇÃO APLICADA	B3
2237-9223	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CRIMINALISTICA	B3
2317-5443	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DESENVOLVIMENTO REGIONAL	A4
1807-1228	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO (PASSO FUNDO)	A1
1809-9092	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO ANIMAL	A1
2358-6974	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO CIVIL	B1
2594-4932	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO CIVIL (IMPRESSO)	B1
1982-2219	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO DAS FAMÍLIAS E SUCESSÕES	B4
2179-9148	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO PREVIDENCIÁRIO	B1

0100-2589	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO PROCESSUAL (IMPRESSO)	A4
2525-510X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO PROCESSUAL PENAL	B1
1678-7072	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO PÚBLICO	B1
1981-2221	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO E FINANÇAS PÚBLICAS	B4
2238-8249	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITOS HUMANOS	B3
0034-7140	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ECONOMIA (IMPRESSO)	A3
2595-4067	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ECONOMIA CRIATIVA E DA CULTURA	B4
1983-9391	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ECOTURISMO	B3
1809-449X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO	A1
1980-0118	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO AMBIENTAL (IMPRESSO)	A3
1981-1764	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO AMBIENTAL (ONLINE)	A3
2317-6571	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO DE JOVENS E ADULTOS	B1
2525-4863	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO DO CAMPO	A4
2237-3098	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO E CULTURA	B4
2358-2391	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO E SAÚDE	B3
2358-3193	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIA DA INFORMAÇÃO	B2
2594-9179	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS E EDUCAÇÃO MA	B3
2236-3904	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO EM GEOGRAFIA	A2
1413-6538	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO ESPECIAL	A1
1807-5509	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA E ESPORTE	B3
0100-5502	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO MÉDICA (IMPRESSO)	B2
1983-0408	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO PROFISSIONAL E TECNOLÓGICA	B3
0104-303X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENERGIA	B2
0034-7167	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENFERMAGEM (IMPRESSO)	A2
1807-1929	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENGENHARIA AGRÍCOLA E AMBIENTAL (ON	B2
0102-9843	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENGENHARIA QUÍMICA	B3
1982-873X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA	B4
2595-7376	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO DE CIÊNCIAS E MATEMÁTICA	A3
1806-1117	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO DE FÍSICA (IMPRESSO)	A1
1806-9126	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO DE FÍSICA (ONLINE)	A1
2595-816X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO MÉDIO	B4
2447-3944	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENSINO SUPERIOR	B2
0085-5626	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENTOMOLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	B1
1980-5497	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EPIDEMIOLOGIA	B2
2448-3923	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS AFRICANOS	B1
1981-6162	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS CONSTITUCIONAIS	B3
2237-2660	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DA PRESENÇA [EPERIODICO]	A1
2358-3916	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DE DEFESA	A2
0102-3098	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DE POPULAÇÃO (IMPRESSO)	A1
2175-053X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DE SEGURANÇA PÚBLICA	B3
2316-2767	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DO CONTATO LINGUÍSTICO (ONLI	A1
2358-1239	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS DO LAZER	B2
1984-5642	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS ESTRATÉGICOS	B2
1809-7278	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS JURÍDICOS	A1
2447-4851	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS ORGANIZACIONAIS	B2
1944-1951	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS PEDAGÓGICOS	A1
2176-6681	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS PEDAGÓGICOS RBEP-INEP	A1
0034-7191	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS POLÍTICOS	A1
2359-5736	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS POLÍTICOS	A1
1981-3953	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS REGIONAIS E URBANOS	A4

2317-1529	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS URBANOS E REGIONAIS	A1
1517-4115	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ESTUDOS URBANOS E REGIONAIS (ANPUR)	A1
2318-7492	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EXPRESSÃO GRÁFICA	B1
1806-2695	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE EXTENSÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA	B2
1981-528X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FARMACOGNOSIA	A4
2358-8284	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FILOSOFIA DA RELIGIÃO	B2
1679-0731	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FINANÇAS (IMPRESSO)	A3
2176-8978	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FÍSICA MÉDICA (IMPRESSO)	B4
1984-9001	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FÍSICA MÉDICA (ONLINE)	B4
1677-8510	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FISILOGIA DO EXERCÍCIO	A3
0100-2945	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FRUTICULTURA (IMPRESSO)	B1
1984-4956	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE FUTSAL E FUTEBOL	B4
0102-261X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GEOFÍSICA (IMPRESSO)	B3
0034-723X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GEOGRAFIA	B3
1984-2295	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GEOGRAFIA FÍSICA	A3
2317-4285	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GEOMÁTICA	B4
2236-5664	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GEOMORFOLOGIA	A1
1981-2256	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GERIATRIA E GERONTOLOGIA	A4
1809-9823	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GERIATRIA E GERONTOLOGIA (UNATI. IMPR	A4
2359-1412	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO AMBIENTAL E SUSTENTABILIDADE	B1
1806-4892	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO DE NEGÓCIOS (SÃO PAULO. IMPRE	A3
1809-239X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO REGIONAL	A1
2237-1664	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO E ENGENHARIA	B4
2319-0639	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO E INOVAÇÃO	B1
0100-7203	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GINECOLOGIA E OBSTETRÍCIA (IMPRESSO)	B2
2236-1065	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HERBICIDAS	B4
1981-2965	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HIGIENE E SANIDADE ANIMAL	B4
2175-3423	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA & CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	A3
0102-0188	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA (IMPRESSO)	A1
2176-3275	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA DA CIÊNCIA	B1
1983-4713	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA DA CIÊNCIA	B1
2238-0094	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA DA EDUCAÇÃO	A1
1519-955X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA DA MATEMÁTICA	B4
2238-3913	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA DA MÍDIA	A3
1983-2850	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA DAS RELIGIÕES	A2
2176-6452	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE HISTÓRIA MILITAR	B3
1414-5685	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE INFORMÁTICA NA EDUCAÇÃO	B3
1677-2504	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE INOVAÇÃO	A4
1809-2632	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE INTELIGÊNCIA	B4
2176-834X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE LINGUÍSTICA ANTROPOLÓGICA	A1
1984-6398	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE LINGUISTICA APLICADA	A1
0103-6963	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE LITERATURA COMPARADA	A1
0104-8058	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MASTOLOGIA	B3
2179-7994	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA DE FAMILIA E COMUNIDADE	B2
1517-8692	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA DO ESPORTE (IMPRESSO)	B2
1679-4435	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA DO TRABALHO	B4
0100-2430	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA VETERINÁRIA	B3
1809-2063	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA VETERINÁRIA DE EQUINOS	B4
2595-4431	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MEIO AMBIENTE	B3
1982-4351	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE METEOROLOGIA	B2

0102-7786	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE METEOROLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	B2
1980-6477	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MILHO E SORGO (ONLINE)	B4
0103-7595	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE MUSICA (RIO DE JANEIRO. 1934)	B1
2358-5153	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE NEGÓCIOS E DESENVOLVIMENTO REGIONA	B4
1414-0365	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE NEUROLOGIA E PSIQUIATRIA	B4
0103-7196	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE NUTRIÇÃO CLÍNICA	B4
1981-9927	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE NUTRIÇÃO ESPORTIVA	B3
1981-9919	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE OBESIDADE, NUTRIÇÃO E EMAGRECIMENTC	B2
0034-7272	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ODONTOLOGIA	B3
1984-3747	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ODONTOLOGIA (ONLINE)	B3
2359-3466	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ODONTOLOGIA LEGAL	B4
0034-7280	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE OFTALMOLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	B3
1679-3390	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ORIENTAÇÃO PROFISSIONAL	A2
1984-7270	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ORIENTAÇÃO PROFISSIONAL	A2
2178-7875	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ORNITOLOGIA/ONLINE	B2
0102-3616	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ORTOPEDIA (IMPRESSO)	B2
1519-7530	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PALEONTOLOGIA	B2
0103-846X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PARASITOLOGIA VETERINÁRIA (IMPRESSO)	A2
2525-426X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISA (AUTO)BIOGRÁFICA	A4
1806-5104	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISA EM EDUCAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS	A2
1984-2686	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISA EM EDUCAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS	A2
2175-3946	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISA EM SAÚDE	B3
1982-6125	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISA EM TURISMO	A4
2317-2363	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PLANEJAMENTO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	A3
2237-3985	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PLANEJAMENTO E ORÇAMENTO	B3
1983-084X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PLANTAS MEDICINAIS	B1
1678-166X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE POLÍTICA E ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA EDUCAÇÃO	A2
1983-3121	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE POLÍTICA INTERNACIONAL (ONLINE)	A1
2236-1677	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE POLITICAS PUBLICAS	A1
2525-5584	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS E INTERNACIONAIS	B2
1981-9900	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PRESCRIÇÃO E FISILOGIA DO EXERCÍCIO	B3
2317-0158	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PREVIDÊNCIA	B4
0486-641X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSICANÁLISE (IMPRESSO)	B1
0104-5393	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSICODRAMA	A4
2319-0361	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSICOLOGIA	B4
1981-9145	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSICOLOGIA DO ESPORTE	A4
1516-8530	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSICOTERAPIA	B2
2318-0404	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSICOTERAPIA	B2
1809-452X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PSIQUIATRIA	B1
2175-0858	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE QUALIDADE DE VIDA	B3
1982-1883	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE QUEIMADURAS	B2
1414-381X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE RECURSOS HÍDIRCOS	A3
1809-3000	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE REPRODUÇÃO ANIMAL	B4
0102-0803	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE REPRODUÇÃO ANIMAL (IMPRESSO)	B4
0482-5004	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE REUMATOLOGIA (IMPRESSO)	B2
1808-0723	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE RISCO E SEGURO (ONLINE)	B4
1519-9940	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SAÚDE E PRODUÇÃO ANIMAL	B2
2358-8691	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SAÚDE FUNCIONAL e REBRASF	B4
1519-3829	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SAÚDE MATERNO INFANTIL (IMPRESSO)	B2
2317-6369	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SAÚDE OCUPACIONAL	B2

1981-1659	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SEGURANÇA PÚBLICA	B4
0103-6122	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SEXUALIDADE HUMANA	B4
2236-0530	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SEXUALIDADE HUMANA	B4
0103-2402	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SOCIOLOGIA	A4
2359-5582	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SOCIOLOGIA DO DIREITO	B1
2318-0544	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE SOCIOLOGIA SBS (ONLINE)	A4
1981-3686	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TECNOLOGIA AGROINDUSTRIAL	B4
2358-2200	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TECNOLOGIAS SOCIAIS	B3
1517-5545	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TERAPIA COMPORTAMENTAL E COGNITIVA	A4
1983-5590	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TERAPIA FAMILIAR	B3
0103-507X	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TERAPIA INTENSIVA (IMPRESSO)	A4
1808-5687	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TERAPIAS COGNITIVAS (IMPRESSO)	B1
2176-2139	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE VITICULTURA E ENOLOGIA	B4
1806-9290	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ZOOTECNIA	A3
1984-6169	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DO CARIBE	B2
1518-6784	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DO CARIBE (IMPRESSO)	B2
0104-8317	REVISTA BRASILEIRA E LATINO - AMERICANA DE MARCAPASSO E AR	B4
1806-1222	REVISTA BRASILEIRA EM PROMOÇÃO DA SAÚDE (PRINT)	B2
1415-3580	REVISTA BRASILEIRA MULTIDISCIPLINAR - REBRAM (UNIARA)	B2
2527-2675	REVISTA BRASILEIRA MULTIDISCIPLINAR. REBRAM (ONLINE)	B3
2317-0344	REVISTA BRASILIENSE DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	B4
1983-2125	REVISTA CAATINGA (ONLINE)	B1
2525-2879	REVISTA CADERNOS DA EDUCAÇÃO BÁSICA	B3
2447-7141	REVISTA CADERNOS DE PESQUISA DA ESCOLA DA CIDADE	B4
0718-4565	REVISTA CALIDAD EN LA EDUCACIÓN	A2
2526-9704	REVISTA CALUNDU	B4
1518-7019	REVISTA CAMINHANDO	B1
1679-1991	REVISTA CAPITAL CIENTÍFICO (UNICENTRO)	A4
2359-0882	REVISTA CARAVANA	B4
2254-7630	REVISTA CARIBEÑA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B2
2525-3522	REVISTA CARIOCA DE CIÊNCIA, TECNOLOGIA E EDUCAÇÃO	B3
2014-038X	REVISTA CATALANA DE DRET AMBIENTAL	A2
1808-3781	REVISTA CATARINENSE DA CIÊNCIA CONTÁBIL	A4
2527-1180	REVISTA CATARINENSE DE ECONOMIA	B4
2007-2198	REVISTA CATHEDRA	A2
2526-4478	REVISTA CBTECLE	B3
1516-1846	REVISTA CEFAC (IMPRESSO)	B3
1414-008X	REVISTA CEJ (BRASÍLIA)	A4
2318-8561	REVISTA CENÁRIO	B3
2177-3491	REVISTA CERES (ONLINE)	B1
2175-7275	REVISTA CEREUS	B3
2448-2692	REVISTA CERRADOS	A2
1678-8346	REVISTA CERRADOS (UNIMONTES)	A2
1516-2664	REVISTA CESUMAR	B2
2525-5576	REVISTA CEUMA PERSPECTIVAS (ONLINE)	B3
1517-6959	REVISTA CFMV (BRASÍLIA)	B4
1027-152X	REVISTA CHAPINGO. SERIE: HORTICULTURA	B2
0719-7551	REVISTA CHILENA DE DERECHO DEL TRABAJO Y DE LA SEGURIDAD S	A2
0034-740X	REVISTA CHILENA DE ENTOMOLOGIA	B4
0719-2215	REVISTA CHILENA DE ESTUDIOS MEDIEVALES	A2

0716-078X	REVISTA CHILENA DE HISTORIA NATURAL (IMPRESA)	A3
0716-1018	REVISTA CHILENA DE INFECTOLOGÍA (IMPRESA)	B2
0718-2295	REVISTA CHILENA DE LITERATURA	B1
0717-7518	REVISTA CHILENA DE NUTRICION	B3
0719-8256	REVISTA CHILENA DE RELACIONES INTERNACIONALES	B3
0717-5346	REVISTA CHILENA DE TERAPIA OCUPACIONAL	B3
0717-6767	REVISTA CHILENA DE TERAPIA OCUPACIONAL	B3
1981-7983	REVISTA CIDADE NOVA	A4
1133-6595	REVISTA CIDOB D'AFERS INTERNACIONALS (1985)	B1
1984-4271	REVISTA CIÊNCIA & DESENVOLVIMENTO	B2
1806-6690	REVISTA CIÊNCIA AGRÔNOMICA (UFC. ONLINE)	A4
2318-0129	REVISTA CIÊNCIA E MAÇONARIA	B2
2179-460X	REVISTA CIÊNCIA E NATURA	A3
1980-0622	REVISTA CIÊNCIA E SAÚDE	B4
1679-4605	REVISTA CIÊNCIA EM EXTENSÃO	B2
2446-7286	REVISTA CIÊNCIA PLURAL	B4
2175-7038	REVISTA CIENCIA, SALUD, EDUCACIÓN Y ECONOMIA	B4
2176-1477	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS & IDÉIAS	B1
2318-0722	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS ADMINISTRATIVAS	A4
2594-3987	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS DA SOCIEDADE	B3
0719-5753	REVISTA CIENCIAS DE LA DOCUMENTACIÓN	B4
2183-7384	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS E POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	B4
2236-3785	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS EM SAÚDE	B1
1794-8347	REVISTA CIENCIAS ESTRATEGICAS	B1
2179-1120	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS	B2
1677-5090	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS E BIOLÓGICAS	A4
1677-1591	REVISTA CIENTEFICO	B4
1677-5716	REVISTA CIENTEFICO	B4
2359-3865	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA & TECNOLÓGICA	B4
1982-0801	Revista Científica CET-FAESA (impresso)	B4
2525-829X	Revista Científica CET-FAESA (online)	B4
2177-5923	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA AJES- RCA	B4
2237-3675	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA FACULDADE DE BALSAS	B4
2179-4200	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA FACULDADE DE EDUCAÇÃO E MEIO AMBIEN	B4
1980-7813	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA FACULDADE DE MEDICINA DE CAMPOS	B4
1518-8051	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA FAI (IMPRESSO)	B3
1807-6912	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA FAMINAS	B4
2172-7929	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DE EDUCACIÓN E COMUNICACIÓN HACHETETE	B4
1415-563X	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DE PRODUÇÃO ANIMAL	B4
1516-4071	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DO CENTRO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE BARRA MANSA	B4
2519-7207	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DO ISCTAC	B3
1983-6708	REVISTA CIENTIFICA DO ITPAC	B1
1677-0293	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA ELETRÔNICA DE AGRONOMIA	B4
1806-0625	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA ELETRÔNICA DE PSICOLOGIA	A4
2238-1899	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA E-LOCUÇÃO	B2
2500-7645	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA GENERAL JOSÉ MARÍA CÓRDOVA	B3
2256-3202	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA GUILLERMO DE OCKHAM (ONLINE)	A2
2175-0556	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA HERMES	B1
2525-9075	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA INTELLETTO	B4
2526-5741	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA INTERDISCIPLINAR INTERLOGOS	B4

2448-0959	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA MULTIDISCIPLINAR NÚCLEO DO CONHECIMENT	B3
2238-5819	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA ON-LINE TECNOLOGIA GESTÃO HUMANISMO	B3
2594-7672	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA SCHOLA	B4
2525-5150	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA UMC	B3
2318-244X	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA UNILAGO	B4
1679-4915	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA/FAP (CURITIBA. IMPRESSO)	B3
1806-6283	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS APLICADAS	B4
2359-0327	REVISTA CIF BRASIL	B4
2422-2208	REVISTA CINTEX	B4
1982-0097	REVISTA CIRANDA (UNIMONTES)	A3
0719-2177	REVISTA CIS	A4
1900-1355	REVISTA CLEPSIDRA	B1
1676-6849	REVISTA CLÍNICA DE ORTODONTIA DENTAL PRESS	B4
2448-2269	REVISTA CLÓVIS MOURA DE HUMANIDADES	B2
2237-0315	REVISTA COCAR (ONLINE)	A4
2179-1287	REVISTA COLETIVA FUNDAJ	B4
2357-8203	REVISTA COLINEARES	B1
0486-6525	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE ANTROPOLOGIA	A2
1900-6896	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE BIOETICA	A4
0120-5633	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CARDIOLOGIA	B2
2027-4297	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CIENCIA ANIMAL RECIA	B4
2027-1840	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CIÊNCIAS ANIMA	B4
2011-2173	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CIENCIAS HORTICOLAS	B4
0120-0690	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CIENCIAS PECUARIAS	B2
2256-2958	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CIENCIAS PECUARIAS	B2
1909-6356	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE CIENCIAS QUIMICO FARMACEUTICAS	A3
1657-2831	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE COMPUTACION	B2
1909-1621	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE ENFERMERIA	B4
0120-0488	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE ENTOMOLOGÍA	B4
0120-1751	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE ESTADISTICA	B1
0120-9957	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE GASTROENTEROLOGIA	B3
0121-5469	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE PSICOLOGIA	A2
0034-7450	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE PSIQUIATRIA	B3
0120-2804	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE QUIMICA	B3
2256-5485	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE SOCIOLOGÍA	B1
2526-5970	REVISTA COMMUNITAS	B1
2447-8903	REVISTA COMPARTILHE DOCÊNCIA	B4
2359-5876	REVISTA COMPETITIVIDADE E SUSTENTABILIDADE	B3
1130-2496	REVISTA COMPLUTENSE DE EDUCACIÓN	A1
1132-8312	REVISTA COMPLUTENSE DE HISTORIA DE AMÉRICA	A2
2236-4781	REVISTA COMPOLITICA	A3
2183-7198	REVISTA COMUNICAÇÃO E LINGUAGENS	B2
1678-9822	REVISTA COMUNICAÇÃO MIDIÁTICA	B2
2317-7519	REVISTA COMUNICAÇÃO, CULTURA E SOCIEDADE	B2
2238-121X	REVISTA COMUNICAÇÕES	A3
2182-4037	REVISTA COMUNICANDO	B1
2525-6815	REVISTA CONBRAD	B3
2310-0265	REVISTA CON-CIENCIA	A3
2238-7315	REVISTA CONEXÃO UEPG	A4
2447-2921	REVISTA CONHECIMENTO CONTÁBIL	B4

2525-7935	REVISTA CONHECIMENTO EM AÇÃO	B2
2176-8501	REVISTA CONHECIMENTO ONLINE	B3
2313-013X	REVISTA CONJETURAS SOCIOLÓGICAS	B2
1519-7077	REVISTA CONTABILIDADE & FINANÇAS (IMPRESSO)	A2
2236-4846	REVISTA CONTEMPORÂNEA	B2
1807-1821	REVISTA CONTEMPORÂNEA DE CONTABILIDADE (UFSC)	A2
1809-5747	REVISTA CONTEMPORÂNEA DE EDUCAÇÃO	B1
2347-0011	REVISTA CONTENCIOSA	A4
1676-188X	REVISTA CONTEXTO & SAÚDE	A4
2595-7236	REVISTA CONTEXTO GEOGRÁFICO	B3
2525-5509	REVISTA CONTEXTURA (ONLINE)	B3
2317-8825	REVISTA CONTINENTES	A3
2238-2577	REVISTA CONTRACAMPO	A2
2317-2134	REVISTA CONTRASTE	B4
1807-5371	REVISTA CONTRAVENTO	B4
2527-1253	REVISTA CONTROLE SOCIAL E DESENVOLVIMENTO TERRITORIAL	B3
0120-4165	REVISTA CONTROVERSIA	B4
2316-6134	REVISTA CONVERGÊNCIA LUSÍADA	B1
2500-8870	REVISTA COPALA	B3
2178-5945	REVISTA CORPOCONSCIÊNCIA (ELETRÔNICA)	B4
1980-4466	REVISTA CPC (USP)	A3
1984-1124	REVISTA CRIAÇÃO & CRÍTICA	A3
1981-7169	REVISTA CRIOLA (USP)	A3
0254-1106	REVISTA CRÍTICA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	A1
2182-7435	REVISTA CRÍTICA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	A1
1510-8090	REVISTA CRITICA DE DERECHO PRIVADO	B3
2177-9961	REVISTA CRÍTICA HISTÓRICA	B1
2310-3469	REVISTA CUBANA DE CIÊNCIA FORESTALES	B2
1561-2961	REVISTA CUBANA DE ENFERMERIA	B1
1561-297X	REVISTA CUBANA DE ESTOMATOLOGIA	B3
0864-0289	REVISTA CUBANA DE HEMATOLOGÍA, IMMUNOLOGÍA Y HEMOTERA	B3
2307-2113	REVISTA CUBANA DE INFORMACIÓN EN CIENCIAS DE LA SALUD	A4
2411-9970	REVISTA CUBANA DE INFORMACIÓN Y COMUNICACIÓN	A4
0375-0760	REVISTA CUBANA DE MEDICINA TROPICAL (IMPRESA)	B4
1028-4796	REVISTA CUBANA DE PLANTAS MEDICINALES	B4
0864-3466	REVISTA CUBANA DE SALUD PÚBLICA (IMPRESA)	B4
2316-9060	REVISTA CULTURA E EXTENSÃO USP	B2
2359-5744	REVISTA CULTURAS JURÍDICAS	A2
2219-1631	REVISTA CYCL ALAS	B2
2177-4870	REVISTA D.: DESIGN, EDUCAÇÃO, SOCIEDADE E SUSTENTABILIDADE	A4
1518-2630	REVISTA DA ABEM	A2
1679-5954	REVISTA DA ABENO	B3
2595-0274	REVISTA DA ABENO	B3
1679-2483	REVISTA DA ABET (IMPRESSO)	A4
2179-0078	REVISTA DA ABIFA - FUNDIÇÃO & MATÉRIAS-PRIMAS	B4
1414-8889	REVISTA DA ABOP	A2
1809-6867	REVISTA DA ABORDAGEM GESTÁLTICA (IMPRESSO)	A3
1980-2846	REVISTA DA ABPI	B4
1678-1805	REVISTA DA ABRALIN	A2
2178-7603	REVISTA DA ABRALIN	A2

2236-9643	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA AMAZONENSE DE LETRAS	B2
1676-1480	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO CONSTITUCIONAL	B1
1677-7247	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE LETRAS	B1
1518-1766	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA DE LETRAS DA BAHIA	B4
2525-4057	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA DE LETRAS JURÍDICAS DA BAHIA	B4
0567-5995	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA NORTE-RIO-GRANDENSE DE LETRAS/ ANL	B4
2594-3979	REVISTA DA ADVOCACIA PÚBLICA FEDERAL	B4
1981-2035	REVISTA DA AGU (IMPRESSO)	B1
2525-328X	REVISTA DA AGU (ONLINE)	B1
1679-768X	REVISTA DA ANPEGE	B1
1982-7830	REVISTA DA ANPOLL (ONLINE)	A2
1516-5892	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA ANTROPOSÓFIC	B3
2177-2770	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISADORES/AS NEGR	B1
0104-4230	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO MÉDICA BRASILEIRA	B1
2175-5590	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO MINEIRA DE DIREITO E ECONOMIA	B4
1647-3337	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE SOCIOLOGIA	B2
1516-9162	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO PSICANALÍTICA DE PORTO ALEGRE	B4
1984-5154	REVISTA DA BIOLOGIA	B4
2316-8056	REVISTA DA CASA DA GEOGRAFIA DE SOBRAL	B1
1981-674X	REVISTA DA CGU	B4
1984-283X	REVISTA DA DEFENSORIA PÚBLICA	B4
1983-7283	REVISTA DA ESCOLA DA MAGISTRATURA DO ESTADO DE RONDÔNIA	B4
1980-220X	REVISTA DA ESCOLA DE ENFERMAGEM DA USP (ONLINE)	A3
2359-3075	REVISTA DA ESCOLA DE GUERRA NAVAL	A3
0102-1788	REVISTA DA ESCOLA SUPERIOR DE GUERRA	B2
2525-9547	REVISTA DA ESMAL (ONLINE)	B4
1415-112X	REVISTA DA ESMAPE	B4
2176-9583	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E ECONOMIA - REFAE	B4
1984-4840	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE CIENCIAS MEDICAS DE SOROCABA	B4
0303-9838	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO	B1
0104-3315	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO (UFPR)	A2
2178-0498	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO (UFU)	B4
1676-1308	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO CANDIDO MENDES	B2
2236-3475	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA UERJ	B1
0101-7187	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA UFG	A3
0104-6594	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA UFRGS	B1
2318-8235	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAI	B1
1984-1841	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DI	A1
1516-0947	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DE SÃO BERNARDO DO CAMPO	B1
1518-6202	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DE VALENÇA (CESSOU EM 1991)	B4
1516-4551	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DO SUL DE MINAS	B1
2447-8709	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DO SUL DE MINAS	B1
0526-4308	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO. UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO P	A2
1679-4273	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE EDUCAÇÃO (UNIVERSIDADE DO ESTAD	B2
0871-164X	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE LETRAS. SÉRIE DE HISTÓRIA	B1
0871-1658	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE LETRAS. SÉRIE FILOSOFIA	B1
2318-7999	REVISTA DA FACULDADE MINEIRA DE DIREITO	A2
1516-1234	REVISTA DA FAE	B3
1519-6569	REVISTA DA FUNDARTE	A2
1982-2537	REVISTA DA MICRO E PEQUENA EMPRESA (FACCAMP)	A4

1982-9965	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA-GERAL DO BANCO CENTRAL	B2
2595-0894	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA-GERAL DO BANCO CENTRAL	B2
2527-1636	REVISTA DA SAÚDE E BIOTECNOLOGIA	B4
1516-0858	REVISTA DA SBPH (BELO HORIZONTE. IMPRESSO)	B1
0103-7544	REVISTA DA SBPH (CURITIBA)	B1
1678-3085	REVISTA DA SEÇÃO JUDICIÁRIA DO RIO DE JANEIRO	B4
1415-1979	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE ECONOMIA POLÍTICA	A4
1676-3793	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE ENFERMEIROS PEDIATRAS	B4
0037-8682	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE MEDICINA TROPICAL (IMPRESSO)	B1
2182-2395	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE DERMATOLOGIA E VENEREAS	B2
1677-2970	REVISTA DA SPAGESP	B1
2447-7117	REVISTA DA TULHA	B1
2316-770X	REVISTA DA UFMG	B4
2182-9608	REVISTA DA UIIPS	B4
1677-4558	REVISTA DA UNIFA (IMPRESSO)	B3
1679-8708	REVISTA DA UNIFEBE	B3
2238-6335	REVISTA DA UNIVERSIDADE IBIRAPUERA	B3
1517-0276	REVISTA DA UNIVERSIDADE VALE DO RIO VERDE	B1
1984-3690	REVISTA DACULTURA	B3
0101-6040	REVISTA DAE	B1
1677-9525	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO (URI. FREDERICO WESTPHALEN)	B3
1415-6555	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO CONTEMPORÂNEA (IMPRESSO)	A2
2176-8412	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA FATEA	B3
2236-1197	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA UEG	B3
1679-5350	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA UNIMEP	A3
2446-9955	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DE EMPRESAS ELETRÔNICA	B4
2237-8057	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DE RORAIMA - RARR	B2
2359-117X	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DO SUL DO PARÁ	B4
2359-5272	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DOM ALBERTO	B3
2447-2719	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E COMÉRCIO EXTERIOR	B4
2525-5487	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E CONTABILIDADE - RAC (IESA)	B4
2358-1948	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E CONTABILIDADE (ESTÁCIO FAP)	B4
2177-8426	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E CONTABILIDADE DA FAT	B3
2176-8366	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E NEGÓCIOS DA AMAZÔNIA (ONLINE)	B3
1414-5987	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO EDUCACIONAL	B3
2237-7956	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRACAO IMED	A4
0034-7604	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO MUNICIPAL	A4
0034-7612	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO PÚBLICA (IMPRESSO)	A2
2447-8156	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO, SOCIEDADE E INOVAÇÃO	B2
0034-7655	REVISTA DE AGRICULTURA (PIRACICABA)	B4
2358-6303	REVISTA DE AGRICULTURA NEOTROPICAL	B4
2254-0644	REVISTA DE ANALISIS TURISTICO	B2
1678-9857	REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGIA	A1
0034-7701	REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGIA (SÃO PAULO)	A1
1578-4282	REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA EXPERIMENTAL	A4
1131-558X	REVISTA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA SOCIAL	A2
1516-7704	REVISTA DE APS (IMPRESSO)	B4
1576-9518	REVISTA DE ARACNOLOGÍA	B4
1679-6462	REVISTA DE ARBITRAGEM E MEDIAÇÃO	B4
1982-1999	REVISTA DE ARQUEOLOGIA	A2

0102-0420	REVISTA DE ARQUEOLOGIA (SOCIEDADE DE ARQUEOLOGIA BRASILE	A2
2237-8294	REVISTA DE ARQUEOLOGIA PÚBLICA	A4
1657-0308	REVISTA DE ARQUITECTURA	A2
2359-3857	REVISTA DE ARQUITETURA E URBANISMO UNIVALI - ARKHÉ (ON LIN	B3
2318-1109	REVISTA DE ARQUITETURA IMED	B1
1885-8643	REVISTA DE ARTES MARCIALES ASIÁTICAS	B3
2174-0747	REVISTA DE ARTES MARCIALES ASIÁTICAS	B3
2359-4330	REVISTA DE ATENÇÃO À SAÚDE	B2
2317-0484	REVISTA DE AUDITORIA, GOVERNANÇA E CONTABILIDADE	B3
1886-5887	REVISTA DE BIOETICA Y DERECHO	A3
0718-1957	REVISTA DE BIOLOGÍA MARINA Y OCEANOGRAFÍA	B3
0717-3326	REVISTA DE BIOLOGÍA MARINA Y OCEANOGRAFÍA (IMPRESA)	B3
0034-7744	REVISTA DE BIOLOGIA TROPICAL	A4
2237-1427	REVISTA DE CARREIRAS E PESSOAS	A4
2237-7417	REVISTA DE CASOS E CONSULTORIA	B1
0034-7752	REVISTA DE CHIMIE (BUCURESTI)	B1
0716-1417	REVISTA DE CIENCIA POLÍTICA (SANTIAGO. IMPRESA)	A1
2358-4610	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA VETERINÁRIA E SAÚDE PÚBLICA	B4
1984-7300	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA, TECNOLOGIA E HUMANIDADES (CIENTEC)	B3
1517-591X	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS AGRÁRIAS (BELÉM)	B4
0120-0135	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS AGRÍCOLAS	B1
1516-3865	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS DA ADMINISTRAÇÃO (CAD/UFSC)	A2
1518-7039	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS DA EDUCAÇÃO	B1
1983-4772	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS DA VIDA	B4
2177-7551	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS DA VIDA	B4
2525-8036	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS DO ESTADO (UFMG)	B1
1982-1115	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS EMPRESARIAIS DA UNIPAR	B3
1517-6304	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS EMPRESARIAIS DA UNIPAR (IMPRESSO)	B3
1808-4532	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS FARMACÊUTICAS BÁSICA E APLICADA	B2
2179-443X	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS FARMACÊUTICAS BÁSICA E APLICADA	B2
1415-6571	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS GERENCIAIS	B3
1981-9250	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS - EDUCAÇÃO	B3
0101-9589	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS (UFSC)	B2
1519-1974	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS (VIÇOSA)	B4
2526-7450	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS REAGES	B4
2236-5176	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS UFV	B4
1518-0719	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS JURÍDICAS (MARINGÁ)	B3
1982-1107	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS JURÍDICAS E SOCIAIS DA UNIPAR	B4
1415-5796	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS (PUCCAMP)	B4
2236-5222	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS E BIOLÓGICAS	A4
2183-0711	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS MILITARES	B1
0303-9862	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS (FORTALEZA)	B3
2318-4620	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS (UFC)	B3
1688-4981	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B2
0716-7725	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES (CHILE)	B4
0797-5538	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES (MONTEVIDEO)	B2
2347-1050	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES.SEGUNDA EPOCA	A4
1984-3704	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE DA UFBA	B2
1984-3291	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE DO MESTRADO EM CIÊNCIAS CONTÁBI	A3
2317-6148	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE DOM ALBERTO	B3

0870-8827	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE E FINANÇAS	B1
2595-7287	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE E GESTÃO CONTEMPORÂNEA	B4
1982-6486	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE E ORGANIZAÇÕES	A2
2317-5001	REVISTA DE CONTABILIDADE, CIÊNCIA DA GESTÃO E FINANÇAS	B4
0252-8843	REVISTA DE CRÍTICA LITERARIA LATINOAMERICANA	A3
1682-1106	REVISTA DE CULTURA	A4
2175-6805	REVISTA DE CULTURA E EXTENSÃO	B2
2317-4307	REVISTA DE CULTURA TEOLÓGICA	A3
2318-2253	REVISTA DE DEFESA DA CONCORRÊNCIA - RDC	B1
1909-7786	REVISTA DE DERECHO COMUNICACIONES Y NUEVAS TECNOLOGIAS	B3
0034-7914	REVISTA DE DERECHO PENAL Y CRIMINOLOGIA	A2
1132-9955	REVISTA DE DERECHO PENAL Y CRIMINOLOGÍA	A3
0123-4366	REVISTA DE DERECHO PRIVADO (BOGOTA, 1998)	B1
1889-8068	REVISTA DE DERECHOS HUMANOS Y ESTUDIOS SOCIALES	B2
2447-360X	REVISTA DE DESENVOLVIMENTO E POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	B4
2178-8022	REVISTA DE DESENVOLVIMENTO ECONÔMICO	B1
2238-5177	REVISTA DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO	A2
2184-1799	REVISTA DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO	A2
2317-4056	REVISTA DE DIREITO AGROAMBIENTAL E TEORIA DO DIREITO (ONLII	B4
1413-1439	REVISTA DE DIREITO AMBIENTAL	B1
1518-2703	REVISTA DE DIREITO BANCÁRIO DO MERCADO DE CAPITAIS E DA AR	B3
1415-6318	REVISTA DE DIREITO BANCÁRIO E DO MERCADO DE CAPITAIS	B4
2358-1352	REVISTA DE DIREITO BRASILEIRA	A1
2237-583X	REVISTA DE DIREITO BRASILEIRA - RDBRAS	A1
2358-1433	REVISTA DE DIREITO CIVIL CONTEMPORÂNEO	A2
1518-272X	REVISTA DE DIREITO CONSTITUCIONAL E INTERNACIONAL	B3
2447-2042	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA ADMINISTRAÇÃO PÚBLICA	B4
1809-6077	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA CIDADE	A1
2595-7627	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA SAÚDE SUPLEMENTAR	B4
1415-7705	REVISTA DE DIREITO DO CONSUMIDOR	A3
0102-8774	REVISTA DE DIREITO DO TRABALHO (SÃO PAULO)	B1
1809-3280	REVISTA DE DIREITO E LIBERDADE	B1
2179-8214	REVISTA DE DIREITO ECONÔMICO E SOCIOAMBIENTAL	A2
2318-7689	REVISTA DE DIREITO EMPRESARIAL	B4
2237-1036	REVISTA DE DIREITO INTERNACIONAL	A1
1980-1955	REVISTA DE DIREITO INTERNACIONAL, ECONÔMICO E TRIBUTÁRIO	B1
1517-6851	REVISTA DE DIREITO MACKENZIE	B1
0102-8049	REVISTA DE DIREITO MERCANTIL INDUSTRIAL, ECONÔMICO E FINAN	B4
1517-6290	REVISTA DE DIREITO PRIVADO (SÃO PAULO)	B4
0034-8015	REVISTA DE DIREITO PÚBLICO	B4
1516-4179	REVISTA DE DIREITO SANITÁRIO	B3
2316-9044	REVISTA DE DIREITO SANITÁRIO	B3
2446-5259	REVISTA DE DIREITO SETORIAL E REGULATÓRIO	B4
2525-4626	REVISTA DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO CONTEMPORÂNEO	B4
1984-9729	REVISTA DE DIREITO, ESTADO E TELECOMUNICAÇÕES (IMPRESSO)	B4
1517-9192	REVISTA DE DIREITOS DIFUSOS	B4
2175-6058	REVISTA DE DIREITOS E GARANTIAS FUNDAMENTAIS	A1
2179-0981	REVISTA DE DIVULGAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA SENA AIRES - REVISA	B4
0103-6033	REVISTA DE DIVULGAÇÃO CULTURAL	B4
0556-5782	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA (CURITIBA)	B2

1981-4771	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA AGRÍCOLA (IMPRESSO)	B2
1980-5527	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA CONTEMPORÂNEA	A3
2013-5254	REVISTA DE ECONOMÍA CRÍTICA	B4
1809-970X	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA DA UEG. SEÇÃO ELETRÔNICA	B3
2011-2106	REVISTA DE ECONOMÍA DEL CARIBE	B1
2145-9363	REVISTA DE ECONOMÍA DEL CARIBE	B1
2447-231X	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA DO CENTRO-OESTE	B3
1679-1614	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA E AGRONEGÓCIO	B2
0103-2003	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA E SOCIOLOGIA RURAL (IMPRESSO)	A3
1806-9479	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA E SOCIOLOGIA RURAL (ONLINE)	A3
1808-2785	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA MACKENZIE	B3
1678-5002	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA MACKENZIE (IMPRESSO)	B3
1809-4538	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA POLÍTICA (ONLINE)	A3
1807-2674	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA POLÍTICA E HISTÓRIA ECONÔMICA	B4
2316-5235	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA REGIONAL, URBANA E DO TRABALHO	B4
1647-5968	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA SOLIDÁRIA	B3
1516-3326	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO CONTINUADA DO CRMV-SP	B4
2179-6645	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO CONTINUADA EM MEDICINA VETERINÁRIA	B4
2358-9299	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO DO COGEIME	B3
2359-0041	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO DO VALE DO ARINOS - RELVA	B1
2316-2260	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO DOM ALBERTO	B3
1981-8610	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO E PESQUISA EM CONTABILIDADE (REPEC)	A2
0873-464X	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO ESPECIAL E REABILITAÇÃO	B4
0102-8464	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA	B4
2447-8946	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA	B4
1676-8868	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	A3
2526-9062	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	A3
1678-5622	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO POPULAR (IMPRESSO)	B1
1519-3993	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO PUC-CAMPINAS	A4
2236-6377	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO, CIÊNCIA E CULTURA	A3
2238-2380	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO, CIÊNCIAS E MATEMÁTICA	B1
0034-8082	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN	A3
0214-0489	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	B1
0124-5481	REVISTA DE EDUCACION DE LAS CIENCIAS	B4
0329-5192	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN EN BIOLOGÍA	B2
2344-9225	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN EN BIOLOGÍA	B2
2393-6789	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR DEL SUR GLOBAL - RESUR	B2
1853-1318	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN. FACULTAD DE HUMANIDADES - UNMD	B1
2447-8407	REVISTA DE EMPREENDEDORISMO E GESTÃO DE MICRO E PEQUENAS	B3
2359-3539	REVISTA DE EMPREENDEDORISMO, INOVAÇÃO E TECNOLOGIA	B4
2448-3664	REVISTA DE EMPREENDEDORISMO, NEGÓCIOS E INOVAÇÃO (RENI)	B3
2526-0502	REVISTA DE EMPREENDEDORISMO E INOVAÇÃO SUSTENTÁVEIS	B3
2238-7234	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM DA UFPI	B3
2179-7692	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM DA UFSM	B1
2236-6091	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM DO CENTRO OESTE MINEIRO (RECOM)	B1
2317-1154	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM E ATENÇÃO À SAÚDE	B2
0874-0283	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM REFERÊNCIA	B1
1981-8963	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM UFPE ON LINE	B4
1678-5738	REVISTA DE ENGENHARIA DA UNIVERSIDADE CATÓLICA DE PETRÓPOLIS	B4
2525-4251	REVISTA DE ENGENHARIA E PESQUISA APLICADA	B4

0326-7091	REVISTA DE ENSEÑANZA DE LA FÍSICA	A2
1982-1867	REVISTA DE ENSINO DE BIOLOGIA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE E	B4
2318-8790	REVISTA DE ENSINO DE BIOQUÍMICA	B4
2447-6129	REVISTA DE ENSINO E PESQUISA EM ADMINISTRAÇÃO E ENGENHAR	B3
2594-4630	REVISTA DE ENSINO EM ARTES, MODA E DESIGN	B1
2447-8733	REVISTA DE ENSINO, EDUCAÇÃO E CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS	A3
2238-3360	REVISTA DE EPIDEMIOLOGIA E CONTROLE DE INFECÇÃO	B4
2340-9029	REVISTA DE ESCRITORAS IBÉRICAS	A4
1988-8996	REVISTA DE ESTILOS DE APRENDIZAJE	B1
2444-6157	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS EN SEGURIDAD INTERNACIONAL	A2
2386-4540	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS BRASILEÑOS	B3
1885-8031	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS COOPERATIVOS	B1
2386-7418	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS E INVESTIGACION EN PSICOLOGIA Y EDUCACI	A4
1659-4223	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS HISTÓRICOS DE LA MASONERÍA LATINOAMEI	A2
2452-4263	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS IUS NOVUM	B4
2445-0669	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS KANTIANOS	B3
2174-7245	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS LINGÜÍSTICOS HISPÁNICOS	A3
2255-1891	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS PORTUGUESES Y BRASILEÑOS	B3
2258-014X	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SOBRE FICHTE / REVISTA DE ESTUDOS SOBRE	A2
2362-3985	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SOBRE GENOCIDIO	B3
1900-5150	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SOCIALES	A1
0123-885X	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SOCIALES (EN LINEA)	A3
2409-3696	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS TEÓRICOS Y EPISTEMOLÓGICOS EN POLÍTICA	B1
0719-7527	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS TRIBUTARIOS	B2
0717-6945	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS Y EXPERIENCIAS EN EDUCACIÓN (IMPRESA)	A3
2358-8403	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS ACADÊMICOS DE LETRAS	B1
1516-3911	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS AMBIENTAIS	B3
1645-751X	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS CURRICULARES	B4
0104-0588	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DA LINGUAGEM	A2
2446-7189	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DE CULTURA	B1
2359-1145	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DE GESTÃO, INFORMAÇÃO E TECNOLOGIA	A4
2238-7587	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS DE LITERATURA, CULTURA E ALTERIDADE - IG.	B1
2446-6972	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS E INVESTIGAÇÕES ANTROPOLÓGICAS	B4
2359-5299	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS AVANÇADAS DO TERCEIRO SETC	B2
1984-1639	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS SOBRE AS AMÉRICAS	A3
2446-774X	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS SOBRE ENSINO TECNOLÓGICO	A3
2319-0817	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS EMPÍRICOS EM DIREITO	B1
2177-5850	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS FILOSÓFICOS E HISTÓRICOS DA ANTIGÜIDADE	B3
2236-4811	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS INTERNACIONAIS	B1
1517-7904	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS JUDAICOS (BELO HORIZONTE)	B2
2179-5177	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS JURÍDICOS DA UNESP	B1
2182-1526	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS LITERÁRIOS	B3
1519-504X	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS SOCIAIS (UFMT)	B4
1519-1850	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS TRIBUTÁRIOS (PORTO ALEGRE)	B3
0102-6437	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS UNIVERSITÁRIAS (SOROCABA)	B2
2448-4245	REVISTA DE EXTENSÃO	B4
2215-2628	REVISTA DE FILOLOGÍA Y LINGÜÍSTICA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE COST	B3
0718-4360	REVISTA DE FILOSOFÍA	A2
1981-9471	REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA ANTIGA (UNICAMP. ED. PORTUGUÊS)	A1
0034-8252	REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE COSTA RICA	B1

2317-9570	REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA MODERNA E CONTEMPORÂNEA	B2
1852-9488	REVISTA DE FILOSOFIA Y CIÊNCIAS - PROMETEICA	B2
2176-8854	REVISTA DE FINANÇAS APLICADAS	B4
2358-2693	REVISTA DE FINANÇAS E CONTABILIDADE DA UNIMEP	B4
2317-837X	REVISTA DE FINANÇAS PÚBLICAS TRIBUTAÇÃO E DESENVOLVIMENT	B4
1413-7879	REVISTA DE FISIOTERAPIA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAULO	B3
2359-2648	REVISTA DE FONTES	B4
0375-0906	REVISTA DE GASTROENTEROLOGIA DE MEXICO	B2
1022-5129	REVISTA DE GASTROENTEROLOGÍA DEL PERÚ (IMPRESA)	B3
2447-3359	REVISTA DE GEOCIÊNCIAS DO NORDESTE	A4
2238-6211	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFIA	A4
2236-837X	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFIA (UFJF)	B3
2182-1267	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFIA E ORDENAMENTO DO TERRITÓRIO	B4
0379-8682	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFÍA NORTE GRANDE (IMPRESA)	B3
0103-2410	REVISTA DE GEOLOGIA (FORTALEZA)	B4
2177-3246	REVISTA DE GEOPOLITICA	A3
2316-9834	REVISTA DE GESTAO AMBIENTAL E SUSTENTABILIDADE	A3
1807-1775	REVISTA DE GESTÃO DA TECNOLOGIA E SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO	B1
2318-1338	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E AVALIAÇÃO EDUCACIONAL	A4
2358-1735	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E CONTABILIDADE DA UFPI	B3
2359-0432	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E ORGANIZAÇÕES COOPERATIVAS	B2
2236-0972	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E PROJETOS	A4
2178-9010	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E SECRETARIADO	B1
2316-3712	REVISTA DE GESTÃO EM SISTEMAS DE SAÚDE	B1
1982-4092	REVISTA DE GESTÃO PÚBLICA/DF	B4
1981-982X	REVISTA DE GESTÃO SOCIAL E AMBIENTAL (RGSA)	A3
2238-5320	REVISTA DE GESTÃO, FINANÇAS E CONTABILIDADE	A3
0719-1839	REVISTA DE GESTIÓN PÚBLICA	B4
1988-7116	REVISTA DE GLOBALIZACION, COMPETITIVIDAD Y GOVERNABILIDAD	A4
2359-313X	REVISTA DE GOVERNANÇA CORPORATIVA	B2
0327-4233	REVISTA DE HISTORIA	B3
2316-9141	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA	A1
2357-8556	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA BILROS	A4
1981-383X	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA COMPARADA (UFRJ)	A3
2447-6447	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	B2
1645-2259	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA SOCIEDADE E DA CULTURA	A2
2316-4379	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA UEG	A3
2179-5703	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA UEG / QUIRINÓPOLIS - GOIÁS	B1
0122-7238	REVISTA DE HISTORIA DE LA EDUCACION LATINOAMERICANA	A3
0211-0040	REVISTA DE HISTORIA DE LA PSICOLOGÍA	B1
2451-6473	REVISTA DE HISTORIA DE LAS PRISIONES	B2
2526-2378	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA E HISTORIOGRAFIA DA EDUCAÇÃO	B2
1414-0055	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA REGIONAL	A1
0717-5248	REVISTA DE HISTORIA SOCIAL Y DE LAS MENTALIDADES	A4
2445-0057	REVISTA DE HISTORIOGRAFÍA	A2
2175-3105	REVISTA DE HOMEOPATIA	B3
2318-0714	REVISTA DE HUMANIDADES	B4
1130-5029	REVISTA DE HUMANIDADES (UNED - SEVILLA)	A3
1414-042X	REVISTA DE HUMANIDADES (UNIFOR)	B4
2238-3948	REVISTA DE HUMANIDADES, TECNOLOGIA E CULTURA - REHUTEC	B3

0034-8341	REVISTA DE INDIAS	A1
1982-3967	REVISTA DE INFORMAÇÃO CONTÁBIL (UFPE)	B3
0034-835X	REVISTA DE INFORMAÇÃO LEGISLATIVA	A2
1909-9991	REVISTA DE INGENIERÍA BIOMÉDICA	B4
0718-5073	REVISTA DE INGENIERÍA DE CONSTRUCCIÓN (EN LÍNEA)	B2
2525-4332	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO À DOCÊNCIA	B4
2317-4323	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA DA ULBRA	B4
2238-5266	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA DA UNIVERSIDADE VALE DO RIO	B3
2318-9452	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA EM RELAÇÕES INTERNACIONAIS	B2
2179-2895	REVISTA DE INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA	B3
2594-4673	REVISTA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E DIVULGAÇÃO EM EDUCAÇÃO MATEM	A4
0798-0329	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN (CARACAS)	B4
2145-6097	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN AGRARIA Y AMBIENTAL	B1
2145-6453	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN AGRARIA Y AMBIENTAL (ONLINE)	B1
2174-5218	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN LOGOPEDIA	B1
0325-6375	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y DESARROLLO PESQUERO	B3
0252-1962	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIONES MARINAS	B4
2255-5986	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIONES POLÍTICAS Y SOCIOLOGÍAS	A4
1682-3419	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIONES VETERINARIAS DEL PERÚ	B3
2359-5639	REVISTA DE INVESTIGAÇÕES CONSTITUCIONAIS	A1
2238-8281	REVISTA DE ITALIANÍSTICA	B1
1515-1786	REVISTA DE LA ASOCIACIÓN ARGENTINA DE ORTOPEDIA Y TRAUMA	B4
1852-7434	REVISTA DE LA ASOCIACIÓN ARGENTINA DE ORTOPEDIA Y TRAUMA	B4
1988-7302	REVISTA DE LA ASOCIACIÓN DE SOCIOLOGÍA DE LA EDUCACIÓN	A4
2341-2690	REVISTA DE LA ASOCIACIÓN ESPAÑOLA DE INVESTIGACIÓN DE LA CI	A3
0004-4822	REVISTA DE LA ASOCIACIÓN GEOLÓGICA ARGENTINA	B2
1853-6484	REVISTA DE LA CARRERA DE SOCIOLOGÍA. ENTRAMADOS Y PERSPEC	B4
0718-915X	REVISTA DE LA CONSTRUCCIÓN	A3
1578-7680	REVISTA DE LA EDUCACION A DISTANCIA	A3
1851-6297	REVISTA DE LA ESCUELA DE CIENCIAS DE LA EDUCACIÓN	A4
1853-9777	REVISTA DE LA ESCUELA DE PERFECCIONAMIENTO EN INVESTIGACI	B3
2477-9407	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE AGRONOMIA	B4
0378-7818	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE AGRONOMÍA	B4
0326-6184	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE AGRONOMÍA. UNIVERSIDAD NACIONA	B2
0121-3814	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE CIENCIA Y TECNOLOGIA	A2
0370-4661	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS AGRARIAS	A4
1853-8665	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS AGRARIAS UNCUYO	A4
2301-0665	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE DERECHO	B3
0120-3886	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE DERECHO Y CIENCIAS POLITICAS	B1
0120-0011	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE MEDICINA	B2
1667-4243	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE ODONTOLOGÍA	B4
0120-386X	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD NACIONAL DE SALUD PUBLICA	B2
1514-9765	REVISTA DE LA FUNDACIÓN JUAN JOSÉ CARRARO	B4
2072-7976	REVISTA DE LA MAESTRÍA EN DERECHO PROCESAL	B4
1578-7303	REVISTA DE LA REAL ACADEMIA DE CIENCIAS EXACTAS, FÍSICAS Y NA	B1
1579-1505	REVISTA DE LA REAL ACADEMIA DE CIENCIAS EXACTAS, FÍSICAS Y NA	B1
2250-7264	REVISTA DE LA RED INTERCÁTEDRAS DE HISTORIA DE AMÉRICA LATI	B2
2304-7887	REVISTA DE LA SECRETARÍA DEL TRIBUNAL PERMANENTE DE REVISI	B2
0373-5680	REVISTA DE LA SOCIEDAD ENTOMOLÓGICA ARGENTINA	B4
1810-634X	REVISTA DE LA SOCIEDAD QUÍMICA DEL PERÚ	B3

1315-2556	REVISTA DE LA SOCIEDAD VENEZOLANA DE MICROBIOLOGÍA	B4
0041-6932	REVISTA DE LA UNIÓN MATEMÁTICA ARGENTINA (1968)	B3
0120-6877	REVISTA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE LA SALLE	A3
0121-0807	REVISTA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD INDUSTRIAL DE SANTANDER. SALUD	B3
2179-5282	REVISTA DE LETRAS	A4
2527-1024	REVISTA DE LETRAS - JUÇARA	B2
0101-8051	REVISTA DE LETRAS (FORTALEZA)	B1
1982-842X	REVISTA DE LETRAS (TAGUATINGA)	B1
2358-4793	REVISTA DE LETRAS (UFC)	B1
1981-7886	REVISTA DE LETRAS (UNESP. ONLINE)	B4
1983-8018	REVISTA DE LETRAS NORTE@MENTOS	A4
1983-1498	REVISTA DE LITERATURA, HISTÓRIA E MEMÓRIA	B1
2178-0382	REVISTA DE LOGÍSTICA DA FATEC-CARAPICUÍBA	B4
0214-4603	REVISTA DE LOGOPEDIA, FONIATRÍA Y AUDIOLOGÍA (ED. IMPRESA)	B2
1808-0626	REVISTA DE MAGISTRO DE FILOSOFIA	B4
2238-5339	REVISTA DE MEDICINA E SAÚDE DE BRASÍLIA	B4
0034-8570	REVISTA DE METALURGIA	B1
2446-8622	REVISTA DE MICRO E PEQUENAS EMPRESAS E EMPREENDEDORISMO	B2
2182-7214	REVISTA DE MORFOLOGIA URBANA	B1
1980-4431	REVISTA DE NEGÓCIOS (ONLINE)	A4
1678-9865	REVISTA DE NUTRIÇÃO	B1
0103-1627	REVISTA DE NUTRIÇÃO DA PUCCAMP	B1
1808-8120	REVISTA DE ODONTOLOGIA DA UNICID	B4
0103-0663	REVISTA DE ODONTOLOGIA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAULO	B2
2446-6492	REVISTA DE PATOLOGIA DO TOCANTINS	B3
1988-7221	REVISTA DE PAZ Y CONFLICTOS	A2
0719-8019	REVISTA DE PEDAGOGIA CRÍTICA PAULO FREIRE	B2
2527-0974	REVISTA DE PEDAGOGIA SOCIAL	B4
2526-3560	REVISTA DE PESQUISA INTERDISCIPLINAR	B3
2175-5361	REVISTA DE PESQUISA: CUIDADO E FUNDAMENTAL (ONLINE)	B1
1583-4433	REVISTA DE PIELARIE INCALTAMINTE (LEATHER AND FOOTWEAR JO	B1
1413-4969	REVISTA DE POLITICA AGRICOLA	B2
2317-224X	REVISTA DE POLÍTICA AGRÍCOLA	B2
2178-2865	REVISTA DE POLITICAS PÚBLICAS DA UFMA	A1
1678-4057	REVISTA DE POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS E GESTÃO GOVERNAMENTAL	B4
0100-1981	REVISTA DE PROCESSO	B1
2238-8044	REVISTA DE PRODUÇÃO DISCENTE EM EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	B4
2316-8080	REVISTA DE PROPRIEDADE INTELECTUAL - DIREITO CONTEMPORÂN	B4
2224-4697	REVISTA DE PROTECCIÓN VEGETAL	B4
1413-4438	REVISTA DE PSICANÁLISE DA SOCIEDADE PSICANALÍTICA DE PORTO	B1
0034-8740	REVISTA DE PSICOANÁLISIS	A4
0719-0581	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA	A4
0254-9247	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA (LIMA)	A2
0716-8039	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA (SANTIAGO)	A4
2179-1740	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA (UFC)	A4
1980-6906	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA : TEORIA E PRÁTICA (ONLINE)	A2
2182-8008	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA DA CRIANÇA E DO ADOLESCENTE	B4
2175-5027	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA DA IMED	B2
1984-9044	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA DA UNESP	B3
2386-2300	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA DE LA SALUD	A1

1132-239X	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA DEL DEPORTE	B1
1576-5962	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA DEL TRABAJO Y DE LAS ORGANIZACIONES (A2
2145-6569	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA GEPU	B3
2175-1390	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGIA POLÍTICA	A4
2385-4804	REVISTA DE QUÍMICA E INDUSTRIA TEXTIL	B4
0370-694X	REVISTA DE QUÍMICA INDUSTRIAL	B3
1909-3063	REVISTA DE RELACIONES INTERNACIONALES, ESTRATEGIA Y SEGURIDAD	A2
1130-4235	REVISTA DE RESERCA HUMANÍSTICA I CIENTÍFICA	B3
1577-9572	REVISTA DE SALUD AMBIENTAL	B4
1677-7522	REVISTA DE SAÚDE COLETIVA DA UEFS	B4
2525-9563	REVISTA DE SAÚDE DIGITAL E TECNOLOGIAS EDUCACIONAIS	B2
2318-7700	REVISTA DE SAÚDE DOM ALBERTO	B3
1518-8787	REVISTA DE SAÚDE PÚBLICA (ONLINE)	A3
0104-4478	REVISTA DE SOCIOLOGIA E POLÍTICA (UFPR. IMPRESSO)	A1
2237-3713	REVISTA DE TECNOLOGIA APLICADA	B1
2237-5112	REVISTA DE TECNOLOGIA DA INFORMAÇÃO E COMUNICAÇÃO	B4
1413-8131	REVISTA DE TECNOLOGIA E AMBIENTE	B3
1133-0953	REVISTA DE TELEDETECCIÓN	B2
1679-5393	REVISTA DE TEOLOGIA E CIÊNCIAS DA RELIGIÃO DA UNICAP	B4
2175-5892	REVISTA DE TEORIA DA HISTÓRIA	A3
1415-9104	REVISTA DE TERAPIA OCUPACIONAL DA UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAULO	B3
2357-8211	REVISTA DE TURISMO CONTEMPORÂNEO	B3
2236-479X	REVISTA DEBATES	A4
2447-6099	REVISTA DEBATES EM ENSINO DE QUÍMICA	A3
2595-2803	REVISTA DEBATES INSUBMISSOS	B4
1853-211X	REVISTA DEBATES LATINOAMERICANOS	B4
2318-2229	REVISTA DECIFRAR	B1
2447-9365	REVISTA DEFESA E SEGURANÇA	B4
2081-1160	REVISTA DEL CESLA	A2
1641-4713	REVISTA DEL CESLA	A2
1315-2378	REVISTA DEL CLAD REFORMA Y DEMOCRACIA	A3
2412-0715	REVISTA DEL COLÉGIO INTERAMERICANO DE DEFENSA (IMPRESSO)	B3
1853-1393	REVISTA DEL INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACIONES EN EDUCACIÓN	B4
1514-5158	REVISTA DEL MUSEO ARGENTINO DE CIENCIAS NATURALES (1999)	B4
1852-060X	REVISTA DEL MUSEO DE ANTROPOLOGIA	A3
0122-9893	REVISTA DERECHO DEL ESTADO	B3
2301-1009	REVISTA DERECHO DEL TRABAJO	B4
2175-3180	REVISTA DESASSOSSEGO	A4
1677-9797	REVISTA DESEMPENHO	B1
1807-2062	REVISTA DESENBALIA	B4
1678-4855	REVISTA DESENVOLVIMENTO EM QUESTÃO	A4
1982-8608	REVISTA DESENVOLVIMENTO SOCIAL	B4
2359-5868	REVISTA DESPIERTA	B2
2526-0405	REVISTA DESVIO	B4
2317-2010	REVISTA DIALECTUS	B1
2317-1391	REVISTA DIALÉTICA	B4
2316-1795	REVISTA DIÁLOGO DAS LETRAS	B3
1981-416X	REVISTA DIÁLOGO EDUCACIONAL	A2
2319-0825	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS (REVDIA)	A3
2594-6978	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS E CONTRAPONTO: ESTUDOS INTERDISCIPLINARES	B4

2317-3793	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS INTERDISCIPLINARES	A4
2237-6585	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS MEDITERRÂNICOS	A3
1677-8898	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS: PESQUISA E EXTENSÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA	B4
2446-7413	REVISTA DIAPHONÍA	B4
1809-3108	REVISTA DIDÁTICA SISTÊMICA	B3
1982-310X	REVISTA DIGITAL CONSTITUIÇÃO E GARANTIA DE DIREITOS (UFRN)	B4
1678-765X	REVISTA DIGITAL DE BIBLIOTECONOMIA E CIÊNCIA DA INFORMAÇÃO	A3
2145-2946	REVISTA DIGITAL DE DERECHO ADMINISTRATIVO	A3
2319-0558	REVISTA DIGITAL DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO	B3
2448-0657	REVISTA DIGITAL DE ENSINO DE FILOSOFIA	B2
2223-2516	REVISTA DIGITAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN DOCENCIA UNIVERSITARIA	B1
2007-1965	REVISTA DIGITAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN LASALIANA	B2
2595-6493	REVISTA DIGITAL DE MÚSICA SACRA BRASILEIRA	B4
2175-2176	REVISTA DIGITAL DO INSTITUTO DOS ADVOGADOS BRASILEIROS - IA	B4
2317-2738	REVISTA DIGITAL DO INSTITUTO LATINO-AMERICANO DE ARTE, CUL	B3
1983-7348	REVISTA DIGITAL DO LAV	B1
1607-6079	REVISTA DIGITAL UNIVERSITARIA	B1
2313-9676	REVISTA DIGITAL: ARTES, LETRAS Y HUMANIDADES	A3
2316-8218	REVISTA DIREITO AMBIENTAL E SOCIEDADE (UCS)	B1
2179-8966	REVISTA DIREITO E PRÁXIS	A1
1806-910X	REVISTA DIREITO EMPRESARIAL (CURITIBA)	B1
2317-6172	REVISTA DIREITO GV (ONLINE)	A1
2317-2622	REVISTA DIREITO MACKENZIE	B1
2447-2336	REVISTA DIREITO UFMS	B2
1982-0496	REVISTA DIREITOS FUNDAMENTAIS & DEMOCRACIA (UNIBRASIL)	A1
2317-5389	REVISTA DIREITOS HUMANOS E DEMOCRACIA	A4
2318-5732	REVISTA DIREITOS SOCIAIS E POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS - UNIFAFIBE	B1
2527-0524	REVISTA DISCENTE OFÍCIOS DE CLIO	B4
2237-7247	REVISTA DISCURSOS CONTEMPORÂNEOS EM ESTUDO	B3
2359-2192	REVISTA DISSOL - DISCURSO, SOCIEDADE E LINGUAGEM	A4
2358-8853	REVISTA DIVERSIDADE E EDUCAÇÃO	B3
0101-7497	REVISTA DO ADVOGADO	B4
2447-908X	REVISTA DO ARQUIVO	B4
1983-6031	REVISTA DO ARQUIVO GERAL DA CIDADE DO RIO DE JANEIRO	B3
2527-2136	REVISTA DO ARQUIVO PÚBLICO DO ESTADO DO ESPÍRITO SANTO	B4
1415-0344	REVISTA DO CAAP	B4
1415-2061	REVISTA DO CCEI	B4
1676-515X	REVISTA DO CENTRO DE ESTUDOS PORTUGUESES (UFMG)	B1
2317-1480	REVISTA DO CENTRO DE ESTUDOS RURAIS (RURIS)	B3
2448-2773	REVISTA DO CENTRO DE PESQUISA E FORMAÇÃO	B2
0103-3093	REVISTA DO CEPA	B2
0100-6991	REVISTA DO COLÉGIO BRASILEIRO DE CIRURGIÕES (IMPRESSO)	B2
2358-3169	REVISTA DO COLÓQUIO DE ARTE E PESQUISA DO PPGA-UFES	B3
0103-5827	REVISTA DO COURO	B4
2594-6374	REVISTA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE BRAZ CUBAS (OI	B4
2236-7632	REVISTA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DO UNIFOR	B4
0102-4582	REVISTA DO DEPARTAMENTO DE GEOGRAFIA (USP)	A4
1982-9957	REVISTA DO DIREITO (SANTA CRUZ DO SUL. ONLINE)	A3
1980-511X	REVISTA DO DIREITO PÚBLICO (LONDRINA)	B1
2317-3815	REVISTA DO EDICC	B3

0101-7284	REVISTA DO EXÉRCITO BRASILEIRO	B4
0101-7184	REVISTA DO EXÉRCITO BRASILEIRO	B4
1984-591X	REVISTA DO GEL	A3
1517-7874	REVISTA DO GELNE	A2
1517-1957	REVISTA DO IBRAC	B3
0103-1945	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO ARQUEOLÓGICO, HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO	B4
1677-1419	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO BRASILEIRO DE DIREITOS HUMANOS	B4
2595-2153	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO BRASILEIRO DE SEGURANÇA PÚBLICA (RIBS)	B4
0122-0799	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO COLOMBIANO DE DERECHO TRIBUTARIO	B4
0104-1894	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE CIENCIAS DA SAUDE (UNIP)	B4
2316-901X	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE ESTUDOS BRASILEIROS	A1
1678-1864	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE HERMENÊUTICA JURÍDICA	A3
1678-9946	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE MEDICINA TROPICAL DE SÃO PAULO	B1
2447-780X	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS DE MARÍLIA	B4
0100-3585	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DO CEARÁ	B4
2237-9657	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO GEOGEBRA INTERNACIONAL DE SÃO PAULO	A3
1516-344X	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO GEOGRÁFICO E HISTÓRICO DA BAHIA	B4
0100-929X	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO GEOLÓGICO	B2
2526-1347	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO BRASILEIRO	A2
1677-0897	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DE MATO GROSSO	B2
0103-9482	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DE PIRACICABA	B4
0100-2953	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DE SÃO PAULO	B2
1981-7347	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DE SERGIPE	A4
2359-0831	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO PARÁ	B1
1519-5678	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO RIO DE JANEIRO	B4
1678-3484	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO RIO GRANDE	B1
0101-4366	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO BRASILEIRO	A2
1679-4540	REVISTA DO ISAT	B1
2236-9155	REVISTA DO ISAT	B1
2595-6957	REVISTA DO LEGISLATIVO PARANAENSE	B3
2359-5973	REVISTA DO LHIESTE	B4
1809-1873	REVISTA DO MESTRADO EM DIREITO (UFAL)	B3
1980-8860	REVISTA DO MESTRADO EM DIREITO UCB	B1
2317-9082	REVISTA DO MESTRADO PROFISSIONAL GESTÃO EM ORGANIZAÇÃO	B4
1677-1060	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO ESTADO DO MARANHÃO	B4
2448-1750	REVISTA DO MUSEU DE ARQUEOLOGIA E ETNOLOGIA	B4
2317-1332	REVISTA DO NESEF	B2
2179-7137	REVISTA DO NÚCLEO DE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS EM GÊNERO & DIREITO	A4
2175-2591	REVISTA DO NUFEN	B2
0102-2571	REVISTA DO PATRIMÔNIO HISTÓRICO E ARTÍSTICO NACIONAL	B2
0102-4981	REVISTA DO PROFESSOR DE MATEMÁTICA	B3
2176-1841	REVISTA DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS GRADUAÇÃO EM ESTUDOS LITERÁRIOS	B1
2236-5850	REVISTA DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM DIREITO DA UNIP	B2
1983-3873	REVISTA DO SELL	A2
2526-9070	REVISTA DO SEMINÁRIO MÍDIAS & EDUCAÇÃO (ONLINE)	B4
0034-9240	REVISTA DO SERVIÇO PÚBLICO	A4
1806-3497	REVISTA DO TRE-RS	B4
0103-1090	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL DE CONTAS DA UNIAO	B4
0102-1052	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL DE CONTAS DO ESTADO DE MINAS GERAIS	B3
0101-7160	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL DE CONTAS DO ESTADO DO PARANÁ	B4

0103-7978	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL SUPERIOR DO TRABALHO	B4
2184-206X	REVISTA DOBRA	B3
2237-5864	REVISTA DOCÊNCIA DO ENSINO SUPERIOR	B2
2594-9004	REVISTA DOCÊNCIA E CIBERCULTURA	B4
2526-4923	REVISTA DOCENTES	A4
2594-8601	REVISTA DOCOMOMO BRASIL	B4
2220-2692	REVISTA DOMINICANA DE ECONOMÍA	B4
1806-0013	REVISTA DOR	A3
2317-6393	REVISTA DOR	A3
0102-7212	REVISTA DOS TRANSPORTES PÚBLICOS	B4
0034-9275	REVISTA DOS TRIBUNAIS (SÃO PAULO. IMPRESSO)	B1
1415-630X	REVISTA DOS TRIBUNAIS. CADERNOS DE DIREITO CONSTITUCIONAL	B4
1415-6296	REVISTA DOS TRIBUNAIS. CADERNOS DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO E FIN.	B4
2318-4922	REVISTA E-CIÊNCIA	B4
1984-6606	REVISTA ECONOMIA & GESTÃO	A4
1390-7921	REVISTA ECONOMÍA Y POLÍTICA	B3
0100-4956	REVISTA ECONÔMICA DO NORDESTE	A4
2357-9226	REVISTA ECONÔMICA DO NORDESTE	A4
2316-2600	REVISTA ECOPOLÍTICA	B3
2175-8689	REVISTA ECO-PÓS (ONLINE)	A2
1806-0331	REVISTA ECOS (CÁCERES)	A2
1809-3876	REVISTA E-CURRICULUM (PUCSP)	A2
2176-171X	REVISTA EDAPECI: EDUCAÇÃO A DISTÂNCIA E PRÁTICAS EDUCATIVA	B4
2236-5753	REVISTA EDICIC	B4
2358-4521	REVISTA EDUC- FACULDADE DE DUQUE DE CAXIAS	B4
2007-1930	REVISTA EDUC@RNOS	B2
2177-2185	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO	B4
2358-4319	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO & EMANCIPAÇÃO	B1
2448-3583	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO & FORMAÇÃO	B1
2179-6122	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO & TECNOLOGIA	B4
1980-6469	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO (GUARULHOS)	B2
2237-258X	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO E FRONTEIRAS ON-LINE	B2
2359-277X	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO E LINGUAGEM	B2
2238-6084	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO E LINGUAGENS	A3
2526-0847	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO EM DEBATE	B3
1981-1802	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO EM QUESTÃO (ONLINE)	A2
1984-686X	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO ESPECIAL (ONLINE)	A2
2525-5932	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO ESPECIAL EM DEBATE	B3
2526-6276	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO GEOGRÁFICA EM FOCO	B2
2179-7374	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO GRÁFICA	A3
2594-7990	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO INCLUSIVA	B4
1984-6290	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO PÚBLICA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	B4
2238-2097	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO PÚBLICA DA UFMT	A2
1984-3178	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO, ARTES E INCLUSÃO	B2
1983-0173	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO, MEIO AMBIENTE E SAÚDE	B4
2594-5343	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO, PSICOLOGIA E INTERFACES	B4
0798-1228	REVISTA EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR Y SOCIEDAD	B2
2011-5318	REVISTA EDUCACIÓN Y DESARROLLO SOCIAL	B2
2445-4109	REVISTA EDUCACIÓN, POLÍTICA Y SOCIEDAD	B2
1983-3423	REVISTA EDUCAMAZÔNIA - EDUCAÇÃO SOCIEDADE E MEIO AMBIEN	B3

1983-2664	REVISTA EDUCAONLINE	B2
2237-9185	REVISTA EDUCAR MAIS (ONLINE)	B1
2178-5236	REVISTA EDUCATIVA	B1
1794-1237	REVISTA EIA	B3
2238-9504	REVISTA EIXO	B3
2238-5630	REVISTA EIXO	B3
2316-4417	REVISTA EJA EM DEBATE	B3
2362-5813	REVISTA EL TACO EN LA BREA	A3
2182-9845	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE DIREITO	B2
2310-0036	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	A4
1607-4041	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EDUCATIVA	A1
1850-6666	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN EDUCACIÓN EN CIENI	A2
1989-2446	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y DOCENCIA	A4
1870-8420	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE PSICOLOGÍA IZTACALA	B3
1669-3582	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE PSICOLOGÍA POLÍTICA (EN LÍNEA)	B3
1695-7504	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE VETERINARIA	B4
1696-4713	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA IBEROAMERICANA SOBRE CALIDAD, EFICACI	B1
1575-0965	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA INTERUNIVERSITARIA DE FORMACIÓN DEL P	A4
2178-2091	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ACERVO SAÚDE	B2
1981-4127	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA AMBIENTE: GESTÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B3
1984-4735	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ARMA DA CRÍTICA	B4
2595-5888	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA CASA DE MAKUNAIMA	B3
2448-0479	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA CIENTÍFICA DA UERGS	B1
2358-7083	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA CIENTÍFICA DO CRA-PR	B1
2447-0783	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA CIENTÍFICA ENSINO INTERDISCIPLINAR	A4
2448-0452	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA COMPETÊNCIAS DIGITAIS PARA AGRICULTUR/	B2
2176-6231	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA COMTEMPO	B4
2177-8256	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO CONST	B1
1679-1061	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA ANPHLAC	A3
1808-2653	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO DOS GEÓGRAFOS BRASILEIRI	B4
2595-4598	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA ESA/RS	B4
1983-4225	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DE FRANCA	B4
1981-0377	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FACULDADE METODISTA GRANBERY	B4
2594-4479	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA UNIVERSIDADE SANT	B4
2236-451X	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIA POLÍTICA	A3
2175-7283	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	B4
1678-8729	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE DIREITO DO CENTRO UNIVERSITÁRIO NEW	B1
1982-7636	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE DIREITO PROCESSUAL	B1
1982-7199	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE EDUCAÇÃO (SÃO CARLOS)	A2
2236-8779	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE EDUCAÇÃO DA FACULDADE ARAGUAIA - R	B4
1518-1944	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ENFERMAGEM	B1
1984-3372	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ESTRATÉGIA E NEGÓCIOS	A3
1980-8372	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ESTUDOS HEGELIANOS	B1
2316-6223	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ESTUDOS JURÍDICOS E DA SOCIEDADE	B4
2317-563X	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE GESTÃO E TECNOLOGIAS AMBIENTAIS	B2
2179-474X	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE INCIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA TECNOLÓGICA E ART	B1
1809-8797	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE MATERIAIS E PROCESSOS (UFCG)	B4
2238-2216	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE PESQUISA DA UNIRP - UNIVERSITAS	B3
1984-557X	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE POTÊNCIA	A4
1677-3071	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO (RESI)	B3

2237-0072	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO E GESTÃO TEC	B3
2236-2150	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DEBATES EM EDUCAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA E TECNO	A4
1980-7791	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DIREITO E POLÍTICA	A4
2317-6989	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DISCENTE HISTÓRIA.COM	B2
1981-3694	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DA UFSM	A1
2446-9513	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO DEPARTAMENTO DE CIÊNCIAS CONTÁBEIS	B2
1678-3182	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO INSTITUTO DE HUMANIDADES	B3
1517-1256	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO MESTRADO EM EDUCAÇÃO AMBIENTAL	A4
2316-6681	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO MESTRADO PROFISSIONAL EM ENGENHAF	B4
2176-5804	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DOCUMENTO/MONUMENTO	B3
2236-1170	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA EM GESTÃO, EDUCAÇÃO E TECNOLOGIA AMB	A4
1983-1617	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ESTÁCIO SAÚDE	B4
1984-0519	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA FRONTISTÉS	B4
1982-4785	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA GESTÃO & SAÚDE	B3
2177-7284	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA GESTÃO E SERVIÇOS	B1
1981-2434	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA HISTÓRIA EM REFLEXÃO (UFGD)	A3
2594-7664	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA INTERAÇÕES SOCIAIS	B4
2237-8588	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA JUDICARE	B4
2527-2624	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA LUDUS SCIENTIAE	A3
2178-9568	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA MACHADO SOBRINHO	B3
1984-4204	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA MESTRADO EM ADMINISTRAÇÃO	B1
2316-2317	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA MULTIDISCIPLINAR FACEAR	B4
2178-7018	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA MUTAÇÕES	B3
2237-4779	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ORGANIZAÇÕES E SOCIEDADE	B3
2178-3039	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA PEDAGOGIA EM FOCO (ITURAMA - MG)	A3
2177-7748	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA SABERES DA EDUCAÇÃO	B4
2316-7297	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA SALA DE AULA EM FOCO	B4
2238-1910	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA SCIENTIA AMAZÔNIA	B4
9729-6465	REVISTA ELO	B4
2447-7648	REVISTA EM GESTÃO, INOVAÇÃO E SUSTENTABILIDADE	B4
2595-5543	REVISTA EMPREENDA UNITOLEDO	B4
2595-1963	REVISTA EMPREERDER E INOVAR	B4
2359-6082	REVISTA EMREDE - REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO À DISTÂNCIA	B4
2177-160X	REVISTA ENBORNAL	B4
1983-828X	REVISTA ENCONTROS DE VISTA	B3
2526-6578	REVISTA ENCONTROS UNIVERSITÁRIOS DA UFC	B4
1692-5858	REVISTA ENCUESTROS	A2
2317-3378	REVISTA ENFERMAGEM CONTEMPORÂNEA	B3
0104-3552	REVISTA ENFERMAGEM UERJ	A4
1998-5487	REVISTA ENFERMERÍA HEREDIANA	B4
1678-1813	REVISTA ENFOQUES (RIO DE JANEIRO)	A4
2236-4757	REVISTA ENGRENAGEM	B2
2316-2341	REVISTA ENIAC PESQUISA	B2
2177-4994	REVISTA ENSAIOS FILOSÓFICOS	B3
2179-4510	REVISTA ENSINO DE GEOGRAFIA	B1
2594-9616	REVISTA ENSINO DE GEOGRAFIA (RECIFE)	A4
2317-1219	REVISTA ENTREIDEIAS: EDUCAÇÃO, CULTURA E SOCIEDADE	B1
2178-9479	REVISTA ENTRELETRAS	B3
2179-3948	REVISTA ENTRELETRAS (ARAGUAÍNA: UFT)	B3
2447-3529	REVISTA ENTRELÍNGUAS	A3

2176-9559	REVISTA ENTRE-LUGAR	A3
2595-3753	REVISTA ENTRERIOS	B4
2527-080X	REVISTA ÉPICAS	B1
2318-8855	REVISTA EPÍGRAFE	B4
2236-2649	REVISTA EPISTEME TRANSVERSALIS	A4
2526-7655	REVISTA EPISTEMOLOGIAS DO SUL	B4
2178-700X	REVISTA EPOS (ELETRÔNICA)	B2
2182-7591	REVISTA E-PSI	B2
2317-3491	REVISTA EQUADOR (UFPI)	A4
2446-5674	REVISTA EQUATORIAL - REVISTA DOS ALUNOS DO PROGRAMA DE P	B3
2357-7509	REVISTA ESCOLA DE NEGÓCIOS	B4
1679-6888	REVISTA ESCRITA (PUCRJ. ONLINE)	B3
2359-0238	REVISTA ESCRITA DA HISTÓRIA	A4
2177-6288	REVISTA E-SCRITA: REVISTA DO CURSO DE LETRAS DA UNIABEU	A3
2316-7122	REVISTA ESFERAS	B1
2177-0360	REVISTA ESMAT	B3
2177-0260	REVISTA ESMAT	B3
2447-9896	REVISTA ESMAT (ON LINE)	B3
2236-1367	REVISTA ESPAÇO ABERTO	A2
1519-6186	REVISTA ESPAÇO ACADÊMICO (UEM)	A4
1981-3007	REVISTA ESPAÇO CIÊNCIA & SAÚDE (UNICRUZ)	B3
1983-1579	REVISTA ESPAÇO DO CURRÍCULO (ONLINE)	A4
2238-0302	REVISTA ESPAÇO PEDAGÓGICO	A4
2595-5535	REVISTA ESPAÇO PÚBLICO	B4
1885-5857	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE CARDIOLOGÍA (INTERNET. ENGLISH ED.)	A4
1130-0558	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE CIRUGÍA ORAL Y MAXILOFACIAL	B3
1137-8875	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE DESARROLLO Y COOPERACIÓN	B1
0210-0614	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE DOCUMENTACIÓN CIENTÍFICA	A3
1130-0108	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE ENFERMEDADES DIGESTIVAS	B2
1575-1198	REVISTA ESPANOLA DE ESTUDIOS AGROSOCIALES Y PESQUEROS	B3
0211-139X	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE GERIATRÍA Y GERONTOLOGÍA (ED. IMPRESA)	B2
2173-1292	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE NUTRICIÓN HUMANA Y DIETÉTICA (ACTIVIDAD)	B3
1575-0620	REVISTA ESPAÑOLA DE SANIDAD PENITENCIARIA	B1
1578-2824	REVISTA ESPANOLA DE SOCIOLOGIA	B1
2317-0611	REVISTA ESPINHAÇO	B2
2594-9721	REVISTA ESPIRALES	B4
1983-1595	REVISTA ESTÁCIO PAPIRUS (FESSC)	B4
2413-8274	REVISTA ESTADO Y POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	A2
2310-550X	REVISTA ESTADO Y POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	A2
2238-362X	REVISTA ESTÉTICA E SEMIÓTICA	B2
1019-4355	REVISTA ESTOMATOLÓGICA HEREDIANA	B2
2183-4075	REVISTA ESTRANHAR PESSOA	B1
2526-9526	REVISTA ESTRATÉGIA E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B4
2526-2432	REVISTA ESTRUTURA	B3
1405-9436	REVISTA ESTUDIOS DE GENERO LA VENTANA	B2
0719-6296	REVISTA ESTUDIOS DE POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	B3
2448-3389	REVISTA ESTUDOS ANGLO-AMERICANOS	B1
2525-703X	REVISTA ESTUDOS APLICADOS EM EDUCAÇÃO	B2
2182-7044	REVISTA ESTUDOS DE JORNALISMO	B2
2595-9018	REVISTA ESTUDOS DE PLANEJAMENTO	B4

2594-7559	REVISTA ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS EM ADMINISTRAÇÃO	B4
2177-2967	REVISTA ESTUDOS FILOSÓFICOS	B4
2177-1006	REVISTA ESTUDOS HUM(E)ANOS	B3
2447-5467	REVISTA ESTUDOS INSTITUCIONAIS	B1
2177-2851	REVISTA ESTUDOS POLÍTICOS	A4
2177-5788	REVISTA ESTUDOS UNIVERSITÁRIOS	B2
1665-2703	REVISTA ETNOBIOLOGÍA	A3
1697-011X	REVISTA EUREKA SOBRE ENSEÑANZA Y DIVULGACIÓN DE LAS CIENC	A1
2387-1555	REVISTA EUROAMERICANA DE ANTROPOLOGIA	B1
2362-583X	REVISTA EUROLATINOAMERICANA DE DERECHO ADMINISTRATIVO	B3
2174-0135	REVISTA EUROPEA DE HISTORIA DE LAS IDEAS POLÍTICAS Y DE LAS II	B3
2236-3165	REVISTA EVENTOS PEDAGÓGICOS	B2
2318-1001	REVISTA EVIDENCIAÇÃO CONTÁBIL & FINANÇAS	A3
2237-9460	REVISTA EXITUS.	A4
1676-045X	REVISTA EXPECTATIVA (IMPRESSO)	B2
2237-8782	REVISTA EXPRESSÃO CATÓLICA	B3
2357-8483	REVISTA EXPRESSÃO CATÓLICA (ONLINE)	B3
2236-6784	REVISTA EXTENSÃO	B4
2319-0566	REVISTA EXTENSÃO & CIDADANIA	B3
2178-6054	REVISTA EXTENSÃO E SOCIEDADE	B4
2316-400X	REVISTA EXTENSÃO EM AÇÃO	B2
2317-9791	REVISTA EXTENSÃO EM FOCO	B3
2236-3467	REVISTA EXTRAPRENSA	B2
0874-6885	REVISTA FACES DE EVA. ESTUDOS SOBRE A MULHER	A3
2238-8524	REVISTA FACISA ON-LINE	B1
2526-2629	REVISTA FACTHUS DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E GESTÃO	B4
1519-5104	REVISTA FACULDADE DE DIREITO PUCSP	B4
0121-6805	REVISTA FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS ECONÓMICAS: INVESTIGACIÓN Y R	B1
0120-6230	REVISTA FACULTAD DE INGENIERÍA UNIVERSIDAD DE ANTIOQUIA	B3
0304-2847	REVISTA FACULTAD NACIONAL DE AGRONOMIA	B3
2178-7476	REVISTA FAED - UNEMAT	B2
0104-7043	REVISTA FAEIBA	A2
1980-3729	REVISTA FAMECOS (ONLINE)	A2
2318-8413	REVISTA FAMÍLIA, CICLOS DE VIDA E SAÚDE NO CONTEXTO SOCIAL	B1
1807-9660	REVISTA FAROL	B4
2358-9817	REVISTA FATEC SEBRAE EM DEBATE: GESTÃO, TECNOLOGIAS E NEG	B3
2317-2932	REVISTA FEMINISMOS	A4
2236-000X	REVISTA FEOL	B3
2236-2037	REVISTA FEVEREIRO - POLÍTICA, TEORIA, CULTURA	B2
2177-1383	REVISTA FIDES	B1
2176-9419	REVISTA FILOGIA E LINGÜÍSTICA PORTUGUESA (VERSÃO ELETRÔN	A2
1982-6613	REVISTA FILOSOFIA CAPITAL	B3
0872-0851	REVISTA FILOSÓFICA DE COIMBRA	B1
1984-1728	REVISTA FILOSÓFICA SÃO BOAVENTURA	B4
2236-5109	REVISTA FOCANDO A EXTENSÃO	B4
2447-0120	REVISTA FOLHA DE ROSTO	B2
2595-9778	REVISTA FONTES DOCUMENTAIS	B3
0102-8413	REVISTA FORENSE (IMPRESSO)	B4
1678-6777	REVISTA FORENSE ELETRÔNICA (CD-ROM)	B4
2215-2504	REVISTA FORESTAL MESOAMERICANA KURU	B1

1806-5457	REVISTA FORMADORES (ONLINE)	B3
2526-7507	REVISTA FORPROLL	B4
2319-0795	REVISTA FÓRUM DE CIÊNCIAS CRIMINAIS	B4
1982-3916	REVISTA FÓRUM IDENTIDADES	A3
1518-6113	REVISTA FRONTEIRA	A3
2317-2983	REVISTA FSA (FACULDADE SANTO AGOSTINHO) (ONLINE)	B2
1806-6356	REVISTA FSA: PERIÓDICO CIENTÍFICO DA FACULDADE SANTO AGOST	B2
2526-5628	REVISTA FUNEC CIENTÍFICA	B4
2526-897X	REVISTA GAE-OMAM	B4
1132-8932	REVISTA GALEGA DE EDUCACIÓN - PUBLICACIÓN DE NOVA ESCOLA	B1
2182-8539	REVISTA GAMA	B1
1809-2586	REVISTA GARRAFA (PPGL/UFRJ)	A4
0102-6933	REVISTA GAÚCHA DE ENFERMAGEM (UFRGS. IMPRESSO)	A2
2447-0740	REVISTA GEAMA (ONLINE)	B1
2357-9854	REVISTA GEARTE	A4
1982-3266	REVISTA GEDECON	B4
2237-0722	REVISTA GEINTEC: GESTÃO, INOVAÇÃO E TECNOLOGIAS	B2
2179-1465	REVISTA GEMINIS	A4
1886-6212	REVISTA GENERAL DE DERECHO CONSTITUCIONAL (INTERNET)	A4
1698-1189	REVISTA GENERAL DE DERECHO PENAL	B2
1132-1873	REVISTA GENERAL DE INFORMACIÓN Y DOCUMENTACIÓN	B2
2316-1108	REVISTA GÊNERO	A4
2358-1778	REVISTA GEOAMAZÔNIA	B3
2236-9716	REVISTA GEOARAGUAIA	A4
1981-089X	REVISTA GEOGRAFAR (UFPR)	B1
1982-9760	REVISTA GEOGRAFIA E PESQUISA	B3
2594-9632	REVISTA GEOGRAFIA, LITERATURA E ARTE	B2
1678-7226	REVISTA GEOGRÁFICA ACADÊMICA	B3
1012-1617	REVISTA GEOGRÁFICA VENEZOLANA	B3
2238-0205	REVISTA GEOGRAFICIDADE - UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL FLUMINENSE	B1
2595-0797	REVISTA GEOMETRIA GRÁFICA	B4
1517-4999	REVISTA GEOPANTANAL	B2
2446-8681	REVISTA GEOPANTANAL	B2
2527-2349	REVISTA GEOPOLÍTICA TRANSFRONTEIRIÇA	B3
2525-5703	REVISTA GEOSERTÕES	B1
2315-028X	REVISTA GEOUECE	B4
1657-7027	REVISTA GERENCIA Y POLITICA DE SALUD	B3
2237-1095	REVISTA GESTÃO & POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	B4
2238-8753	REVISTA GESTÃO & SUSTENTABILIDADE AMBIENTAL	B1
1677-9479	REVISTA GESTÃO & TECNOLOGIA	A3
2526-8384	REVISTA GESTÃO DO CONHECIMENTO E TECNOLOGIA DA INFORMA	B4
1677-9762	REVISTA GESTÃO E CONHECIMENTO	B4
2526-2289	REVISTA GESTÃO E ORGANIZAÇÕES (REGOR)	B3
1984-7297	REVISTA GESTÃO EM ANÁLISE	B3
2177-1243	REVISTA GESTÃO PÚBLICA: PRÁTICAS E DESAFIOS.	B4
1983-4535	REVISTA GESTÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA NA AMÉRICA LATINA - GUAL	B1
2318-4981	REVISTA GESTÃO, SUSTENTABILIDADE E NEGÓCIOS	B4
2358-0216	REVISTA GESTO	B3
2595-9832	REVISTA GPES - ESTUDOS SURDOS	B4
2236-3335	REVISTA GRADUANDO	B3

2175-0157	REVISTA GRIFOS	B3
2447-9551	REVISTA GTLEX	B3
1809-7065	REVISTA HABITUS	B4
2362-2784	REVISTA HACHE	B2
2446-7154	REVISTA HIPÓTESE	B2
1676-2584	REVISTA HISTEDBR ON-LINE	A3
1808-091X	REVISTA HISTÓRIA & LUTA DE CLASSES	B2
2522-3690	REVISTA HISTORIA DE LAS MUJERES	A4
2237-6569	REVISTA HISTÓRIA E DIVERSIDADE	B3
1806-3993	REVISTA HISTÓRIA HOJE	A3
2176-1116	REVISTA HISTORIADOR	B4
2176-3267	REVISTA HISTORIAR - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO CURSO DE HISTÓRIA	B3
1982-3800	REVISTA HOMEM, ESPAÇO E TEMPO	B3
2526-3846	REVISTA HON NO MUSHI	B3
2317-109X	REVISTA HORIZONTES	A4
1807-975X	REVISTA HOSPITALIDADE	A4
1517-7602	REVISTA HUMANA E (RECIFE)	B3
2343-6441	REVISTA HUMANARTES (PRINT)	B4
2236-4358	REVISTA HÚMUS	A4
2447-942X	REVISTA HYDRA	B1
2594-973X	REVISTA ÎANDÉ: CIÊNCIAS E HUMANIDADES	B4
1135-3848	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE DIAGNÓSTICO Y EVALUACIÓN PSICOLÓGICA	A3
2154-4794	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA	B3
2172-8801	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE ARGUMENTACIÓN	A3
1697-7912	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE AUTOMÁTICA E INFORMÁTICA INDUSTRIAL	B3
1983-5213	REVISTA IBERO-AMERICANA DE CIÊNCIA DA INFORMAÇÃO	B1
1850-0013	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE CIENCIA TECNOLOGÍA Y SOCIEDAD (IBEROTECH)	A2
2179-6858	REVISTA IBERO-AMERICANA DE CIÊNCIAS AMBIENTAIS	B1
1696-294X	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE CONTABILIDAD DE GESTIÓN	B4
2358-7156	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE DERECHO PROCESAL	B2
1390-2776	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE ECONOMÍA ECOLÓGICA	A4
1681-5653	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN (ONLINE)	A2
1138-2783	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN A DISTANCIA	B1
2174-6915	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN E INVESTIGACIÓN EN EDUCACIÓN	B3
2007-2872	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR (RIES)	A2
2176-0756	REVISTA IBERO-AMERICANA DE ESTRATÉGIA RIAE	A3
0719-1790	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS MUNICIPALES	B2
2446-8606	REVISTA IBERO-AMERICANA DE ESTUDOS EM EDUCAÇÃO	A2
1989-0397	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE EVALUACIÓN EDUCATIVA	A4
1130-1406	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE MICOLOGÍA	B2
1886-8576	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE PSICOLOGÍA DEL EJERCICIO Y EL DEPORTE	B1
2027-1786	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE PSICOLOGÍA: CIENCIA Y TECNOLOGÍA	B3
1690-8627	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE SISTEMAS, CIBERNÉTICA E INFORMÁTICA	B4
1850-9959	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE TECNOLOGIA EN EDUCACIÓN Y EDUCACIÓN	A4
1665-0204	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE TECNOLOGIA POSTCOSECHA	B4
2236-6040	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE TURISMO	B3
1983-4195	REVISTA IBRACON DE ESTRUTURAS E MATERIAIS	A3
2359-6384	REVISTA IDEAÇÃO	B1
2526-3552	REVISTA IDEALOGANDO	B3
2177-4099	REVISTA IDÉIAS	B4

1548-0992	REVISTA IEEE AMÉRICA LATINA	B2
1984-8625	REVISTA ILUMINART	B4
2237-6933	REVISTA IMAGINÁRIO	B4
1852-9550	REVISTA IMAGOFAGIA	A3
2174-2464	REVISTA IMPOSSIBILIA	A4
0719-4706	REVISTA INCLUSIONES - REVISTA DE HUMANIDADES Y CIENCIAS SOC	A2
2318-8138	REVISTA INCONFIDENTIA	B4
2525-3263	REVISTA INDISCIPLINAR	A3
0719-6202	REVISTA INFANCIA, EDUCACIÓN Y APRENDIZAJE	B4
2525-3204	REVISTA INFINITY	B1
2447-0198	REVISTA INFORMAÇÃO NA SOCIEDADE CONTEMPORÂNEA	B2
1909-9762	REVISTA INGENIERÍA BIOMÉDICA	B4
2594-8288	REVISTA INGI	B4
2359-2265	REVISTA ININGA	A4
2175-8247	REVISTA INNOVARE	B4
2447-598X	REVISTA INOVA CIÊNCIA & TECNOLOGIA / INNOVATIVE SCIENCE & T	B4
1980-1378	REVISTA INOVAÇÃO (FAPEMA)	B2
2318-9851	REVISTA INOVAÇÃO, PROJETOS E TECNOLOGIAS	B3
2595-4520	REVISTA INSIGNARE SCIENTIA	A4
1015-5074	REVISTA INSTITUTO INTERAMERICANO DE DERECHOS HUMANOS	B1
2179-6572	REVISTA INTEGRATIVA EM SAÚDE E EDUCAÇÃO (REVISE)	B4
2236-210X	REVISTA INTELIGÊNCIA COMPETITIVA	B3
2178-1842	REVISTA INTER AÇÃO	B2
2526-9550	REVISTA INTERAÇÃO INTERDISCIPLINAR	B4
1809-5771	REVISTA INTERAGIR	B3
0120-0976	REVISTA INTERAMERICANA DE BIBLIOTECOLOGIA	A3
0188-8838	REVISTA INTERAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN DE ADULTOS - RIEDA	B2
1980-3575	REVISTA INTERATIVIDADE	B4
1982-8640	REVISTA INTERCÂMBIO DOS CONGRESSOS INTERNACIONAIS DE HUI	B3
2237-3373	REVISTA INTERCONTINENTAL DE GESTÃO DESPORTIVA	B2
1983-9413	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR	B3
2317-5079	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR (ONLINE)	B3
2526-3951	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS	B4
2237-9843	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DA MOBILIDADE HUMANA	A2
1518-8167	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE DIREITO	B4
2447-4290	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE DIREITO DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO	B4
2318-9568	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE DIREITOS HUMANOS	B2
2358-6036	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE ENSINO, PESQUISA E EXTENSÃO	B3
2318-2393	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE ESTUDOS CONTEMPORÂNEOS	B3
2238-832X	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE ESTUDOS EM SAÚDE	B2
2317-2428	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE GESTÃO SOCIAL	A4
2447-2948	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE PESQUISA E INOVAÇÃO	A2
2447-5955	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE TECNOLOGIAS E EDUCAÇÃO	B3
2446-6778	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DO PENSAMENTO CIENTÍFICO	B4
2447-6498	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR EM CULTURA E SOCIEDADE	B3
2358-7490	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR EM SAÚDE	B4
2595-0959	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR ENCONTRO DAS CIÊNCIAS - RIEC	B4
2595-8569	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR SULEAR	B4
1853-399X	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINARIA DE ESTUDIOS AGRARIOS	B3
1853-1679	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINARIA DE ESTUDIOS SOCIALES	B3

1617-6871	REVISTA INTERESSE PÚBLICO	B1
1518-6768	REVISTA INTERFACE	B2
2176-5227	REVISTA INTERFACES	B4
2317-434X	REVISTA INTERFACES - SAÚDE, HUMANAS E TECNOLOGIA	B4
1516-0033	REVISTA INTERFACES (UFRJ)	B3
2179-0027	REVISTA INTERFACES (UNICENTRO)	A3
2316-3348	REVISTA INTERFACES CIENTÍFICAS - HUMANAS E SOCIAIS	B2
2359-4942	REVISTA INTERFACES CIENTÍFICAS ç EXATAS E TECNOLÓGICAS	B3
2447-7915	REVISTA INTERFACIS	B3
2359-6856	REVISTA INTERINSTITUCIONAL ARTES DE EDUCAR	B1
2183-6396	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL CONSINTER DE DIREITO	B4
1887-8369	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE ACUPUNTURA	B3
2387-0907	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE APOYO A LA INCLUSIÓN, LOGOPEDIA, ...	B3
2386-7582	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE APRENDIZAJE EN LA EDUCACIÓN SUPE	B1
1885-3137	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE CIENCIAS DEL DEPORTE	B1
0379-0762	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES (IMPRESA)	B4
2386-3730	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE COMUNICACIÓN Y DESARROLLO	B1
0188-4999	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE CONTAMINACIÓN AMBIENTAL	B2
2382-5014	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE COOPERACIÓN Y DESARROLLO	B2
2238-2569	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE DIREITO AMBIENTAL	A4
2595-6329	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCAÇÃO DE JOVENS E ADULTOS	B3
2446-9424	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCAÇÃO SUPERIOR	A3
2255-453X	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCACION Y APRENDIZAJE	B4
2173-1950	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE ESTUDIOS MIGRATORIOS	B2
1807-4960	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE FOLKCOMUNICAÇÃO	B2
2447-8288	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE FORMAÇÃO DE PROFESSORES (RIPF)	B3
2255-5129	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE HISTORIA DE LA COMUNICACIÓN	B2
2225-5117	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B2
2226-4000	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B2
1579-9425	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE LINGÜÍSTICA IBEROAMERICANA	A4
1577-0354	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE MEDICINA Y CIENCIAS DE LA ACTIVIDA	B2
0213-1315	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE MÉTODOS NUMÉRICOS PARA CÁLCULO	B1
1886-158X	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE MÉTODOS NUMÉRICOS PARA EL CÁLCULO	B1
2238-0345	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE PESQUISA EM EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	B2
1577-7057	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE PSICOLOGIA Y TERAPIA PSICOLOGICA	A2
2174-3681	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE RELACIONES PUBLICAS	A2
2174-8985	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE TECNOLOGIA, CONOCIMIENTO Y SOCIEDAD	B4
1516-5485	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL D'HUMANITATS	B4
2182-4452	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL EM LINGUA PORTUGUESA	B3
1692-4053	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL MAGISTERIO: EDUCACION Y PEDAGOGIA	B3
2525-7668	REVISTA INTERTERRITÓRIOS	B3
2526-396X	REVISTA INTOLERÂNCIA RELIGIOSA	B4
2176-6789	REVISTA INTRATEXTOS	B3
0874-7695	REVISTA INVESTIGAÇÃO EM ENFERMAGEM	B4
2145-8480	REVISTA ION	B3
2359-5078	REVISTA IPECEGE	B3
2358-3630	REVISTA IPH	B2
1983-4810	REVISTA JESUS HISTÓRICO	A4
2526-2440	REVISTA JORNALISMO E CIDADANIA	B3
2237-048X	REVISTA JOVENS PESQUISADORES	B1

2316-753X	REVISTA JURÍDICA - UNICURITIBA	A1
1982-4858	REVISTA JURÍDICA (FURB. ONLINE)	A4
0103-3379	REVISTA JURIDICA (PORTO ALEGRE. 1953)	B4
2176-9184	REVISTA JURÍDICA CESUMAR: MESTRADO (ONLINE)	B1
2316-6959	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA ESCOLA SUPERIOR DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO I	B2
2447-9055	REVISTA JURIDICA DA FA7 (ONLINE)	B1
2236-3645	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA PRESIDÊNCIA	A2
1984-512X	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA SEÇÃO JUDICIÁRIA DE PERNAMBUCO	B4
1519-1753	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA UNIVERSIDADE DE CUIABÁ	B4
2526-9267	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA UNOPAR	B4
2177-224X	REVISTA JURÍDICA FADEP	B4
2183-539X	REVISTA JURÍDICA LUSO BRASILEIRA	B1
2357-7940	REVISTA JURIS	B4
1517-7327	REVISTA JUSTIÇA ELEITORAL EM DEBATE	B4
1516-2567	REVISTA KAIRÓS	A3
1982-0259	REVISTA KATALYSIS	A1
2027-2391	REVISTA KAVILANDO	B2
2526-2688	REVISTA KIRI-KERÊ - PESQUISA EM ENSINO	B4
1983-5000	REVISTA LABOR	B2
2316-6746	REVISTA LABORATIVA	B2
0718-7467	REVISTA LABORATÓRIO LITERATURA E EXPERIMENTACIÓN	B1
2526-0707	REVISTA LABORATÓRIOS DE HISTÓRIA	B4
1794-4449	REVISTA LASALLISTA DE INVESTIGACION	B3
1138-5820	REVISTA LATINA DE COMUNICACIÓN SOCIAL	A3
2253-6469	REVISTA LATINA DE SOCIOLOGIA	B2
2527-0184	REVISTA LATINO AMERICANA EM AVALIAÇÃO DO CICLO DE VIDA	B4
2591-2755	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA DEL TRABAJO	B2
1657-4702	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE BIOETICA	A4
2462-859X	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE BIOETICA	A4
1807-3026	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE CIENCIAS DE LA COMUNICACIÓN	A4
2238-1694	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE CIENCIAS DE LA COMUNICACIÓN O	A4
2027-7679	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES	A3
1692-715X	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE CIENCIAS SOCIALES, NIÑEZ Y JUVEN	A3
0719-7160	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE DERECHO Y RELIGIÓN	B1
1806-7573	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE EDUCAÇÃO EM ASTRONOMIA	B4
1853-3744	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN COMPARADA	B3
1518-8345	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE ENFERMAGEM (ONLINE)	A2
1405-1311	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS DEL TRABAJO	B2
1856-8378	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS DEL TRABAJO	B2
0185-1284	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS EDUCATIVOS	A4
2525-1635	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS RURALES	B2
1852-8759	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS SOBRE CUERPOS, EMOC	A2
2447-9543	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE ESTUDOS DO DISCURSO	A1
0325-0725	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE FILOSOFÍA	B1
2177-2886	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE GEOGRAFIA E GÊNERO	A2
2238-0620	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE HISTÓRIA	A4
2409-1308	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE INVESTIGACIÓN CRÍTICA	B2
2007-6819	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN MATEMÁTICA I	A1
1853-4961	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE LA PAPA	B4
0255-6952	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE METALURGIA Y MATERIALES	B2

1853-6190	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE METODOLOGÍA DE LA INVESTIGACI	B2
1853-7863	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE METODOLOGÍA EN CIENCIAS SOCIA	B4
2175-8581	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE POBLACIÓN	B1
2408-4573	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE POLÍTICAS Y ADMINISTRACIÓN DE I	B3
0120-0534	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE PSICOLOGIA	A2
2357-9692	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE PSICOLOGIA CORPORAL (ONLINE)	B4
1853-3051	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE PSICOLOGIA EXISTENCIAL	B4
0719-4420	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE PSICOLOGÍA POSITIVA	B4
1415-4714	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE PSICOPATOLOGIA FUNDAMENTAL	A2
1695-288X	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE TECNOLOGÍA EDUCATIVA	A2
2175-2990	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE TELESSAÚDE	B4
0259-9872	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE TEOLOGÍA	B3
2448-198X	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE TURISMOLOGIA	B2
0719-8310	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DO COLÉGIO INTERNACIONAL DE FILO	B1
2317-9945	REVISTA LEITURA (ONLINE)	B3
2448-4482	REVISTA LETRA CAPITAL	B3
2236-0999	REVISTA LETRAS	A2
2176-1485	REVISTA LETRAS (UFSM/ON-LINE)	A2
2317-2347	REVISTA LETRAS RARAS	A3
1983-2192	REVISTA LEVS (MARÍLIA)	B4
2175-5280	REVISTA LIBERDADES	B3
2319-0159	REVISTA LIBERTAS	B1
2179-5975	REVISTA LICEU ON-LINE	B4
2520-9795	REVISTA LIDERA	B4
2318-423X	REVISTA LIMIAR	B1
1984-381X	REVISTA LÍNGUA & LITERATURA (ONLINE)	B1
1983-2400	REVISTA LINGUAGEM & ENSINO (ONLINE)	A2
2448-4520	REVISTA LINGUAGENS & LETRAMENTOS	B3
2238-975X	REVISTA LINGUÍSTICA	A2
2358-6826	REVISTA LINGUÍSTICA RIO	B2
1851-8931	REVISTA LIS - LETRA, IMAGEN, SONIDO (1851-8931)	B4
2237-6291	REVISTA LITTERARIUS	B2
1983-7429	REVISTA LITTERIS	B2
2357-8807	REVISTA LIVRE DE CINEMA	B2
2448-2889	REVISTA LIVRE DE SUSTENTABILIDADE E EMPREENDEDORISMO	B3
2316-9923	REVISTA LOGOS E EXISTÊNCIA	B2
2027-1557	REVISTA LUCÍERNAGA	B1
2462-845X	REVISTA LÚDICA PEDAGÓGICA	B4
2447-8717	REVISTA LUMEN	B2
1645-7250	REVISTA LUSÓFONA DE EDUCAÇÃO	A1
2183-0886	REVISTA LUSÓFONA DE ESTUDOS CULTURAI	A3
1692-5114	REVISTA M	A4
2525-3050	REVISTA M. ESTUDOS SOBRE A MORTE, OS MORTOS E O MORRER	A4
2594-5084	REVISTA MACHADIANA ELETRÔNICA	B3
2528-8091	REVISTA MAGAZINE DE LAS CIENCIAS	A3
2175-1994	REVISTA MAGISTER DE DIREITO AMBIENTAL E URBANÍSTICO	B2
1807-0930	REVISTA MAGISTER DE DIREITO CIVIL E PROCESSUAL CIVIL	B1
2236-7810	REVISTA MAGISTER DE DIREITO DO TRABALHO	B1
1807-3395	REVISTA MAGISTER DE DIREITO PENAL E PROCESSUAL PENAL	B1
2178-7956	REVISTA MAGISTRO (UNIGRANRO)	B3

2318-6550	REVISTA MAIËUTICA - HISTÓRIA	B3
2358-1301	REVISTA MAIS DADOS	B4
2175-3644	REVISTA MAL-ESTAR E SUBJETIVIDADE (VERSÃO ELETRÔNICA)	A2
2525-2801	REVISTA MANGAIO ACADÊMICO	B4
2526-2890	REVISTA MARINATAMBALO	B4
0034-9860	REVISTA MARÍTIMA BRASILEIRA	B4
1139-1138	REVISTA MATEMÁTICA COMPLUTENSE	A3
0213-2230	REVISTA MATEMÁTICA IBEROAMERICANA	A1
2182-9756	REVISTA MATÉRIA PRIMA	A3
2182-9829	REVISTA MATÉRIA PRIMA	A3
2358-193X	REVISTA MÉDICA DA UFPR	B4
2447-3308	REVISTA MÉDICA DA UFPR	B4
0034-9887	REVISTA MÉDICA DE CHILE (IMPRESA)	A4
1018-130X	REVISTA MÉDICA HEREDIANA	A2
2359-3318	REVISTA MEDITATIO	B4
1989-872X	REVISTA MEDITERRANEA DE COMUNICACION	A2
2316-2856	REVISTA MEIO AMBIENTE E SUSTENTABILIDADE	B3
2176-1736	REVISTA MELP (ONLINE)	B3
2358-0593	REVISTA MEMORARE	A4
2177-4129	REVISTA MEMÓRIA EM REDE	B1
2523-0891	REVISTA MERCOSUR DE POLÍTICAS SOCIALES	B4
2358-2790	REVISTA METALINGUAGENS	B3
2318-3233	REVISTA METROPOLITANA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E DESENVOLVIMEN	B2
2447-8024	REVISTA METROPOLITANA DE GOVERNANÇA CORPORATIVA	B3
0185-4534	REVISTA MEXICANA DE ANÁLISIS DE LA CONDUCTA	A3
0185-1101	REVISTA MEXICANA DE ASTRONOMÍA Y ASTROFÍSICA	B2
1870-3453	REVISTA MEXICANA DE BIODIVERSIDAD	B2
2007-0934	REVISTA MEXICANA DE CIENCIAS AGRÍCOLAS	A3
1026-8774	REVISTA MEXICANA DE CIENCIAS GEOLÓGICAS	B1
0185-1918	REVISTA MEXICANA DE CIENCIAS POLÍTICAS Y SOCIALES	A1
2448-492X	REVISTA MEXICANA DE CIENCIAS POLÍTICAS Y SOCIALES	A1
2448-8283	REVISTA MEXICANA DE ESTUDIOS ELECTORALES	B1
0035-001X	REVISTA MEXICANA DE FÍSICA	B2
1405-6666	REVISTA MEXICANA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EDUCATIVA	B4
2007-0926	REVISTA MEXICANA DE INVESTIGACIÓN EN PSICOLOGÍA	B1
1665-7527	REVISTA MEXICANA DE ORIENTACIÓN EDUCATIVA	B1
0185-6073	REVISTA MEXICANA DE PSICOLOGÍA (1984)	A2
0188-2503	REVISTA MEXICANA DE SOCIOLOGÍA	A1
2178-602X	REVISTA MÍDIA E COTIDIANO	A4
1806-5988	REVISTA MINEIRA DE CONTABILIDADE	B1
2594-9950	REVISTA MISSIONEIRA	B2
2526-2963	REVISTA MODOS	A1
2236-1308	REVISTA MONOGRAFIAS AMBIENTAIS	B3
1808-589X	REVISTA MOSAICUM (IMPRESSO)	B4
2238-8699	REVISTA MOVIMENTO (ECA-USP)	B2
2238-8052	REVISTA MOVIMENTOS SOCIAIS E DINÂMICAS ESPACIAIS	B1
1808-6969	REVISTA MULTIDISCIPLINAR DAS FACULDADES INTEGRADAS PITÁGC	B4
2178-6925	REVISTA MULTIDISCIPLINAR DO NORDESTE MINEIRO	B4
2316-4484	REVISTA MULTITEXTO	B3
2526-3188	REVISTA MUNDAÚ	B4

2525-4782	REVISTA MUNDI ENGENHARIA, TECNOLOGIA E GESTÃO	B4
2525-4790	REVISTA MUNDI MEIO AMBIENTE E AGRÁRIAS	B3
2525-4766	REVISTA MUNDI SAÚDE E BIOLÓGICAS	B4
2525-4774	REVISTA MUNDI SOCIAIS E HUMANIDADES	B4
2238-8788	REVISTA MUNDO ANTIGO	A4
1984-9222	REVISTA MUNDOS DO TRABALHO	A3
2177-7314	REVISTA MURAL INTERNACIONAL	A3
2526-6411	REVISTA MURMULLOS DEL SUR (ONLINE)	B4
2317-2231	REVISTA MUSEITEC	B4
2238-5436	REVISTA MUSEOLOGIA E INTERDISCIPLINARIDADE	A4
1981-6332	REVISTA MUSEU	B4
0103-5525	REVISTA MUSICA	B1
1909-0544	REVISTA MVZ CORDOBA	B2
2358-3223	REVISTA NACIONAL DE DIREITO DE FAMÍLIA E SUCESSÕES	B4
2318-8472	REVISTA NACIONAL DE GERENCIAMENTO DE CIDADES	A4
2317-8590	REVISTA ÑANDUTY	B2
2179-5738	REVISTA NAU SOCIAL	B2
2525-7757	REVISTA NAVA	B1
2178-6259	REVISTA NEGÓCIOS EM PROJEÇÃO	B2
2317-3459	REVISTA NEIBA - CADERNOS ARGENTINA-BRASIL	B2
2447-5548	REVISTA NEP - NÚCLEO DE ESTUDOS PARANAENSES DA UFPR	B4
1806-6755	REVISTA NERA (UNESP)	A2
2237-8383	REVISTA NEXI	B4
2539-4355	REVISTA NEXUS COMUNICACIÓN	B2
1889-7231	REVISTA NÓMADAS - REVISTA CRÍTICA DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIALES Y JUR	A3
2317-3092	REVISTA NORTE MINEIRA DE ENFERMAGEM - RENOME	A4
2448-1793	REVISTA NÓS ¿ CULTURA, ESTÉTICA & LINGUAGENS	B3
0102-5864	REVISTA NOVOS RUMOS	B4
0719-3092	REVISTA NUESTRAMERICA	A1
1677-1605	REVISTA NUPEART	B1
2175-7429	REVISTA NUPEM (IMPRESSO)	B3
1645-3247	REVISTA O COMUNEIRO	B4
2526-754X	REVISTA OBSERVAÇÕES	B4
2447-4266	REVISTA OBSERVATÓRIO	B2
2526-7647	REVISTA OBUTCHÉNE	B4
1983-2435	REVISTA ODISSÉIA	B1
0102-9460	REVISTA ODONTO CIÊNCIA (PUCRS. IMPRESSO)	B4
1983-3857	REVISTA OLHARES E TRILHAS	B1
2177-3807	REVISTA OLHO D'ÁGUA	B1
2595-9859	REVISTA ONLINE DE PESQUISA	B4
2237-9991	REVISTA OPARA - CIÊNCIAS CONTEMPORÂNEAS APLICADAS	B3
2177-3815	REVISTA OPINIÕES ? REVISTA DOS ALUNOS DE LITERATURA BRASILE	B1
2178-1176	REVISTA OPINIÃO FILOSÓFICA	B3
1806-0420	REVISTA OPINIÃO JURÍDICA (FORTALEZA)	A2
2183-7511	REVISTA ORBE	B4
2237-6976	REVISTA ORBIS LATINA	B2
2238-5702	REVISTA ORG & DEMO (ONLINE)	B1
2318-1702	REVISTA PAGMAR	B3
2446-4791	REVISTA PAGMAR	B3
2359-1786	REVISTA PALOTINA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO	B4

2176-6215	REVISTA PAN-AMAZÔNICA DE SAÚDE (IMPRESSO)	B2
1680-5348	REVISTA PANAMERICANA DE SALUD PUBLICA (PRINT)	A4
2175-3318	REVISTA PANDORA BRASIL	B1
2238-9210	REVISTA PANORÂMICA	B4
2525-5568	REVISTA PARADOXOS	B4
2526-950X	REVISTA PARAENSE DE CONTABILIDADE	B4
2314-1638	REVISTA PARAGUAY DESDE LAS CIENCIAS SOCIALES	B1
2595-5985	REVISTA PARAJÁS	A4
0556-6916	REVISTA PARANAENSE DE DESENVOLVIMENTO	B1
2238-5800	REVISTA PARANAENSE DE EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	A3
2448-5659	REVISTA PASAJES	B2
2182-8512	REVISTA PASSAGENS	B2
2179-9938	REVISTA PASSAGENS: REVISTA DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO	B2
2526-3218	REVISTA PAULUS	B4
2177-6490	REVISTA PEDAGOGIA	B4
0719-5885	REVISTA PEDAGOGÍA UNIVERSITARIA Y DIDÁCTICA DEL DERECHO	B2
1415-8175	REVISTA PEDAGÓGICA (UNOCHAPECÓ. IMPRESSO)	B2
1676-3025	REVISTA PEGADA ELETRÔNICA (ONLINE)	A2
1138-9168	REVISTA PENAL	B1
2007-4700	REVISTA PENAL MÉXICO (IMPRESSO)	B3
1982-2596	REVISTA PENSAMENTO CONTEMPORÂNEO EM ADMINISTRAÇÃO	A3
2215-3586	REVISTA PENSAMIENTO ACTUAL	B1
2027-2448	REVISTA PENSAMIENTO AMERICANO	A4
1853-4554	REVISTA PENSAMIENTO PENAL	B3
2177-3300	REVISTA PERCURSO (UEM) ONLINE	B1
2236-0603	REVISTA PERCURSO ACADÊMICO	B3
2358-0844	REVISTA PERIÓDICUS	B3
1989-8924	REVISTA PERIPLO	B4
1983-9707	REVISTA PERSPECTIVA	B2
2178-5937	REVISTA PERSPECTIVA (ONLINE)	B4
1981-4801	REVISTA PERSPECTIVA GEOGRÁFICA (ONLINE)	B1
2177-3548	REVISTA PERSPECTIVAS EM ANÁLISE DO COMPORTAMENTO	B1
1727-9933	REVISTA PERUANA DE BIOLOGÍA (EN LÍNEA)	B3
1561-0837	REVISTA PERUANA DE BIOLOGÍA (IMPRESA)	B3
1726-4642	REVISTA PERUANA DE MEDICINA EXPERIMENTAL Y SALUD PUBLICA	B3
1726-4634	REVISTA PERUANA DE MEDICINA EXPERIMENTAL Y SALUD PÚBLICA	B3
2236-7160	REVISTA PESQUISA & EXTENSÃO	B4
2594-8032	REVISTA PESQUISA EM ADMINISTRAÇÃO UFPE	B4
1809-0257	REVISTA PESQUISA QUALITATIVA	B3
2525-8222	REVISTA PESQUISA QUALITATIVA	B3
2179-6238	REVISTA PESQUISA SAÚDE	B4
0874-9493	REVISTA PHAINOMENON	B2
1413-6457	REVISTA PHILOLOGUS	A3
2527-225X	REVISTA PHOÏNIX	A4
1699-8774	REVISTA PHONICA	A3
2448-1947	REVISTA PHOTO & DOCUMENTO	B3
2447-7354	REVISTA PIAUIENSE DE HISTÓRIA SOCIAL E DO TRABALHO	B3
1983-0963	REVISTA PILARES DA HISTÓRIA	B4
1984-3755	REVISTA PISTIS & PRAXIS: TEOLOGIA E PASTORAL	A2
0719-2932	REVISTA PLANEO	A3

1984-3941	REVISTA PLURAIS	A4
1982-8888	REVISTA PLURAL	B4
2177-8566	REVISTA POIÉSIS	A2
2594-4398	REVISTA POLIEDRO	B3
2358-3592	REVISTA POLÍTICA E PLANEJAMENTO REGIONAL	A4
1517-5901	REVISTA POLÍTICA E TRABALHO	A4
2469-1763	REVISTA POLITICA LATINOAMERICANA	B2
0718-462X	REVISTA POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	B2
2359-1552	REVISTA POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS & CIDADES	A4
2236-0514	REVISTA POLYPHONÍA	A2
2238-8850	REVISTA POLYPHONÍA (ONLINE)	A2
2525-4200	REVISTA PORTAL: SAÚDE E SOCIEDADE (ONLINE)	B3
0870-2551	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE CARDIOLOGIA	B2
1645-0523	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE CIÊNCIAS DO DESPORTO	B3
0871-9187	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE EDUCAÇÃO	A1
1647-2160	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE ENFERMAGEM DE SAÚDE MENTAL	B1
1647-6700	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE ESTOMATOLOGIA, MEDICINA DENTARIA	B2
1645-586X	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE ESTUDOS REGIONAIS	A4
0870-5283	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE FILOSOFIA	A2
0870-4147	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE HISTÓRIA	A2
2183-9506	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE HISTÓRIA DA COMUNICAÇÃO	B4
0874-0321	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE HUMANIDADES	A4
2183-4938	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO COMPORTAMENTAL E SC	B3
1645-4006	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO EDUCACIONAL	B2
0871-9705	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE MUSICOLOGIA	B2
2183-8410	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE MUSICOLOGIA	B2
0872-0169	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE NEFROLOGIA E HIPERTENSÃO	B4
0870-418X	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE PEDAGOGIA	B2
0873-2159	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE PNEUMOLOGIA	B2
0873-9129	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE PSICANÁLISE	B4
2183-8453	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE SAÚDE OCUPACIONAL	B4
1645-4464	REVISTA PORTUGUESA E BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO (LISBOA)	B1
1983-4527	REVISTA PÓS-CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	A4
2448-1939	REVISTA PRÂKSIS	B1
2526-2149	REVISTA PRÁTICA DOCENTE	A3
2526-6292	REVISTA PRÁTICAS DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO PÚBLICA (ONLINE)	B4
2236-7268	REVISTA PRÁTICAS DE LINGUAGEM (UFJF)	B4
2216-0159	REVISTA PRAXIS & SABER: MAESTRÍA EN EDUCACIÓN	A3
1984-4239	REVISTA PRÁXIS (VOLTA REDONDA.IMPRESSO)	A3
2446-6646	REVISTA PRESENÇA GEOGRÁFICA	B1
2393-7076	REVISTA PRESENCIA. MIRADAS DESDE Y HACIA LA EDUCACIÓN	B4
1517-672X	REVISTA PRETEXTO	A3
2446-7901	REVISTA PREVENÇÃO DE INFECÇÃO E SAÚDE	B3
2526-2106	REVISTA PRIMORDIUM	B3
2500-5200	REVISTA PROCESSOS URBANOS (ONLINE)	B1
2448-2757	REVISTA PRODUÇÃO ACADÊMICA	B2
2446-9580	REVISTA PRODUÇÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B2
2358-6125	REVISTA PROFANAÇÕES	B2
1519-0919	REVISTA PROFISSÃO DOCENTE	B3
2447-617X	REVISTA PROJETER - PROJETO E PERCEPÇÃO DO AMBIENTE	A3

2179-8931	REVISTA PRÓ-UNIVERSUS	B4
2447-1798	REVISTA PSICOFÁE	B4
2177-093X	REVISTA PSICOLOGIA E SAÚDE	A4
1981-3236	REVISTA PSICOLOGIA EM FOCO (URI. FREDERICO WESTPHALEN)	B4
2175-3539	REVISTA PSICOLOGIA ESCOLAR E EDUCACIONAL	A1
1519-549X	REVISTA PSICOLOGIA POLÍTICA (IMPRESSO)	A4
1984-6657	REVISTA PSICOLOGIA: ORGANIZAÇÕES E TRABALHO	A2
2176-0969	REVISTA PSICÓLOGO INFORMAÇÃO	B4
2179-4057	REVISTA PSICOPEDAGOGIA	B1
2238-7552	REVISTA PUBLICATIO	B2
1946-2026	REVISTA PUERTORRIQUEÑA DE PSICOLOGÍA	B1
0719-0417	REVISTA PUNTO EN GÉNERO	A3
1676-7845	REVISTA QUALIDADE BANAS	B4
1809-3264	REVISTA QUERUBIM	B3
2179-6033	REVISTA RÁDIO-LEITURAS	A4
2317-2169	REVISTA RASCUNHO	B3
2177-3424	REVISTA RASCUNHOS CULTURAIS	B3
2236-0700	REVISTA RAZÃO CONTÁBIL E FINANÇAS	B2
2318-6674	REVISTA REAMEC	A3
2358-3088	REVISTA RECIEN - REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DE ENFERMAGEM	A4
2077-9445	REVISTA REDBIOÉTICA/UNESCO	A4
1851-7072	REVISTA REDES	A4
2359-5728	REVISTA REFERÊNCIA	B1
2238-6408	REVISTA REFLEXÕES	B1
2358-8276	REVISTA RELICÁRIO	B3
2527-1814	REVISTA RESTAURO	B3
2527-2594	REVISTA RETRATOS DE ASSENTAMENTOS	A4
2594-4916	REVISTA RE-UNIR	B3
0210-5020	REVISTA ROL. DE ENFERMERÍA	B3
0718-4182	REVISTA RUMBOS TS	B3
2359-4071	REVISTA RUMOS DA HISTÓRIA	B4
2215-2466	REVISTA RUPTURAS	B1
1666-7883	REVISTA SAAP	A2
1853-1970	REVISTA SAAP (ON LINE)	A2
2526-4559	REVISTA SABERES PEDAGÓGICOS	B2
2447-9411	REVISTA SABERES UNIVERSITÁRIOS	B1
0718-7475	REVISTA SALUD & SOCIEDAD	B4
1697-2791	REVISTA SALUD AMBIENTAL	B4
2528-7907	REVISTA SAN GREGORIO	B4
1984-3968	REVISTA SANTA CATARINA EM HISTÓRIA	B3
1980-1742	REVISTA SANTA RITA (FACEAS)	B4
2183-3184	REVISTA SANTUÁRIOS 1	B4
1982-2308	REVISTA SÃO LUIS ORIONE	B3
2446-5062	REVISTA SÃO LUIS ORIONE	B3
2238-3565	REVISTA SAPIÊNCIA: SOCIEDADE, SABERES E PRÁTICAS EDUCACIONAL	B1
2316-2864	REVISTA SAÚDE E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B3
2447-8822	REVISTA SAÚDE E MEIO AMBIENTE & RESMA	B2
1983-1870	REVISTA SAÚDE E PESQUISA	A3
2358-7946	REVISTA SAÚDE EM FOCO	B4
2446-4813	REVISTA SAÚDE EM REDES	B4

2447-7079	REVISTA SAÚDE INTEGRADA	B1
2358-5323	REVISTA SAÚDE NA COMUNIDADE	B4
1809-0761	REVISTA SAÚDE.COM	B4
2525-4553	REVISTA SCIENTIA: CIÊNCIA, INFORMAÇÃO, HABILIDADE E CONHECI	B3
2318-9584	REVISTA SCIENTIATEC	B3
2525-5940	REVISTA SEDA	B4
2238-359X	REVISTA SEM ASPAS	B3
2359-3105	REVISTA SENTIDOS DA CULTURA	B3
2359-4993	REVISTA SERGIPANA DE EDUCAÇÃO AMBIENTAL.	B2
2525-5444	REVISTA SERGIPANA DE MATEMÁTICA E EDUCAÇÃO MATEMÁTICA	A3
2527-1849	REVISTA SERVIÇO SOCIAL EM PERSPECTIVA	B3
1678-1252	REVISTA SETREM	B4
0718-0934	REVISTA SIGNOS	A1
1983-0378	REVISTA SIGNOS - CENTRO UNIVERSITÁRIO UNIVATES	A4
2526-4486	REVISTA SIMETRIA (PRINT)	B4
1981-3988	REVISTA SINAIIS	B2
2448-0797	REVISTA SINALIZAR	B1
1519-1818	REVISTA SÍNTESE DE DIREITO PENAL E PROCESSUAL PENAL	B4
2359-3121	REVISTA SÍSIFO	B3
2594-7036	REVISTA SÍTIO NOVO	B3
2358-2871	REVISTA SOBECC (ONLINE)	B2
1414-4425	REVISTA SOBECC (SÃO PAULO)	B2
2174-7210	REVISTA SOBRE LA INFANCIA Y LA ADOLESCENCIA (ONLINE)	B2
2317-1758	REVISTA SOCIAIS E HUMANAS	B2
1980-5462	REVISTA SOCIEDADE E ESTADO	A1
2177-8396	REVISTA SOCIEDADE E TERRITÓRIO	B1
1809-2721	REVISTA SOCIOLOGIA JURÍDICA	B4
1809-3957	REVISTA SODEBRAS	B3
2317-2339	REVISTA SOFIA - VERSÃO ELETRÔNICA	A4
1980-6973	REVISTA SOLDAGEM E INSPEÇÃO	B2
2316-8838	REVISTA SOLETRAS	A3
1121-7480	REVISTA SPAGNA CONTEMPORANEA	A2
2525-3395	REVISTA STRICTO SENSU	B4
2318-650X	REVISTA SUL AMERICANA DE PSICOLOGIA	B2
2317-5338	REVISTA SUL-AMERICANA DE CIÊNCIA POLÍTICA	A4
2316-2457	REVISTA SUL-AMERICANA DE ENGENHARIA ESTRUTURAL (ONLINE)	B3
1679-8775	REVISTA SUL-AMERICANA DE FILOSOFIA E EDUCAÇÃO	B2
2594-6285	REVISTA SYNTHESIS LETRAS EDUCAÇÃO E HUMANIDADES (ONLINE)	B3
1980-4490	REVISTA TAMOIOS (ONLINE)	A3
2318-0730	REVISTA TECNOLOGIA	B3
0101-8191	REVISTA TECNOLOGIA (UNIFOR)	B3
2526-6004	REVISTA TECNOLOGIA DA INFORMAÇÃO E COMUNICAÇÃO: TEORIA	B3
1809-0044	REVISTA TECNOLOGIA E SOCIEDADE	B2
1984-4751	REVISTA TECNOLOGIAS NA EDUCAÇÃO	B2
1517-8048	REVISTA TECNOLÓGICA (UEM)	B3
2446-7049	REVISTA TECNOLÓGICA DA FATEC DE AMERICANA	B4
1669-726X	REVISTA TEFROS	A2
1982-0305	REVISTA TEIAS (UERJ. ONLINE)	A2
1549-2230	REVISTA TEKNOKULTURA	B1
1900-7388	REVISTA TEKNOS	B4

2359-1943	REVISTA TELLUS	A2
1981-3724	REVISTA TEMPO DE CONQUISTA	B4
2176-7025	REVISTA TEMPO NO MUNDO	B3
2177-6644	REVISTA TEMPO, ESPAÇO E LINGUAGEM	B3
2358-1425	REVISTA TEMPOS E ESPAÇOS EM EDUCAÇÃO (ONLINE)	A3
1989-8614	REVISTA TENDÊNCIAS PEDAGÓGICAS - UNIVERSIDAD AUTÓNOMA D	A4
2238-0388	REVISTA TEOLOGIA BRASILEIRA	B4
2318-8448	REVISTA TEORIA E EVIDÊNCIA ECONÔMICA (ONLINE)	B3
2358-727X	REVISTA TERCEIRA MARGEM	B3
2238-7641	REVISTA TERCEIRA MARGEM AMAZÔNIA	B3
2525-4812	REVISTA TERCEIRA MARGEM AMAZÔNIA	B3
2317-5419	REVISTA TERRITORIUM TERRAM	B3
1887-2255	REVISTA TESELA	B4
2177-2894	REVISTA THEMA	A3
1515-6443	REVISTA THEOMAI (EN LÍNEA)	B2
2447-8679	REVISTA THÉSIS	B3
2317-3580	REVISTA THESIS JURIS	A4
2422-2704	REVISTA TIEMPO&ECONOMÍA	B2
2317-9430	REVISTA TOCANTINENSE DE GEOGRAFIA	B1
1980-6914	REVISTA TODAS AS LETRAS (MACKENZIE. ONLINE)	A2
2250-4524	REVISTA TOMA UNO	B3
2448-2978	REVISTA TOPUS	B3
2526-2319	REVISTA TRABALHO, POLÍTICA E SOCIEDADE	B2
2178-4485	REVISTA TRAJETÓRIAS MULTICURSOS	B4
1807-5711	REVISTA TRAMA (CASCAVEL. IMPRESSO)	A4
2177-5672	REVISTA TRAMA INTERDISCIPLINAR	B4
2175-8255	REVISTA TRANSFORMAR	B3
2318-0277	REVISTA TRANSGRESSÕES	B3
2525-6475	REVISTA TRANSMUTARE	B2
1852-7175	REVISTA TRANSPORTE Y TERRITORIO	A3
2236-4129	REVISTA TRANSVERSO: DIÁLOGOS ENTRE DESIGN, CULTURA E SOCIE	B4
2179-7528	REVISTA TRANSVERSOS	A3
1982-5935	REVISTA TRAVESSIAS	B1
1808-169X	REVISTA TRÊS [...] PONTOS (UFMG)	B4
1518-2711	REVISTA TRIBUTÁRIA E DE FINANÇAS PÚBLICAS	B4
2237-0153	REVISTA TRILHAS PEDAGÓGICAS	B4
1415-6393	REVISTA TURISMO & AÇÃO	A4
2182-1453	REVISTA TURISMO & DESENVOLVIMENTO (EDIÇÃO ELETRÔNICA)	B3
1645-9261	REVISTA TURISMO & DESENVOLVIMENTO (ONLINE)	B3
1519-4744	REVISTA TURISMO E DESENVOLVIMENTO	B3
1984-4867	REVISTA TURISMO EM ANÁLISE	B1
2316-1493	REVISTA TURISMO ESTUDOS E PRÁTICAS	B2
1677-9037	REVISTA UFG (IMPRESSO)	B2
2179-2925	REVISTA UFG (ONLINE)	B2
2316-1655	REVISTA ULTRAMARES - REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA COLONIAL	B4
2316-8072	REVISTA UNEMAT DE CONTABILIDADE	B3
2179-5037	REVISTA UNIABEU	B2
1677-0188	REVISTA UNIABEU	B2
1519-5694	REVISTA UNIANDRADE (IMPRESSO)	B3
1677-8308	REVISTA UNIFAMMA	B3

2358-9485	REVISTA UNIFESO - HUMANAS E SOCIAIS	B4
2236-9074	REVISTA UNIÍTAO EM PESQUISA	B3
1807-8850	REVISTA UNILUS ENSINO E PESQUISA (IMPRESSO)	B2
2318-2083	REVISTA UNILUS ENSINO E PESQUISA (ONLINE)	B2
2357-9870	REVISTA UNINTER DE COMUNICAÇÃO	B2
2250-8489	REVISTA UNIPE: TEMA (UNO)	B4
1517-3275	REVISTA UNIVAP	B4
2254-6111	REVISTA UNIVERSITARIA DE HISTORIA MILITAR	A2
2175-3024	REVISTA UNIVERSO ACADÊMICO	B4
1809-3337	REVISTA UNIVERSO CONTÁBIL	A2
2393-6886	REVISTA URUGUAYA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA Y ETNOGRAFÍA	B4
2393-7068	REVISTA URUGUAYA DE ANTROPOLOGÍA Y ETNOGRAFÍA	B4
0797-9789	REVISTA URUGUAYA DE CIENCIA POLÍTICA	A2
2301-0371	REVISTA URUGUAYA DE ENFERMERÍA	B4
0103-9989	REVISTA USP	A1
2525-9008	REVISTA VALORE	A3
2526-043X	REVISTA VALORE - REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA FASF FACULDADE SUL FLU	A3
1315-3617	REVISTA VENEZOLANA DE ANÁLISIS DE COYUNTURA	B2
1315-9984	REVISTA VENEZOLANA DE GERENCIA	B4
1981-8203	REVISTA VERDE DE AGROECOLOGIA E DESENVOLVIMENTO SUSTENT	B4
1677-0196	REVISTA VERNÁCULO	B3
2359-0106	REVISTA VERTENTES DO DIREITO	B4
2179-5894	REVISTA VÉRTICES	B1
2177-7837	REVISTA VIDERE (ON LINE)	A4
1982-6842	REVISTA VIRTUAL DE CULTURA SURDA E DIVERSIDADE	B1
1678-8931	REVISTA VIRTUAL DE ESTUDOS DA LINGUAGEM	A3
1984-6835	REVISTA VIRTUAL DE QUÍMICA	B2
1518-5494	REVISTA VIS (UNB)	A4
2238-9636	REVISTA VISÃO: GESTÃO ORGANIZACIONAL	B4
2477-9547	REVISTA VISIÓN GERENCIAL	B1
2447-1313	REVISTA VISUAIS	B1
2318-9665	REVISTA VIVER IFRS	B3
1853-8819	REVISTA VOCES EN EL FENIX	A4
2317-9937	REVISTA VÓRTEX	A2
2359-5183	REVISTA VOX - FADILESTE	B4
1980-0614	REVISTA X	A4
2145-9444	REVISTA ZONA PRÓXIMA	B1
1807-6211	REVISTALEPH	B4
2176-9125	REVLET: REVISTA VIRTUAL DE LETRAS	A3
1645-6726	REVSTAT STATISTICAL JOURNAL	B3
2101-0714	REVUE APPAREIL	A4
2117-4350	REVUE DE DROIT COMPARÉ DU TRAVAIL ET DE LA SÉCURITÉ SOCIAL	B1
2426-296X	REVUE DE L'ENFANCE ET DE L'ADOLESCENCE.	B4
0035-1555	REVUE DE MÉDECINE VÉTÉRINAIRE	B1
0035-1563	REVUE DE MÉTALLURGIE (IMPRIMÉ)	B3
0035-1571	REVUE DE MÉTAPHYSIQUE ET DE MORALE	A1
0035-1598	REVUE DE MICROPALÉONTOLOGIE	A3
0035-1601	REVUE DE MUSICOLOGIE	B1
0253-6730	REVUE DE PALÉOBIOLOGIE	B1
0297-1194	REVUE DE PSYCHOTHÉRAPIE PSYCHANALYTIQUE DE GROUPE	A4

2213-6533	REVUE DE STOMATOLOGIE, DE CHIRURGIE MAXILLO-FACIALE ET DE	B4
1773-0198	REVUE D'ÉCONOMIE INDUSTRIELLE	A3
0398-7620	REVUE D'ÉPIDÉMIOLOGIE ET DE SANTÉ PUBLIQUE	B2
1573-7888	REVUE DES ÉTUDES COOPÉRATIVES, MUTUALISTES ET ASSOCIATIVE	A2
0703-6337	REVUE D'INTE'GRATION EUROPE'ENNE	A1
1247-4819	REVUE DU MAUSS SEMESTRIELLE	A2
2101-8413	REVUE ERGOLOGIA	B4
1779-7179	REVUE EUROPÉENNE DE MÉCANIQUE NUMÉRIQUE	B1
0152-7401	REVUE FRANÇAISE D'ADMINISTRATION PUBLIQUE	B4
1386-1204	REVUE FRANÇAISE DE LINGUISTIQUE APPLIQUEE	A4
0035-2942	REVUE FRANÇAISE DE PSYCHANALYSE (PARIS)	A3
0035-2950	REVUE FRANÇAISE DE SCIENCE POLITIQUE	B1
2263-0856	REVUE FRANÇAISE DES SCIENCES DE L'INFORMATION ET DE LA COM	A2
1260-5875	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE GÉOMATIQUE	B1
2262-8401	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE PSYCHOSOCIOLOGIE ET DE GESTION DI	A3
0390-6701	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE SOCIOLOGIE	A4
1664-1531	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE SOINS PALLIATIFS	B4
1254-4590	REVUE INTERNATIONALE D'ÉDUCATION SÈVRES	A4
2554-3415	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DES ÉTUDES DU DÉVELOPPEMENT	B2
2101-647X	REVUE INTERNATIONALE D'INTELLIGENCE ÉCONOMIQUE	B4
0035-3787	REVUE NEUROLOGIQUE (PARIS)	B2
1493-8871	REVUE ORGANISATIONS & TERRITOIRES	B4
0035-3965	REVUE ROUMAINE DE MATHÉMATIQUES PURES ET APPLIQUÉES	B3
0253-1933	REVUE SCIENTIFIQUE ET TECHNIQUE - OFFICE INTERNATIONAL DES	A3
0035-418X	REVUE SUISSE DE ZOOLOGIE	B2
0718-5162	REXE REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS Y EXPERIENCIAS EN EDUCACIÓN	A3
0103-6971	RGO - REVISTA GAUCHA DE ODONTOLOGIA	B4
1806-6720	RGO. REVISTA DE GESTÃO ORGANIZACIONAL (UNOCHAPECÓ. IMPRI	A3
1516-3954	RHEMA (JUIZ DE FORA)	B4
0035-4511	RHEOLOGICA ACTA (PRINT)	A3
1462-0324	RHEUMATOLOGY (OXFORD. PRINT)	A1
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0172-8172	RHEUMATOLOGY INTERNATIONAL (BERLIN. PRINT)	B1
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0036-1399	SIAM JOURNAL ON APPLIED MATHEMATICS (PRINT)	A2
0363-0129	SIAM JOURNAL ON CONTROL AND OPTIMIZATION (PRINT)	A2
1095-7146	SIAM JOURNAL ON DISCRETE MATHEMATICS	A3
0895-4801	SIAM JOURNAL ON DISCRETE MATHEMATICS (PRINT)	A3
0036-1410	SIAM JOURNAL ON MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS (PRINT)	A1
0036-1429	SIAM JOURNAL ON NUMERICAL ANALYSIS (PRINT)	A1
1052-6234	SIAM JOURNAL ON OPTIMIZATION (PRINT)	A1
1064-8275	SIAM JOURNAL ON SCIENTIFIC COMPUTING (PRINT)	A1
1806-289X	SIBILA (COTIA)	B3
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1286-1715	SIGILA (PARIS)	B1
1533-6263	SIGN LANGUAGE STUDIES	A2
1406-4243	SIGN SYSTEMS STUDIES (TARTU)	A4
0165-1684	SIGNAL PROCESSING (PRINT)	A1
0923-5965	SIGNAL PROCESSING. IMAGE COMMUNICATION	A2
1863-1711	SIGNAL, IMAGE AND VIDEO PROCESSING	A3
2316-7114	SIGNIFICAÇÃO. REVISTA DE CULTURA AUDIOVISUAL	A3
1982-2014	SIGNO (UNISC. ONLINE)	A1
2314-2189	SIGNO Y SEÑA	A3
1984-5057	SIGNOS DO CONSUMO	B2
2316-3690	SIGNÓTICA	A4
0097-9740	SIGNS (CHICAGO, ILL.)	A3
2177-7306	SIGNUM - REVISTA DA ABREM	A3
2237-4876	SIGNUM [LONDRINA]: ESTUDOS DE LINGUAGEM	A2
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2509-8934	SILVAE GENETICA	B4
2316-1620	SIMBIÓTICA. REVISTA ELETRÔNICA	A4
1046-8781	SIMULATION & GAMING	A3
0037-5497	SIMULATION (SAN DIEGO, CALIF.)	A4
1569-190X	SIMULATION MODELLING PRACTICE AND THEORY	A1
1646-0715	SINAIS DE CENA	A4
1809-9815	SINAIS SOCIAIS	B3
2316-4514	SINAPSE MÚLTIPLA	B3
2236-7608	SINERGIA	B2
1677-499X	SINERGIA (CEFETSP)	B4
0102-7360	SINERGIA (FURG)	B2
2177-451X	SINERGIA (IFSP. ONLINE)	B4
0103-4332	SINTESE (BELO HORIZONTE. 1974)	A2
1981-3074	SINTESE: REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL DE CONTAS DO ESTADO DO RIO DE	B4
2185-3762	SISAL JOURNAL	A2
2182-9640	SISYPHUS - JOURNAL OF EDUCATION	A3
1984-5812	SITIENTIBUS : UNIVERSIDADE DE FEIRA DE SANTANA (SÉRIE CIÊNCIA	B4
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0364-2348	SKELETAL RADIOLOGY	A4
1432-2161	SKELETAL RADIOLOGY	A4
1105-1582	SKEPSIS	B1
1981-4534	SKÉPSIS (SALVADOR. ONLINE)	B3
1660-5527	SKIN PHARMACOLOGY AND PHYSIOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
1600-0846	SKIN RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY	A4
0909-752X	SKIN RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY	A4
2472-5552	SLAS DISCOVERY	B4
0144-039X	SLAVERY & ABOLITION	A1
1520-9512	SLEEP & BREATHING	A4
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1446-9235	SLEEP AND BIOLOGICAL RHYTHMS (PRINT)	B2
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2352-7218	SLEEP HEALTH (IMPRESSO)	A2
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1984-0063	SLEEP SCIENCE	B3
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1613-6810	SMALL (WEINHEIM. PRINT)	A1
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2154-1256	SMALL GTPASES	A2
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1743-9590	SOCCKER AND SOCIETY (ONLINE)	B1
1679-0251	SOCIABILIDADES (USP)	B4
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0964-0282	SOCIAL ANTHROPOLOGY	A1
1469-8676	SOCIAL ANTHROPOLOGY (ONLINE)	A1
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1873-5347	SOCIAL SCIENCE & MEDICINE (ONLINE)	A1
1874-8937	SOCIAL SCIENCES AND MISSIONS (PRINT)	A4
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0361-6525	SOCIOBIOLOGY	B1
0038-0121	SOCIO-ECONOMIC PLANNING SCIENCES	A2
1475-1461	SOCIO-ECONOMIC REVIEW (PRINT)	A1
2238-3875	SOCIOLOGIA & ANTROPOLOGIA	A1
0872-3419	SOCIOLOGIA (PORTO)	B1
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0392-5048	SOCIOLOGIA DEL LAVORO	A3
0210-8364	SOCIOLOGÍA DEL TRABAJO	B1
2603-9710	SOCIOLOGÍA DEL TRABAJO	B1
2236-7527	SOCIOLOGIA E ANTROPOLOGIA	A1
2611-5255	SOCIOLOGIA ITALIANA ¿ AIS JOURNAL OF SOCIOLOGY (ONLINE)	B4
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1517-4522	SOCIOLOGIAS (UFRGS. IMPRESSO)	A1
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2108-6915	SOCIOLOGIE	A1
2108-8845	SOCIOLOGIE	A1
1295-9278	SOCIOLOGIES PRATIQUES	B4
1865-5106	SOCIOLOGUS	B4
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2332-6492	SOCIOLOGY OF RACE & ETHNICITY	B2
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1838-675X	SOIL RESEARCH	A3

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0266-0032	SOIL USE AND MANAGEMENT	A3
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2225-8531	SOUTH AFRICAN JOURNAL OF GEOMATICS	B4
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1808-9798	SOUTH AMERICAN JOURNAL OF HERPETOLOGY (IMPRESSO)	A4
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1869-344X	STEEL RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	A2
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1666-244X	SUBJETIVIDAD Y PROCESOS COGNITIVOS	B2
0889-7077	SUBSTANCE ABUSE	A3
1747-597X	SUBSTANCE ABUSE TREATMENT, PREVENTION, AND POLICY	A2
1082-6084	SUBSTANCE USE & MISUSE	A2
1314-2615	SUBTERRANEAN BIOLOGY	A3
2314-1174	SUDAMÉRICA	B4
0972-1525	SUGAR TECH	A4

2075-051X	SULTAN QABOOS UNIVERSITY MEDICAL JOURNAL	A2
2215-910X	SUMA DE NEGOCIOS	B1
0121-4381	SUMA PSICOLOGICA	A3
0327-9022	SUMMA + (BUENOS AIRES)	B4
0100-5405	SUMMA PHYTOPATHOLOGICA (IMPRESSO)	B3
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0953-2048	SUPERCONDUCTOR SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (PRINT)	A3
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1359-8546	SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT	A1
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2295-0729	SUR LE JOURNALISME, ABOUT JOURNALISM, SOBRE JORNALISMO	A3
0257-8972	SURFACE & COATINGS TECHNOLOGY	A2
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0267-0844	SURFACE ENGINEERING	A2
2050-6252	SURFACE INNOVATIONS	A4
0039-6028	SURFACE SCIENCE	A3
2051-672X	SURFACE TOPOGRAPHY: METROLOGY AND PROPERTIES	A3
2468-0230	SURFACES AND INTERFACES	A4
0039-6060	SURGERY	A1
1550-7289	SURGERY FOR OBESITY AND RELATED DISEASES	A1
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0930-1038	SURGICAL AND RADIOLOGIC ANATOMY (PRINT)	A4
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1553-3506	SURGICAL INNOVATION	A3
1530-4515	SURGICAL LAPAROSCOPY, ENDOSCOPY & PERCUTANEOUS TECHNIC	B2
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1090-3941	SURGICAL TECHNOLOGY INTERNATIONAL	A2
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0039-6265	SURVEY REVIEW	A4
0169-3298	SURVEYS IN GEOPHYSICS	A1
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1862-4065	SUSTAINABILITY SCIENCE	A1
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0862-8440	SV&T LITERATURE (PRINT)	A4
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0953-7325	TECHNOLOGY ANALYSIS & STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT	A2
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0928-7329	TECHNOLOGY AND HEALTH CARE	B2
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1927-0321	TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION MANAGEMENT REVIEW	B1
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0379-3982	TECNOLOGÍA EN MARCHA	B3
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2316-6576	TEMPO PSICANALÍTICO	A3
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1365-3121	TERRA NOVA	A2
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1860-7330	TEXT & TALK	A2
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0104-0707	TEXTO & CONTEXTO ENFERMAGEM	A3
1807-9288	TEXTO DIGITAL (UFSC)	A3
1983-3652	TEXTO LIVRE	A4
1808-5385	TEXTO POÉTICO	A4
1677-9509	TEXTOS & CONTEXTOS (PORTO ALEGRE)	A1
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1413-9987	TEXTOS E DEBATES (UFRR)	B2
1415-3777	TEXTOS GRADUADOS (UNB)	B4
1413-9243	TEXTOS NEPO (UNICAMP)	B3
2595-2951	TEXTOS PARA DISCUSSÃO - CEPECON	B4
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1941-5923	THE AMERICAN JOURNAL OF CASE REPORTS	A2

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2162-0989	THE ASIA-PACIFIC JOURNAL OF OPHTHALMOLOGY	A4
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1538-4357	THE ASTROPHYSICAL JOURNAL (ONLINE)	A2
2041-8205	THE ASTROPHYSICAL JOURNAL LETTERS	A1
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2318-7115	THE ESPECIALIST	A3
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1292-8941	THE EUROPEAN PHYSICAL JOURNAL. E, SOFT MATTER (PRINT)	A4
0903-1936	THE EUROPEAN RESPIRATORY JOURNAL	A1
2214-790X	THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRIES AND SOCIETY	A1
0892-6638	THE FASEB JOURNAL	A1
1742-464X	THE FEBS JOURNAL (PRINT)	A2
2412-2688	THE FIEP BULLETIN	B3
0015-4040	THE FLORIDA ENTOMOLOGIST	A4
1018-5895	THE GENEVA PAPERS ON RISK AND INSURANCE. ISSUES AND PRACT	A3
0016-9013	THE GERONTOLOGIST (WASHINGTON, D.C.)	A1
0745-7472	THE HEARING JOURNAL	B2
0018-1196	THE HEYTHROP JOURNAL	A3
0018-2168	THE HISPANIC AMERICAN HISTORICAL REVIEW	A1

0739-1110	THE INDUSTRIAL-ORGANIZATIONAL PSYCHOLOGIST	B4
1682-1777	THE INTERNATIONAL ARCHIVES OF THE PHOTOGRAMMETRY, REMC	B4
1748-0485	THE INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION GAZETTE (PRINT)	A3
1096-7508	THE INTERNATIONAL FOOD AND AGRIBUSINESS MANAGEMENT REV	A2
1559-2448	THE INTERNATIONAL FOOD AND AGRIBUSINESS MANAGEMENT REV	A2
0707-5332	THE INTERNATIONAL HISTORY REVIEW	A2
1949-6540	THE INTERNATIONAL HISTORY REVIEW (ONLINE)	A2
0020-7063	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING	B1
0361-7882	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF AFRICAN HISTORICAL STUDIES	A4
0391-3988	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTIFICIAL ORGANS (TESTO STAN	B1
2327-1779	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS THEORY AND HISTORY	B3
1479-5868	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BEHAVIOURAL NUTRITION AND F	A1
1357-2725	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOCHEMISTRY	A3
0393-6155	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL MARKERS (TESTO ST	A4
1569-5794	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CARDIOVASCULAR IMAGING	A3
1176-9106	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMON	A2
1028-6632	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CULTURAL POLICY	A1
2325-162X	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DESIGN MANAGEMENT AND PRC	B1
2325-1379	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DESIGNED OBJECTS	A4
0214-6282	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DEVELOPMENTAL BIOLOGY	A4
2325-1085	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILIT	B3
2447-6730	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ESTHETIC DENTISTRY	A3
0749-6753	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH PLANNING AND MANAG	B1
1099-1751	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH PLANNING AND MANAG	B1
1094-3420	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTIN	A3
1466-4399	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEME	A1
0885-0607	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INTELLIGENCE AND COUNTER IN	B1
0948-3349	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT	A2
1614-7502	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (ONLIN	A2
1748-1317	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LOW CARBON TECHNOLOGIES (P	A2
1472-8117	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT EDUCATION	A2
1750-9548	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIPHYSICS	B2
0882-2786	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ORAL AND MAXILLOFACIAL IMPL	A2
1029-8436	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PAVEMENT ENGINEERING	A2
2327-7963	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGY AND CURRICULUM	B4
0198-7569	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PERIODONTICS & RESTORATIVE I	B1
1741-0401	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTIVITY AND PERFORMAN	A2
0893-2174	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PROSTHODONTICS	A4
0278-3649	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ROBOTICS RESEARCH	A1
1099-2340	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TOURISM RESEARCH	A1
1027-3719	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TUBERCULOSIS AND LUNG DISEA	A3
2325-1581	THE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF VISUAL DESIGN	B1
0272-684X	THE INTERNATIONAL QUARTERLY OF COMMUNITY HEALTH EDUCA1	B2
0946-5448	THE INTERNATIONAL TINNITUS JOURNAL	B2
1750-399X	THE INTERPRETER AND TRANSLATOR TRAINER (IMPRESSO)	A2
1751-7362	THE ISME JOURNAL (PRINT)	A1
1125-0003	THE ITALIAN JOURNAL OF ZOOLOGY (MODENA)	B3
2202-4433	THE JBI DATABASE OF SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS AND IMPLEMENTATIO	B1
0554-5579	THE JOURNAL AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY	A3
1568-5381	THE JOURNAL AMPHIBIA-REPTILIA	A3

0021-8464	THE JOURNAL OF ADHESION (PRINT)	A3
2005-7806	THE JOURNAL OF ADVANCED PROSTHODONTICS	A3
2576-5310	THE JOURNAL OF AGING AND SOCIAL CHANGE	B4
1389-224X	THE JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION AND EXTENSION	B3
1469-5146	THE JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE (ONLINE)	A1
0021-8596	THE JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE (PRINT)	A1
1075-5535	THE JOURNAL OF ALTERNATIVE AND COMPLEMENTARY MEDICINE (A4
0148-9917	THE JOURNAL OF AMBULATORY CARE MANAGEMENT	B2
1018-7081	THE JOURNAL OF ANIMAL AND PLANT SCIENCES	B2
0021-8863	THE JOURNAL OF APPLIED BEHAVIORAL SCIENCE	A1
1557-7224	THE JOURNAL OF APPLIED PACKAGING RESEARCH	B4
0161-8202	THE JOURNAL OF ARACHNOLOGY	A3
0883-5403	THE JOURNAL OF ARTHROPLASTY	A1
1076-9757	THE JOURNAL OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2
0277-0903	THE JOURNAL OF ASTHMA	A3
0021-9258	THE JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL CHEMISTRY (PRINT)	A1
0885-8624	THE JOURNAL OF BUSINESS & INDUSTRIAL MARKETING	A1
0889-4655	THE JOURNAL OF CARDIOVASCULAR NURSING	A1
0021-9525	THE JOURNAL OF CELL BIOLOGY	A1
0021-9606	THE JOURNAL OF CHEMICAL PHYSICS	A2
1941-2789	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND AESTHETIC DERMATOLOGY	A4
0895-8831	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL DENTISTRY	B2
0021-972X	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ENDOCRINOLOGY AND METABOLISM	A1
1524-6175	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL HYPERTENSION (GREENWICH, CONN.)	A3
0021-9738	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL INVESTIGATION	A1
1053-4628	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL PEDIATRIC DENTISTRY (PRINT)	A4
1552-4604	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY	A3
0160-6689	THE JOURNAL OF CLINICAL PSYCHIATRY	A1
0736-3761	THE JOURNAL OF CONSUMER MARKETING	A1
1067-0564	THE JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY CHINA	A1
0894-1912	THE JOURNAL OF CONTINUING EDUCATION IN THE HEALTH PROFES	A4
1049-2275	THE JOURNAL OF CRANIOFACIAL SURGERY (PRINT)	B1
1095-0680	THE JOURNAL OF ECT	A4
0736-4679	THE JOURNAL OF EMERGENCY MEDICINE	A4
2051-3305	THE JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING	B3
2527-1075	THE JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND EXACT SCIENCES	B4
2191-9216	THE JOURNAL OF ENGLISH AS A LINGUA FRANCA (IMPRESSO)	A1
0095-8964	THE JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION	A1
1041-2905	THE JOURNAL OF ESSENTIAL OIL RESEARCH	B1
1382-4554	THE JOURNAL OF ETHICS	A2
1550-7408	THE JOURNAL OF EUKARYOTIC MICROBIOLOGY (ONLINE)	A4
1532-3382	THE JOURNAL OF EVIDENCE-BASED DENTAL PRACTICE	A2
0022-1007	THE JOURNAL OF EXPERIMENTAL MEDICINE	A1
0022-1082	THE JOURNAL OF FINANCE (NEW YORK. PRINT)	A1
1067-2516	THE JOURNAL OF FOOT AND ANKLE SURGERY	A4
0258-414X	THE JOURNAL OF FORENSIC ODONTO-STOMATOLOGY	B3
1069-5869	THE JOURNAL OF FOURIER ANALYSIS AND APPLICATIONS	A1
1531-5851	THE JOURNAL OF FOURIER ANALYSIS AND APPLICATIONS	A1
2273-4309	THE JOURNAL OF FRAILITY & AGING	A1
0270-7314	THE JOURNAL OF FUTURES MARKETS	A2

1099-498X	THE JOURNAL OF GENE MEDICINE	B1
1349-8037	THE JOURNAL OF GENERAL AND APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY	B3
0022-1309	THE JOURNAL OF GENERAL PSYCHOLOGY	A4
0022-1376	THE JOURNAL OF GEOLOGY	A2
1050-6926	THE JOURNAL OF GEOMETRIC ANALYSIS	A1
1559-002X	THE JOURNAL OF GEOMETRIC ANALYSIS (ONLINE)	A1
0363-5023	THE JOURNAL OF HAND SURGERY (ST. LOUIS, MO.)	A3
1053-2498	THE JOURNAL OF HEART AND LUNG TRANSPLANTATION	A1
1029-8479	THE JOURNAL OF HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS (ONLINE)	A2
0022-1554	THE JOURNAL OF HISTOCHEMISTRY AND CYTOCHEMISTRY	A2
0195-6701	THE JOURNAL OF HOSPITAL INFECTION	A2
0022-166X	THE JOURNAL OF HUMAN RESOURCES	A1
0022-1767	THE JOURNAL OF IMMUNOLOGY (1950)	A1
1550-6606	THE JOURNAL OF IMMUNOLOGY (1950. ONLINE)	A1
0972-4052	THE JOURNAL OF INDIAN PROSTHODONTIC SOCIETY	B2
1522-2527	THE JOURNAL OF INDIVIDUAL PSYCHOLOGY (1998)	A4
0163-4453	THE JOURNAL OF INFECTION	A2
2036-6590	THE JOURNAL OF INFECTION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	A2
0022-1899	THE JOURNAL OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES	A1
1308-7649	THE JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL ADVANCED OTOLOGY	B2
2429-2133	THE JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS, PEACE STUDIES, AND	B2
1042-3931	THE JOURNAL OF INVASIVE CARDIOLOGY	A4
1087-0024	THE JOURNAL OF INVESTIGATIVE DERMATOLOGY SYMPOSIUM PRO	B2
1538-8506	THE JOURNAL OF KNEE SURGERY	A2
1385-3457	THE JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND GOVERNANCE (PRINT)	A2
1066-9817	THE JOURNAL OF MANUAL & MANIPULATIVE THERAPY	A4
1476-4954	THE JOURNAL OF MATERNAL-FETAL & NEONATAL MEDICINE	B1
0022-2631	THE JOURNAL OF MEMBRANE BIOLOGY (PRINT)	A4
0832-7823	THE JOURNAL OF MICROWAVE POWER AND ELECTROMAGNETIC EN	B1
0271-0137	THE JOURNAL OF MIND AND BEHAVIOR	B3
1539-736X	THE JOURNAL OF NERVOUS AND MENTAL DISEASE	A3
0022-3018	THE JOURNAL OF NERVOUS AND MENTAL DISEASE (PRINT)	A3
0895-0172	THE JOURNAL OF NEUROPSYCHIATRY AND CLINICAL NEUROSCIENC	B1
0270-6474	THE JOURNAL OF NEUROSCIENCE	A1
0161-5505	THE JOURNAL OF NUCLEAR MEDICINE (1978)	A1
1682-3141	THE JOURNAL OF NURSING RESEARCH	A4
0022-3166	THE JOURNAL OF NUTRITION (PRINT)	A1
1279-7707	THE JOURNAL OF NUTRITION, HEALTH & AGING	A2
2475-9066	THE JOURNAL OF OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE	B4
0160-6972	THE JOURNAL OF ORAL IMPLANTOLOGY	B1
0190-6011	THE JOURNAL OF ORTHOPAEDIC AND SPORTS PHYSICAL THERAPY	A2
1526-5900	THE JOURNAL OF PAIN (PRINT)	A1
0022-3395	THE JOURNAL OF PARASITOLOGY	A4
1743-9361	THE JOURNAL OF PEASANT STUDIES (ONLINE)	A1
0022-3476	THE JOURNAL OF PEDIATRICS	A1
0893-2190	THE JOURNAL OF PERINATAL & NEONATAL NURSING	A4
0022-3565	THE JOURNAL OF PHARMACOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL THERAPEU	A2
1089-5639	THE JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY. A	A3
1520-5207	THE JOURNAL OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY. B (1997 : ONLINE)	A2
0022-3816	THE JOURNAL OF POLITICS	A1

2426-0266	THE JOURNAL OF PREVENTION OF ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE	B3
1096-5572	THE JOURNAL OF PRIVATE EQUITY	B4
0022-3913	THE JOURNAL OF PROSTHETIC DENTISTRY (PRINT)	A2
0022-3980	THE JOURNAL OF PSYCHOLOGY	A2
2206-9658	THE JOURNAL OF PUBLIC SPACE	B2
0892-1016	THE JOURNAL OF RAPTOR RESEARCH	B1
1499-2752	THE JOURNAL OF RHEUMATOLOGY (ONLINE)	A3
1465-1211	THE JOURNAL OF RISK	B2
1099-6362	THE JOURNAL OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES & MATERIALS (PRINT)	A2
1059-8405	THE JOURNAL OF SCHOOL NURSING	A3
0887-6045	THE JOURNAL OF SERVICES MARKETING	A1
0022-4499	THE JOURNAL OF SEX RESEARCH (PRINT)	A1
1743-6095	THE JOURNAL OF SEXUAL MEDICINE (PRINT)	A1
1834-2612	THE JOURNAL OF SMOKING CESSATION	A4
1088-1697	THE JOURNAL OF SOLID WASTE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT	B3
2044-7507	THE JOURNAL OF SPACE SYNTAX: ARCHITECTURE URBANISM SOCIE'	B4
1079-0268	THE JOURNAL OF SPINAL CORD MEDICINE	A4
1827-1928	THE JOURNAL OF SPORTS MEDICINE AND PHYSICAL FITNESS	B2
0896-8446	THE JOURNAL OF SUPERCRITICAL FLUIDS	A2
1523-2409	THE JOURNAL OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT	A1
0022-4804	THE JOURNAL OF SURGICAL RESEARCH (PRINT)	A2
0164-1212	THE JOURNAL OF SYSTEMS AND SOFTWARE	A2
0892-9912	THE JOURNAL OF TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER	A1
0001-4966	THE JOURNAL OF THE ACOUSTICAL SOCIETY OF AMERICA	A3
0002-8177	THE JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN DENTAL ASSOCIATION (1939)	A2
0002-9726	THE JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN LEATHER CHEMISTS ASSOCIATION	A4
1055-3290	THE JOURNAL OF THE ASSOCIATION OF NURSES IN AIDS CARE	A2
0021-9142	THE JOURNAL OF THE ASTRONAUTICAL SCIENCES	A3
2212-828X	THE JOURNAL OF THE ECONOMICS OF AGEING	A2
2248-9002	THE JOURNAL OF THE FOUNDATION FOR AGRARIAN STUDIES	B1
1095-5674	THE JOURNAL OF THE TORREY BOTANICAL SOCIETY	A4
2163-0755	THE JOURNAL OF TRAUMA AND ACUTE CARE SURGERY	A1
1063-0732	THE JOURNAL OF URBAN TECHNOLOGY	A1
0022-5347	THE JOURNAL OF UROLOGY	A1
1129-7298	THE JOURNAL OF VASCULAR ACCESS (PRINT)	A4
1678-9199	THE JOURNAL OF VENOMOUS ANIMALS AND TOXINS INCLUDING TF	A3
0022-541X	THE JOURNAL OF WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT	A2
1079-5006	THE JOURNALS OF GERONTOLOGY. SERIES A, BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES	A1
1079-5014	THE JOURNALS OF GERONTOLOGY. SERIES B, PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIEF	A1
2093-0569	THE KOREAN JOURNAL OF PAIN	A1
0099-5355	THE LANCET (NORTH AMERICAN EDITION)	A1
2352-4642	THE LANCET CHILD & ADOLESCENT HEALTH (IMPRESSO)	B4
2213-8587	THE LANCET DIABETES & ENDOCRINOLOGY	A1
2468-1253	THE LANCET GASTROENTEROLOGY & HEPATOLOGY	A4
2214-109X	THE LANCET GLOBAL HEALTH	A1
2352-3026	THE LANCET HAEMATOLOGY	A1
2352-3018	THE LANCET HIV	A1
2215-0366	THE LANCET PSYCHIATRY	A3
2213-2600	THE LANCET RESPIRATORY MEDICINE	A1
1531-4995	THE LARYNGOSCOPE	A1

0023-852X	THE LARYNGOSCOPE (ST. LOUIS)	A1
2519-1217	THE LATIN AMERICAN AND IBERIAN JOURNAL OF LAW AND ECONO	B4
1676-7497	THE LATIN AMERICAN JOURNAL OF AQUATIC MAMMALS	B4
1943-3867	THE LAW AND DEVELOPMENT REVIEW	A4
1048-9843	THE LEADERSHIP QUARTERLY	A1
1549-652X	THE LIBRARY QUARTERLY	A2
0024-2519	THE LIBRARY QUARTERLY (CHICAGO, ILL.)	A2
1096-1135	THE LICHENOLOGIST (ONLINE)	A3
0025-7125	THE MEDICAL CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA	A3
0026-2285	THE MICHIGAN MATHEMATICAL JOURNAL	A4
2210-3163	THE NATURAL PRODUCTS JOURNAL	B2
0028-1344	THE NAUTILUS (PHILADELPHIA)	B2
1660-8151	THE NEPHRON JOURNALS	A3
1074-7931	THE NEUROLOGIST (BALTIMORE, MD.)	B2
1971-4009	THE NEURORADIOLOGY JOURNAL	B1
1073-8584	THE NEUROSCIENTIST (BALTIMORE, MD.)	A1
1732-6729	THE NEW EDUCATIONAL REVIEW	A4
1073-6700	THE NONPROLIFERATION REVIEW	B2
1062-9408	THE NORTH AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE	A2
1542-0124	THE OCULAR SURFACE	A1
1083-7159	THE ONCOLOGIST (DAYTON, OHIO)	A2
1874-3315	THE OPEN AGRICULTURE JOURNAL	B4
1874-091X	THE OPEN BIOCHEMISTRY JOURNAL	B1
1874-1924	THE OPEN CARDIOVASCULAR MEDICINE JOURNAL	B1
1874-1495	THE OPEN CIVIL ENGINEERING JOURNAL	B3
1874-8368	THE OPEN CONSTRUCTION & BUILDING TECHNOLOGY JOURNAL	B1
1874-2106	THE OPEN DENTISTRY JOURNAL	A4
2168-6408	THE OPEN JOURNAL OF OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY	B3
1874-2858	THE OPEN MICROBIOLOGY JOURNAL	A4
1874-205X	THE OPEN NEUROLOGY JOURNAL	B1
1874-4346	THE OPEN NURSING JOURNAL (ONLINE)	B1
1874-3641	THE OPEN OPHTHALMOLOGY JOURNAL	B2
1874-3250	THE OPEN ORTHOPAEDICS JOURNAL	B4
1876-3863	THE OPEN PAIN JOURNAL	B2
1874-9445	THE OPEN PUBLIC HEALTH JOURNAL	B4
1875-399X	THE OPEN SPORTS SCIENCES JOURNAL	B2
1874-303X	THE OPEN UROLOGY & NEPHROLOGY JOURNAL	B3
1011-601X	THE PAKISTAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES	B2
0031-3955	THE PEDIATRIC CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA	A2
0891-3668	THE PEDIATRIC INFECTIOUS DISEASE JOURNAL	A2
0031-921X	THE PHYSICS TEACHER	B3
1040-4651	THE PLANT CELL	A1
1940-3372	THE PLANT GENOME	A1
2353-723X	THE POLISH JOURNAL OF AESTHETICS	B3
1612-3824	THE PRIVACY MARKETING REVIEW	B4
1525-318X	THE PROFESSIONAL ANIMAL SCIENTIST	B2
0033-0124	THE PROFESSIONAL GEOGRAPHER	B1
0270-4137	THE PROSTATE (PRINT)	A2
1572-3887	THE PROTEIN JOURNAL	B1
0193-953X	THE PSYCHIATRIC CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA	A2

0033-2933	THE PSYCHOLOGICAL RECORD	A2
0272-3433	THE PUBLIC HISTORIAN	A4
1068-6967	THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	B1
0033-5533	THE QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS	A1
1824-4785	THE QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF NUCLEAR MEDICINE AND MOLECULA	A3
2305-8927	THE QUARTERLY OF LATIN AMERICAN ECONOMY AND TRADE	B3
0033-5770	THE QUARTERLY REVIEW OF BIOLOGY	A1
1062-9769	THE QUARTERLY REVIEW OF ECONOMICS AND FINANCE	A2
2073-4859	THE R JOURNAL	A2
0741-6261	THE RAND JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS	A1
1230-4379	THE RELIGIOUS STUDIES REVIEW	B1
0034-6535	THE REVIEW OF ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS	A1
0486-6134	THE REVIEW OF RADICAL POLITICAL ECONOMICS	A2
1553-0892	THE REVIEW OF REGIONAL STUDIES (ONLINE)	A3
0035-7596	THE ROCKY MOUNTAIN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICS	B2
1013-9052	THE SAUDI DENTAL JOURNAL	A3
2066-8880	THE SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF HUMANISTIC STUDIES	B1
1537-744X	THE SCIENTIFIC WORLD JOURNAL	B1
0147-1724	THE SOUTHWESTERN ENTOMOLOGIST	B2
1138-7416	THE SPANISH JOURNAL OF PSYCHOLOGY	A2
1529-9430	THE SPINE JOURNAL	A2
1541-7794	THE STRUCTURAL DESIGN OF TALL AND SPECIAL BUILDINGS	A1
0171-6425	THE THORACIC AND CARDIOVASCULAR SURGEON	B1
1754-2731	THE TQM JOURNAL (PRINT)	A2
2146-7242	THE TURKISH ONLINE JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY	A1
2220-2293	THE UNESCO COURIER	B2
0749-0739	THE VETERINARY CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA. EQUINE PRACTICE (F	A3
0195-5616	THE VETERINARY CLINICS OF NORTH AMERICA. SMALL ANIMAL PRA	A2
1090-0233	THE VETERINARY JOURNAL (LONDON, ENGLAND. 1997)	A1
0165-2176	THE VETERINARY QUARTERLY	A2
0178-2789	THE VISUAL COMPUTER	A4
1432-2315	THE VISUAL COMPUTER (INTERNET)	A4
1939-4551	THE WORLD ALLERGY ORGANIZATION JOURNAL	A1
1562-2975	THE WORLD JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL PSYCHIATRY	A2
1527-196X	THEATER (NEW HAVEN, CONN. ONLINE)	B2
2332-2551	THEATRE AND PERFORMANCE DESIGN	A2
0307-8833	THEATRE RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	A2
0335-2927	THÉÂTRE/PUBLIC	B3
1517-6312	THEMA (PELOTAS)	A3
2237-843X	THEMA ET SCIENTIA	A4
2525-5096	THEMIS - REVISTA DA ESMEC	B4
0120-3649	THEOLOGICA XAVERIANA	A2
0040-5671	THEOLOGISCHE LITERATURZEITUNG	B2
2550-6625	THEOREIN	B4
0177-798X	THEORETICAL AND APPLIED CLIMATOLOGY	A3
0167-8442	THEORETICAL AND APPLIED FRACTURE MECHANICS (PRINT)	A1
0040-5752	THEORETICAL AND APPLIED GENETICS	A1
0935-4964	THEORETICAL AND COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS	A2
2065-3913	THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL RESEARCHES IN URBAN MANAGEME	A4
2197-0025	THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PLANT PHYSIOLOGY	A4

0040-5779	THEORETICAL AND MATHEMATICAL PHYSICS	B2
1742-4682	THEORETICAL BIOLOGY AND MEDICAL MODELLING	A3
1432-881X	THEORETICAL CHEMISTRY ACCOUNTS (PRINT)	B1
0304-3975	THEORETICAL COMPUTER SCIENCE	A4
1874-1746	THEORETICAL ECOLOGY	A4
1874-1738	THEORETICAL ECOLOGY	A4
2162-2086	THEORETICAL ECONOMICS LETTERS	A3
0040-5795	THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING	B2
0495-4548	THEORIA (MADRID)	A4
1092-311X	THEORY & EVENT	A3
0959-3543	THEORY & PSYCHOLOGY	A2
0040-5833	THEORY AND DECISION	A2
2050-8840	THEORY AND PRACTICE OF LEGISLATION	A1
1471-0684	THEORY AND PRACTICE OF LOGIC PROGRAMMING	B2
1543-0421	THEORY INTO PRACTICE	A3
1432-4350	THEORY OF COMPUTING SYSTEMS	B2
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2175-3369	URBE. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GESTÃO URBANA	A1
2358-6958	URDIMENTO	A1
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1078-1439	UROLOGIC ONCOLOGY	A1
0090-4295	UROLOGY (RIDGEWOOD, N.J.)	A4
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0042-207X	VACUUM (OXFORD)	A4
1539-1663	VADOSE ZONE JOURNAL	A2
1098-3015	VALUE IN HEALTH	A1
2212-1099	VALUE IN HEALTH REGIONAL ISSUES (PRINT)	A2
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1396-0482	VARIACIONES BORGES	A4
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1176-6344	VASCULAR HEALTH AND RISK MANAGEMENT (PRINT)	A1
1358-863X	VASCULAR MEDICINE (LONDON)	A4
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2594-5491	VAZANTES - REVISTA DO PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM ART	B3

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1805-9392	VETERINÁRNÍ MEDICÍNA	A4
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1913-1852	MODERN APPLIED SCIENCE	C
2329-6798	MODERN CHEMISTRY & APPLICATIONS	C
0194-4533	MODERN DRUMMER	C
2333-2581	MODERN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING	C
2637-7764	MODERN RESEARCH IN DENTISTRY	C
2169-9690	MODERN RESEARCH IN INFLAMMATION	C
1982-3150	MODERNA HEPATOLOGIA	C
1984-3313	MODERNO MAM	C
2448-2293	MOITARÁ - REVISTA DE SERVIÇO SOCIAL	C
2471-139X	MOJ ANATOMY & PHYSIOLOGY	C
2576-4519	MOJ APPLIED BIONICS AND BIOMECHANICS	C
2574-9722	MOJ BIOLOGY AND MEDICINE	C
2572-8520	MOJ CIVIL ENGINEERING	C
2574-8130	MOJ GERONTOLOGY & GERIATRICS	C
2374-6920	MOJ PROTEOMICS & BIOINFORMATICS	C
2379-6383	MOJ PUBLIC HEALTH	C
2574-9935	MOJ SPORTS MEDICINE	C
2379-6294	MOJ TOXICOLOGY	C
2296-9209	MOLECULAR NEUROPSYCHIATRY	C
1433-1373	MOLECULES ONLINE	C
2340-5457	MONFRAGÜE DESARROLLO RESILIENTE	C
1133-4797	MONOGRAFÍAS DE LA REVISTA ARAGONESA DE ADMINISTRACIÓN P	C
1808-4028	MOSAICOS (UEMS)	C
2172-2862	MOTRICIDAD. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF HUMAN MOVEMENT	C

2594-6463	MOTRICIDADES: REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE DE PESQUISA QUALITATIV.	C
2358-9205	MOVIMENTAÇÃO	C
2059-8521	MRS ADVANCES	C
2526-2394	MULTICULTURA REVISTA ELETRONICA	C
2573-3435	MULTIDISCIPLINARY ADVANCES IN VETERINARY SCIENCE	C
2414-4088	MULTIMODAL TECHNOLOGIES INTERACT	C
2055-2173	MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS JOURNAL - EXPERIMENTAL, TRANSLATIONAL /	C
2520-8179	MULTISCALE AND MULTIDISCIPLINARY MODELING, EXPERIMENTS A	C
2359-6902	MULTI-SCIENCE JOURNAL	C
2447-8725	MULTIVERSO - REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO CAMPUS JUIZ DE FORA	C
2594-4096	MUNDO EM TRANSE	C
2408-0748	MUSEUMEDU	C
1980-3303	MÚSICA & CULTURA (SALVADOR. ONLINE)	C
1980-5802	MÚSICA EM CONTEXTO (UNB)	C
2175-3172	MÚSICA NA EDUCAÇÃO BÁSICA	C
2316-7858	MÚSICA POPULAR EM REVISTA	C
2161-1068	MYCOBACTERIAL DISEASES (OPEN ACCESS)	C
0953-7562	MYCOLOGICAL RESEARCH (PRINT)	C
1984-0098	MYTHOS (CATAGUASES)	C
2501-0727	NAME AND NAMING - PROCEEDINGS OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONFI	C
1793-2920	NANO (PRINT)	C
2297-3400	NANO HYBRIDS AND COMPOSITES	C
2471-9838	NANO RESEARCH & APPLICATIONS	C
2379-1101	NANO WORLD JOURNAL	C
2318-5880	NANOCELL NEWS	C
2574-187X	NANOMEDICINE & NANOTECHNOLOGY OPEN ACCESS	C
2516-0230	NANOSCALE ADVANCES	C
0499-9320	NASA TECHNICAL MEMORANDUM	C
2158-706X	NATURAL RESOURCES	C
2043-0116	NATURE PROTOCOL EXCHANGE	C
1806-7409	NATUREZA ON LINE (ESPÍRITO SANTO)	C
2444-9032	NEFROLOGÍA LATINOAMERICANA	C
2358-436X	NEMATODA	C
1809-5348	NEODIVERSITY (FEIRA DE SANTANA)	C
2572-4983	NEONATAL AND PEDIATRIC MEDICINE	C
2218-6425	NEOTROPICAL HELMINTHOLOGY	C
2399-908X	NEPHROLOGY AND RENAL DISEASES	C
0028-2766	NEPHRON	C
1660-2129	NEPHRON. EXPERIMENTAL NEPHROLOGY	C
2220-8879	NETWORK BIOLOGY	C
1807-1058	NEUROCIÊNCIAS (RIO DE JANEIRO)	C
2359-4462	NEUROEDUCAÇÃO	C
2637-8329	NEUROGRAPHICS	C
2514-4790	NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS AND THERAPEUTICS	C
1758-2008	NEUROPSYCHIATRY	C
2158-2912	NEUROSCIENCE & MEDICINE	C
2524-2237	NEUROSCIENCE INTERNATIONAL	C
2397-2092	NEW FRONTIERS IN OPHTHALMOLOGY	C
2380-6540	NEW WATER POLICY & PRACTICE	C
1171-0462	NEW ZEALAND JOURNAL OF OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY (AUCKLAND)	C

1174-5339	NEW ZEALAND MANAGEMENT	C
1818-6742	NEXO	C
1516-9022	NEXOS ECONÔMICOS	C
2447-794X	NEXUS - REVISTA DE EXTENSÃO DO IFAM	C
1522-4600	NEXUS NETWORK JOURNAL	C
2317-3351	NICS REPORTS	C
2522-6673	NON-CODING RNA INVESTIGATION	C
2571-8010	NORRAG SPECIAL ISSUE	C
2236-7640	NOTAS TÉCNICAS DO CBPF	C
2009-8987	NOTULAE ALGARUM	C
1339-004X	NOVA BIOTECHNOLOGICA ET CHIMICA	C
2007-0705	NOVA SCIENTIA	C
1646-5989	NOVA SÍNTESE	C
2175-6279	NOVOS TEMAS	C
2373-8057	NPJ PARKINSON'S DISEASE	C
2397-4648	NPJ QUANTUM MATERIALS (ONLINE)	C
1923-7332	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF UBIQUITOUS SYSTEMS AND PERSASIV	C
0325-6960	NUEVAMÉRICA (BUENOS AIRES)	C
2358-9825	N'UMBUNTU EM REVISTA	C
2532-862X	NUOVI QUADERNI DEL CIRCOLO SEMIOLOGICO SICILIANO	C
1467-1158	NURSE PRESCRIBER- CAMBRIDGE UNIVERSITY PRESS - (ONLINE)	C
2572-8474	NURSING & CARE OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL	C
1677-0234	NUTRIÇÃO BRASIL	C
1676-2274	NUTRIÇÃO EM PAUTA	C
1519-8928	NUTRIRE (SÃO PAULO)	C
0034-6659	NUTRITION & FOOD SCIENCE	C
2474-767X	NUTRITION & FOOD SCIENCE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL	C
0985-0562	NUTRITION CLINIQUE ET MÉTABOLISME	C
1111-1119	NYSSA	C
2318-1478	O ADJUNTO - REVISTA PEDAGÓGICA DA ESCOLA DE APERFEIÇOAME	C
0365-2726	O AGRÔNOMICO (CAMPINAS)	C
0103-8125	O ALFERES (BELO HORIZONTE)	C
0366-0567	O BIOLÓGICO (IMPRESSO)	C
2178-4396	O DIREITO À SAÚDE DE MULHERES SOROPOSITIVAS COMO VIA DE E	C
0104-7671	O PERCEVEJO (UNIRIO)	C
1983-7658	O SABER (BRASÍLIA)	C
2236-6644	O TEATRO TRANSCENDE (ONLINE)	C
2053-0781	OA MEDICAL HYPOTHESIS	C
2374-8354	OBESITY & CONTROL THERAPIES: OPEN ACCESS	C
2165-7904	OBESITY & WEIGHT LOSS THERAPY	C
2377-8385	OBESITY RESEARCH	C
2055-2238	OBESITY SCIENCE & PRACTICE	C
2378-3168	OBESITY, WEIGHT MANAGMENT & CONTROL	C
1853-2713	OBSERVATORIO LATINOAMERICANO	C
2287-8572	OBSTETRIC AND GYNECOLOGY SCIENCE	C
2377-4304	OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL	C
2577-2236	OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY: OPEN ACCESS	C
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1258-8210	OCL. OLÉAGINEUX CORPS GRAS LIPIDES	C
2525-4715	ODEERE	C

1413-4640	ODISSÉIA (UFRN)	C
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1390-9967	ODONTOLOGÍA	C
1560-9111	ODONTOLOGÍA SANMARQUINA	C
0103-7870	ODONTOLOGIA-USF	C
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0473-2812	OIML BULLETIN	C
2176-9249	OLHARES PLURAIS	C
2526-6314	OLIMPIANOS - JOURNAL OF OLYMPIC STUDIES	C
2448-4172	OLIVE REVISTA CIENTÍFICA ELETRÔNICA	C
2595-2188	OLYMPIO	C
2183-4008	OMNIA - REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE CIÊNCIAS E ARTES	C
1328-925X	ONLINE JOURNAL OF VETERINARY RESEARCH	C
2578-0247	OPEN ACCESS BIOSTATISTICS & BIOINFORMATICS	C
2474-8846	OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH	C
2476-0501	OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY & NEUROSURGERY	C
2474-7599	OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL OF TOXICOLOGY	C
2640-2718	OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL OF WASTE MANAGEMENT & XENOBIOTICS	C
2352-6335	OPEN BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES JOURNAL	C
2169-2661	OPEN JOURNAL OF AIR POLLUTION (ON LINE)	C
2165-3925	OPEN JOURNAL OF APPLIED SCIENCES	C
9999-111X	OPEN JOURNAL OF BIOCHEMISTRY AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	C
2578-0204	OPEN JOURNAL OF CARDIOLOGY & HEART DISEASES	C
2164-3164	OPEN JOURNAL OF CIVIL ENGINEERING	C
2162-5816	OPEN JOURNAL OF CLINICAL DIAGNOSTICS.	C
2162-1993	OPEN JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY	C
2165-7432	OPEN JOURNAL OF ENDOCRINE AND METABOLIC DISEASES	C
2165-7459	OPEN JOURNAL OF EPIDEMIOLOGY	C
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2165-3372	OPEN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL MICROBIOLOGY	C
2165-3380	OPEN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL MICROBIOLOGY	C
2160-8792	OPEN JOURNAL OF OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY	C
2325-7091	OPEN JOURNAL OF OPTIMIZATION	C
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2160-5629	OPEN JOURNAL OF UROLOGY	C
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2177-6504	OPINIÕES	C

2171-8814	OPTICA PURA Y APLICADA	C
2160-8881	OPTICS AND PHOTONICS JOURNAL	C
2509-8837	ORAL CANCER	C
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2471-8726	ORAL HEALTH CASE REPORTS	C
1741-9409	ORAL ONCOLOGY EXTRA	C
2474-7610	ORGANIC AND MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL	C
1847-5450	ORGANIZATION, TECHNOLOGY & MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION	C
2147-0634	ORIGINAL INVESTIGATION	C
0148-3897	ORNAMENT	C
1808-7221	ORNITHOLOGIA (CEMAVE/IBAMA. IMPRESSO)	C
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1097-797X	ORTHODONTIC PRODUCTS	C
0030-5944	ORTODONTIA	C
2233-6052	OSONG PUBLIC HEALTH AND RESEARCH PERSPECTIVES	C
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2405-5255	OSTEOPOROSIS AND SARCOPENIA (IMPRESSO)	C
2574-2167	OTA INTERNATIONAL	C
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2476-2490	OTOLARYNGOLOGY OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL	C
2398-4937	OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY-HEAD AND NECK SURGERY	C
2174-1425	OTROLUNES	C
1853-4457	OTROS LOGOS - REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS CRÍTICOS	C
0840-7339	OUR SCHOOLS, OUR SELVES	C
1806-7530	OUTRAS PALAVRAS (BRASÍLIA)	C
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2278-0335	PANAMERICAN JOURNAL OF TRAUMA, CRITICAL CARE & EMERGENCY	C
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1578-7265	PAPELES SALMANTINOS DE EDUCACIÓN	C
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1980-4342	PARADIGMAS: FILOSOFIA, REALIDADE E ARTES	C
2308-796X	PARAGUAY ORAL RESEARCH	C
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2250-1991	PARIPEX - INDIAN JOURNAL OF RESEARCH	C
2571-712X	PARTICLES	C
1575-2259	PASAJES (VALENCIA)	C
1665-4986	PASO DE GATO	C

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2090-8091	PATHOLOGY RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL	C
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2175-7003	PEDAGOGIA EM AÇÃO	C
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2215-2016	PERSPECTIVAS EN INVESTIGACIÓN	C
0100-2929	PERSPECTIVAS MÉDICAS (FMJ)	C
2236-8868	PERSPECTIVAS ONLINE: BIOLÓGICAS E SAÚDE	C
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2316-5146	PESQUISA & TECNOLOGIA	C
0104-9070	PESQUISA AGROPECUÁRIA GAÚCHA	C
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2595-9409	PESQUISAS EM TEOLOGIA	C
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2379-6367	PHARMACY & PHARMACOLOGY INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL	C
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2182-4371	PHILOSOPHY@LISBON	C
0554-1182	PHYKOS	C
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2446-564X	PHYSICAE ORGANUM	C
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2348-0130	PHYSICAL SCIENCE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL	C
0959-8472	PHYSICS REVIEW (DEDDINGTON)	C
2083-8204	PHYSIOTHERAPY (WARSAW)	C
2516-7081	PHYSIOTHERAPY RESEARCH AND REPORTS	C
2471-2906	PHYTOBIOMES JOURNAL	C
2360-9516	PINNACLE MEDICINE & MEDICAL SCIENCES	C
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1679-5938	POLÍTICA ECONÔMICA EM FOCO	C
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2526-4982	POSGERE. PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM REVISTA	C
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2446-9793	PROFESSARE	C
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2317-3394	PSICOLOGIA, DIVERSIDADE E SAÚDE	C
1646-6977	PSICOLOGIA.PT	C
2316-2449	PSICOPATOLOGIA FENOMENOLÓGICA CONTEMPORÂNEA	C
1807-3379	PSIQUE	C
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1359-7620	PSYCHIATRY ON-LINE	C
2236-4374	PUBLICAÇÕES DA ESCOLA DA AGU (IMPRESSO)	C
1676-8485	PUBLICATIO UEPG. CIÊNCIAS BIOLÓGICAS E DA SAÚDE (IMPRESSO)	C
1809-0273	PUBLICATIO UEPG. CIÊNCIAS BIOLÓGICAS E DA SAÚDE (ONLINE)	C
2316-3763	PUBLICATIO UEPG: CIENCIAS HUMANAS, LINGUISTICA, LETRAS E AR	C
2304-6775	PUBLICATIONS	C
2526-4729	PUÇÁ: REVISTA DE COMUNICAÇÃO E CULTURA NA AMAZÔNIA	C
2176-2465	PULMÃO RJ ATUALIZAÇÕES TEMÁTICAS	C
2531-0429	PULMONOLOGY	C
2175-6651	PULSAR (JUNDIAÍ)	C
0033-4413	PUPPET MASTER	C
2237-0617	QORPUS	C
1825-8301	QUADERNI DI DIDATTICA DELLA SCRITTURA	C

1124-4542	QUALE STATO	C
2368-6669	QUALITY ADVANCEMENT IN NURSING EDUCATION - AVANÇÉES EN I	C
1479-1072	QUALITY IN PRIMARY CARE (PRINT)	C
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2058-9565	QUANTUM SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	C
2196-5609	QUANTUM STUDIES: MATHEMATICS AND FOUNDATIONS	C
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2394-6709	RA JOURNAL OF APPLIED RESEARCH (ONLINE)	C
2236-3548	RABISCO: REVISTA DE PSICANÁLISE	C
0288-2043	RADIATION MEDICINE	C
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1133-1747	RADIOPROTECCIÓN (MADRID)	C
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2595-5373	RBG - REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE GASTRONOMIA	C
2236-1103	R-BITS - REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA EM SAÚ	C
1679-8953	RBUS. REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ULTRA-SONOGRAFIA	C
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1876-1429	RECENT PATENTS ON FOOD, NUTRITION & AGRICULTURE	C
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1868-2405	REFRACTORIES WORLDFORUM	C
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2176-4565	REVISTA CIATEC-UPF	C
2318-4213	REVISTA CICLOS	C
2526-026X	REVISTA CIDADANIA E ACESSO À JUSTIÇA	C

2448-1092	REVISTA CIDADES	C
2447-2301	REVISTA CIÊNCIA & SABERES - FACEMA	C
2178-9436	REVISTA CIÊNCIA & TECNOLOGIA: FATEC-JB	C
2317-0816	REVISTA CIÊNCIA (IN) CENA	C
2527-0869	REVISTA CIÊNCIA CONTEMPORÂNEA	C
2358-3134	REVISTA CIÊNCIA E ESTUDOS ACADÊMICOS DE MEDICINA	C
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1807-5916	REVISTA CIÊNCIA E SOCIEDADE	C
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2527-0214	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS E ODONTOLOGIA	C
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2178-2768	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA FACULDADE CAMPO REAL	C
2448-3354	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA FACULDADES DO SABER	C
2525-5045	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA FAGOC - SAÚDE	C
2526-3994	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA FATECIE (ONLINE)	C
2594-8849	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA FOZ (ONLINE)	C
2359-4632	REVISTA CIENTIFICA INTEGRADA UNAERP CAMPUS GUARUJÁ	C
2177-3645	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA INTR@CIÊNCIA	C
1413-8263	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA RURAL	C
1316-869X	REVISTA CIENTIFICA UNET	C
2175-4462	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA VIRTUAL DA ESCOLA SUPERIOR DE ADVOCACIA	C

2318-9509	REVISTA CIPERJ	C
2447-6927	REVISTA CLEA	C
2525-4502	REVISTA CNJ	C
2422-0582	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE INVESTIGACIONES AGROINDUSTRIALES	C
2500-5006	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE NEFROLOGIA (ONLINE)	C
1692-7257	REVISTA COLOMBIANA DE TECNOLOGIAS DE AVANZADA	C
2359-2494	REVISTA COM CENSO ESTUDOS EDUCACIONAIS DO DISTRITO FEDER	C
2595-1890	REVISTA COMCIÊNCIA	C
2448-1904	REVISTA COMING - COMMUNICATIONS AND INNOVATIONS GAZETT	C
2526-3900	REVISTA COMPARTILHAR	C
2316-6665	REVISTA CONEXÃO ELETRÔNICA	C
2358-839X	REVISTA CONEXÕES GERAES	C
2238-0159	REVISTA CONEXÕES PARCIAIS	C
1982-2960	REVISTA CONGREGA URCAMP (CD-ROM)	C
2447-5068	REVISTA CONTAS ABERTAS	C
1806-0498	REVISTA CONTEMPORÂNEA (UERJ. ONLINE)	C
1808-7558	REVISTA CONTINENTE	C
1980-086X	REVISTA CONTROLE	C
2238-9288	REVISTA CONVERGÊNCIA CRÍTICA	C
2525-9709	REVISTA CONVERSATIO	C
2177-5052	REVISTA COOPEX	C
2176-4174	REVISTA CORDIS- REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE HISTÓRIA SOCIAL DA CID	C
2359-6961	REVISTA CORIXO DE EXTENSÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA	C
2526-7930	REVISTA CORPUS HIPPOCRATICUM	C
2178-7514	REVISTA CPAQV	C
2182-8547	REVISTA CROMA	C
2447-3650	REVISTA CSBEA	C
1981-6146	REVISTA CTEX P&D	C
2545-6180	REVISTA CUADERNOS	C
0864-179X	REVISTA CUADERNOS DE NUESTRA AMÉRICA	C
0258-5995	REVISTA CUBANA DE QUÍMICA	C
2224-5421	REVISTA CUBANA DE QUÍMICA (ONLINE)	C
2447-2913	REVISTA CUIDADO EM ENFERMAGEM	C
1414-7076	REVISTA CULT	C
2175-2214	REVISTA CULTIVANDO O SABER	C
2446-8355	REVISTA CULTURA AGRONÔMICA	C
2359-5620	REVISTA D+	C
2594-4940	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE DIREITO DO TRABALHO (PRII	C
1676-1545	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA BRASILEIRA DE FILOGOLOGIA	C
2176-6517	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA ESPÍRITO-SANTENSE DE LETRAS	C
1982-6680	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA MINEIRA DE LETRAS	C
1984-0853	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA NACIONAL DE DIREITO DO TRABALHO	C
0103-7439	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA NACIONAL DE MUSICA	C
1678-0272	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA PARANAENSE DE LETRAS JURÍDICAS	C
2236-5796	REVISTA DA ACADEMIA PAULISTA DE DIREITO	C
2237-6437	REVISTA DA AFLAG	C
1679-2262	REVISTA DA AJUFERGS	C
2238-0000	REVISTA DA ALESDE	C
0004-5276	REVISTA DA APCD - ASSOCIAÇÃO PAULISTA DE CIRURGIÕES DENTIST/	C
2318-2970	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE ADVOGADOS TRABALHIST.	C

2359-2974	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE ATIVIDADE MOTORA ADAI	C
1983-3164	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE NUTRIÇÃO	C
2357-7894	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE NUTRIÇÃO	C
2358-4653	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO DOS JUÍZES PARA A DEMOCRACIA	C
2359-4128	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO NACIONAL DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO C	C
1646-1290	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE HORTICULTURA	C
2183-9077	REVISTA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE LINGUÍSTICA	C
2175-876X	REVISTA DA CATÓLICA	C
1982-2065	REVISTA DA CIÊNCIA DA ADMINISTRAÇÃO (RECIFE)	C
1984-0322	REVISTA DA DEFENSORIA PÚBLICA DA UNIÃO	C
2177-8116	REVISTA DA DEFENSORIA PÚBLICA DO ESTADO DO RIO GRANDE DO	C
1517-4611	REVISTA DA EAP/APCD	C
0103-3948	REVISTA DA EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA (UEM. IMPRESSO)	C
2236-8957	REVISTA DA EMERJ	C
2348-4602	REVISTA DA ESCOLA DA MAGISTRATURA DO TRF DA 4ª REGIÃO	C
2358-4602	REVISTA DA ESCOLA DA MAGISTRATURA DO TRF DA 4ª REGIÃO	C
1518-918X	REVISTA DA ESCOLA DE MAGISTRATURA REGIONAL FEDERAL	C
2447-3413	REVISTA DA ESDM	C
2595-7589	REVISTA DA ESDM	C
1678-0450	REVISTA DA ESMAL	C
2526-0812	REVISTA DA ESMAM (ONLINE)	C
2178-0501	REVISTA DA ESMA-PB	C
1983-3830	REVISTA DA ESMAT 13	C
1519-8731	REVISTA DA ESMESC	C
2237-8111	REVISTA DA ESTATÍSTICA UFOP	C
2238-9377	REVISTA DA ESTRUTURA DE AÇO	C
2238-0167	REVISTA DA EXTENSÃO DA UFRGS	C
2316-6673	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO ARNALDO JANSSEN	C
1982-2979	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA FMP	C
0870-3116	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA	C
2176-6118	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE ILHÉUS	C
0101-8418	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE ODONTOLOGIA DA UNIVERSIDADE FED	C
0104-7582	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE ODONTOLOGIA DE LINS	C
0566-1854	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE ODONTOLOGIA DE PORTO ALEGRE	C
1413-4012	REVISTA DA FACULDADE DE ODONTOLOGIA. UNIVERSIDADE DE PAS	C
1677-5627	REVISTA DA FADIVALE	C
2184-2973	REVISTA DA FEDERAÇÃO NACIONAL DE MEDIAÇÃO DE CONFLITOS	C
1517-5286	REVISTA DA FUNDAÇÃO ESCOLA SUPERIOR DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLIC	C
1677-9088	REVISTA DA GAMA E SOUZA	C
1983-1374	REVISTA DA GRADUAÇÃO (PUCRS)	C
2595-3605	REVISTA DA MOSTRA DE TRABALHOS DE CONCLUSÃO DE CURSO - T	C
0102-4353	REVISTA DA OAB SÃO PAULO	C
1518-6075	REVISTA DA OLIMPÍADA	C
2319-0671	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO ESTADO DE SANTA CATARIN	C
0102-8065	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO	C
1808-897X	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO ESTADO DO ESPÍRITO SANT	C
0101-1480	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO ESTADO DO RIO GRANDE D	C
1806-0862	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO MUNICÍPIO DE CURITIBA	C
1806-5619	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO MUNICÍPIO DE FORTALEZA	C
2236-3726	REVISTA DA PROCURADORIA-GERAL DO MUNICÍPIO DE JOÃO PESS	C

2526-1894	REVISTA DA PRODUÇÃO INDUSTRIAL & SERVIÇOS	C
0100-7246	REVISTA DA PROPRIEDADE INDUSTRIAL	C
2359-4284	REVISTA DA RECEITA FEDERAL - ESTUDOS TRIBUTÁRIOS E ADUANEI	C
1980-7694	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE ARBORIZAÇÃO URBANA	C
1413-9006	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE ATIVIDADE MOTORA ADAP1	C
1679-1010	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE CLÍNICA MÉDICA	C
1678-040X	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE CEARENSE DE CARDIOLOGIA	C
0103-8559	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE DE CARDIOLOGIA DO ESTADO DE SAO PAUL	C
0101-0395	REVISTA DA SOCIEDADE PAULISTA DE ORTODONTIA (CESSOU EM 19	C
2317-3777	REVISTA DANÇA	C
2526-3528	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO EM SAÚDE (ONLINE)	C
2595-0045	REVISTA DE AGROECOLOGIA NO SEMIÁRIDO	C
2179-5959	REVISTA DE AGROTECNOLOGIA	C
1676-8566	REVISTA DE APARECIDA	C
2526-0103	REVISTA DE ARGUMENTAÇÃO E HERMENÊUTICA JURÍDICA (ONLINE)	C
2178-9789	REVISTA DE ARTETERAPIA DA AATESP	C
2525-9695	REVISTA DE BIODIREITO E DIREITOS DOS ANIMAIS	C
1982-2774	REVISTA DE BIOLOGIA E SAÚDE DA UNISEP	C
1807-9652	REVISTA DE BIOLOGIA NEOTROPICAL	C
2238-6629	REVISTA DE BIOTECNOLOGIA & CIÊNCIAS	C
0103-8575	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA & TECNOLOGIA	C
2448-4091	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA E INOVAÇÃO DO IF FARROUPILHA	C
2238-1252	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA	C
2447-1518	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA - FATEC LINS	C
0329-8922	REVISTA DE CIENCIA Y TECNOLOGÍA	C
2526-415X	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA, TECNOLOGIA E INOVAÇÃO	C
2183-041X	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS AGRARIAS	C
0871-018X	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS AGRÁRIAS (LISBOA)	C
1677-6062	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS AGRO-AMBIENTAIS (ONLINE)	C
1676-9732	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS AGROVETERINÁRIAS (UDESC)	C
1679-1983	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS DA SAÚDE NOVA ESPERANÇA	C
0719-4013	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS DE LA ACTIVIDAD FÍSICA	C
1885-7019	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS DEL DEPORTE	C
2238-7102	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS EXATAS	C
2175-5620	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS EXATAS E NATURAIS (UNICENTRO)	C
0034-7787	REVISTA DE CIENCIAS JURÍDICAS	C
2595-3990	REVISTA DE CIÊNCIAS POLICIAIS	C
1679-5458	REVISTA DE CIRURGIA E TRAUMATOLOGIA BUCO-MAXILO-FACIAL (I	C
1807-5274	REVISTA DE CLÍNICA E PESQUISA ODONTOLÓGICA (IMPRESSO) / JOL	C
2525-670X	REVISTA DE COMUNICAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA	C
1647-5801	REVISTA DE CONCORRÊNCIA E REGULAÇÃO	C
2595-9840	REVISTA DE CONSTITUCIONALIZAÇÃO DO DIREITO BRASILEIRO	C
2316-5499	REVISTA DE CONTRATOS PÚBLICOS	C
2526-0065	REVISTA DE CRIMINOLOGIAS E POLITICAS CRIMINAIS (ONLINE)	C
1510-3714	REVISTA DE DERECHO - UNIVERSIDAD CATÓLICA DÁMASO A. LARRA	C
2545-6431	REVISTA DE DERECHO DEL CONSUMIDOR	C
0123-6458	REVISTA DE DERECHO Y ECONOMÍA	C
2358-9582	REVISTA DE DESIGN, TECNOLOGIA E SOCIEDADE	C
1806-8790	REVISTA DE DIREITO (VIÇOSA)	C
2317-7349	REVISTA DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO CONTEMPORÂNEO	C

2526-0073	REVISTA DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO E GESTÃO PÚBLICA (ONLINE)	C
2526-8120	REVISTA DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO E INFRAESTRUTURA	C
2236-5338	REVISTA DE DIREITO ADUANEIRO, MARÍTIMO E PORTUÁRIO	C
0100-1582	REVISTA DE DIREITO AGRÁRIO	C
2526-0081	REVISTA DE DIREITO AGRÁRIO E AGROAMBIENTAL (ONLINE)	C
2525-9628	REVISTA DE DIREITO AMBIENTAL E SOCIOAMBIENTALISMO (ONLINE)	C
2594-5432	REVISTA DE DIREITO CONSTITUCIONAL INTERNACIONAL E COMPAR.	C
2357-8440	REVISTA DE DIREITO COSMOPOLITA	C
1808-5822	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA ADVOCEF	C
1981-1950	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA DEFENSORIA PÚBLICA	C
2526-9348	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA EMPRESA E DOS NEGÓCIOS	C
2447-6536	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA FACULDADE GUANAMBI	C
0101-2096	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA PROCURADORIA GERAL DO ESTADO DO RIC	C
1984-7920	REVISTA DE DIREITO DA UNIGRANRIO	C
1981-1020	REVISTA DE DIREITO DAS NOVAS TECNOLOGIAS	C
2446-6166	REVISTA DE DIREITO DAS SOCIEDADES E DOS VALORES MOBILIÁRIO	C
2358-2057	REVISTA DE DIREITO DE FAMÍLIA E DAS SUCESSÕES	C
2526-0227	REVISTA DE DIREITO DE FAMÍLIA E SUCESSÃO (ONLINE)	C
2692-8695	REVISTA DE DIREITO DE LÍNGUA PORTUGUESA	C
2526-1592	REVISTA DE DIREITO DO IAP (ONLINE)	C
1981-2493	REVISTA DE DIREITO DO TERCEIRO SETOR	C
2179-1155	REVISTA DE DIREITO DOM ALBERTO	C
2525-9687	REVISTA DE DIREITO E SUSTENTABILIDADE (ONLINE)	C
2177-5486	REVISTA DE DIREITO EMPRESARIAL E RECUPERACIONAL	C
2525-460X	REVISTA DE DIREITO FIBRA LEX	C
2526-6284	REVISTA DE DIREITO INTERNACIONAL E GLOBALIZAÇÃO ECONÔMIC	C
2526-0200	REVISTA DE DIREITO PENAL, PROCESSO PENAL E CONSTITUIÇÃO	C
1646-9119	REVISTA DE DIREITO PÚBLICO (COIMBRA)	C
2594-813X	REVISTA DE DIREITO PÚBLICO CONTEMPORÂNEO	C
1678-7102	REVISTA DE DIREITO PÚBLICO DA ECONOMIA	C
2526-4451	REVISTA DE DIREITO RECUPERACIONAL E EMPRESA	C
2525-9881	REVISTA DE DIREITO SOCIAIS E POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS (ONLINE)	C
1982-663X	REVISTA DE DIREITO TJRJ	C
2526-0138	REVISTA DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO E FINANCEIRO	C
2525-989X	REVISTA DE DIREITO URBANÍSTICO, CIDADE E ALTERIDADE (ONLINE)	C
2525-9911	REVISTA DE DIREITO, ARTE E LITERATURA (ONLINE)	C
2526-0057	REVISTA DE DIREITO, ECONOMIA E DESENVOLVIMENTO SUSTENTÁV	C
2526-0030	REVISTA DE DIREITO, GLOBALIZAÇÃO E RESPONSABILIDADE NAS REI	C
2526-0049	REVISTA DE DIREITO, GOVERNANÇA E NOVAS TECNOLOGIAS (ONLIN	C
2526-0014	REVISTA DE DIREITO, INOVAÇÃO, PROPRIEDADE INTELECTUAL E COI	C
2525-9903	REVISTA DE DIREITOS FUNDAMENTAIS NAS RELAÇÕES DO TRABALH	C
2526-0022	REVISTA DE DIREITOS HUMANOS E EFETIVIDADE	C
2526-0197	REVISTA DE DIREITOS HUMANOS EM PERSPECTIVA (ONLINE)	C
2525-9865	REVISTA DE DIREITOS SOCIAIS, SEGURIDADE E PREVIDÊNCIA SOCIAL	C
2318-9290	REVISTA DE DIVULGAÇÃO INTERDISCIPLINAR VIRTUAL	C
1980-458X	REVISTA DE DOCTRINA 4. REGIÃO	C
0101-8868	REVISTA DE DOCTRINA E JURISPRUDÊNCIA	C
2529-976X	REVISTA DE ECOCARDIOGRAFÍA - PRÁTICA Y OTRAS TÉCNICAS DE IM	C
2526-4109	REVISTA DE ECONOMIA POLÍTICA E PENSAMENTO CRÍTICO	C
2526-9089	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO	C

1983-5280	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO ANEC	C
2316-7556	REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO HISTÓRICA	C
1133-0546	REVISTA DE EDUCACIÓN FÍSICA	C
2446-5739	REVISTA DE ENFERMAGEM DA UFJF	C
2358-6508	REVISTA DE ENGENHARIA CIVIL IMED	C
2176-7270	REVISTA DE ENGENHARIA E TECNOLOGIA	C
0101-5001	REVISTA DE ENSINO DE ENGENHARIA	C
2595-7643	REVISTA DE ENSINO E CULTURA	C
1852-0669	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS MARÍTIMOS Y SOCIALES	C
2359-3679	REVISTA DE ESTUDIOS SARAMAGUIANOS	C
0871-682X	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS ANGLO-PORTUGUESES	C
2073-9109	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS CABO-VERDIANOS	C
2525-2984	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS E DEBATES	C
2238-9180	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS JURÍDICOS E SOCIAIS	C
2359-1226	REVISTA DE EXTENSÃO UENF	C
2346-9986	REVISTA DE EXTENSION UNIVERSITARIA E+	C
1646-9127	REVISTA DE FINANÇAS PÚBLICAS E DIREITO FISCAL	C
2525-9679	REVISTA DE FORMAS CONSENSUAIS DE SOLUÇÃO DE CONFLITOS	C
2525-9849	REVISTA DE GÊNERO, SEXUALIDADE E DIREITO (ONLINE)	C
2448-7368	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFÍA AGRÍCOLA	C
0719-0573	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFIA ESPACIOS	C
1453-5068	REVISTA DE GEOMORFOLOGIE	C
2448-3052	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E NEGÓCIOS DO ESPORTE	C
2236-0301	REVISTA DE GESTÃO E OPERAÇÕES PRODUTIVAS	C
2525-376X	REVISTA DE GRADUAÇÃO DA USP	C
1984-6894	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA (SALVADOR)	C
2179-2305	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DA ARTE E ARQUEOLOGIA	C
0870-0958	REVISTA DE HISTÓRIA DAS IDEIAS	C
0717-0491	REVISTA DE HUMANIDADES (SANTIAGO)	C
1809-5585	REVISTA DE INFORMÁTICA APLICADA	C
2175-2745	REVISTA DE INFORMÁTICA TEÓRICA E APLICADA: RITA	C
1808-6217	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA DO UNIFEG	C
1677-3527	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA EM ODONTOLOGIA	C
2545-8604	REVISTA DE INTERÉS PÚBLICO	C
1808-0006	REVISTA DE INVESTIGAÇÃO BIOMÉDICA	C
2250-3189	REVISTA DE INVESTIGACIÓN DEL DEPARTAMENTO DE HUMANIDAD	C
1517-2686	REVISTA DE JURISPRUDÊNCIA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL FEDERAL DA	C
0370-3908	REVISTA DE LA ACADEMIA COLOMBIANA DE CIENCIAS EXACTAS, FÍS	C
2007-3798	REVISTA DE LA ESCUELA JACOBEO DE POSGRADO	C
1655-7063	REVISTA DE LA ESCUELA NACIONAL DE ENFERMERIA Y OBSTETRÍCIA	C
2448-8933	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE DERECHO DE MÉXICO	C
0041-8676	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE AGRONOMÍA (LA PLATA)	C
0375-1066	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE CIENCIAS MÉDICAS, UNIVERSIDAD CEI	C
0188-3658	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE DERECHO Y CIENCIAS SOCIALES. UNIV	C
0121-246X	REVISTA DE LA FACULTAD DE ODONTOLOGIA UNIVERSIDAD DE ANT	C
1688-8499	REVISTA DE LEGISLACIÓN URUGUAYA: SISTEMATIZADA Y ANALIZAD	C
2317-3610	REVISTA DE LETRA EM LETRA	C
2316-2635	REVISTA DE LETRAS DOM ALBERTO	C
1984-318X	REVISTA DE LÍNGUA E LITERATURA	C
2237-8103	REVISTA DE MATEMÁTICA DA UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE OURO PF	C

0034-8554	REVISTA DE MEDICINA (USP)	C
2447-6595	REVISTA DE MEDICINA DA UFC (ONLINE)	C
0100-1302	REVISTA DE MEDICINA DA UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO CEARÁ	C
0375-1074	REVISTA DE MEDICINA VETERINARIA (BOGOTÁ)	C
0122-9354	REVISTA DE MEDICINA VETERINARIA ED: UNIVERSIDAD DE LA SALLE	C
1885-5210	REVISTA DE MEDICINA Y CINE	C
2519-5352	REVISTA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE MINERO Y MINERÍA	C
2525-9830	REVISTA DE MOVIMENTOS SOCIAIS E CONFLITOS (ONLINE)	C
0163-0350	REVISTA DE MÚSICA LATINOAMERICANA (PRINT)	C
2357-9617	REVISTA DE NUTRIÇÃO E VIGILÂNCIA EM SAÚDE / JOURNAL OF NUT	C
1519-681X	REVISTA DE ODONTOLOGIA (SÃO PAULO. IMPRESSO)	C
1807-2577	REVISTA DE ODONTOLOGIA DA UNESP (ONLINE)	C
1983-5183	REVISTA DE ODONTOLOGIA DA UNICID - UNIVERSIDADE CIDADE DE	C
2174-0798	REVISTA DE ODONTOLOGIA LATINOAMERICANA	C
1886-3450	REVISTA DE OPERATORIA DENTAL Y BIOMATERIALES	C
0301-0406	REVISTA DE PATOLOGIA TROPICAL (IMPRESSO)	C
1980-8178	REVISTA DE PATOLOGIA TROPICAL (ONLINE)	C
2595-1769	REVISTA DE PEDIATRIA DA SOPERJ (ON-LINE)	C
1676-1014	REVISTA DE PEDIATRIA SOPERJ	C
2525-9636	REVISTA DE PESQUISA E EDUCAÇÃO JURÍDICA	C
2525-9822	REVISTA DE POLÍTICA JUDICIÁRIA, GESTÃO E ADMINISTRAÇÃO DA JI	C
2594-3855	REVISTA DE POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS E SEGURANÇA SOCIAL	C
2448-4067	REVISTA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO DA FACULDADE CIDADE VERDE	C
0101-823X	REVISTA DE PREVIDÊNCIA SOCIAL	C
2358-7164	REVISTA DE PROCESSO COMPARADO	C
2525-9814	REVISTA DE PROCESSO, JURISDIÇÃO E EFETIVIDADE DA JUSTIÇA (ON	C
2224-7920	REVISTA DE PRODUCCIÓN ANIMAL (EN LÍNEA)	C
2256-1102	REVISTA DE PSICOLOGÍA UNIVERSIDAD DE ANTIOQUIA	C
1133-2670	REVISTA DE PSICOPEDAGOGÍA	C
2179-2739	REVISTA DE SAÚDE	C
2357-7908	REVISTA DE SAÚDE DO HOSPITAL SANTA IZABEL	C
1981-9722	REVISTA DE SAÚDE PÚBLICA DE MATO GROSSO DO SUL	C
2175-1323	REVISTA DE SAÚDE PÚBLICA DE SANTA CATARINA	C
2595-4474	REVISTA DE SAÚDE PÚBLICA DO PARANÁ	C
1963-5605	REVISTA DE SISTEMA DE INFORMAÇÃO DA FSMA	C
2237-2903	REVISTA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTAÇÃO - RSC	C
2526-0251	REVISTA DE SOCIOLOGIA, ANTROPOLOGIA E CULTURA JURÍDICA	C
2542-2413	REVISTA DE TELEMEDICINA E SAÚDE ELETRÔNICA	C
2176-8986	REVISTA DE TEOLOGIA DA FACULDADE FAIFA	C
2525-9660	REVISTA DE TEORIAS DA DEMOCRACIA E DIREITOS POLÍTICOS	C
2525-9644	REVISTA DE TEORIAS DA JUSTIÇA, DA DECISÃO E DA ARGUMENTAÇÃO	C
2525-9652	REVISTA DE TEORIAS E FILOSOFIAS DO ESTADO	C
2318-4760	REVISTA DE TEORIAS E PRÁTICAS EDUCACIONAIS	C
2595-5772	REVISTA DE TRABALHOS ACADÊMICOS LUSOFONA	C
2385-779X	REVISTA DE VICTIMOLOGÍA / JOURNAL OF VICTIMOLOGY	C
2318-0536	REVISTA DEBATE ECONÔMICO	C
2236-918X	REVISTA DEBATES EM PSIQUIATRIA	C
2385-6203	REVISTA DEL CONGRÉS INTERNACIONAL DE DOCÈNCIA	C
2346-3473	REVISTA DEL INSTITUTO COLOMBIANO DE DERECHO PROCESAL	C
1996-3696	REVISTA DEL INSTITUTO DE MEDICINA TROPICAL	C

2447-9403	REVISTA DEMOCRÁTICA	C
1807-2488	REVISTA DENTAL PRESS DE ESTÉTICA (MARINGÁ)	C
2595-4792	REVISTA DESLIMITES	C
1677-8936	REVISTA DEVIR	C
2238-4618	REVISTA DI	C
1413-7097	REVISTA DIALÉTICA DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO	C
2238-7374	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS ACADÊMICOS	C
2448-1270	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS ACADÊMICOS	C
0719-7705	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS EN MERCOSUR	C
2595-5845	REVISTA DIÁLOGOS ESTRATÉGICOS	C
1806-2962	REVISTA DIGITAL ART&	C
2526-8155	REVISTA DIGITAL DA ACADEMIA PARAENSE DE ODONTOLOGIA	C
1853-3256	REVISTA DIGITAL DE POLITICAS LINGUISTICAS	C
2618-2882	REVISTA DIGITAL INTERNACIONAL DE LEXICOLOGÍA, LEXICOGRAFÍA	C
2446-5941	REVISTA DIGITAL SIMONSEN	C
2527-1784	REVISTA DIORITO	C
2447-987X	REVISTA DIPLOMATIZE	C
2250-7558	REVISTA DIRECHO PENAL	C
2527-1563	REVISTA DIREITO (S)EM FRONTEIRAS	C
2446-8908	REVISTA DIREITO DAS RELAÇÕES SOCIAIS E TRABALHISTAS	C
2525-4065	REVISTA DIREITO DO ESTADO - CULONISTAS	C
2526-4753	REVISTA DIREITO E CIDADANIA	C
1679-3803	REVISTA DIREITO E CIDADANIA (ROLÂNDIA)	C
2448-4512	REVISTA DIREITO E DEMOCRACIA	C
2318-6879	REVISTA DIREITO E SOCIEDADE: REFLEXÕES CONTEMPORÂNEAS	C
2179-8176	REVISTA DIREITO EM MOVIMENTO	C
1982-9418	REVISTA DIREITO HOJE	C
2237-955X	REVISTA DIREITO IZABELA HENDRIX	C
2527-1555	REVISTA DIREITO SEM FRONTEIRAS - ONLINE	C
2595-7155	REVISTA DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO INTERNACIONAL ATUAL	C
2316-3054	REVISTA DIREITOS EMERGENTES NA SOCIEDADE GLOBAL	C
2595-8348	REVISTA DIREITOS HUMANOS E SOCIEDADE	C
2526-0839	REVISTA DISCURSO & IMAGEM VISUAL EM EDUCAÇÃO	C
2318-2016	REVISTA DIVERSITAS	C
2594-4207	REVISTA DIZER	C
2594-5718	REVISTA DO AMBIENTE DE NITERÓI	C
0104-5849	REVISTA DO BNDES	C
1519-6968	REVISTA DO CEAM	C
2319-0876	REVISTA DO CEJUR/TJSC	C
1413-8026	REVISTA DO CEP-PA	C
2177-9325	REVISTA DO CFCH (CENTRO DE FILOSOFIA E CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS DA	C
2594-9578	REVISTA DO COLETIVO SECONBA	C
2236-840X	REVISTA DO CONGRESSO MINEIRO DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO E DIREI'	C
2236-2363	REVISTA DO CONSELHO NACIONAL DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO	C
2176-1094	REVISTA DO CURSO DE DIREITO (SÃO BERNARDO DO CAMPO. ONLII	C
2358-0607	REVISTA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DA FSG	C
1518-3408	REVISTA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL DE M	C
1809-3779	REVISTA DO CURSO DE LETRAS	C
1809-161X	REVISTA DO DEPARTAMENTO DE DIREITO DO TRABALHO E DA SEGL	C
1983-5361	REVISTA DO DEPARTAMENTO DE DIREITO PÚBLICO	C

2177-3556	REVISTA DO DERC	C
1807-958X	REVISTA DO DIREITO DA ENERGIA	C
2182-8768	REVISTA DO DIREITO DE LÍNGUA PORTUGUESA	C
2525-9857	REVISTA DO DIREITO DO TRABALHO E MEIO AMBIENTE DO TRABALHADOR	C
1413-4543	REVISTA DO DIREITO IMOBILIÁRIO	C
2177-2991	REVISTA DO DIREITO UNIDAVI	C
2527-1377	REVISTA DO FÓRUM INTERNACIONAL DE IDEIAS	C
1980-0428	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS	C
2359-0017	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS	C
2596-0075	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE DIREITO CONSTITUCIONAL E CIDADANIA	C
0020-3890	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE GEOGRAFIA E HISTORIA MILITAR DO BRASIL	C
2238-6416	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DE LATICÍNIOS CÂNDIDO TOSTES	C
0104-5466	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO DOS ADVOGADOS DO PARANA	C
0103-2674	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO FLORESTAL	C
1981-9528	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO ESPÍRITO SAÍ	C
1981-7770	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO MARANHÃO	C
2526-4958	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO RIO GRANDE	C
1981-8763	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HUMANITAS UNISINOS (ONLINE)	C
2237-2261	REVISTA DO MESTRADO EM DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SANTA CATARINA	C
0870-6107	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO	C
1413-3873	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO (RIO DE JANEIRO)	C
2359-0955	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DE CONTAS DO ESTADO DO PARANÁ	C
1809-5917	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO ESTADO DE GOIÁS	C
1806-2598	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO ESTADO DE SERGIPE	C
1980-5535	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO ESTADO DO PARÁ	C
1983-3229	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO TRABALHO	C
1981-3457	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO TRABALHO DO MATO GROSSO	C
0103-6769	REVISTA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO MILITAR	C
2317-8523	REVISTA DO NÚCLEO DE ESTUDOS DE ECONOMIA CATARINENSE	C
2318-1664	REVISTA DO PORTAL JURÍDICO INVESTIDURA	C
2594-4746	REVISTA DO PROFESSOR DE FÍSICA (ONLINE)	C
1980-7481	REVISTA DO TCE - PI	C
2176-7181	REVISTA DO TCMRJ	C
0076-8855	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO 3. REGIÃO	C
0104-7027	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA 10ª REGIÃO	C
1679-8694	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA 15. REGIÃO	C
1980-9913	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA 7ª REGIÃO	C
0100-1736	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA 8ª. REGIÃO	C
0100-5448	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA 9. REGIÃO	C
1984-3658	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA DÉCIMA SEGUNDA REGIÃO	C
1981-6715	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA VIGÉSIMA PRIMEIRA REGIÃO	C
0103-703X	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL FEDERAL 1. REGIÃO	C
1982-1506	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL FEDERAL DA TERCEIRA REGIÃO	C
1981-9684	REVISTA DOS ESTUDANTES DE DIREITO DA UNIVERSIDADE DE BRASÍLIA	C
2318-3136	REVISTA DOS TRIBUNAIS SUL	C
2237-2334	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO A DISTÂNCIA	C
1519-6194	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO E CIDADANIA	C
2595-9980	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO E CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS	C
1984-3437	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO E LINGUAGEM (ONLINE)	C
2316-8919	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO EM REDE: FORMAÇÃO E PRÁTICA DOCENTE	C

2358-9868	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO EM SAÚDE	C
2317-0603	REVISTA EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA UNIFAFIBE	C
2527-1083	REVISTA EDUCARE (ONLINE)	C
2244-7318	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA ACTIVIDAD FÍSICA Y CIENCIAS	C
2007-9249	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE EDUCACIÓN ESPECIAL Y FAMILIA	C
2531-1565	REVISTA ELECTRÓNICA DE ESTUDIOS PENALES Y DE LA SEGURIDAD	C
2236-4269	REVISTA ELETÔNICA JURÍDICA FACECLA	C
2319-0310	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA AD JUDICIA	C
2446-7634	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ARGENTINA-BRASIL DE TECNOLOGIAS DA INF	C
2237-5597	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ARTIGOS JURÍDICOS E DIREITO EM DEBATE (R	C
2175-1846	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA CIENTÍFICA INOVAÇÃO E TECNOLOGIA	C
2317-3556	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA EJUD DA 17ª REGIÃO	C
2526-1290	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA ESMPE	C
1980-7570	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DE CAMPOS	C
2448-3303	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FACULDADE DE DIREITO DE PELOTAS	C
2595-8178	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FACULDADE INVEST DE CIÊNCIAS E TECNO	C
2179-1880	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DA FEATI	C
2594-7966	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CIÊNCIAS HUMANAS	C
2179-8443	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE CULTURAS E EDUCAÇÃO	C
1981-9439	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE DIREITO INTERNACIONAL	C
2318-4892	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE DIREITO PENAL	C
2357-9293	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE DIREITO TRIBUTÁRIO DA ABDF	C
2448-3257	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE DIREITO, DEMOCRACIA E SOCIEDADE	C
2317-1170	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE EDUCAÇÃO DE ALAGOAS ¿ REDUC	C
2237-3462	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE EDUCAÇÃO E CIÊNCIA	C
1808-0804	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE FARMÁCIA	C
1519-8219	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA	C
2236-5044	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA DO CEJURPS RICC	C
2527-2071	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE ODONTOLOGIA E CLINICA INTEGRADA DA	C
2177-0425	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DE TECNOLOGIA E CUTURA	C
2178-2938	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DIADORIM CULTURAL	C
2526-4745	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DIREITO E CONHECIMENTO	C
1981-8386	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO CEJUR	C
2176-977X	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO CURSO DE DIREITO (PUC MINAS SERRO)	C
2178-5651	REVISTA ELETRONICA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO 1A. R	C
2238-6114	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DO P	C
1984-1604	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO VESTIBULAR	C
2177-4641	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DON DOMÊNICO	C
2179-2275	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA LABVERDE	C
2176-6894	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA MUSIFAL	C
1983-9006	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA NUTRITIME	C
2526-1223	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA OAB/RJ	C
2316-9664	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA PAULISTA DE MATEMÁTICA	C
1983-9952	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA PRODUÇÃO & ENGENHARIA	C
1980-5969	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA S@ABER	C
2359-6074	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA SABERES MÚLTIPLOS	C
2316-6266	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA SAPERE AUDE	C
2238-4111	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA SAÚDE E CIÊNCIA	C
1984-0993	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA TECCEN	C
2317-5451	REVISTA ELO - DIÁLOGOS EM EXTENSÃO	C

1980-3915	REVISTA EMERGÊNCIA (NOVO HAMBURGO)	C
1809-0583	REVISTA ENCICLOPÉDIA BIOSFERA	C
2358-0259	REVISTA ENGENHARIA E CONSTRUÇÃO CIVIL	C
2175-0564	REVISTA ENSAIOS	C
1983-6341	REVISTA ENSAIOS E DIÁLOGOS	C
2447-4878	REVISTA ENSAIOS TEOLÓGICOS	C
2594-8806	REVISTA ENSINO DE CIÊNCIAS E HUMANIDADES	C
2176-9524	REVISTA EQUILÍBRIO CORPORAL E SAÚDE	C
2175-4470	REVISTA ESASP: REVISTA CIENTÍFICA VIRTUAL DA ESCOLA SUPERIOR	C
1807-6203	REVISTA ESMAFE	C
0719-8922	REVISTA ESPACIO Y SOCIEDAD	C
2358-2413	REVISTA ESQUERDA PETISTA	C
2526-6918	REVISTA ESTAÇÃO DA LEITURA	C
1807-426X	REVISTA ESTRADAS (PORTO ALEGRE)	C
2183-8402	REVISTA ESTREIA DIÁLOGOS	C
1659-3316	REVISTA ESTUDIOS (EN LÍNEA)	C
2316-4743	REVISTA ESTUDOS DE POLÍTICA	C
2237-8553	REVISTA ESTUDOS LEGISLATIVOS	C
0719-7284	REVISTA EUROPA DEL ESTE UNIDA	C
2526-964X	REVISTA EXPRESSÃO CATÓLICA SAÚDE	C
2238-8710	REVISTA EXPRESSÃO: CULTURA UNIBRASIL	C
2236-5842	REVISTA EXTENSÃO EM DEBATE	C
2446-5151	REVISTA EXTENSIVA	C
2358-2804	REVISTA FAATUAL	C
1679-1851	REVISTA FACTUS (IMPRESSO)	C
1982-5854	REVISTA FAFIRE (IMPRESSO)	C
2179-9660	REVISTA FAIPE	C
2448-4458	REVISTA FATEC GUARULHOS	C
1982-9671	REVISTA FERIDAS, OSTOMIAS & CIA...	C
2526-7353	REVISTA FISIOTERAPIA & REABILITAÇÃO	C
1808-9569	REVISTA FITOS (ALANAC)	C
2359-4829	REVISTA FLAMMAE	C
0556-6592	REVISTA FLORESTAL DEL PERÚ	C
2357-8300	REVISTA FLORESTAN	C
2237-3853	REVISTA FLUMINENSE DE EXTENSÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA	C
1413-2966	REVISTA FLUMINENSE DE ODONTOLOGIA	C
2183-2722	REVISTA FORGES	C
0121-2559	REVISTA FORO	C
2446-6867	REVISTA FÓRUM	C
2176-1671	REVISTA FORUM DE DIREITO CIVIL	C
2238-8508	REVISTA FÓRUM DE DIREITO ECONÔMICO E FINANCEIRO	C
2238-4138	REVISTA FÓRUM TRABALHISTA	C
2595-962X	REVISTA FRONTEIRAS EM PSICOLOGIA	C
2145-8502	REVISTA FUENTES EL REVENTÓN ENERGÉTICO	C
1657-6527	REVISTA FUENTES EL REVENTÓN ENERGÉTICO	C
2178-0668	REVISTA FUNDACOES & OBRAS GEOTECNICAS	C
2317-2754	REVISTA FUNDAMENTOS	C
2526-9682	REVISTA FUNEC CIENTÍFICA - ODONTOLOGIA	C
1138-1663	REVISTA GALEGO-PORTUGUESA DE PSICOLOXÍA E EDUCACIÓN	C
2316-2236	REVISTA GÉFYRA	C

1011-484X	REVISTA GEOGRAFICA DE AMERICA CENTRAL (IMPRESSO)	C
2215-2563	REVISTA GEOGRAFICA DE AMERICA CENTRAL (ONLINE)	C
2447-3545	REVISTA GEPESVIDA	C
1677-2768	REVISTA GERENCIAIS (UNINOVE. IMPRESSO)	C
1984-8153	REVISTA GESTÃO & SAÚDE (CURITIBA)	C
2359-3989	REVISTA GESTÃO EM ENGENHARIA	C
1808-0448	REVISTA GESTÃO INDUSTRIAL (ONLINE)	C
2177-7586	REVISTA GESTÃO PÚBLICA EM CURITIBA	C
2447-8520	REVISTA GESTÃO, INOVAÇÃO E NEGÓCIOS	C
2238-4405	REVISTA GETEC	C
0034-9585	REVISTA GOIANA DE MEDICINA	C
1692-6250	REVISTA GRÁFIA	C
2316-2007	REVISTA GUARÁ	C
2446-9491	REVISTA GUARÁ	C
1645-3298	REVISTA GYMNASIUM	C
1983-0831	REVISTA HISTÓRIA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	C
1980-1637	REVISTA HISTÓRIA CATARINA	C
0797-9282	REVISTA HISTORIA Y DOCENCIA	C
1983-9685	REVISTA HISTORIAR	C
1984-7165	REVISTA HOMEOPATIA BRASILEIRA	C
2316-4808	REVISTA HOMINUM	C
1677-4400	REVISTA HORIZONTE TEOLÓGICO	C
1676-8280	REVISTA HOSPITAL UNIVERSITÁRIO PEDRO ERNESTO (IMPRESSO)	C
1982-7547	REVISTA HUMANIDADES EM DIÁLOGO	C
2358-1670	REVISTA IBDFAM	C
2529-9573	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE BIOÉTICA	C
2179-8419	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE ESTUDOS LEGISLATIVOS	C
1137-2729	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE INGENIERÍA MECÁNICA	C
0121-6651	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE POLIMEROS	C
1988-4206	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE POLÍMEROS (INTERNET)	C
2183-6663	REVISTA IBERO-AMERICANA DE SAÚDE E ENVELHECIMENTO	C
0719-4994	REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DE VITICULTURA, AGROINDUSTRIA Y RL	C
1415-224X	REVISTA IBRACON	C
1982-257X	REVISTA IDEAS	C
2359-4799	REVISTA IFES CIÊNCIA	C
2182-7486	REVISTA INCOMUNIDADE	C
2238-2496	REVISTA INEANA (REVISTA TÉCNICA DO INSTITUTO ESTADUAL DO A	C
0717-9103	REVISTA INGENIERIA INDUSTRIAL	C
2358-5951	REVISTA INICIATIVA ECONÔMICA	C
2175-537X	REVISTA INSPIRAR	C
0214-1892	REVISTA INTEGRACIÓN	C
1982-9280	REVISTA INTEGRALIZAÇÃO UNIVERSITÁRIA	C
2596-0202	REVISTA INTERCIÊNCIA	C
2359-4756	REVISTA INTERCIENTE	C
2358-6966	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR CIÊNCIAS E SAÚDE (ONLINE)	C
2525-3824	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE CIÊNCIA APLICADA	C
2177-3440	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE ESTUDOS EXPERIMENTAIS - ANIMAIS	C
2447-6102	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE PESQUISA EM ENGENHARIA	C
2595-3664	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR DE PROMOÇÃO DA SAÚDE	C
2594-6447	REVISTA INTERDISCIPLINAR FMB	C

2526-3544	REVISTA INTERINSTITUCIONAL BRASILEIRA DE TERAPIA OCUPACION	C
2236-1219	REVISTA INTERLÚDIO	C
2340-9991	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE CIENCIA Y SOCIEDAD	C
2316-7041	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE CIÊNCIAS	C
1535-0088	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE DESASTRES NATURALES, ACCIDENTES I	C
2446-9823	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE DIREITO PÚBLICO	C
2594-7907	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCAÇÃO E SAÚDE	C
2307-4841	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE EDUCACIÓN MUSICAL	C
2254-5859	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE HUMANIDADES MÉDICAS	C
2445-1711	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN Y DOCENCIA	C
2386-7507	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE SALUD, BIENESTAR Y SOCIEDAD	C
2530-4895	REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE TECNOLOGIA, CIENCIA Y SOCIEDAD	C
0719-5370	REVISTA INVESTIGACIONES GEOGRAFICAS UNIVERSIDAD DE CHILE	C
2526-5830	REVISTA IPT	C
0120-3088	REVISTA JAVERIANA	C
2595-1661	REVISTA JRG DE ESTUDOS ACADÊMICOS	C
2316-4212	REVISTA JUDICIÁRIA DO PARANÁ	C
2236-0093	REVISTA JUNIOR DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA EM CIÊNCIAS EXATAS E E	C
2236-5788	REVISTA JURÍDICA	C
1519-7476	REVISTA JURÍDICA (ANÁPOLIS)	C
1809-0699	REVISTA JURÍDICA (FIP)	C
2525-5800	REVISTA JURÍDICA CORREGEDORIA NACIONAL	C
2447-9624	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA AMPPE	C
2238-5738	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA CNM	C
2358-0038	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA ESCOLA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO DOS MAGISTRADOS	C
2525-5770	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA ESCOLA SUPERIOR DE ADVOCACIA DA OAB-PI	C
1982-1034	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA FADISMA (IMPRESSO)	C
1982-5552	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA FADISMA (ONLINE)	C
2177-4145	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA JUSTIÇA FEDERAL DA BAHIA	C
2526-9488	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA UFERSA	C
1807-1627	REVISTA JURÍDICA DA UNIFIL	C
0326-7431	REVISTA JURÍDICA DE BUENOS AIRES (1985)	C
2359-1447	REVISTA JURÍDICA DE SEGUROS	C
2237-0870	REVISTA JURÍDICA DIREITO & REALIDADE	C
2526-737X	REVISTA JURÍDICA DIREITO E CIDADANIA NA SOCIEDADE CONTEMP(C
2358-7970	REVISTA JURÍDICA DO CURSO DE DIREITO DA FAAP (PRINT)	C
1980-9662	REVISTA JURÍDICA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO (JOÃO PESSOA. IMPRES	C
0101-1235	REVISTA JURÍDICA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO CATARINENSE	C
2359-1021	REVISTA JURÍDICA DO MINISTÉRIO PÚBLICO DO ESTADO DO PARAN	C
1807-3956	REVISTA JURÍDICA DO UNIARAXÁ	C
1984-8854	REVISTA JURÍDICA ELETRÔNICA	C
2317-9880	REVISTA JURÍDICA ELETRÔNICA DIREITO, SOCIEDADE E DESENVOLVI	C
1413-2605	REVISTA JURIDICA IN VERBIS (UFRN)	C
1808-6861	REVISTA JURÍDICA LOGOS	C
2179-7714	REVISTA JURÍDICA O SABER COMPLETANTE	C
2183-5705	REVISTA JURÍDICA PORTUCALENSE - PORTUCALENSE LAW JOURNAL	C
1983-2036	REVISTA JURÍDICA THEMIS	C
2595-9689	REVISTA JURÍDICA TRABALHO E DESENVOLVIMENTO HUMANO	C
1806-6771	REVISTA JURÍDICA UNIANDRADE	C
1516-7674	REVISTA JURÍDICA UNIGRAN	C

2526-6500	REVISTA JURIS UNITOLEDO	C
1807-779X	REVISTA JUSTIÇA & CIDADANIA	C
2525-7161	REVISTA JUVENTUDE E POLÍTICAS PÚBLICAS	C
2422-5401	REVISTA LACANIANA DE PSICOANÁLISIS	C
2526-219X	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA AMBIENTE E SAÚDE - RLAS	C
2526-8090	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE CERVEJA	C
1659-4304	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE DERECHOS HUMANOS	C
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2346-920X	REVISTA LATINOAMERICANA DE ESTUDIOS CRÍTICOS ANIMALES	C
1678-6742	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE ESTUDOS CONSTITUCIONAIS	C
2317-6792	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE INOVAÇÃO E ENGENHARIA DE PRC	C
2317-4846	REVISTA LATINO-AMERICANA DE INOVAÇÃO E ENGENHARIA DE PRC	C
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2317-7985	REVISTA LITERÁRIA CAFÉ-COM-LETRAS	C
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1870-3267	REVISTA MÉDICA DE LA UNIVERSIDAD VERACRUZANA	C
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0185-3309	REVISTA MEXICANA DE FITOPATOLOGÍA	C
1665-2738	REVISTA MEXICANA DE INGENIERÍA QUÍMICA	C
1665-5044	REVISTA MEXICANA DE NEUROCIENCIA. ORGANO OFICIAL DE DIFUC	C
1646-8104	REVISTA MIGRAÇÕES	C
2447-9071	REVISTA MILITAR BRASILEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS	C
2237-7077	REVISTA MIRANTE	C
1981-4089	REVISTA MIRANTE (ONLINE)	C
1808-5024	REVISTA MULHERES E LITERATURA	C
1414-6304	REVISTA MÚLTIPLA (UPIS)	C
1413-4837	REVISTA NACIONAL DA CARNE	C
2357-4607	REVISTA NACIONAL DE ODONTOLOGÍA	C
0102-7506	REVISTA NAVAL DE ODONTOLOGIA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	C
2527-1164	REVISTA NAWA	C
0124-1265	REVISTA NEUROPSICOLOGÍA, NEUROPSIQUIATRÍA Y NEUROCIENCIA	C
2237-1443	REVISTA NOCTUA	C

2526-7973	REVISTA NOCTUA	C
2595-3729	REVISTA NORDESTINA DE CIÊNCIAS BIOLÓGICAS	C
1808-7663	REVISTA NORDESTINA DE ZOOLOGIA	C
2237-8170	REVISTA NORTE MINEIRA DE EDUCAÇÃO FÍSICA	C
2177-2959	REVISTA NOSSO ALHO	C
1807-7994	REVISTA O PROFESSOR	C
1984-2627	REVISTA OABRJ	C
0719-5729	REVISTA OBSERVATORIO DEL DEPORTE	C
1870-199X	REVISTA ODONTOLOGIA MEXICANA	C
1677-6704	REVISTA ODONTOLÓGICA DE ARAÇATUBA	C
0123-7810	REVISTA ODONTOS	C
2525-5622	REVISTA OLD	C
2525-2941	REVISTA OLHAR - REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA ESAMC	C
2447-0171	REVISTA OLHAR DIVERSO	C
2176-3291	REVISTA OLHARES	C
2238-1082	REVISTA OLHARES SOCIAIS. UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO RECÔNCAV	C
1809-3159	REVISTA ONLINE FADIVALE	C
0121-3709	REVISTA ORINOQUIA	C
2238-0299	REVISTA OSESP	C
2176-3216	REVISTA OURICURI	C
2317-0131	REVISTA OURICURI.	C
2595-9638	REVISTA PAISAGENS HÍBRIDAS	C
2526-8708	REVISTA PALAU	C
1679-7140	REVISTA PANAMERICANA DE INFECTOLOGÍA (IMPRESSO)	C
2172-3168	REVISTA PANGEA	C
1414-3070	REVISTA PARAENSE DE ODONTOLOGIA	C
2077-5172	REVISTA PARAGUAYA DE ESTUDIOS POLÍTICOS CONTEMPORÁNEO -	C
2318-4248	REVISTA PARLAMENTO & SOCIEDADE	C
2594-634X	REVISTA PARQUET EM FOCO	C
0100-8889	REVISTA PAULISTA DE ENFERMAGEM	C
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2359-3482	REVISTA PAULISTA DE PEDIATRIA (ENGLISH EDITION)	C
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1809-1865	REVISTA PAVIMENTAÇÃO	C
2358-4831	REVISTA PEABIRU	C
2359-3598	REVISTA PEBMED DE CIÊNCIAS MÉDICAS	C
2359-6554	REVISTA PEDAGOGIA - UFMT	C
2358-6133	REVISTA PEDAGÓGICA	C
2237-5252	REVISTA PENSAR TECNOLOGIA	C
0103-9393	REVISTA PERIODONTIA (SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE PERIODONTOLC	C
2238-8486	REVISTA PERSPECTIVA EM EDUCAÇÃO, GESTÃO & TECNOLOGIA (ON	C
1809-9459	REVISTA PERSPECTIVA JURÍDICA (FGF)	C
2526-1541	REVISTA PERSPECTIVA: CIÊNCIA E SAÚDE	C
1984-025X	REVISTA PESQUISA EDUCACIONAL	C
2238-2704	REVISTA PESQUISA EM FISIOTERAPIA	C
1983-3946	REVISTA PESQUISA EM FOCO EM EDUCAÇÃO E FILOSOFIA	C
0329-5001	REVISTA PETROQUÍMICA, PETRÓLEO, GAS & QUÍMICA	C
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2596-1098	REVISTA PLURI	C
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1808-6462	REVISTA PONTES	C
2446-9319	REVISTA POPULUS	C
2178-3454	REVISTA PORTAL DE DIVULGAÇÃO	C
0871-8563	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE CIÊNCIA CRIMINAL	C
0035-0389	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE CIÊNCIAS VETERINÁRIAS	C
0870-984X	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE ENGENHARIA DE ESTRUTURAS	C
1646-2122	REVISTA PORTUGUESA DE ORTOPEDIA E TRAUMATOLOGIA	C
2359-3741	REVISTA POSIÇÃO	C
2594-6528	REVISTA PRÁTICAS EM EXTENSÃO	C
2237-2423	REVISTA PRIMEIROS ESTUDOS	C
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2237-5163	REVISTA PRODUÇÃO EM FOCO	C
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2178-6275	REVISTA PROJEÇÃO E DOCÊNCIA	C
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2594-8946	REVISTA RASANTE	C
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2526-2874	REVISTA REMECS - REVISTA MULTIDISCIPLINAR DE ESTUDOS CIENTÍFICOS	C
2359-1358	REVISTA RE-PRODUÇÃO	C
2238-8478	REVISTA REVESTRES	C
2177-8086	REVISTA REVISTA DE EDUCAÇÃO TÉCNICA E DE EDUCAÇÃO TÉCNICA	C
2595-1203	REVISTA RIOS SAÚDE	C
1677-0110	REVISTA RISCOS	C
2526-947X	REVISTA RIZOMA	C
2525-6092	REVISTA RURAL E URBANO - UFPE	C
2177-7381	REVISTA SABERES ACADÊMICOS	C
2525-4227	REVISTA SABERES DOCENTES EM AÇÃO	C
2014-1874	REVISTA SANS SOLEIL - ESTUDIOS DE LA IMAGEN	C
2176-9044	REVISTA SAPERE (ONLINE)	C
2317-8469	REVISTA SAÚDE & CIÊNCIA ONLINE	C
0103-4490	REVISTA SAÚDE (SANTA MARIA)	C
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2177-6679	REVISTA SAÚDE E CIÊNCIA	C
2525-4383	REVISTA SAÚDE EM FOCO - SECRETARIA MUNICIPAL DE SAÚDE	C
2318-3780	REVISTA SAÚDE MULTIDISCIPLINAR	C
2358-4033	REVISTA SAÚDE QUÂNTICA	C
1676-4196	REVISTA SCAPE	C
2357-9668	REVISTA SEMANA DA ÁFRICA NA UFRGS	C
1665-8639	REVISTA SEMESTRAL DE LA FACULTAD DE DERECHO	C

1983-0602	REVISTA SEMINÁRIO INTEGRADO	C
2526-589X	REVISTA SENSO	C
2177-0794	REVISTA SETE FACES	C
2236-9406	REVISTA SÍNTESE - DIREITO AMBIENTAL	C
2179-166X	REVISTA SÍNTESE - DIREITO CIVIL E PROCESSUAL CIVIL	C
2236-3025	REVISTA SÍNTESE - LICITAÇÕES, CONTRATOS E CONVÊNIOS	C
2179-1651	REVISTA SÍNTESE DE DIREITO ADMINISTRATIVO	C
2236-9414	REVISTA SÍNTESE DE DIREITO DESPORTIVO.	C
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2179-1627	REVISTA SÍNTESE DIREITO PENAL E PROCESSUAL PENAL	C
2237-714X	REVISTA SÍNTESE DIREITO PREVIDENCIÁRIO	C
2236-3033	REVISTA SÍNTESE RESPONSABILIDADE PÚBLICA	C
2179-1643	REVISTA SÍNTESE TRABALHISTA E PREVIDENCIÁRIO	C
2525-9555	REVISTA SISTEMAS E MÍDIAS DIGITAIS	C
2447-701X	REVISTA SOMMA	C
1517-0144	REVISTA SOUZA MARQUES	C
2359-5817	REVISTA SUBVERSA - LITERATURA LUSO-BRASILEIRA	C
2236-0417	REVISTA SUL-BRASILEIRA DE ENFERMAGEM	C
2316-8900	REVISTA SUSTENTABILIDADE ORGANIZACIONAL	C
2359-3261	REVISTA TAMANDUÁ	C
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2178-8456	REVISTA TÉCNICA DO TRIBUNAL DE CONTAS DE MATO GROSSO	C
2358-5420	REVISTA TÉCNICO CIENTÍFICA DO CREA-PR	C
1678-8532	REVISTA TECNOLÓGICA	C
2446-5046	REVISTA TEMA - LETRAS, ARTES E HISTÓRIA	C
2526-2300	REVISTA TEOLÓGICA DOXIA	C
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1794-984X	REVISTA TRABAJO SOCIAL	C
1677-2784	REVISTA TRABALHISTA (RIO DE JANEIRO)	C
1688-6348	REVISTA TRAMA CULTURA Y PATRIMONIO	C
2318-9614	REVISTA TRANSDISCIPLINAR LOGOS E VERITAS	C
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1982-4881	REVISTA TRÓPICA ¿ CIÊNCIAS AGRÁRIAS E BIOLÓGICAS	C
1657-4583	REVISTA UIS INGENIERIAS	C
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2317-5966	REVISTA UNIASSELVI-PÓS	C
1517-1612	REVISTA UNIFIEO	C
2357-7266	REVISTA UNIFREIRE	C
1676-9228	REVISTA UNILAGO	C
1807-5053	REVISTA UNINGÁ	C

2237-1753	REVISTA UNIVAP ON-LINE	C
0124-7107	REVISTA UNIVERSIDAD Y SALUD	C
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2177-4951	REVISTA UNIVERSITÁRI@	C
0326-8373	REVISTA UNIVERSITARIA DE GEOGRAFÍA	C
1688-4949	REVISTA UNIVERSITÁRIA DE LA EDUCACIÓN FÍSICA Y EL DEPORTE	C
2317-8116	REVISTA UNIVERSO & EXTENSÃO	C
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1809-0028	REVISTA VEREDAS	C
2176-641X	REVISTA VIAS REFLEXIVAS	C
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2237-3586	REVISTA VOCÁBULO	C
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2179-5940	REVIVSTA AGROTECNOLOGIA	C
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2497-2614	REVUE ÉTUDIANTE DES EXPRESSIONS LUSOPHONES	C
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2491-6366	REVUE INTERNATIONALE D'ART ET D'ARTOLOGIE	C
0223-5404	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE DROIT PÉNAL	C
1260-1705	REVUE INTERNATIONALE DE PSYCHOSOCIOLOGIE	C
0990-1027	REVUE JURIDIQUE DE L'OUEST	C
2600-6553	REVUE PSYCHISME ET ANTHROPOS	C
2526-8074	RG NEWS	C
1646-9372	RHÊTORIKÉ: REVISTA DIGITAL DE RETÓRICA	C
2399-7370	RHEUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDIC MEDICINE	C
2386-3781	RIBAGUA - REVISTA IBEROAMERICANA DEL AGUA	C
1939-8425	RICE	C

1939-8433	RICE	C
1672-6308	RICE SCIENCE	C
1626-3596	RICHARDIANA	C
1274-6711	RIDICULOSA	C
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0272-4332	RISK ANALYSIS	C
2227-9091	RISKS	C
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2577-2899	ROBOTICS & AUTOMATION ENGINEERING JOURNAL	C
0104-7914	ROBRAC (GOIÂNIA. IMPRESSO)	C
2074-0735	ROCA	C
2595-4512	ROCINANTE	C
1220-5648	ROMANIAN JOURNAL OF MINERAL DEPOSITS	C
2344-4959	ROMANIAN NEUROSURGERY (ONLINE)	C
1841-0162	ROMANIAN SPORTS MEDICINE JOURNAL	C
2317-8027	ROPLAC	C
1752-1580	ROSETA - PAPERS OF THE DEPARTAMENT OF CLASSICS, ANCIENT HI!	C
1806-8669	RPE. REVISTA INTERNACIONAL DE PERIODONTIA CLÍNICA	C
1688-6194	RSEUS. REVISTA SUDAMERICANA DE EDUCACIÓN, UNIVERSIDAD Y S	C
1729-7427	RUSSIAN MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	C
1982-792X	SABER CIENTÍFICO	C
0101-6717	SABER ELETRÔNICA	C
2448-0576	SABERES DA AMAZÔNIA	C
1679-687X	SABERES E FAZERES EDUCATIVOS	C
1982-6532	SABERES INTERDISCIPLINARES	C
2525-507X	SABERES PLURAIS: EDUCAÇÃO NA SAÚDE	C
1980-0002	SABIOS (FACULDADE INTEGRADO DE CAMPO MOURÃO. ONLINE)	C
2050-313X	SAGE OPEN MEDICAL CASE REPORTS	C
2176-7130	SALA 206	C
1315-0138	SALUD DE LOS TRABAJADORES	C
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2238-1244	SAÚDE EM REVISTA	C
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2182-8938	WORKERS OF THE WORLD. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON STRIKES A	C
2070-3724	WORLD ACADEMY OF SCIENCE, ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY. C	C
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2042-5961	WORLD JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP, MANAGEMENT AND SU¿	C
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1647-3248	A PÁGINA DA EDUCAÇÃO	NP
1060-2011	ABSTRACTS OF THE GENERAL MEETING OF THE AMERICAN SOCIETY	NP
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0257-0076	ACTES DES COLLOQUES INSECTES SOCIAUX	NP
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1276-2458	AFRICULTURES: LA REVUE DE REFERENCE DES CULTURES AFRICAINE	NP
1981-7827	AISTHE (ONLINE)	NP
2317-3971	ALGAZARRA	NP
1948-9919	AMERICAN JOURNAL OF NEUROSCIENCE (ONLINE)	NP
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1981-559X	ARTE! BRASILEIROS	NP
1984-056X	ARTESESC (PORTO ALEGRE)	NP
1086-7058	ARTFORUM INTERNATIONAL	NP
2525-7099	ARTIGOS ESTRATÉGICOS	NP
2331-8422	ARXIV E-PRINT	NP
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1050-3390	ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY OF THE PACIFIC CONFERENCE SERIES	NP
2241-2891	ATINER'S CONFERENCE PAPER SERIES, NO: ART2012-0216	NP
1809-5720	ATITUDE (PORTO ALEGRE)	NP
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1676-918X	BOLETIM DE PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO (EMBRAPA CERRADO	NP
1809-5003	BOLETIM DE PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO (EMBRAPA MANDIOC	NP
1677-891X	BOLETIM DE PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO (EMBRAPA PECUÁRIA	NP
1808-9968	BOLETIM DE PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO (EMBRAPA SEMI-ÁRII	NP
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1808-0812	BOLETIM INFORMATIVO (SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE ZOOLOGIA)	NP

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2317-1707	BOOK OF ABSTRACTS- WORLD CONGRESS ON COMMUNICATION AN	NP
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1807-0590	CADERNOS TEOLOGIA PÚBLICA (UNISINOS)	NP
1678-3638	CADERNOS THEMIS: GÊNERO E DIREITO (IMPRESSO)	NP
1677-860X	CAMINHANDO COM O ITEPA	NP
1066-7814	CANADIAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED PHYSIOLOGY	NP
2526-494X	CANGURU	NP
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1980-5144	CARTA SOCIAL E DO TRABALHO	NP
2357-7487	CARTOGRAFIAS.MITSP - REVISTA DE ARTES CÊNICAS	NP
1519-4787	CBCIMAT - CONGRESSO BRASILEIRO DE ENGENHARIA E CIÊNCIA DO	NP
1982-0941	CD-ROM DO 8º COLÓQUIO DE MODA	NP
1519-728X	CESUR EM REVISTA	NP
1088-7105	CHELONIAN RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS	NP
1679-6756	CIBERCULTURA (ITAÚ CULTURAL)	NP
1809-2888	CIBERTEOLOGIA: REVISTA DE TEOLOGIA E CULTURA	NP
2319-0574	CIÊNCIAS DO TRABALHO	NP
1647-0893	CIES E-WORKING PAPERS	NP
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2572-7656	CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY AND TRANSLATIONAL MEDICINE	NP
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2448-2722	COLLOQUIUM: REVISTA MULTIDISCIPLINAR DE TEOLOGIA	NP
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1809-2748	COLÓQUIO DO POLO DE PESQUISA SOBRE RELAÇÕES LUSO-BRASILE	NP
1756-0098	COMMODITIES OF EMPIRE WORKING PAPER (ONLINE)	NP
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1981-7231	COMUNICADO TÉCNICO (EMBRAPA PANTANAL. ONLINE)	NP
1679-9259	CONASEMS (BRASÍLIA)	NP
1437-9023	CONCRETE PLANT INTERNATIONAL (PRINT)	NP
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1676-661X	CONFLITOS NO CAMPO BRASIL	NP
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1984-0101	CONHECIMENTO PRÁTICO GEOGRAFIA	NP
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0011-250X	CUADERNOS HISPANOAMERICANOS	NP
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2352-3409	DATA IN BRIEF	NP
2236-2711	DAVAR POLISSÊMICA: REVISTA DE TEOLOGIA E ESTUDOS AFINS	NP
2594-0937	DEBATES SOBRE INNOVACIÓN	NP
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1594-8528	DISEGNO INDUSTRIALE INDUSTRIAL DESIGN	NP
1517-8498	DOCUMENTOS - EMBRAPA AGROBIOLOGIA	NP
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1516-8840	DOCUMENTOS (EMBRAPA CLIMA TEMPERADO. IMPRESSO)	NP
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2318-1400	DOCUMENTOS / EMBRAPA PESCA E AQUICULTURA	NP
1517-5111	DOCUMENTOS. EMBRAPA CERRADOS	NP
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1980-8380	DOM / REVISTA DA FUNDAÇÃO DOM CABRAL	NP
0012-5377	DOMUS (MILANO)	NP
2175-6716	DROPS (SÃO PAULO)	NP
2267-1242	E3S WEB OS CONFERENCES (ONLINE)	NP
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1678-0701	EDUCAÇÃO AMBIENTAL EM AÇÃO	NP
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2177-2576	ENANPAD - ENCONTRO DA ANPAD	NP
2175-8875	ENCONTRO NACIONAL DA ANPEGE	NP
2316-5219	ENCONTRO NACIONAL DE HISTÓRIA ORAL	NP
1476-9506	ENCYCLOPEDIA OF LIFE SCIENCES (ONLINE)	NP
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2324-9250	EOS TRANSACTIONS	NP
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2518-0991	ERCOFTAC BULLETIN	NP
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1951-6355	EUR. PHYS. J. SPECIAL TOPICS	NP
2190-5444	EUROPEAN PHYSICAL JOURNAL PLUS	NP
1519-7069	EXPRESSION (GUAXUPÉ)	NP
0393-3687	FAMILIA ET VITA	NP
0972-0960	FAR EAST JOURNAL OF APPLIED MATHEMATICS	NP
0972-0871	FAR EAST JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES: FJMS	NP
1995-1949	FE Y PUEBLO	NP
2177-6547	FEIRA DE CIÊNCIAS E CULTURA	NP
2526-8309	FILOSOFIA DE DUNAS	NP
0254-8453	FLORA DEL PARAGUAY	NP
1414-5723	FOLHA DE S. PAULO	NP
1808-0715	FONTE (BELO HORIZONTE)	NP
1851-5606	FOROALFA	NP
0939-4435	FRUIT PROCESSING	NP
2477-9202	FUERA DE CAMPO - REVISTA DE CINE	NP
2385-2291	FUOCO AMICO	NP
2595-7775	GESTUS CADERNOS DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E GESTÃO PÚBLICA	NP
1806-8979	GV EXECUTIVO	NP
2237-4639	GV NOVOS NEGÓCIOS	NP
2359-5124	HOMENS DO MATO - REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DE PESQUISA EM SEGUR	NP
1808-3064	HORIZONTE CIENTÍFICO (UBERLÂNDIA)	NP
1415-8868	HSM MANAGEMENT	NP
1464-5653	HUMAN ECOLOGY	NP
1837-2104	IARTEM E-JOURNAL	NP
2007-2716	IDEAS @ CONCYTEG	NP
1350-2360	IEEE PROCEEDINGS. GENERATION, TRANSMISSION & DISTRIBUTION	NP
0278-0097	IEEE TECHNOLOGY & SOCIETY MAGAZINE	NP
2405-8963	IFAC-PAPERSONLINE	NP

1981-8769	IHU ON-LINE (UNISINOS. IMPRESSO)	NP
1983-6171	ÍMPETO	NP
1554-2483	IMPLANT NEWS & VIEWS (PRINT)	NP
1678-7293	INESC EM REVISTA	NP
2448-1106	INFORMAÇÃO. REVISTA DIGITAL DO CEFOR/SEDUC	NP
1678-6335	INFORMAÇÕES FIPE	NP
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1982-517X	INFORMATIVO PROGRAMA DE EDUCAÇÃO TUTORIAL - PET GEO UD	NP
2317-305X	INFORMATIVO TÉCNICO DO SEMIÁRIDO	NP
2448-220X	INFORMATIVO: APECS-BRASIL	NP
2595-8232	INSTITUTO DE ESTUDOS ESTRATÉGICOS DE PETRÓLEO, GÁS NATURAL	NP
1517-3860	INTELIGÊNCIA EMPRESARIAL (UFRJ)	NP
2013-679X	INTERARTIVE	NP
2349-3259	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CLINICAL TRIALS	NP
2349-3240	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CLINICAL TRIALS	NP
0976-6359	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY	NP
2010-1945	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MODERN PHYSICS: CONFERENCE SERIES	NP
0002-9416	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ORTHODONTICS	NP
2176-297X	INTERNATIONAL SECURITY: A EUROPEAN-SOUTH AMERICAN DIALOGUE	NP
0915-2822	INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM IN BRAZIL	NP
2340-1079	INTERNATIONAL TECHNOLOGY, EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT CONFERENCE SERIES	NP
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2177-0212	ISTO É INCONFIDÊNCIA	NP
1517-7807	ITAICI: REVISTA DE ESPIRITUALIDADE INACIANA	NP
2176-2406	IV SIMPÓSIO DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA	NP
2238-9229	IX SEMINARIO DE PESQUISA EM EDUCAÇÃO DA REGIÃO SUL- ANPEI	NP
0021-3470	IZVESTIA VYSSIH UCEBNIH ZAVEDENIJ. RADIOELEKTRONIKA	NP
9789-8961	JANUS - ANUÁRIO DE RELAÇÕES EXTERIORES	NP
2177-8892	JORNADA HISTEDBR. CAMPINAS	NP
0962-449X	JOURNAL - BRITISH TARANTULA SOCIETY	NP
0975-0851	JOURNAL OF BIOEQUIVALENCE & BIOAVAILABILITY	NP
1553-5495	JOURNAL OF GLOBAL BUSINESS AND TECHNOLOGY	NP
1669-8649	JOURNAL OF LATIN AMERICAN THEOLOGY: CHRISTIAN REFLECTIONS	NP
2334-2307	JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS AND STROKE	NP
1742-6588	JOURNAL OF PHYSICS. CONFERENCE SERIES (PRINT)	NP
0093-5433	JOURNAL OF THE OPTICAL SOCIETY OF AMERICA	NP
2317-7144	JUSTIÇA ELEITORAL EM DEBATE	NP
1807-5096	KAIRÓS (INSTITUTO TEOLÓGICO-PASTORAL DO CEARÁ)	NP
2237-7557	KERYGMA	NP
1812-7886	KIRU	NP
2178-4930	KOINONIA - REVISTA DE TEOLOGIA E CULTURA	NP
2453-188X	LA CHARRETTE	NP
0009-8167	LA CIVILTÀ CATTOLICA	NP
1676-1951	LABRYS	NP
1676-966X	LABRYS (EDITIÓN FRANÇAISE. ONLINE)	NP
1824-1360	LATINOAMERICA-ONLINE	NP
1981-7525	LE MONDE DIPLOMATIQUE (BRASIL)	NP
2078-0958	LECTURE NOTES IN ENGINEERING AND COMPUTER SCIENCE	NP
1982-2464	LEITURAS DA HISTÓRIA	NP
1809-0540	LEITURAS PAISAGÍSTICAS (UFRJ)	NP

1677-342X	LIÇÕES	NP
0147-0809	LIGHT METALS (NEW YORK)	NP
1981-6804	LOCUS CIENTÍFICO (ANPROTEC. ONLINE)	NP
1126-0653	L'OMBRA	NP
0873-4003	LUSOFONIA (LISBOA)	NP
2358-6362	MAIS 60: ESTUDOS SOBRE ENVELHECIMENTO	NP
2238-2801	MAL-ESTAR E SOCIEDADE	NP
0839-7708	MARINE TURTLE NEWSLETTER	NP
2261-236X	MATEC WEB OF CONFERENCES	NP
2214-7853	MATERIALS TODAY: PROCEEDINGS	NP
0948-7557	MATICES: ZEITSCHRIFT ZU LATEINAMERIKA, SPANIEN UND PORTUG.	NP
2531-9477	MD JOURNAL (ONLINE)	NP
1927-0178	MÉDIAS 19	NP
2375-1916	MEDICAL RESEARCH ARCHIVES	NP
2076-3271	MEDICAL SCIENCES	NP
1517-7831	MEMÓRIA ABRACE	NP
1981-6243	MENSAGEM DOCE (ASSOCIAÇÃO PAULISTA DE APICULTORES, CRIAL	NP
9788-5509	MENTE, CÉREBRO E FILOSOFIA	NP
1982-9922	MINHA CIDADE	NP
2448-3885	MÓBILE - REVISTA DO CONSELHO DE ARQUITETURA E URBANISMO	NP
2236-9759	MONOGRAFIA IFCH UNICAMP	NP
1195-1037	MUNDOGEO	NP
1807-8095	MUNDOPM (CURITIBA)	NP
1807-6149	MUSAS (IPHAN)	NP
2471-2620	NACLA REPORT ON THE AMERICAS	NP
1071-4839	NACLA REPORT ON THE AMERICAS (1993)	NP
2059-6553	NEURONAL SIGNALING	NP
1798-565X	NEW HORIZONS IN TRANSLATION RESEARCH AND EDUCATION. PUB	NP
0028-7571	NEW YORK STATE DENTAL JOURNAL	NP
0104-8384	NEWSLAB	NP
1462-5733	NORRAG NEWS	NP
2316-6436	NOSSA FÉ. REVISTA DO PROFESSOR	NP
2595-217X	NOTA DE COMÉRCIO VAREJISTA	NP
0104-5512	NOTAS E COMUNICAÇÕES DE GEOGRAFIA. SERIE B, TEXTOS DIDATIC	NP
1679-9313	NOTÍCIAS ASGARDIANAS	NP
0103-0116	NOVA ESCOLA	NP
2405-6014	NUCLEAR AND PARTICLE PHYSICS PROCEEDINGS	NP
0097-0166	NUTRITION RESEARCH	NP
2318-3063	Ô CATARINA	NP
1647-7073	O FOGUETE	NP
1983-0912	O SETOR ELÉTRICO	NP
1519-7670	OBSERVATÓRIO DA IMPRENSA (SÃO PAULO)	NP
2358-6087	OBSERVATÓRIO DA RELIGIÃO	NP
0378-6978	OFFICIAL JOURNAL OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITIES. L. LEGISLATI	NP
2182-7966	OFICINA DO CES	NP
1982-3878	OKARA : GEOGRAFIA EM DEBATE (UFPB)	NP
1331-7571	ORIS	NP
0103-6750	ORQUIDARIO (RIO DE JANEIRO)	NP
2237-3381	ORSON REVISTA DOS CURSOS DE CINEMA DO CEARTE/UFPEL	NP
1981-9803	P&D: REVISTA PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO DA ANEEL	NP

1414-4638	PÁGINAS ABERTAS (SÃO PAULO)	NP
2447-9918	PAINEL ACADÊMICO	NP
1022-3398	PAPERS OF THE 38TH INTERNATIONAL WITTGENSTEIN SYMPOSIUM	NP
1677-3721	PÁTIO (PORTO ALEGRE. 2002)	NP
2179-4375	PÁTIO ENSINO MÉDIO, PROFISSIONAL E TECNOLÓGICO	NP
2177-0506	PBL 2010 - CONGRESSO INTERNACIONAL	NP
2606-4979	PEER COMMUNITY IN ECOLOGY	NP
2167-9843	PEERJ PREPRINTS	NP
2527-0540	PENSAR GEOGRAFIA	NP
1983-0076	PERSPECTIVA SOCIOLÓGICA	NP
2275-9190	PERSPECTIVE	NP
0101-5397	PETRO & QUÍMICA	NP
0210-3877	PHASE: REVISTA DE PASTORAL LITÚRGICA	NP
2158-916X	PHILOSOPHY RESEARCH INDEX	NP
2236-3521	PHYSICAE	NP
1853-1997	PLOT	NP
1983-9456	PMKT: REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE PESQUISAS DE MARKETING, OPINIÃO	NP
2526-9658	POEMAS - POLÍTICA, ECONOMIA, MINERAÇÃO, AMBIENTE E SOCIED	NP
1518-7446	POLÍTICA DEMOCRÁTICA	NP
2358-9841	POLITIKA	NP
2595-3591	PÓRTICO DE EPICTETO	NP
2317-5699	POSTAIS - REVISTA DO MUSEU NACIONAL DOS CORREIOS	NP
2319-0485	PRÁTICAS EM CONTABILIDADE E GESTÃO	NP
1677-9878	PRÁXIS EVANGÉLICA	NP
2310-287X	PREPRINTS	NP
1413-1862	PRESENÇA PEDAGOGICA	NP
1806-3470	PROAGO. PROGRAMA DE ATUALIZAÇÃO EM GINECOLOGIA E OBSTE	NP
2212-8271	PROCEDIA CIRP	NP
1877-0509	PROCEDIA COMPUTER SCIENCE	NP
1877-7058	PROCEDIA ENGINEERING	NP
2351-9789	PROCEDIA MANUFACTURING	NP
2311-4487	PROCEEDINGS FROM NORTH AMERICAN SYMPOSIUM ON KNOWLEI	NP
0277-786X	PROCEEDINGS OF SPIE, THE INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR OPTICAL	NP
1541-9312	PROCEEDINGS OF THE HUMAN FACTORS AND ERGONOMICS SOCIET	NP
1808-6586	PROJETO DESIGN	NP
2595-4245	PROJETOS	NP
1809-0435	PROMEF - PROGRAMA DE ATUALIZAÇÃO EM MEDICINA DE FAMÍLIA	NP
1679-4737	PRORN. PROGRAMA DE ATUALIZAÇÃO EM NEONATOLOGIA	NP
2395-8642	QUAERENTIBUS	NP
2177-1855	RADAR: TECNOLOGIA, PRODUÇÃO E COMÉRCIO EXTERIOR	NP
1415-3173	RAÍZES (SÃO CAETANO DO SUL)	NP
0104-8341	RBC: REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE CONTABILIDADE	NP
1519-8057	RDT (BRASÍLIA)	NP
2380-2367	REACTIVE OXYGEN SPECIES	NP
2358-3401	REALIZAÇÃO - REVISTA ONLINE DE EXTENSÃO DA UFGD	NP
2175-6694	RESENHAS ONLINE	NP
2318-8928	RESUMOS DO SEMINÁRIO DE PESQUISAS EM ANDAMENTO PPGAC/	NP
2236-1294	REVERTE	NP
1984-3577	REVINTER	NP
2317-1022	REVISTA À MOSTRA	NP

2237-9851	REVISTA ABCM ENGENHARIA	NP
2319-0752	REVISTA ACADÊMICA GUETO	NP
1807-3506	REVISTA ADUSP	NP
2316-686X	REVISTA BATISTA PIONEIRA	NP
0102-5074	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE COMÉRCIO EXTERIOR	NP
2178-9606	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE ENERGIA SOLAR	NP
1807-7056	REVISTA BRASILEIRA DE TEOLOGIA	NP
1413-9316	REVISTA CASA E JARDIM	NP
2175-7224	REVISTA CECILIANA (ONLINE)	NP
2357-9056	REVISTA CIÊNCIA PANTANAL	NP
1980-9425	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS DA RELIGIÃO: HISTÓRIA E SOCIEDADE	NP
2595-5055	REVISTA CIÊNCIAS JURÍDICAS E CIDADANIA	NP
2594-5068	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA DA ASSOCIAÇÃO BRASILEIRA DE OUVIDORES	NP
1806-1508	REVISTA CIENTÍFICA JOPEF	NP
0124-2172	REVISTA CLAR	NP
2178-8154	REVISTA CONTEXTO (PETROLINA)	NP
1983-1102	REVISTA CONVIVER	NP
2248-5406	REVISTA CRONOPIO	NP
2177-3092	REVISTA DA ANPOCS	NP
1676-1316	REVISTA DA ESPM	NP
1980-2331	REVISTA DA SET	NP
2183-4725	REVISTA DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO E EMPREGO PÚBLICO	NP
1676-2630	REVISTA DE CATEQUESE	NP
1677-0668	REVISTA DE CONJUNTURA	NP
2446-9378	REVISTA DE ENGENHARIA DA FACULDADE SALESIANA	NP
2526-5458	REVISTA DE ESTUDOS PENTECOSTAIS ASSEMBLEIANOS	NP
0101-9457	REVISTA DE GEOGRAFIA (SÃO PAULO)	NP
2594-7931	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA	NP
1678-7706	REVISTA DE INICIAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA (CRICIÚMA)	NP
1982-6303	REVISTA DE LITURGIA	NP
0102-7336	REVISTA DE TEATRO - SBAT	NP
1646-6896	REVISTA DEL INSTITUTO INTERNACIONAL DE COSTOS	NP
2317-577X	REVISTA DEMOCRACIA SOCIALISTA	NP
2359-5264	REVISTA DESAFIOS DO DESENVOLVIMENTO	NP
2525-9288	REVISTA DI FACTUM (ELETRÔNICA)	NP
2525-927X	REVISTA DI FACTUM (IMPRESSA)	NP
2525-6653	REVISTA DO INSTITUTO HISTÓRICO E GEOGRÁFICO DO DISTRITO FEI	NP
0100-7637	REVISTA DO TRIBUNAL REGIONAL DO TRABALHO DA 4ª REGIÃO	NP
2525-8583	REVISTA DOMINGUEIRA DA SAÚDE	NP
2183-928X	REVISTA DOS ENCONTROS INTERNACIONAIS ERGOTRIP DESIGN	NP
2179-9075	REVISTA E	NP
2357-8513	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA DO ARQUIVO PÚBLICO DA CIDADE DE BELO H	NP
2358-1271	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ENGENHARIA VIVA	NP
2177-952X	REVISTA ELETRÔNICA ESPAÇO TEOLÓGICO	NP
1983-1684	REVISTA ENFRENTAMENTO	NP
1515-3983	REVISTA ESPACIOS	NP
2316-3011	REVISTA ESPAÇO LIVRE	NP
0033-1983	REVISTA ESTRATÉGIA & ANÁLISE	NP
2525-9997	REVISTA EXTENSÃO E CULTURA DA UFPI	NP
2177-3912	REVISTA FILME CULTURA	NP

1413-4675	REVISTA FILOSOFAZER	NP
2526-3889	REVISTA GEOINTERAÇÕES	NP
2236-255X	REVISTA GEOTEMAS	NP
2594-6870	REVISTA HADES	NP
2448-3451	REVISTA INSEPE	NP
2179-0167	REVISTA JURES	NP
1806-3381	REVISTA LUMIÈRE (IMPRESSO)	NP
0718-0527	REVISTA MAD	NP
2319-0264	REVISTA MESA	NP
1405-2059	REVISTA MEXICANA DE ASTRONOMÍA Y ASTROFÍSICA. SERIE DE CON	NP
2179-748X	REVISTA MONOLITO	NP
2526-284X	REVISTA MOVENTES	NP
1982-1832	REVISTA MUNDOLOGÍSTICA	NP
2316-5588	REVISTA O QI	NP
1981-125X	REVISTA OBSERVATÓRIO ITAÚ CULTURAL	NP
1677-3942	REVISTA OMNIA	NP
2179-0248	REVISTA PÁTIO - ENSINO FUNDAMENTAL	NP
1980-1750	REVISTA PIAUÍ	NP
2362-5856	REVISTA PLOT	NP
1983-909X	REVISTA POLI	NP
2178-213X	REVISTA POLÍTICA , PLANEJAMENTO E GESTÃO EM SAÚDE	NP
2595-1424	REVISTA SOBRECINEMA	NP
2176-2511	REVISTA SOPHIA	NP
2236-2614	REVISTA TAE - TRATAMENTO DE ÁGUA & EFLUENTES	NP
1414-9796	REVISTA TEOLÓGICA (CAMPINAS)	NP
2176-011X	REVISTA UNESPCIENCIA	NP
2316-2287	REVISTA V@RVITU - REVISTA DE CIÊNCIA, TECNOLOGIA E CULTURA	NP
2357-8939	REVISTA VOX FASES	NP
2039-9251	RIVISTA DI FILOSOFIA E DI TEORIA DELLE ARTI	NP
1808-3544	RTI. REDES, TELECOM E INSTALAÇÕES	NP
0148-7191	SAE TECHNICAL PAPER SERIES	NP
1138-1094	SAL TERRAE: REVISTA DE TEOLOGÍA PASTORAL	NP
1414-3755	SALA DO ARTISTA POPULAR	NP
1809-0915	SAPIÊNCIA (FAPEPI. IMPRESSO)	NP
2237-1923	SEMINÁRIO DE HISTÓRIA DA ARTES	NP
2594-7613	SEMINÁRIO NACIONAL E SEMINÁRIO INTERNACIONAL POLÍTICAS PÍ	NP
2238-6807	SENAC AMBIENTAL	NP
2357-8866	SENAC.DOC : REVISTA DE INFORMAÇÃO E CONHECIMENTO	NP
0101-2940	SÉRIE ESTUDOS E PESQUISAS	NP
2525-6416	SERIE ORIENTAÇÕES E RECOMENDAÇÕES FEBRASGO	NP
1678-2283	SÉRIE RELATÓRIOS TÉCNICOS (INSTITUTO DE PESCA. ONLINE)	NP
1679-060X	SÉRIE TEXTO DIDÁTICO (UCB)	NP
2177-9058	SIEDUCA 2011	NP
2595-6345	SIMPÓSIO DO GRUPO DE PESQUISA CRISTIANISMO E INTERPRETAÇ	NP
2178-5112	SIMPÓSIO INTERNACIONAL DE HISTÓRIA AMBIENTAL E MIGRAÇÕES	NP
2178-6135	SIMPÓSIO NACIONAL DE ENSINO DE CIÊNCIA E TECNOLOGIA	NP
0101-7276	SINOPSE ECONÔMICA	NP
2190-3018	SMART INNOVATION, SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES	NP
0037-9735	SOCIETY OF HISTORICAL ARCHAEOLOGY NEWSLETTER	NP
1014-5494	SOURCES UNESCO	NP

1390-0382	SPIRITUS: REVISTA DE MISSIONOLOGÍA - EDICIÓN HISPANOAMERIC	NP
2157-9407	SURGICAL SCIENCE	NP
1676-4218	SUSTENTAÇÃO (COSEMS/CE)	NP
0802-8966	SYNOPSIS FUNGORUM	NP
2316-7726	TECHNOLOGICAL LEARNING AND INDUSTRIAL INNOVATION WORKII	NP
0958-5079	TENTACLE	NP
2526-0790	TEOLOGIA, SOCIEDADE & ESPIRITUALIDADE	NP
1676-2509	TEOLÓGICA	NP
0103-9466	TEXTO PARA DISCUSSÃO (CAMPINAS)	NP
1415-4765	TEXTO PARA DISCUSSÃO (IPEA. BRASÍLIA)	NP
2318-2377	TEXTO PARA DISCUSSÃO CEDEPLAR/UFMG	NP
1676-7055	TEXTOS DIDÁTICOS (UNICAMP)	NP
2179-5495	TEXTOS PARA DISCUSSÃO DA CEPAL - IPEA	NP
1951-6401	THE EUROPEAN PHYSICAL JOURNAL. SPECIAL TOPICS (ONLINE)	NP
1017-1371	THE GLOOM, BOOM AND DOOM REPORT	NP
2307-8235	THE IUCN RED LIST OF THREATENED SPECIES	NP
0949-541X	TÓPICOS (BONN)	NP
2305-6304	TOXICS ¿ OPEN ACCESS JOURNAL	NP
1519-1028	TRABALHOS PARA DISCUSSÃO - BANCO CENTRAL DO BRASIL (ONLIN	NP
1087-0849	TRANSMISSION & DISTRIBUTION WORLD	NP
1984-9524	TRANSVERSALIDADES	NP
0103-5576	TRAVESSIA (SAO PAULO)	NP
1572-6126	TRENDS IN LOGIC	NP
2178-910X	TURISMO EM PAUTA	NP
2347-9442	UK JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND BIOSCIENCES	NP
0041-6436	UNASYLVA (ENGLISH ED. PRINT)	NP
1517-2570	UNOPAR CIENTÍFICA. CIÊNCIAS BIOLÓGICAS E DA SAÚDE	NP
1982-856X	URBÂNIA	NP
0392-5005	URBANISTICA INFORMAZIONI	NP
2317-398X	V SIMPÓSIO DE PÓS-GRADUANDOS EM MÚSICA (SIMPOM 2018)	NP
1676-9090	VERVE (PUCSP)	NP
2421-2687	VICEVERSA	NP
1809-2071	VIDA PASTORAL - REVISTA BIMESTRAL PARA SACERDOTES E AGENTI	NP
1984-9354	VIII CONGRESSO NACIONAL DE EXCELÊNCIA EM GESTÃO	NP
2184-1284	VISTA	NP
2222-0763	VOICES. THEOLOGICAL JOURNAL OF EATWOT, ECUMENICAL ASSOCI	NP
2056-4864	WATERLAT-GOBACIT NETWORK WORKING PAPERS	NP
0950-7116	WELDING INTERNATIONAL	NP
2398-502X	WELLCOME OPEN RESEARCH	NP
1812-108X	WORKING PAPER	NP
1695-5935	WORKING PAPER	NP
1518-3548	WORKING PAPER SÉRIES - BANCO CENTRAL DO BRASIL (ONLINE)	NP
2045-5763	WORKING PAPERS SERIES	NP
2178-1281	WWW.CONGRESSOHISTORIAJATAI.ORG	NP
1016-8257	YACHAY (COCHABAMBA)	NP
2465-3020	ZEROUNDICIPIU	NP
0798-7269	ZOOTECNIA TROPICAL - FONAIAP	NP